

**Artificial Intelligence Based Conversational Agents Implementation
Success in the UK Retail E-Commerce Customer Service Context**

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence-powered, text-based conversational agents (CAs) capable of automating communication has opened new avenues not only for the UK e-commerce retail organisations but also for their customers` value creation. AI-based CAs are increasingly becoming a Frontline Service Technology (FST) to improve service quality in retail e-commerce customer service context while offering several cost-saving opportunities. Although these CAs potentially bring many opportunities, at this early stage, enterprise-level AI-based CA implementations frequently fail. There is a need for an in-depth understanding of how these CAs can be implemented successfully in retail e-commerce organisations to obtain the plethora of benefits conversational AI technology has to offer. In light of this deficit, this study investigates the customer service CAs implementation benefits, critical success factors (CSFs), and conversational interface`s success criteria that can positively influence the implementation success and general challenges organisations must pay close attention to during the implementation process to ensure the project success.

The present study adopted an interpretivist research philosophy and an inductive approach. The qualitative method and multiple case study research strategy were considered the most suitable approach for this investigation. An in-depth study was conducted with 7 UK e-commerce retailers who have successfully implemented an AI-based CA for their customer service purposes. The data collection was conducted through semi-structured interviews with technical and managerial level participants who directly contributed to the implementation project and also through observations of company online records. The data analysis was undertaken using content analysis supported by NVivo12 software.

This research made several contributions to knowledge. These included 1) Identifying a comprehensive set of 13 CSFs for CAs implementation success under three categories, namely: organisational, technological, and governance. 2) Identification of success criteria that can significantly influence an AI-based CA implementation success under three quality dimensions, namely: information quality (semantic analysis, knowledgebase creation), service quality (the personality of the CA), and system quality (usability of the CA). 3) Development of a synthesised model that contains CSFs and success criteria that support the CAs implementation success. In addition to these reflected theoretical contributions, this research also provides recommendations for top managers for a successful CAs implementation, particularly for, but not limited to, the UK retail e-commerce organisations.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AGI	Artificial General Intelligence
ASI	Artificial Super Intelligence
CAs	Conversational Agents
CASA	Computers Are Social Actors
DM	Dialogue Management
CSFs	Critical Success Factors
DL	Deep Learning
FLE	Frontline Employees
FST	Frontline Service Technology
GPU	Graphics Processing Units
GVA	Gross Value Added
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
IS	Information Systems
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLU	Natural Language Understanding
NLG	Natural Language Generation
ML	Machine Learning
RL	Reinforcement Learning
ROI	Return on Investment

Chapter 1 : Introduction

1.1 Research Background

The role of artificial intelligence (AI) today has progressed from initial sci-fi notions of movie robots to a new technological phenomenon that is poised to unleash the next wave of digital disruption to deliver real-life business benefits. Massive amounts of data, high computational power, and the availability of sophisticated algorithms are reshaping industries and have brought AI to a commercial level (Bughin et al., 2017). According to the World Economic Forum (2018), AI has been identified as the leading technology that drives the Fourth Industrial Revolution or industry 4.0 (Daugherty and Wilson, 2018). In a similar vein, the development of artificial intelligence is radically and rapidly changing the organisational frontline and customer service's very nature of the ways in which it can be delivered (Van Doorn et al., 2017). According to Gartner (2018), AI is ranked first as a strategic technology for organisations, and this has been proven by Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon, IBM, and others, all of whom through leveraging AI to deliver a better customer service experience.

In the context of AI, developing an intelligent dialogue system that can emulate human conversation has been a goal among AI practitioners stimulated by the 'Turing Test' for many decades (Turing 1950). This goal remained exclusive until the recent emergence of several commercial levels of conversational AI platforms in the market, such as Siri (Apple, 2011), Alexa (Amazon, 2014), Cortana (Microsoft, 2015), and Google Assistant (Google, 2016) (Fang, 2019). The emergence of 'AI-based Conversational Agents (CAs)' (also known as Conversational AI, Chatbots, Conversational interfaces, Virtual personal assistants, Avatars) that are capable of automating communication-powered by AI technology have opened new avenues using data to benefit not only for firms but also customers` value creation (Mikko et al., 2018; Gao et al., 2019). Conversational Agents (CAs) are built on the idea that people interact with intelligent systems using natural language, just like engaging in a conversation with another human being (McTear et al., 2016). Thus, a CA refers to an intelligent system designed to mimic human-level conversations offering a communication experience through digital and telecommunication technologies (Van Pinxteren et al., 2020; Adam et al., 2020). As Adam et al., (2020) explain, a CA is similar to a typical messaging application; however, the difference is a human chatting with a robot (AI system) instead of another human. These AI-powered CAs consist of two main categories, namely: voice-based and text-based

(Gnewuch et al., 2017). Although the voice-based has been recognised as the most popular CA version in the market today, many researchers have shown that even the text-based CAs capable of automating communication has the potential to usher in an era of significant efficiency and unprecedented productivity gains in various industries, particularly with e-commerce retail customer service tasks (Van Doorn et al., 2017; De Keyser et al., 2019; Adam et al., 2020; Rese et al., 2020).

In recent years, the increasing digitalisation and technological advancements have enabled especially the retail sector to dramatically advance its online operations. These advancements have created retailers the opportunity to connect and conduct transactions with their customers through multiple interactive touchpoints during customer shopping journeys using different channels (Omnichannel) such as websites, social media, mobile apps, and brick and mortar (Lynch and Barnes, 2020). In such an omnichannel setting, retail organisational frontlines, particularly in the e-commerce customer service context, have been identified as a critical area with great importance due to its ability to create effective interactions between the company, its customers, and other stakeholders (Singh et al., 2017; Cui et al., 2017). The organisational frontline refers to the discrete interactions that take place between an organisation and its customers (Singh et al., 2017). Traditionally, 'Frontline Employees (FLEs)' play a key role in organisations with 'high-touch, low-tech' service encounters with their customers to provide a pleasing and rewarding interaction (Giebelhausen et al., 2014). Traditional communication methods, i.e. email and telephone, communicating through live chat interfaces to provide real-time customer service to obtain information (i.e. product or service details) or assist them with their queries, have become an increasingly popular method for e-commerce retailers (Adam et al., 2020). Subsequently, providing real-time customer service via live chat services has transformed customer service with significant effects on customer satisfaction, trust, word of mouth intentions, and repurchase (Adam et al., 2020). However, in such a live chat environment, serving all the customers in a timely and personal manner while providing service quality and a balanced service efficiency at the same time has been challenging for many organisations. These challenges stem from live chat agents getting overwhelmed with chat requests, customer service agents getting overwhelmed with floods of emails and phone lines, and difficulty maintaining 24x 7 support service due to high operational cost (Adam et al., 2020; Cui, 2017), and this is where AI-powered text-based CAs come in.

As a solution for the above challenges, today, the service encounter is increasingly infused with technology. Prior research suggests that frontline service technology (FST), incorporating

technological elements with automated self-service presence using AI, can significantly change the nature of the communication between customers and organisations (Van Doorn et al., 2017; De Keyser et al., 2019). Many authors assert that AI-powered, text-based CAs (hereafter simply 'CAs') are increasingly becoming a popular FST to improve service quality and frontline-customer encounters in e-commerce retail settings while offering several cost-saving opportunities (Gnewuch et al., 2017; Van Doorn et al., 2017; De Keyser et al., 2019; Adam et al., 2020). Like many other industries, the retail sector is entering a new technological innovation phase with intelligent automation at its core offering a host of previously unimaginable capabilities with profound ramifications (Alaimo, 2018). Today, with recent technological and digital development, AI is being lauded as having the infinite potential to unlock opportunities to deliver fast, tailored experiences to meet those rapidly changing consumer needs of the UK retail e-commerce domain. The following section discusses the context of UK e-commerce retail and how CAs can be introduced for its customer service purposes as a self-service tool.

1.2 UK Retail E-Commerce Context

The activity of selling products or services directly to customers or end-users is referred to as retail (Hoang et al., 2019). The retail sector has defined as any company or individual that sells goods or services directly to customers, including shops, department stores, supermarkets, market stalls, and door-to-door salespeople, and the internet (Retail sector UK report, 2018). Retailers comprise the wholesale sector (which supplies retailers), the logistics sector (which connects wholesalers and producers with retailers), and the manufacturing sector (which produces the products sold by retailers). Although the idea of retail is often associated with the purchase of goods, the term can be applied to service providers, and these retail providers may also include retail banking and tourism (Pride et al., 2018). Generically retail can be differentiated between brick-and-mortar (selling from a fixed location as a department store, boutique, or kiosk) and online retailing or distance trading (E-commerce) (Weber and Schütte, 2019).

According to the British Retail Consortium (BRC) and advisory firm KPMG, 2019 was the worst of record for the British retail sector, with an overall decline in retail sales for the first time in 24 years as a dire performance on the high street dragged down the industry partly driven by online sales rising by 2.6% in November and December 2019. PWC's study on 'Retail Outlook 2020' states that the UK's economic outlook is uncertain given Brexit, with most economists forecasting little or no growth. As the report suggests, when consumer spending is

tight, retailers need to give consumers a reason to spend with them by offering better value (not just the lowest price). The report further argues that UK retailers must remain competitive in the market, offering something uniquely different to their consumers and offering greater accessibility with a particular focus on online shopping. To add to the point, the retail industry also faces increased pressure to successfully face challenges such as cost reduction, operation efficiency, customer expectations, inflation, and managing human resources (Waghmare, 2019).

In recent decades, e-commerce transactions in the UK retail sector have gained momentum due to its highly dynamic and rapidly changing online presence. As a result, retail consumers' spending has shifted to online channels with their changing purchasing habits seeking a hyper-personalised and convenient shopping experience (Koponen and Rytsy et al., 2019). 'E-commerce' or electronic commerce refers to transactions conducted via the internet or buying and selling goods and services via the internet (Koponen and Rytsy et al., 2019). A more comprehensive definition has been provided by Singh and Srivastava (2019), and they characterised e-commerce as the purchase and sale of goods and services over the internet or a network of computers, as well as the sharing of information for both internal and external stakeholders. E-commerce has been divided into two categories: B2B e-commerce (transactions between business to business), and B2C e-commerce (transactions between business to customers) (Singh and Srivastava, 2019). In the context of e-commerce, the UK has been identified as the most advanced e-commerce market in Europe, with the highest diverse online retailing environment offering more opportunities for rapid market growth of 44% in the next five years (Kendall, 2019). In addition to Europe's market leader position, with the onset of the COVID-19 crisis, the value of online shopping via e-commerce is estimated to reach 100 billion British pounds during 2020/2021(see fig 1.1), representing 45.4 million digital buyers accounting for 81.1% of the UK population (Fisher, 2020; Statista, 2021).

Figure 1.1: From 2012 to 2020, the value of online retail sales in the UK (in billion GBP)

Source: Statista (2021)

Due to the rapid adoption of digital technologies and evolving customer shopping behaviour in the retail context, today, e-commerce and retail have become highly dynamic and interchangeable concepts (Kendall, 2019; Fisher, 2020). Consequently, many authors claim that contemporary retail e-commerce consumers' purchasing patterns have been shifted from a shop in a single channel to move across channels (omnichannel) during different purchasing processes (Lynch and Barnes, 2020; Kuppelwieser and Klaus, 2020). According to Murfield et al., (2017), in contrast to traditional e-commerce shoppers, omnichannel shoppers spend 15-30 percent more, and retailers with a robust omnichannel customer service strategy have a 91 percent better customer retention. Regardless of the channel, delivering customers with seamless and consistent experiences for information exchange, promotion, and even after-sales services is cited as a top priority in omnichannel e-commerce retailing (Lynch and Barnes, 2020). Hence, applying omnichannel customer service strategies to serve customers creating a well-integrated and unified customer experience through any channel, any place at any time, has become crucial for e-commerce retailers (Lynch and Barnes, 2020; Kuppelwieser and Klaus, 2020).

E-commerce customer service infused by FST has been identified as a prominent customer service strategy since it is altering customer interactions as we know them at a rapid pace (Van Doorn et al., 2017; De Keyser et al., 2019). FST refers to organisations incorporating technological elements into their customers' 'frontline experience' (Van Doorn et al., 2017). FST is defined as any combination of hardware, software, information, and/or networks that supports the value creation between a service provider and customer at the organisational

frontline (De Keyser et al., 2019,). Traditionally, 'Frontline Employees (FLEs)' play a key role in organisations with their 'high-touch, low-tech' service encounters with their customers to provide a pleasing and rewarding interaction (Giebelhausen et al., 2014). Today, however, due to increasing challenges e-commerce organisations face to reduce cost, manage and maintain FLEs while offering more personalised service through bigdata insights, service encounter is increasingly infused with technology (Rust and Huang, 2014; De Keyser et al., 2019). Rapid advances in digital technologies have brought significant changes to service innovation's role with the introduction of technology-based self-service channels (Gnewuch et al., 2017). The authors have identified that AI-based CAs have a high potential to play an essential role as a key FST tool in the retail e-commerce omnichannel setting (De Keyser et al., 2019). This is due to the advances in AI and the massive popularity of communication via messenger platforms such as Facebook Messenger and WhatsApp in addition to company websites and Apps (Gnewuch et al., 2017; Van Doorn et al., 2017; Keyser et al., 2019; Rese et al., 2020; Adam et al., 2020).

As the recent literature claims, a new communication paradigm where companies can communicate to their customers via messaging platforms using text-based CAs whilst providing a human level touch have the potential to become the norm for many organisations in the near future (Rese et al., 2020). Today, communication with friends, acquaintances, and colleagues is increasingly taking place via messaging platforms such as WhatsApp or Facebook Messenger, and thus communication via text messages is not a new concept to the world (Gentsch, 2019). Figures 1.2 and 1.3 show the communication explosion over time using various apps in the market.

Figure 1.2: Messaging based communication explosion over time

Source: Van Doorn, (2016)

Figure 1.3: Most popular global messaging apps as of January 2021

(The number of monthly active users, presented in millions)

Source: Statista (2021)

The concept of 'conversations' is not new for any enterprise as every form of trading traditionally starts with a conversation. Yet, when it comes to online shopping, the term 'conversation' has taken a back seat due to the difficulties of having one-to-one conversations in real-time with many customers (Gentsch, 2019). Some authors have presented the view that although communicating through live chat interfaces has become an increasingly popular method among e-commerce retailers, in such live chat settings, providing service quality whilst maintaining a balanced service efficiency can be an extremely challenging task (Scherer et al., 2015; Adam et al., 2020).

Furthermore, as discussed above, communication via text messages is not a new concept to the world since communication with friends, acquaintances, and colleagues is increasingly taking place via messaging platforms such as WhatsApp or Facebook Messengers (see figure 1.2 and 1.3). Consequently, as the proportion of mobile/internet natives (users who grew up with digital services) is increasing, messaging services have also been growing due to the large number of people who use messaging apps (Gentsch, 2019). This approach enables retailers to meet their customers halfway online via their preferred channel using AI. As a part of this change, Alaimo, (2018) notes that by 2023 over 70% of CAs will be retail-based, and retailers will gain the most from AI technology (Alaimo, 2018). Subsequently, Gentsch (2019) postulates that retailers' next logical step could be to meet their customers halfway through online and social media and deliver their customer engagement in an automated self-service strategy without only attracting customers to their websites (Gentsch, 2019).

Hence, implementing CAs in retail creates new opportunities and capabilities for retailers by leveraging new possibilities, fastening processes, and making organisations adaptable to changes in the future (Meticulous Market Research, 2019). Through the implementation of such CAs, UK retail e-commerce organisations have the potential to bring a plethora of benefits to enhance their online shopping activities and unprecedented level of productivity while saving costs.

1.3 Research Rationale

The significance and the rationale of this study can be explained by a number of reasons. First, while CAs potentially expand cost and time-saving opportunities for e-commerce retailers and individual flexibility of their customer service, the implementation success of these CAs frequently fails (Brandtzaeg and Folstad, 2018; Adam et al., 2020). Despite technical advances at this early stage of AI-based CAs, reasons for such failures have been identified as unsatisfactory customer engagement and poor responses to user requests leading to a gap between system performance and user satisfaction (Luger and Sellen, 2016, Orłowski, 2017; Adam et al., 2020). Second, despite high expectations, many organisations' lack of understanding of how to use CAs effectively and lack of competence in implementing CAs have also been identified as primary reasons for such failures (Brandtzaeg and Folstad, 2018).

Third, Gnewuch, et al., (2017) advocate the view that there's extensive research on CAs design and technical issues of CA systems in the context of information systems (IS), computer science (CS), and human-computer interaction (HCI) related fields. Similarly, Lo and Lee (2017) noted the limited availability of literature about AI-based CAs from a business and organisational perspective as many of the existing studies about CAs are based on the technical perspective, such as 'passing the Turing Test'. Therefore, Lo and Lee (2017), highlight the importance of paying more attention to “how businesses can drive benefits from the use of CAs, what is the future role of CAs, and other related issues” in future CAs related studies (p.218). Dwivedi et al., (2019) also postulate the view that “there is a lack of research on identifying the critical success factors affecting the current use of AI and its impact in the era of big data.” (p.11)

Fourth, a variety of issues related to CAs have been widely discussed in white papers, online forums, trade magazines, industry reports, and yet to date, little or no comprehensive research or formal theorising can be found with respect to CAs implementation success-related topics in the literature. The literature findings suggest, applying conversational AI technology to the

enterprise context is still in its infancy and a relatively new phenomenon to many organisations, and thus it takes time to reveal its implementation success attributes and organisational implications (Lo and Lee, 2017). Although CAs adoption is still in its infancy in the business context, the practice of CAs implementation is less likely to flourish without corresponding theoretical foundations and rigorous research.

Based on the above facts, it has already raised some complex questions about how CAs can be used to augment frontline service employee capabilities, which areas must go right to implement CAs successfully to boost the customer service of the e-commerce domain, and what challenges companies are facing during the implementation process. In light of this deficit, this study proposes to explore the critical success factors (CSFs) and success criteria as focal points organisations must pay close attention to during the implementation and ensure the project's success. This study only investigates the text-based CAs implementation success from organisational and managerial perspectives, and thus, the focus of voice-based CAs is not within the scope.

1.4 Research Aim and Objectives

This research aims to understand how AI-based conversational agents (CAs) can be implemented successfully in the UK retail e-commerce context as a frontline self-service tool by meeting the following objectives:

- (1) To conduct a comprehensive and critical literature review on AI technology and AI-based conversational agents (text-based) in the UK and particularly in the UK retail e-commerce sector.
- (2) To investigate customer service use case benefits of implementing AI-based conversational agents in the UK retail e-commerce sector.
- (3) To explore critical success factors (CSFs) and the success criteria that are significant in AI-based conversational agents' implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce sector.
- (4) To investigate the major challenges the UK retail e-commerce organisations face during the process of AI-based conversational agents implementation.
- (5) To provide a set of feasible recommendations on the CSFs of AI-based conversational agents implementation.

1.5 Research Questions

1. What are the benefits of implementing AI-based conversational agents to the UK Retail e-commerce sector as a customer self-service tool?
2. What are the significant CSFs and the success criteria that could contribute to ensure AI-based conversational agents' implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce sector?
3. What are the challenges the UK retail e-commerce organisations are facing when implementing AI-based conversational agents?
4. What are the recommendations the UK e-commerce retailers must follow when implementing AI-based conversational agents for the first time as a customer self-service tool?

1.6 Intended Research Contributions

1.6.1 Contribution to Theory

The contribution to the knowledge of this study includes:

First: This study extends the current CSFs literature into a novel concept of AI-powered, text-based CAs implementation CSFs particularly focusing on the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. This study is one of the early academic studies highlighting such a comprehensive set of CSFs explicitly focusing on enhancing organisational understanding towards AI-based CAs implementation success and is the first study of its kind in the UK retail e-commerce context.

Second: In addition to determining a comprehensive set of CSFs, identifying a CA's quality dimensions also play a crucial role in ensuring implementation success. Although there was an extensive number of studies that have discussed how DeLone and McLean's (2003) three quality dimensions can be applicable for Information Systems implementation in general, there were limited studies that have examined how these three quality dimensions can be applied for AI-infused CAs implementation. This study is one of the early academic studies that have discussed CAs implementation success criteria under three D & M model's quality dimensions and is the first study of its kind in the UK retail e-commerce context.

Third: The field of AI-based CAs implementation as an academic discipline in the organisational context is new and still evolving. While AI-based customer service CAs benefits and its implementation-related challenges have been widely discussed in white papers, online forums, trade magazines, and yet to date, little or no comprehensive research can be found with

respect to the phenomenon under investigation. By investigating the customer service-related benefits e-commerce retailers can achieve by implementing CAs and general challenges e-commerce retailers highly likely might face during the implementation, this study provides another significant perspective to increase the overall body of knowledge on AI-powered, text-based CAs implementation.

Fourth: The study findings of the set of CSFs and success criteria could serve as a good representation in customer self-service use cases in other UK service sectors such as insurance, health care, and hospitality due to the limited literature availability.

1.6.2 Contribution to Practice

Despite technical advances, at this early stage, many AI-powered, text-based CAs implementations frequently fail within a few months after the launch. One of the reasons for such failures has been identified as e-commerce retailers choosing 'easy to deploy, off the shelf' CAs (without any AI capabilities in the system) due to the lack of knowledge these organisations have about this specific technology (Brandtzaeg and Folstad, 2018). Consequently, organisations are forced to abandon their CAs a few months after the launch when they get complaints from frustrated customers. To address this issue, the present study provides top managers with recommendations and guidelines for a successful CAs implementation process in order to 1) identify the most suitable customer self-service use case objectives; 2) determine the most suitable conversational AI implementation partner; 3) determine the most appropriate implementation strategy; 4) decide the AI components that must be infused to a self-service CA to deliver more accurate and intelligent answers; 5) determine the change management strategies, 6) role and responsibilities the UK retail e-commerce organisations must maintain to ensure the governance of their CA, 8) improve the CAs performance after the launch.

1.7 Thesis Structure

This research thesis is divided into seven chapters, and a summary of each chapter is as follows:

Chapter one: Research Introduction

The first chapter presents the background to the study: this includes the research problem, the research context of the UK retail e-commerce service setting in general, research rationale,

followed by the research aim and objectives. It also highlights the significance of the study by presenting the theoretical and practical contributions of the research.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

This chapter begins with a comprehensive and critical literature review on Artificial Intelligence technology and AI-powered text-based CAs. Subsequently, this chapter reviews the literature regarding (a) the benefits of implementing CAs as a customer self-service tool, (b) CSF and success criteria that are significant to CAs implementation success, (c) significant challenges organisations face during the implementation that would hinder the implementation success. Drawing on a synthesis of theoretical underpinnings, a conceptual framework for successful CA implementation in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context is developed for this research.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

This chapter discusses the present study's position in relation to the major scientific research paradigms and philosophies. It then explains the research strategy, data collection methods, and data analysis methods chosen to fulfil the study's objectives. The rationale for choosing the interpretivism philosophy, the qualitative research method, the multiple case study strategy, the semi-structured interview method, and the analytic tools and techniques selected are justified and explained.

Chapter Four: Case Study Backgrounds

This chapter presents a summary of the seven UK case studies that have successfully implemented a CA for their frontline customer service tasks. Each case study discusses the company background, the motivation behind implementing a CA as a customer self-service tool, and the background of the implemented CA.

Chapter Five: Analysis of Results

This chapter presents and analyses the qualitative data gathered using semi-structured interviews from the seven case studies. The presentation of findings is grouped into three sections and presented according to the three main research questions. The first section analyses the benefits that have been achieved by successfully implementing a CA. The second section analyses the CSFs and the success criteria that have positively influenced and

contributed towards CAs implementation success. The third and final section analyses the challenges faced during the implementation.

Chapter Six: Discussion

The significance of the empirical findings is comprehensively explained and associated with the research objectives. The present study's data analysis findings are linked to the literature review findings and discussed to draw the study's conclusions. The discussion and outcome of this chapter are based on three of the main research questions. It discusses the findings under the implementation benefits the UK retail e-commerce organisations can be achieved by implementing a self-service CA; CSFs and the success criteria that are significant to CAs implementation success; and the challenges that would hinder the success when implementing a CA in the context of UK retail e-commerce customer service.

Chapter Seven: Conclusion

This chapter summarises the entire research study, including the key findings, contribution to theory and practice. This section offers a set of recommendations for UK e-commerce retail organisations to follow as focal points when implementing an AI-based CA for the first time as a customer self-service tool. This chapter also highlights the limitations of the study, potential directions for future research, and also a personal reflection of the research journey.

Chapter 2 : Literature Review

When it comes to the discussion of implementing AI-based CAs in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context successfully, it is imperative to understand what AI is, where it currently stands, what an AI-based CA is, and what value these CAs can provide as a customer-self service tool. These constructs are explored in the first section of this chapter to familiarise the reader with the main concepts relevant to the phenomenon of AI-based CAs implementation in the UK retail e-commerce sector and fulfil the first research objective. As the second step, this chapter reviews the literature regarding the benefits of implementing CAs as a customer self-service tool. As the third step, this chapter critically reviews and examines the available CSF and success criteria that are significant to CAs implementation success. Subsequently, drawing on a synthesis of theoretical underpinnings of available CSFs and success criteria, a conceptual framework for successful CA implementation in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context will be developed. The fourth step of this chapter investigates the significant challenges organisations face during the implementation that would hinder the implementation success.

2.1 Artificial Intelligence

Although there are many variations of Artificial Intelligence as a technology, the concept can be broadly defined as an umbrella term that consists of a heterogeneous set of tools, techniques, and algorithms (Jarrahi, 2018; Gates, 2020). AI, as an umbrella term, is used to refer to machines capable of performing tasks in a way that would be considered smart, simulating human-level intelligence (Jarrahi, 2018; Gates, 2020). The most common subsets of AI are: Machine Learning (and deep learning), Natural Language Processing, Expert Systems, Robotics, Computer Vision (Najafabadi et al., 2015; Jablonska and Polkowski, 2017; Simon, 2018; Simon, 2018). This section covers the background concepts about the subfields of AI relevant to power CAs (Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing), which is essential to the context of this research. This study only aims to investigate the CAs implementation success and its critical success factors that would drive organisations towards that success from organisational and managerial perspectives. Therefore, this study will only discuss the key themes related to CAs and will not dig deep into the technicalities or other subsets of AI.

2.1.1 Definition and development of AI

By the 1940s, computer scientists such as Alan Mathison Turing, John von Neumann, and Norbert Wiener wanted to create programmes beyond only 'processing zeros and ones' that would allow computers to learn and equip them with programmes that contained intelligence (Buchanan, 2005). Their interest also included finding out the ability to self-copy, learn, and control their environment, model the human brain imitating human learning, and simulate biological evolution (Mitchel, 1999). Research in Artificial Intelligence began after World War 2 in 1947 by Alan Mathison Turing mainly after publishing an article about 'whether machines could think' in 1950 (García et al., 2018). This article is where the famous 'The Imitation Game' comes from, which introduces the '*Turing Test*' to understand if a machine is intelligent enough to confuse it with a human being (García et al., 2018; Simon, 2019). In that article, Turing also explained how an intelligent machine should be created, starting with the creation of a child machine (mind) that would be learning as an adult (McCarthy, 2001; Simon, 2019). Subsequently, in the decade of the 1950s, many more researchers joined this field, and later, John McCarthy, Marvin L. Minsky, Nathaniel Rochester, and Claude E. Shannon coined the term 'Artificial Intelligence' in 1956 in the Dartmouth Summer Research Project (Russel and Norvig, 2003). This research project considered the birthplace of the field of AI, and the proposed investigation examined the principles of learning another type of intelligence and see how computers could simulate it (Russel and Norvig, 2003).

AI generally refers to an umbrella term for the science of making machines smart inspired by biological systems (Simon, 2018). AI encompasses multiple technologies that include machine learning (and deep learning), natural language processing, computer vision, and machine reasoning (Najafabadi et al., 2015; Simon, 2018). AI is primarily inspired by the way people use their nervous system and the human body to sense, learn, reason, and take action. Therefore, research on AI focuses on these four critical components of human intelligence, namely: learning, reasoning, problem-solving, and perception (Najafabadi et al., 2015; Jablonska and Polkowski, 2017; Simon, 2018).

There are multiple Artificial Intelligence (AI) descriptions and not a universally accepted definition by practitioners of what it covers and does not cover. Shenoy (1985) described AI as an obscure branch of computer science. Definitions of AI have evolved and changed over time. For example, Najafabadi et al., (2015) define AI as emulating the human brain's ability to study, analyse, learn and make decisions, particularly for complex problems.

According to Jablonska and Polkowski (2017), AI is a computer-based analytical process to create intelligent computational systems. Bughin et al., (2017) refer AI to as machines' ability to exhibit human-like intelligence, such as solving a problem without using hand-coded software containing detailed instructions. Akerkar (2019) described AI as various tools and technologies that can be combined in diverse ways to sense, cognise, and perform with the ability to learn from experience and adapt over time. Pannu (2015) argues that AI is neither psychology nor computer science as it emphasises computation, reasoning, perception, and action. When defining Artificial Intelligence, understanding the meaning of 'intelligence' is also a vital part. Intelligence is defined as the ability to achieve objectives/solve problems similar to various types and degrees that occur among humans, some machines, and many animals Jablonska and Polkowski (2017).

Over the past sixty years, AI had ups (known as AI Summers) and also downs (known as AI Winters) (Stone et al., 2016). Similar to AI Summers, there were a couple of 'AI Winters' (withdrawal of funding) when advances in AI stagnated for several years as AI's capabilities didn't live up to the initial hype (Simon, 2018; Burges, 2018). The first `AI Winter` occurred between 1974 and 1980. The second AI Winter lasted from 1987 to 1993, and it was clearly due to the failure of 'expert systems' to meet their over-inflated expectations (Daugherty and Wilson, 2018). Buchanan (2005) claims that philosophy, fiction, and logic theory influenced early AI studies heavily. According to CAICT and Gartner (2018), AI growth goes through three stages: infancy (1956-1980), industrialization (1980-2000), and thriving (2000-present) (2000-2018).

Figure 2.1: AI development milestones

Source: CAICT & Gartner, 2018)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Figure can be found in CAICT & Gartner, 2018.

After decades of false starts, at present, AI is on the verge of a breakthrough, with the latest progress propelled by machine learning. AI-powered systems are forecasted to add US\$15 trillion to the global economy by 2030 (IDRC, 2019). It has been estimated that AI could add \$814 billion (£630bn) to the UK economy by 2035, increasing the annual growth rate of GVA from 2.5 to 3.9%, with the possibility to increase productivity by up to 14.3% by 2030 (PWC, 2017). As a result of these future predictions, to build the UK government's own AI strategy, in 2019 UK has invested £1 billion to support AI development in industry and academia across the country (Forbes, 2018). According to PWC (2017), there will be significant gains as a result of adopting and implementing AI across all UK regions; Scotland £16.7bn in 2030 (8.4% of GDP), England £204.5bn in 2030 (10.6% of GDP), Northern Ireland £2.6bn in 2030 (5.4% of GDP) and Wales £7.9bn in 2030 (9.8% of GDP).

Recent studies have identified four key drivers to boost the third stage and achieve the flourishing level depicted in figure 2.1, and also this time to avoid another AI winter. Those key drivers are 1) The role of Big Data, 2) The Role of Cheap Storage, 3) The Role of Faster Processers, 4) The role of Ubiquitous Connectivity.

2.1.2 Key drivers for the development of AI

1) Role of big data

The term 'Big Data' describes the large, diverse sets of information from various data sources that consist of volume, variety, and velocity. 'Volume' refers to the size of the data which could be available in multiple terabytes or petabytes. 'Variety' refers to the heterogeneity of the available data sets (i.e.structured, semi-structured, and unstructured datasets), and the 'velocity' refers to the rapid pace at which data is being generated (OECD, 2020). The amount of data generated across the globe is doubling in size every two years, and as a result, by 2020 there will be 44 zettabytes (or 44 trillion gigabytes) of data created or copied every year (Burgess, 2018). The availability of large and diverse data sets is classified as the first driver for the explosion of interest and activity in AI (Burgess, 2018). Data availability has been identified as a critical component of AI technology, and as Burgess (2018) argues, without data AI technology would be worthless. To train an AI system with any degree of accuracy, it would generally need thousands if not millions of examples as the more complex the AI system gets, the more examples the system required. More data translate into more insights and higher accuracy because it exposes algorithms to more examples they can use to reject incorrect answers and identify correct answers (Daugherty and Wilson, 2018).

2) The Role of Cheap Storage

All the data that is being created needs to be stored somewhere: the rapidly diminishing cost of storage (coupled with the speed that data can be accessed) has been identified as another vital factor for AI success. In 1980, one gigabyte of storage would cost an average of \$437,500. Ten years later in 1990 that had dropped to \$11,200, in 2000, it was around \$11.00 per gigabyte, and in 2005 it was \$1.24. In 2016 the average one-gigabyte cost stood at just under 2 cents (\$0.019). Today it's not just costs that have shrunk; size has too. In 1956, the hard drive was the size of a large shed and only had a capacity of 5Mb, but today, which would be enough to store one MP3 song (Burgess, 2018).

3) The role of faster processes

Just as cheap storage for massive amounts of data, 'faster processor speed' is also vitally important for AI success. During the previous AI summers, traditional central processing units or CPUs were not ideal for processing large amounts of data sets. Graphical processing units (GPU) developed today to run computer visualisations such as computer games that can process images 40 to 80 times faster than the fastest versions available in 2013, identified more suitable for AI technology. Improvement in processor speed helps enormously for AI systems during the initial development and design of the models as well as these AI systems' day-to-day activities to use the most up-to-date models (Burgess, 2018; Daugherty and Wilson, 2018).

4) The role of Ubiquitous Connectivity

At present, the final driver working in AI's favour is connectivity. Today, networks such as broadband, 4G, and 5G have become fast enough to allow large amounts of data to be distributed between servers and devices. This has enabled AI technology to carry out the bulk of the intensive real-time processing of data to servers in data centres. Amazon's Alexa (on the echo) and Apple's Siri (on the iPhone) are prime examples of sophisticated AI applications that exploit processing power in data centres to carry out the bulk of the hard work. Faster connectivity also helps to train an AI system/model and connect to share learnings. (Burgess, 2018; Daugherty and Wilson, 2018).

2.1.3 Types of Artificial Intelligence

AI Technology can be split into three broad types: 'Narrow Artificial Intelligence, Artificial General Intelligence, and Artificial Super Intelligence'.

i) Narrow AI (Weak AI)

This type of AI is what we see all around us in computers today; meaning, intelligent systems that have been trained or learned how to carry out 'specific tasks' without being explicitly programmed how to do so. This is called narrow AI, mainly because unlike humans, these types of AI systems can only learn or be taught how to do specific tasks (tech republic, 2018). For example, this type of AI can be used in organisations to do narrow tasks such as: to answer factual questions, provide directions, manage business schedules, make recommendations based on past choices, prevent online fraud, and so on (Rose, 2018). Narrow AI can also be seen in the latest generation of personal assistants/ AI-based CAs (chatbots). CAs include Apple's Siri and Microsoft's Cortana, enabling users to talk to these apps and ask questions – converting spoken language into machine language and use pattern matching to answer user's questions and respond to requests (Rose, 2018).

ii) Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)

AGI is the type of adaptable intellect found in humans, a flexible form of intelligence capable of learning how to carry out vastly different tasks that humans are capable of doing (Simon, 2018). AGI is the sort of AI more commonly seen in movies but which doesn't exist today. Some AI experts believe such projections are wildly conceptual, given our limited understanding of the human brain, and believe that AGI is still decades away (Simon, 2018; Tech Republic, 2018).

iii) Artificial Superhuman Intelligence (ASI)

This type of AI is far superior beyond the comprehension of human beings and smarter than the smartest humans that can understand and solve problems (Gates, 2020). Many AI experts have warned that building an intelligence superior to humans could negatively affect our existence (Gates, 2020).

The literature provides evidence to claim that we are currently using AI technology called 'Narrow AI', which performs one narrow task as opposed to 'Artificial General Intelligence', or 'Artificial Superhuman Intelligence', which seeks to perform any intellectual task that a human can do (Vorhies, 2016; Bughin et al., 2017). This thesis's primary focus is on 'narrow AI' because it has near-term business potential, as AGI and ASI have yet to arrive.

In the context of the present study, the term 'AI-based' is added when describing CAs mainly since these types of CAs are powered by artificial intelligence's two of the main subsets,

namely: Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning (ML). The following section presents a brief discussion of the CAs, the types of available CAs, technologies that are used to power the 'intelligent' component in a CA, and a sample customer self-service CA conversation to provide an in-depth overview of the phenomenon under investigation.

2.2 AI-Powered Text-Based Conversational Agents

CAs are defined as "software that accepts natural language as input and generates the same language as output while engaging in a conversation with the user" (Griol et al., 2013, p. 760). A CA is a discussion-like interface in which companies leverage their data combined with AI subsets of natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML) to provide information and converse with their customers automatically (Mikko et al., 2018). However, a more holistic definition has been provided by Gnewuch et al., (2017), and they describe a CA as a computer program capable of eliciting human-like conversation in natural language includes *written* and *spoken*. The interfaces of CAs vary in types and are classified differently with a plethora of terms such as chatbots, avatars, intelligent personal assistants (IPA), and digital or virtual assistant interface agents (McGoldrick et al., 2008; Luger & Sellen, 2016; Ugale, 2019). Therefore, CAs are referred to as the umbrella term for software that incorporates Natural Language Processing (NLP) to converse in natural language with its user.

The idea of a CA started long ago in 1950 by Alan Turing when he proposed the '*Turing Test*' to gauge computer intelligence in which a human being should not be able to distinguish a machine from another human being based on the replies provided to questions by both the parties (Vincze, 2017). After the inception of the 'Turing Test', in 1966 Joseph Weizenbaum developed the first Natural Language Processing CA ever coded called 'ELIZA' (see figure 2.2) which simulates a dialogue with a Rogerian psychotherapist (Weizenbaum, 1966).

Figure 2.2: Sample conversation with ELIZA

Source: Rubin and Chen (2010)

Since a therapist's role was understood to be non-judgmental and passive, ELIZA was designed to often rephrase patient statements in the form of a question by following the typical conversational flow (Weizenbaum, 1966). However, ELIZA was only managed to make simple responses based on the user's input against a set of stored patterns with both scripted and limited responses and were primarily developed to pass the Turing test (McTear et al., 2016; Shah et al., 2016). Despite its shortcomings, ELIZA was the most well-known and revolutionary CA system in AI history (Shah et al., 2016).

Subsequently, in recent years due to advancements in artificial intelligence, specifically in natural language processing and machine learning, CAs` capabilities have enormously improved (Berg, 2015; Knijnenburg and Willemsen, 2016). Today, AI-based CAs focus on providing intelligent responses while exhibiting the characteristics typically associated with intelligence in human communication (Chen and Thorimbert, 2010). Gnewuch et al., (2017) classified modern CAs in two dimensions: (1) developed for general purposes, (2) developed for a specific domain (see Table 2.1).

Table 2.1: Types of AI-based conversational agents

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Table can be found in Gnewuch, U., Morana, S., and Maedche, A. (2017) 'Towards Designing Cooperative and Social Conversational Agents for Customer Service, Short Paper, to appear in: Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS)

Source: Gnewuch et al., (2017)

Text-based CAs are often referred to as natural dialogue systems (Zadrozny et al., 2000; Shah et al., 2016) that use text messages to interact with its user. At present, Domain-specific text-based CAs that are limited to a specific domain has been identified as the more popular version with examples in retail (Bridgwater et al., 2017), healthcare (Miner et al., 2016), e-commerce (BenMimoun et al., 2016), insurance (Mikko et al., 2018) in contrast with General-purpose text-based CAs. Speech-based CAs are often called virtual or digital assistants (Sarikaya 2017; McTear et al., 2016), primarily relying on spoken input. At present, General-purpose speech-based CAs have been identified as the more popular version in contrast with domain-specific speech-based CAs. General-purpose speech-based CA examples are 'Apple's Siri, Amazon's Alexa, Google Now, and Amazon's Echo' to support users in finding information or accomplishing basic tasks (Gnewuch et al., 2017). For this study's purpose, the researcher only seeks to investigate domain-specific text-based CAs (hereafter just CAs) that are more suitable for e-commerce customer self-service operations.

As mentioned in chapter one, most CA implementations fail after the launch mainly because top managers lack of knowledge they have in regards to the technical aspect of artificially intelligent powered CAs. Therefore, before discussing the business aspect of CAs, to provide a rich context to enhance the understanding of this relatively new concept of using CAs as an FST self-service tool, it is vital to get a brief understanding of the technical aspect of CAs. Therefore, the following section discusses the technologies that power an AI-based CA. Figure 2.3 shows the different technologies used in a CA in order to deliver intelligent responses simulating components of a human conversation (i.e. reason, perceive, understand, learn and interact). Some of these technologies (NLP, Machine Learning, reinforcement learning) have been discussed in-depth in section 2.4.

Figure 2.3: Technologies used in an AI-based conversational agent

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Figure can be found in Deloitte, 2018

Source: Deloitte (2018)

i) Natural Language Processing (NLP)

'Natural Language Processing (NLP)' refers to computers' ability to understand natural human language or process large amounts of natural language data during human-machine communication-related tasks (Deng and Liu, 2018). NLP is a subset of AI that helps create more sophisticated CAs and generate pre-programmed responses to user queries and improve responsiveness to simulate a conversation (Ranavare and Kamath, 2020). NLP helps the CA understand speech and text-based human commands and is defined as one of the critical components of a CA that forms the basis to recognise user requests by their language (Khurana et al., 2017). NLP has the capability to extract and analyse the meaning of responses received through multiple forms of communication using speech recognition, natural language understanding, and then generate responses (Lester et al., 2004). To truly be effective and make business processes automated, CAs must have natural language processing (NLP) and deep neural networks to extract meaning from the input and generate output from that same natural human language (Nuruzzaman and Hussain, 2018). NLP consists of two main components: Natural Language Understanding (NLU) and Natural Language Generation (NLG). 'NLU' refers to the CA's ability to convert chunks of human language text or voice (user input) into a more formal machine-readable format. 'NLG' refers to the CA's ability to convert information from its databases or semantic intents into the natural human language (Baes et al., 2020).

ii) Machine Learning (ML)

Machine learning is one of the significant subsets of AI that refers to the study of computer algorithms that improve through the experience without being explicitly programmed (Oliver, 2014). Learning in humans is mostly composed of memorising, undertaking comprehension tasks, and learning from examples (Oliver, 2014). In cognitive science and related fields, the term learning is used to express the process in which obtaining information through observation (Plamen, 2012; Oliver, 2014). Thus, machine learning is the process of teaching a computer system how to make accurate predictions with the use of data. Machine learning in a CA enables the system to better respond to the user by analysing training data sets and previous user conversations. The machine learning component is also identified as a necessary component in a CA to improve intent recognition (Ramezani, 2014). According to (Rose, 2018, p.19), "Machine learning still qualifies as weak AI, since the computer doesn't understand what's being said; it only matches symbols and identifies patterns. The noticeable difference is that instead of having an expert provide the patterns, the computer identifies patterns in the data. Over time, the computer becomes smarter". Rose, (2018) further points out that fuelling the rise of machine learning is the availability of massive amounts of data, often referred to as big data.

iii) Reinforcement Learning (RL)

RL is a type of machine learning that learns based on the world that surrounds it, mainly from the outside world's answers based on its actions through trial-error learning while criticising them if they were good or bad. RL is based on how a system ought to take actions in an environment to maximize long-term rewards where a penalty is given for a wrong output, and a reward is given for the correct output. The primary purpose of deploying RL in a CA is to enhance a CA's self-added performance and satisfy the user`s request in the shortest time.

iv) Dialogue Management (DM)

Dialogue management or Dialogue Manager refers to the central controller of a CA's dialogue system (Zhou et al., 2020). Dialogue management defines the CA`s conversational behaviour in response to user utterances according to the conversational environment (McTear et al., 2016). Dialogue manager`s fundamental task is to decide what action or response the CA should take for a user query (input) and usually involves four main tasks, namely: i) updating the dialogue context, ii) providing a context for interpretation, iii) coordinating with other

sources of information (i.e. results of database queries, application domain knowledge, and the user's previous conversation history), iv) deciding the most suitable response to generate (McTear et al., 2016; Larsson, 2003).

DM is responsible for keeping track of the dialogue state and dialogue policy when responding to a specific user query (Zhou et al., 2020). Once the CA has selected the user query response, the dialogue manager goes through several communication strategies to deliver the response in a human-like manner while focusing on going beyond simple Q & A scripted answers. Dialogue management is usually designed to achieve three high-level objectives: user engagement, coherence, and user experience (Fang et al., 2018). '*User engagement*' consists of promoting a diversity of interaction strategies that maintain user interest. '*Coherence*' refers to the dialogue manager's focus to maintain user interaction by choosing content related to the same topic during a conversation session. '*User experience*' refers to the dialogue manager's focus to enhance the conversation experience through the CA's explicit and implicit actions and through user instructions to have a seamless conversation (Fang et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2020).

v) Intent Recognition

An *Intent* refers to the user's goal (or intention) in mind when sends a message to the CA (Ranavare and Kamath, 2020). Intent recognition has been identified as a critical component for a CA's functionality as the CA's ability to parse intent is the ultimate determinant factor for the level of success during an interaction between the CA and user. An intent represents a mapping between what a user says and determining the CA's next actions. When user inputs trigger specific intents, intent recognition involves the CA recognising that the corresponding steps must be taken following detailed information and user request parameters (Adamopoulou and Moussiades, 2020). In order to ensure the effectiveness of intent recognition, CAs must be programmed well and trained using training data sets while using machine learning for continuous improvements to enhance the intent recognition capabilities (Ranavare and Kamath, 2020; Adamopoulou and Moussiades, 2020). A well-trained CA's intent recognition has the ability to understand what the user is requesting, even if phrased unexpectedly, and to avoid roadblocks during a conversation.

vi) Entity Recognition

Entity recognition is defined as the conversational context variables recognition from the knowledge repositories used in a CA to extract parameter values and provide personalised and accurate responses for user intents. Entities contain words and phrases with similar characteristics and are categorised into 'system entities and user entities'. The entity recognition process involves identifying user names, phone numbers, email addresses, organisations, places, and dates, categorising and identifying a specific user (Ranavare and Kamath, 2020). Moreover, in addition to these examples, there might be many more entities and entity types in a real-world scenario. For instance, when placing a coffee order via a CA, 'coffee type (a regular espresso)' can be defined as a critical and yet a simply structured entity during that conversation. However, suppose it's a home delivery order. In that case, the 'Address' can be defined as a critical and complex, less structured entity from an extensive set of addresses in the city or town (Shevat, 2017).

vii) Q &A Pairs/Script

In customer self-service CAs, providing responses to frequently asked company-specific questions is one of the main goals of implementing a CA. Creating the CA's knowledge base with question/response pairs using the company-specific data sets helps the CA understand the user queries coherently and effectively generate the most appropriate responses. There are two types of Q & A data sets training in a CA: Manual training and Automated training. '*Manual training*' refers to domain experts create frequently asked questions for specif use case objectives and map the most suitable responses a CA can generate during a conversation. '*Automated training*' refers to submitting different types of company documents to the CA (i.e. Q&A pairs, policy documents) and let the CA train itself using AI components (Deloitte, 2018; Ayanouz et al., 2020).

The above section provided an overview of the technologies that are powered by CA to generate a human-level conversation experience. The following section presents a summary of a CA-user interaction process depicted in figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: A Summary of a customer self-service CA-user conversation process

Source, Mislevics et al., (2018)

Step 1: A user initiates a new conversation for a self-service query with a CA via one of the supported channels (i.e. company website, Facebook messenger, skype, or a mobile app), and depending on the channel used, a user will be identified or remain anonymous. Identified users have the advantage of engaging with the CA to continue the conversation at a later occasion (i.e. to ask follow-up questions), whilst anonymous users have to start a new conversation each time when they converse (Mislevics et al., 2018).

Step 2: Upon receiving a new message, the CA has to identify the user's goal to accomplish and then provide responses coherently according to the conversation's context. Two popular approaches to generating CA responses are 'retrieval-based and generative-based methods'. Retrieval-based techniques rely on large data-based responses and match the most appropriate answer for the user request. This approach looks for particular sentence structures and generates responses as an output of a machine learning model. This approach's main advantage is that an organisation or the CA maintainers can control the responses generated for user queries and avoid inappropriate replies. On the other hand, generative-based techniques rely on the CA to generate responses without the need for specific database examples. However, as of today, due to some famous CA failures (Microsoft 'Tay'), the industry is not convinced of

the potential of deploying only generative-based techniques for CAs and encourages a hybrid approach (Perez. S., 2016; Tammewar et al., 2017; Mislevics et al., 2018).

Step 3: In a scenario where the CA cannot respond to a specific query or handle a conversation by itself, it can pass the conversation to a human operator. This allows the CA to submit questions received from the user to a live chat agent/or a customer service agent (Mislevics et al., 2018).

To better understand the possible usage of CAs as a self-service tool in the UK retail e-commerce setting, it is necessary to reflect upon the new customer service organisational capabilities it can bring to retail e-commerce organisations in the UK. Thus, the following section presents and discusses CA customer service use cases and the benefits derived from the literature.

2.3 AI-based CAs Implementation Benefits

Creating and conveying value for customers has been deemed the central mission for all customer service settings. Customer service capabilities have been considered central to the process of increasing productivity leading to greater organisational competitiveness. CAs as an FST tool that shows autonomy and independent learning characteristics make them an important organisational capability to generate value and benefits not only in B2B but also in B2C retail e-commerce markets. As the initial step, to better understand the possible usage of CAs before the implementation process begins, it is necessary to reflect upon the available benefits CAs have to offer in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. Assuming that CAs provide new customer service organisational competencies, this section presents and discusses the existing literature on the CAs implementation benefits.

i). Enhance the human agents` productivity

Customer engagement`s ultimate goal is to provide deep, intense, and tangible customer experiences to meet their different expectations while receiving customer loyalty, positive word of mouth, increase sales and ultimately enhance company profits (Atwal & Williams, 2009; Chung et al., 2018). During achieving that goal, traditional `customer – FLE` interactions have become somewhat obsolete (Chung et al., 2018). Customers who have previously used regular human service interactions now find online services as effective, accessible, and both time and cost-saving (Escobar, 2016; Chung et al., 2018). Whilst industry experts and researchers agree that there is nothing like the quality of one to one, human to human

interaction to boost customer engagement and service delivery, this approach is increasingly becoming a challenge with the popularity of e-commerce and online shopping (Gnewuch et al., 2017; Cancel, and Gerhardt, 2019). For instance, to simultaneously interact with 100 potential customers with personalised conversations through 'live chat agents' (human service agents) in a busy e-commerce retail environment would require a large group of live chat human agents around the clock. During this process, improving efficiency without compromising service quality while satisfying every customer has been identified as a significant customer service challenge in the retail e-commerce setting (Scherer et al., 2015). As a solution to address these challenges, CAs are being lauded to have the infinite potential to unlock opportunities and deliver fast, tailored experiences to meet those customer service needs (Gnewuch et al., 2017).

Human service agents were once the primary source of the contact point to gather additional information, and technology changes are now allowing CAs and service agents to work together (Forbes, 2017a, Chung et al., 2018). Recent literature has moved from the somewhat dated concept of AI-based machines replacing all human workers, and studies have now recognised how AI can be used to augment human capabilities, with the idea of 'humans in the loop' (Katz, 2017; Kumar, 2017). Meaning, the concept of artificial intelligence must be revisited and redefined towards how humans and machines need to work symbiotically to augment and enhance each other's capabilities in contrast to imagining a fully automated workplace (Miller, 2018; Wilson & Daugherty 2018; Dwivedi et al., 2019). This has been discussed by a great number of authors in literature. For example, Jarrahi (2018) also shares this view and postulates that AI systems should be designed to augment, not to replace human contributions. Daugherty and Wilson (2018) argue that one of the most significant powers in AI technology is in complementing and augmenting human capabilities enabling organisations to fill the 'missing middle'.

Figure 2.5: The missing middle

Source: Daugherty and Wilson (2018)

Daugherty and Wilson define the 'missing middle' as giving human employees to do tasks they do best such as '*lead, empathise, create, judge*' while giving AI systems to do jobs that they do best such as '*transact, iterate, predict, adapt*'. They further stress that the fundamental concept behind filling this missing middle is freeing employees to do more productive complex job tasks while giving these AI systems to do more tedious grunt job tasks in organisations. As Daugherty and Wilson (2018) claim, this is called the 'missing middle' since only a small fraction of companies are currently working towards filling this crucial gap in organisations while nobody else talks about it. By filling this critical gap, organisations are set to achieve an unprecedented level of productivity while saving costs (Daugherty and Wilson, 2018). Subsequently, these literature findings suggest that customer service employees working with CAs dramatically improve human agents` capabilities and embody new human potential in the workplace.

ii). Personalised offers and recommendations

Due to the ever-increasing shift in the e-commerce structure, location, and size of the target market, retailers` ability to provide more relevant communications and set up better customer experience through personalisation, identified as another primary challenge e-commerce retailers face (Chopra and Batra, 2017). By 2030 it is expected to have significant changes in the customer service practice due to the development in Artificial Intelligence, ubiquitous internet connectivity, and widespread Internet of Things (IoT) (more senses and more immersion) (Spychalska, 2019). Consequently, organisations and customers will have to deal with: predictive social media, automation of the shopping experiences, smarter CRM processes

and hyper-targeting involved with CAs (Daugherty and Wilson 2018). A study conducted by Arsenijevic and Jovic (2019) claims that CAs will boost sales: a) by producing more personalised products and services; b) by accurately determining the target market, resulting in a higher conversion rate; c) by creating highly personalised sales offers.

Personalisation is defined as a process that tailors marketing and service strategies to target each customer individually (Srinivasan, 2019). Personalised customer service and marketing help organisations bridge the gap between offering endless choices and offers to customers who are not interested. Instead, provide products and services, targeting specific customer needs and wants (Keane, 2019). This process involves using customer information such as their `preferences, demographics, buying history/behaviour` to create a personal connection with them by understanding customers better (Srinivasan, 2019). As Waghmare explains, online retailers need to innovate every day, if not more often, by understanding customer preferences and fulfilling their expectations to survive and grow their businesses in the market. Although personalised customer service is not a brand new concept today, the new layer of AI technology's ability to offer a human-like conversation by assuring that personalised service is available to meet customer needs anytime and anywhere is an innovative approach for many organisations.

Helping customers via chat in their product search by offering personalised recommendations and suggestions (based upon their request or previous buying behaviour) is becoming a vehicle for enhancing customer relationships and loyalty for e-commerce retailers (Rese et al., 2020). Retail brick and mortar stores have long held an advantage over e-commerce shopping interactions, mainly since service agents can observe shopper behaviour and offer personalised recommendations. Personalised recommendations through CAs (see figure 2.6) are an evolving movement in e-commerce that can bridge the gap between e-commerce and in-person shopping experiences.

Figure 2.6: CAs product recommendation example from the luxury retail brand 'Burberry'

Source: Chung et al., (2018)

Figure 2.6 illustrates the kind of customer – CA recommendations dialogue that can occur while making a purchasing decision. In the above example, the conversation consists of three segments of conversation types, namely: '*Social chat segment, recommendation segment and the task completion segment*'. '*Social chat segment*' refers to the CAs ability to have a conversation seamlessly and appropriately with users, similar to the Turing test. '*Recommendation segment*' refers to the CA`s ability to provide concise, direct recommendations to user queries based on rich knowledge drawn from various data sources, including text collections such as Web documents and pre-compiled knowledge bases such as sales and marketing data sets. '*Task completion*' segment refers to the CAs ability to accomplish tasks given by the user. in this example - provide all the fundamental information regarding the dress recommendation, provide available offers and direct the user to a staff member for further details (Chung et al., 2018; Gao, et al., 2019).

As Weber and Schütte (2019) assert, AI applications in the retail sector, particularly related to personalised offers and promotions, are well-suited due to the technology`s analytical nature. They further explain dynamic pricing management can be carried out with intelligent and self-learning solutions in both the highly dynamic changing e-commerce market needs. '*Dynamic pricing*' as new development is a pricing strategy in which companies adjust prices for products or services in real-time based on the current market demand using automatic algorithms

(Jaekel, 2017). Combining dynamic pricing with CAs has the potential to bring new values to sustainable organisational growth.

iii). An Effective omnichannel customer service strategy

With the rise of mobile channels and social media platforms, today, nearly 50% of total e-commerce sales are reported to drive sales from omnichannel retailing (De Keyser et al., 2018; Sing and Srivastava 2019). Although e-commerce sales were mainly taking place on traditional laptop and desktop platforms, it is becoming increasingly clear that e-commerce business model reconfiguration through a combination of traditional platforms and omnichannel plays a critical role in customer acquisition and retention. A large number of existing studies have provided evidence that omnichannel customer engagement in the e-commerce retail setting as a prominent source that generates additional revenue, expand the market share, and remains competitive in the market (Verhoef et al., 2015). Omnichannel refers to the multichannel approach (combining brick and mortar and e-commerce) that retailers seek to provide a seamless shopping experience from physical stores, websites, mobile apps, social media, allowing customers to shop through their preferred channel (Verhoef et al., 2015). As half of the UK retail population engages with online shopping (Fisher, 2020), it is suggested that UK e-commerce retailers proactively prepare and position themselves in the diverse omnichannel population.

The literature review shows that today e-commerce shoppers digitally go through different channels – i.e. check product's features on social media, request prices via emails, and purchase through the website (Frascaroli 2019; Deloitte, 2019). For example, in 2019, around 67% of e-commerce shoppers had made purchases that have involved multiple channels (Frascaroli 2019). However, providing seamless customer service across all these channels is challenging and costly for many e-commerce retailers. As a solution to this challenge, a CA can be implemented successfully in the retailer's digital channels such as website, Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp or the company mobile apps. Thus, implementing CAs allow e-commerce retailers to provide comprehensive and consistent real-time customer self-service through all the channels. Using conversational AI, e-commerce retailers have the ability to provide an omnichannel customer experience in a more effective manner by integrating channels to offer consistent support to their customers (Deloitte, 2019).

iv). Ability to provide faster responses

A large number of existing studies in the broader literature have discussed that when interactions taking place between e-commerce retailers and digital native shoppers, they expect to find the information they are looking for while shopping online quickly and easily (De Keyser et al., 2018; Sing and Srivastava 2019; Cancel and Gerhardt 2019). As the literature review shows when online shoppers failed to find the information they seek quickly and easily, they become frustrated and mostly abandon the purchasing process to switch to other competitor brands available online. According to Cancel and Gerhardt (2019), one of the key reasons why today's e-commerce customer service experience has become overly complex and unnecessarily slow is mainly due to 'lead capture forms'. As they further explain, these forms have become such an integral part of the traditional sales and customer service process. Yet, these lead capture forms identified as no longer effective as they once were since customers are sceptical about filling out forms and would instead go elsewhere than go through the hassle. A study published in the Harvard Business Review found that waiting five minutes to respond to a new lead/inquiry resulted in a 10x drop, and waiting to respond after ten minutes resulted in a 400% drop in the odds to connect and follow up with that lead/ inquiry. Therefore the report suggests that when engaging with customers, companies should target staying below the five-minute mark (Cancel and Gerhardt, 2019).

Prior research suggests that communicating with CAs through their preferred channel has become more effective since customers don't have time anymore for calls or emails due to reasons such as only 43% of people answer unknown calls, and the average email open rate has fallen to 20% (Drift, 2018). Moreover, it was reported in the literature that customers are more likely to be engaged with a product or service via real-time conversations than going through FAQs or exchanging multiple emails to get the answers they seek (Nwokike, 2018). As a solution, CAs ability to offer fast responses to customers 24/7/365, even during the closing hours, to converse in real-time with customers can shorten the customer interaction time while delivering a satisfying online experience (Ikumoro and Jawad, 2019). Hence, implementing a CA allows customers to engage with a company 24/7 for specific queries through the company website, social media platforms, or company app, instead of sending a message, writing an email or making a phone call to a company and wait in line for a response (Adam et al., 2020).

v). Data-driven analytics to get new customer insights

Traditionally, data-driven analytics among brick and mortar retailers is time-consuming and often a highly iterative process. On the contrary, e-commerce giants spent money on data science or Business Intelligence (BI) experts who know how to use complex toolsets to manage their data and utilise it for customer engagement strategies. However, among small & medium-sized e-commerce retail companies, only a few can afford the right tools needed to analyse the data and provide predictive insights. They often rely on gut instincts and best guesses to make crucial business decisions to engage with their customers. Consequently, valuable data insights and information generated about customers usually go unused and are typically locked in segregated silos (Hoon et al., 2020). Although much attention is focused on introducing a CA as a self-service tool, it can also enable organisations to obtain much more profound and broader insights about their customer that can optimise the customer experience and nearly all aspects of the business (Waghmare, 2019). For instance, daily 'user – CA' chat history can provide daily insights into the context of overall customer behaviour, preferences, and issues they are experiencing during transactions and service engagement in the e-commerce setting. Hence, human-to-machine engagement by implementing CAs offers e-commerce retailers the guidance to yield better business decisions, get deeper insights about their consumer needs and create new business opportunities from retention to loyalty (Hoon et al., 2020).

To summarise, this section has examined and discussed the most prominent benefits the UK retailers can achieve by successfully implementing a self-service CA as an FST tool in their e-commerce setting. These identified benefits from the literature are; i) enhance the human agents' productivity, ii) personalised Offers and recommendations, iii) an effective omnichannel customer service strategy, iv) the ability to provide faster responses, v). Data-driven analytics to get new customer insights. While large companies increasingly employ these CAs for their business operations, the technology has thus far yielded mixed results indicating high failure rates among many e-commerce organisations (Araujo, 2018). Moreover, according to market research, the technology itself is frequently met with consumer scepticism in several European countries (Elsner, 2017) as they indicate a preference to engage with humans instead of conversational AI technology (Araujo, 2018). Therefore, to be successful, companies and CA designers must understand how to best introduce these CAs as a self-service tool to their users without disrupting the business process. Moreover, before companies can exploit the opportunities yielded by CAs and fully benefit from them, they need to implement

the CA in a targeted and adequate way. The following section discusses the CAs implementation of critical success factors and success criteria.

2.4 Critical Success Factors (CSFs)

To investigate the research issues extracted from chapter one, this section reviews and critically discusses the literature related to AI-based CAs implementation success. Despite the hype around the CAs implementation and its benefits, critical success factors (CSFs) contributing to the implementation success remain poorly understood thus far. Notably, there is limited systematic work on characterising a collective set of CSFs for AI-based CAs implementation to utilise as a Frontline Service Technology (FST) in the UK retail e-commerce sector. Hence this section of the literature review aims to identify the factors that lead to a successful CA implementation and to highlight which areas organisations must pay close attention to during that implementation process. Based on the themes and concepts highlighted by the literature review, a conceptual framework will be developed as a theoretical underpinning for this research.

2.4.1 The Concept of CSFs

CSFs are often confused with organisational goals (Amberget et al., 2005). Goals are organisational targets that are established to achieve the organisation's mission which comes with specificity in terms of what needs to be achieved, when and by whom (Amberget et al., 2005). Critical Success Factors (CSFs), on the other hand, are the antecedents of realising the goal (Amberget et al., 2005). Meyer (2004) noted that goals should be S.M.A.R.T, meaning: '*specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and timely*' in order to be effective. Therefore, it is evident that although goals and critical success factors (CSFs) are separate constructs, there is a robust cardinal relationship between them, and identifying the relevant CSFs is crucial to achieving a specific goal. This raises the question of what set of critical success factors is relevant to achieve the purpose of 'AI-based conversational agents' implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce sector as an FST.

The concept of important factors that influence the success of a business was first introduced by Daniel (1961), and then Rockart (1979) extended these crucial factors in the field of management information systems refining this concept into Critical Success Factors (CSFs). Rockart (1979) describes a number of areas where things must go right for a business to flourish and to get successful competitive performance for an organisation. Rockart stressed that the concept of CSFs should result in key information under two main categories. These categories

are: i) CSFs should be useful to a CEO and which pinpoints crucial areas that require managers' attention, ii) CSFs should provide a focal point for directing computer-based information systems (CBIS) development.

Rockart (1979) defined CSFs as satisfactory areas that will ensure successful competitive performance for the organisation. Similarly, Leidecker and Bruno (1984) defined CSFs as properly managed factors, characteristics, or variables that can significantly impact a firm's success in a particular industry. Barat (1992) defined the concept of CSFs as "those few things must go well to ensure success and which organisation management must give special and continued attention to bring about high performance". Pinto and Slevin (1987) described CSFs as the factors that significantly improve project implementation chances. Saraph et al., (1989) viewed CSFs as those critical areas of action that the top management must focus on and practiced to achieve a specific project's effectiveness. Similarly, Wong (2005) described CSFs as those activities and practices that should be addressed in order to ensure the successful implementation of a specific project.

Since then, researchers have extensively used CSFs in the analysis of the Information Systems (IS) implementation in order to understand what leads to the success or failure of these sorts of complex projects (Saxena and McDonagh, 2017). Critical success factors (CSFs) have also been widely recognised as a powerful enabler for identifying key issues for organisational attention prior to and during project implementation within the IS literature. Although many researchers have studied the CSFs inherent in IS implementation, limited studies have investigated AI-based CAs implementation success, and the CSFs contribute to that success in the context of IS literature. The existing literature mostly has focused on the technical or design aspects of CAs implementation (Magaña-Martínez and Fernandez-Rodriguez, 2015; Lalwani et al., 2018), but not from an organisational and managerial perspective. The below section discusses the limited number of CSFs studies identified from CAs' and other AI systems implementation success literature.

2.4.2 Conversational Agents Implementation Literature

The term 'Implementation' in this thesis's context refers to the process of e-commerce retailers' decision or plan to use AI-based CAs into effect or execution. Subsequently, this study looks at 'AI-based Conversational Agents' as a form of Information Systems (IS) (Trivedi, 2019). IS defined as an organised collection of information, people, processes and technology to achieve a specific organisational goal (Piercy and Mckeown, 2008). For this study, a thorough literature

review was conducted to develop a complete set of CSFs for CAs implementation that can impact the most for a successful implementation initiative. The literature review of CSFs has been conducted analysing the CSFs identified in each article across different industries and countries. Then these most discussed factors were condensed into a single distinct set of CSFs as shown in table 2.5 for the purpose of conceptual framework development. In order to develop a comprehensive set of CSFs to achieve the third research objective, this study reviewed the construct of CSFs from the limited CAs implementation studies which include: general CAs implementation related CSFs studies (rule-based and AI-based), general AI systems implementation success studies (without limiting to a specific AI system), and CSFs studies that are common to any information system implementation which has discussed in the body of knowledge. These factors are discussed below.

A study conducted by Zhang et al., (2020) to explore organisational factors affecting the successful implementation of CAs for customer service identified five main organisational factors that influence a CA implementation project's success. An exploratory research design was chosen to meet the research aim, and findings were gathered from Norway-based organisations using semi-structured interviews. These five organisational factors affecting the success of CA implementation were: *i) competencies and competency acquisition, ii) organisational resources, iii) works and team organisation, iv) change management, v) performance measures.*

Kousa (2019) conducted a study to explore success factors in CA implementation projects proposed a best practice framework with success factors organisations to consider during four CA project implementation phases (initiation, planning, executing, and controlling). The framework was built based on findings from qualitative research and insights had gathered from CAs implementation experts` with semi-structured interviews. Study results highlighted CSFs include: *defining project goals, involving key people in the organisation, forming coherent teams from the organisation and vendor's sides, effective communication, management support, use case and project scope, testing from early stages, user training, data set quality and satisfaction surveys to monitor customer experience.*

Alhashmi et al., (2019), another recent study on the CSFs of AI systems implementation in the United Arab Emirates Healthcare Sector using a qualitative study comprising 53 IT and healthcare employees in Dubai, propose five CSF categories: *'Managerial, Organisational, Technological, Strategic, and IT infrastructure'* to determine the AI systems implementation

success. In their study, the results indicate a positive relationship with Managerial factors, Organisational factors, Operational factors, and IT infrastructure, while Strategic factors illustrated a negative relationship.

Chatterjee and Ghosh (2020) examined sixteen CSFs for AI-integrated CRM system implementation with interpretative structural modelling (ISM) methodology using Indian companies from Mumbai, Bengaluru, and Delhi. Their study found that the goal may be successfully achieved by nurturing three key drivers, namely: '*Leadership support welcoming AI-CRM integration, Support of functional area lead, and Adequate fund allocation*'. Their results show that the impact of nine factors is limited, and thus, special attention is to be focussed on these nine factors. These factors are: '*Design and develop AI-CRM tool, Business value addition, Adequate training and readiness, Simplicity of new AI-CRM system, Supporting legal requirements, Ease of use, Develop privacy policy for AI-CRM system, Support of immediate manager and Adequate security mechanism*'. Other factors such as '*Behavioural intention of the employees using AI-CRM system, Overcoming resistance to change, Enhance trust towards using new AI CRM system and Driving adoption of AI-integrated CRM system in the organisation*' were considered as weakest drivers.

A study conducted by Mölsä (2017) to explore success factors in implementing AI-powered solutions using two case studies highlighted that '*business use case, supportive company culture, multidisciplinary development team and agile development approach*' are success factors organisations should consider when implementing AI systems.

An expanded study conducted by McKinsey Global Institute using 3000 surveyed data shows a range of successful AI transformations requirement factors: '*Use case, data ecosystems, techniques and tools, workflow integration, open culture and organisation*' (Bughin et al., 2017).

Another comprehensive study conducted by Buren et al., (2020) postulates that AI's transformative nature typically calls for the preparation of multiple critical areas than merely preparing to buy and install new technology. To capture AI's potential to create value, they have conducted a study by focusing on government organisations and presented the '*AI Operating Model*' distinguishing six key areas to deploy AI in organisations. Buren et al., (2020) 's '*AI Operating Model*' describes the following crucial factors for organisations to consider when implementing an AI system. These factors are namely: '*Data, Strategy, People, Change Management, Process, and Ethics*'. According to the AI Operating Model, Buren et

al., (2020) describe the following crucial factors for AI systems deployment. 'Strategy'– Due to the transformative nature of the AI technology, the AI implementation's goal and its vision that align with organisational objectives have been identified as crucial to deploy AI successfully. 'Data' – The success and the accuracy of an AI system can build upon the quality of the data and its voracious nature. Building a data governance system that includes sourcing, accessing, and quality management is also vitally important. 'People' – Organisation`s readiness to help employees to develop AI skills or else recruit necessary technical skills have been considered as another crucial area when it comes to integrating AI with human workflows. Change management, redefining talent models, and getting stakeholder buy-in through effective communications are other essential areas organisations must consider under this context. 'Process'– As Buren et al., (2020) state, the real value of AI cannot be captured until processes and organisational activities are integrated with it. Therefore, a successful AI implementation must focus on design/define processes and governance of the AI system. 'Ethics' – AI systems' ability to promote fairness and transparency, prevent AI bias, privacy, ensure values and integrity are embedded in AI-driven initiatives are focal points organisations should consider when it comes to AI ethics.

In the following table, this study reviews the above-discussed literature according to three parameters: context, Critical Success Factor, and Country.

Table 2.2: CSFs identified in the literature

Reference	Context	Critical Success Factor	Country
Yu (2020)	Organisational Factors affecting the successful implementation of CAs for customer service use cases	<i>Proposed CSFs under the Organisational Category:</i> Competencies and competency acquisition, Organisational resources, Works and organisation, Change management, Performance measures	Norway
Kousa (2019)	CAs implementation best practice framework during four implementation phases: initiation, planning, executing, and controlling	<i>Proposed CSFs:</i> Defining project goals, Involving key people in the organisation, Forming coherent teams from the organisation and vendor`s side, Effective communication, Management support, Use case and project scope, Testing from early stages, User training, Data set quality, and satisfaction surveys to monitor customer experience	Europe based
Alhashmi et al., (2019)	AI systems implementation CSFs in the UAE healthcare system	<i>Proposed five CSF categories:</i> Managerial, Organisational, Technological, Strategic, and IT infrastructure	United Arab Emirates (continued)

Reference	Context	Critical Success Factor	Country
Chatterjee and Ghosh (2019)	AI-integrated CRM system implementation CSFs	<i>Proposed 16 CSFs:</i> Leadership support, Support of functional area lead, Adequate fund allocation, Design and develop AI-CRM tool, Business value addition, Adequate training and readiness, Simplicity of new AI-CRM system, Supporting Legal requirements, Ease of use, Develop privacy policy for AI-CRM system, Management support, Adequate security mechanism, employees behavioural intention, Change management, Enhance trust towards using new AI system, Driving adoption of AI-integrated CRM system in the organisation	India
Mölsä (2017)	Success Factors contributes toward AI-powered solutions	<i>Proposed Success Factors:</i> Business use case, Supportive company culture, Multidisciplinary development team, and Agile development approach	Finland
Buren et al., (2020)	`AI Operating Model` consists of the crucial factors for organisations to consider when implementing an AI system (developed using the government organisations)	<i>Proposed CSFs:</i> Data strategy, People, Change management, Process, and Ethics	United States

Developed by Author

In addition to the above CSFs literature findings, this study has compiled four categories of critical areas derived from a combination of separate studies that have discussed one or two critical factors (without a comprehensive set of CSFs) in general that organizations must focus on when implementing CAs (see table 2.4). Therefore, based upon academic literature findings, below four categories have considered as the most influential CSF categories that can be discussed under CAs implementation.

These four categories are Organisational, data-related, technological, and governance-related factors and the CSFs identified are presented in table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Table CSF categories derived from CAs/AI systems literature

CSFs Category	CSFs	Authors
Organisational Factors	<p>Vendor selection, Strategy</p> <p>Innovation adoption, Top management support, Strategy</p> <p>Top management support, Vendor selection, Strategy, Change management,</p> <p>Strategy, Funds and resource allocation, Change management</p> <p>Funds and resource allocation</p> <p>Vendor selection, Funds and resource allocation</p> <p>Top management support, Project management, Vendor selection</p>	<p>Brandtzaeg and Folstad (2018); Sun & Medaglia (2019)</p> <p>Dwivedi et al., (2019)</p> <p>Davenport & Ronanki (2018)</p> <p>Sjøberg (2019)</p> <p>Shaw et al., (2019)</p> <p>Wirtz et al., (2019)</p> <p>Huang et al., (2020;2018)</p>
Data Related Factors	<p>Data quality, Data preparation</p> <p>Data quality, Data preparation, Knowledge base</p> <p>Knowledge base</p>	<p>Dwivedi et al., (2019); Gupta (2017); Følstad and Brandtzæg (2017)</p> <p>Sjøberg (2019); Elish and Boyd (2018); Lawnboy (2018)</p> <p>Ram et al., (2018)</p>
Technological Factors	<p>Natural language processing, Data sharing and integration, Machine learning</p>	<p>Dwivedi et al., (2019); Sjøberg (2019); Gupta (2017); Lawnboy (2018); Ram et al., (2018); Abdul-Kader and Woods (2015); Pryss et al., (2018); Fadhil and Gabrielli (2017); Hu, (2019); Wei et al., (2018); Xu et al., (2017); Liao (2018); Zamora (2017); Radziwill (2017)</p>
Governance Factors	<p>Data privacy, System security, Transparency</p>	<p>Wirtz et al., (2019); Sjøberg, (2019); Dwivedi et al., (2019); Følstad and Brandtzæg (2017); Fadhil and Gabrielli, (2017); Miller, (2019); Shams et al., (2016); Mercado et al., (2016); Hayes and Shah (2017); Chen et al., (2016); De Visser et al., (2014); Lee and See (2004); Pickup, (2019); Zandi et al., (2019); Sjøberg, (2019); Thesmar et al., (2019)</p>

Developed by Author

However, after an extensive literature search, it was revealed that there's a gap in the body of knowledge as no studies were found that discuss a comprehensive set of CSFs that can be used as a guiding light to ensure CAs implementation success, not only in the context of UK retail e-commerce setting but also in any other e-commerce market focusing a developed country in relation to the phenomenon under investigation. Therefore, in order to provide a rich context for the present study due to limited literature on CAs and AI systems implementation CSFs besides the studies described above, this section seeks to review CSFs of well-studied enterprise-wide Information Systems (IS) implementation. This review aims to gather valuable insights in identifying factors that may determine the success of AI-based CAs implementation as another innovative enterprise-wide initiative.

IS Implementation CSFs

A successful IS implementation can result in lower operational costs and higher operational efficiency while maintaining improved business processes for organisations (Abbas, 2011; Ahmed and Khan, 2013). Studies suggest that the success of an information system mainly depends on a balanced alignment between two major aspects, namely, 1) organisational aspects contribute to the implementation process and 2) technical aspects of the IS system (Coakes et al., 2004; Beynon, 2009; Ahmed and Khan, 2013). One of the early information system research conducted by Reel (2001) summarised a set of essential CSFs to consider in software project implementations regardless of the system design and application domain. These factors are: '*committed leadership, effective communication, and a balanced and competent team*'.

The critical success factors (CSFs) of Information Systems (IS) implementation have been widely studied in empirical studies through the approaches of surveys, case studies, meta-analysis, and researchers have developed lists of CSFs for IS implementation. Despite the slightly different ranking, the literature demonstrates that the most prominent and commonly used CSFs for any IS implementation are: '*Top management support, Clear Goals and objectives, Stakeholders active involvement, Effective project management, User training and education, System reliability and flexibility, IT infrastructure*' (Sangar and Lahad, 2013).

Building upon the previous studies on Information Systems CSFs within the large enterprises and SMEs contexts, Huang et al., (2018) propose six sub-CSFs within the Technical, Organisational and Environmental (TOE) framework. These factors are namely: '*Change Management, Functional Fit, Project Management, Top Management Support, and external factors*'.

2.4.3 Evaluation and Critique of Studies on CSFs of CAs Implementation

During the synthesis of the final set of studies, the researcher observed that the above-identified sets of CSFs are highly inconsistent. While the conclusions and contributions that arose from the CSFs studies above are valuable (Bughin et al., 2017; Hong 2019; Kousa 2019; Alhashmi, 2019; Chatterjee et al., 2019; Buren et al., 2020; Yu, 2020), common characteristics of all these studies, however, are: (a) different CSFs using different AI tools and studies, (b) studies not only restricted to AI-based conversational agents, some have focused exclusively on rule-based CAs, (c) existing studies have used different methodologies (d) many studies discuss CAs/AI systems implementation challenges but only limited studies exist on CAs implementation success (e) the extent to which the CSFs affecting AI-based CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce setting has not yet been examined. Moreover, above mentioned existing studies have used different sets of CSF variables often examined using different backgrounds and research interests where findings seem subjective and isolated, making it difficult to use as common CSFs for the UK e-commerce retail companies to rely on.

In addition to that, conventional Information systems are rule-based systems where rules are clearly defined and implemented in the programming language as to how the system behaves and functions in certain conditions. On the contrary, AI-driven machine learning systems are classified as computer's ability to learn and perform without being explicitly programmed (Daugherty and Wilson, 2018). Therefore, the challenge is distinguishing key drivers that can contribute to AI-powered conversational agents' implementation success from conventional Information Systems implementation success due to the novelty and complexity of AI technology compared with traditional IS systems at the enterprise level. Thus, there is still a significant gap in the current research literature which calls for further investigation of factors affecting the success of AI-based CAs implementation in the UK retail e-commerce sector. In this study, critical success factors (CSFs) are defined as those practices an organisation must specifically focus on in order to ensure successful CAs implementation. Thus, if these factors already exist, they would need to be nurtured or if they do not already exist, they would need to be developed.

2.4.4 Deriving the Critical Success Factors

Following the above literature review, this study proposes a comprehensive list of 16 CSF variables with 4 CSF categories for the development of the conceptual research framework.

Table 2.4: CAs implementation Studies from the literature review to identify CSFs

	Organisational Factors							Data Related Factors			Technological Factors			Governance Factors		
	Innovation Adoption	Top Management	Vendor Selection	Project Management	Strategy	Funds and Resource	Change Management	Data Quality	Data Preparation	Knowledge Base	Natural Language Processing	Data Sharing and Integration	Machine Learning	Data Privacy	System Security	Transparency
Buren et al., (2020)					✓	✓	✓			✓		✓		✓	✓	✓
Huang and Rust (2020)	✓															
Huang et al., (2020)			✓													
Srivastava (2020)				✓												
Adamopoulou and Moussiades, (2020)											✓		✓			
Alhashmi et al., (2019)		✓			✓	✓				✓						
Chatterjee and Ghosh (2019)		✓				✓	✓							✓	✓	
Kousa (2019)		✓	✓					✓								
Dwivedi et al., (2019)	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓
Sun & Medaglia (2019)					✓			✓	✓	✓		✓				
Sjøberg, (2019)					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓
Shaw et al., (2019)						✓								✓	✓	✓
Wirtz et al., (2019)			✓			✓								✓	✓	✓
Clohessy and Acton (2019)	✓															
Cardona et al., (2019)	✓															
Davenport & Ronanki, (2018)		✓	✓		✓		✓									✓
Elish and Boyd (2018)								✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓
Lawnboy, (2018)								✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			
Huang et al., (2018)		✓		✓												

Brandtzaeg and Folstad (2018)			✓														
Ram et al., (2018)										✓	✓		✓				
Bughin et al., (2017)	✓				✓							✓					
Følstad and Brandtzæg (2017)								✓	✓						✓		
Pryss et al., (2018)											✓	✓	✓				
Radujković and Sjekavica, (2017)				✓													
Gupta, (2017)								✓	✓		✓		✓				
Abdul-Kader and Woods (2015)											✓		✓				
Sangar and Lahad, (2013)				✓													

Developed by Author

Table 2.5: Proposed conversational agents implementation CSFs for this study

CSFs Category	Critical Success Factors
Organisational Factors	Innovation Adoption Top Management Support Vendor Selection Project Management Strategy Funds and Resource Allocation Change Management
Data Related Factors	Data Quality Data Preparation Knowledge Base Creation
Technological Factors	Natural Language Processing Machine Learning Data Sharing and Integration
Governance Related Factors	Data Privacy Security Transparency

Developed by Author

These CSFs presented in Table 2.5 were derived from a process of identification and filtering from the previous sections` most re-occurring CSF themes used in CAs/AI and IS implementation academic studies and research reports from well-reputed research institutes. Table 2.4 illustrates the CSF filtering process, and four categories were grouped for certain factors (identified in table 2.3), as different authors have used various labels to describe similar characteristics. This means, 7 CSFs were merged into the 'Organisational factors' category; 3 CSFs were merged into the 'Data related factors' category; 3 CSFs were merged into the 'Technological factors' category, and 3 CSFs were merged into the 'Governance related factors' category. Based upon the above literature review and after discussing the rationale for choosing the 16 CSFs under four categories, as shown in Table 2.4, the following section discusses the significance of the chosen CSFs in-depth.

2.4.5 Organisational Factors

i) Innovation Adoption

It has been stressed in a number of research studies that 'Innovation adoption' should be included as a critical success factor in any AI, IS, or IT project to ensure its implementation success (Bughin et al., 2017; Cardona et al., 2019; Clohessy and Acton, 2019; Dwivedi et al., 2019; Huang and Rust, 2020). In order to be able to meet the needs and expectations of increasingly digitally influenced customers in the e-commerce service setting, today, organisations are compelled to undertake profound digital transformation approaches in which enable them to engage with customers through various service innovation adoptions (Barrett et al., 2015; Cardona et al., 2019). Conversational agents, manifested by artificial intelligence to perform specific human-level job tasks in the service frontline, have been identified as a prominent source of innovation adoption to meet such digitally influenced customer demand and expectations in the e-commerce setting (Huang and Rust, 2020).

Innovation is considered one of the main drivers to bring sustainable competitive advantage to companies (Schumpeter, 1942; Tushman *et al.*, 1997). Innovation is known as a non-simple phenomenon that involves new idea generation and then the translation of that idea into a brand new product or process (Lohmuller, 2003). For example, an early study conducted by Drucker, (1985) on innovation highlights that from a managerial perspective, the main purpose of innovation is to introduce change in organisations to generate new opportunities or reconfigure existing ones. However, on the other side, another early academic researcher Amabile (1983) argues that innovation can not be regarded as just creativity, as creativity is only coming up with a new idea but not the whole innovation process of the idea generation, development, and adaptation of novel ideas to produce value to customers and enhance the overall revenue. Most of the definitions of innovation stress the importance of the adoption of a new idea and its implementation. This implies the need to investigate the importance of adopting AI-based conversational agents as an innovation and its implementation.

As studies highlight, there are two main innovation types namely: organisational level and individual level. 'Organisational level' studies analyses the effect of IT/IS adoption on business performances while studies at an 'individual level' of analysis are mainly concentrated on effective routine use, individual behaviour, and their acceptance of the innovation as a whole (Wu et al., 2006; Venkatesh et al., 2012). A study conducted by Hameed et al., (2012a) states

that 'organisation level' innovation adoption is significant when the organisation seeks innovation until they acquire the technology while 'individual level' is more significant/related when the actual use of innovation.

Studies have highlighted that the adoption of innovative technology can bring significant transformations for internal and external organisational processes, and thus the decision for such innovation adoption must be treated carefully (Wang, 2010; Kaganer et al., 2010; Clohessy and Acton, 2019). Hameed et al., (2012b) explains that innovation adoption in an organisation frequently referred to as a stage-based process, consists of the decision-making phase to project completion. However, to provide more depth to the stage-based innovation process, a study conducted by Ammirato et al., (2019) has provided an overview of studies in table 2.6 proposing a categorisation of innovation adoption.

Table 2.6: Categorisation of IT and IS innovation adoption stages

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.
Table can be found in Ammirato, S., Francesco S., Alberto, F., Cinzia, R. (2019) 'A methodology to support the adoption of IoT innovation and its application to the Italian bank branch security context', *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 22 (1), pp.146-174.

Source: (Ammirato et al., (2019)

The above categorisation presents a number of different stages previous studies have discussed concerning innovation adoption. However, based on an extensive literature review, Ammirato et al., (2019) have identified three general innovation adoption phases that have been widely

discussed in previous studies. These three phases have been categorised as the initiation phase, adoption phase, and implementation phase (Damanpour and Schneider, 2006; Mergel and Bretschneider; 2013; Ammirato et al., 2019).

Initiation Phase – This phase consists of activities related to identifying the need for choosing a specific technology as an innovation adoption. This stage involves identifying the awareness towards change, collecting information, and proposing innovative ideas for adoption. This is the stage where managers are required to learn about the suggested technology and identify its key characteristics as an innovative adoption and verify its suitability for the organisation's expectations (Saad, 2000; Hameed et al., 2012a).

Adoption phase – This stage involves the activities consists of the organisation accepting the idea for the suggested innovation and then evaluating the proposed technology from a financial, technological, and strategic perspective (Ammirato et al., 2019). This is also the stage where top management (CEO, company directors, board members, and senior managers) show interest and acceptance for the innovation adopting decision and allocating resources for innovation acquisition and implementation (Jacobs and Snijders, 2008; Mergel and Bretschneider, 2013).

Implementation Phase – This stage represents the integration of innovative technology in organisational processes and completes the technology adoption decision's ultimate goal (Saad, 2004). The implementation phase involves actions to be taken for the acquisition of the innovation, steps taken to ensure the acceptance of the innovation by the users, and apply the innovation as a prominent part of the business process to get the anticipated results (Ammirato et al., 2019).

In addition to the innovation phases, several theoretical and empirical studies have examined IT and IS-based innovations, and many theories have been tested and suggested for the technology innovation adoption process (Rui, 2007; Oliveira and Martins, 2011). At the firm level, theories such as `Institutional theory` (Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990), Rogers` (2003) diffusion of innovation (DOI), and technology, organisation and environment (TOE) framework` (DePietro et al. 1990) have been widely applied to studies looking at how technological innovations are adopted and implemented. Davis`s (1986) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has been widely used to predict the acceptance and use of innovative technology in organisations explaining a wide range of human behaviour (drawn from social psychology) across the business context (Davis, 1986, Davis, et al., 1989).

To sum up, AI-based CAs are frequently referred to as an influential technology innovation adoption within the next five years (Alhashmi et al., 2019; Pillai and Sivathanu 2020). Hence, in the context of CAs implementation as a self-service FST tool, organisations decision concerning the adoption of a CA is one of the primary and critical factors of the project implementation success.

ii) Top Management Support

Top managers refer to the influencers (leaders) in an organisation that impacts implementing new technology and its outcomes (Salloum et al., 2018). Top management support is defined as organizational leaders' engagement for implementation success and willingness to provide required resources at every stage of the implementation process (Zwikael 2008; AISheibani et al., 2018). Despite the widespread use of 'Top management support' as a CSF in the IS/IT implementations related studies, there is now growing literature to support (Hung, 2016; Mhamdi, 2017a; AISheibani et al., 2018; Salloum et al., 2018; Dwivedi et al., 2019) the role of top management support and commitment as one of the crucial factors in the research on CAs and AI systems implementations to ensure its project success. Authors such as Mhamdi (2017a) and Salloum et al., (2018) discuss the top management support for CA implementation as the degree to which company leaders understand the importance of using AI technology as a communication strategy and the extent to which top management is willing to support the implementation process. Moreover, study findings conducted by Markus (2017) and Dwivedi et al., (2019) suggest that transparent and visible top management support encourages positive results during the process of maximising the benefits of AI-enabled automation.

The theory of dynamic managerial capabilities (DMC) provides an insightful theoretical lens that can influence the top management support for CAs implementation success as technological innovation (Li et al., 2017). Dynamic Managerial Capabilities (DMC) are defined as “the capabilities with which managers build, integrate and reconfigure organisational resources and competencies” (Adner & Helfat, 2003, p.1012). Prior research has suggested that Dynamic managerial capability (DMC) is built on three core underpinnings, namely: managerial human capital, managerial cognition, and managerial social capital.

Managerial human capital

Managerial human capital refers to the subject knowledge, education, skills, and experience of managers' individual and teams have on specific technology adoption (Martin, 2011; Helfat

and Martin 2015). A study conducted by Helfat and Martin (2015) explains that managers with different backgrounds in terms of the subject knowledge, education, skills, and experience will respond differently in recognising opportunities and allocating resources to seize opportunities. From CAs implementation perspective, to add to the above point, Wright and Moliterno (2014) and Li et al., (2017) also have discussed that when facilitating the decision to adopt AI technology and implement a CA, having a diversified team of top managers with complementary knowledge, skills, experience are highly likely to positively impact in recognising and seizing opportunities as first movers in the market. When considering the CA implementation for a customer self-service experience, various authors have discussed managerial human capital can significantly influence a CA project's success by directly contributing to a set of specific tasks. These tasks include: defining the use case, making the adoption decision, identifying characteristics of the most suitable tasks for self-service, determining the level of automation, selecting an implementation partner, allocating funds and resources, and ensuring the governance of the CA (Dwivedi et al., 2019; Hung and Rust 2020; Sony et al., 2020).

Managerial cognition

Managerial cognition has defined by Adner & Helfat (2003) as the managers' personal beliefs and mental models for decision making. It includes managers' knowledge and understanding of current events and future development predictions (Li et al., 2017). Thus, Li et al., (2017) postulate that managerial cognition affects managers' sense of market changes and their decision towards adaptations to those changes. Helfat and Martin (2015) have echoed that statement and emphasised managers with inert managerial cognition will fail to recognise those changes and, consequently, obstruct their organisations' effort to transform. For instance, a study conducted by Vagia et al., (2016) states that when adopting AI as a response to market needs and changes, managerial cognition also involves organisational leaders' ability to understand the level of automation AI systems can bring to job tasks. The automation level may range from Level 1, 'manual control where the computer offers no assistance' to Level 8, 'autonomous control stage where the computer does everything without human notification'. This example shows the importance of organisational leaders who wish to embark upon a conversational AI journey must bring their managerial cognition to decide the level of control for decision-making of their AI-powered CA and the extent to which humans are kept in the loop to get the most effective outcomes. Moreover, another view was shared by Onnasch et al., (2013) and they point out the need for organisational leaders to understand the factors that may

influence human workers' performance when working alongside AI-enabled automation. Whereas a higher level of automation may reduce the worker's situation awareness and increase a tendency to rely on automation technology overly. Therefore, as Onnasch et al., (2013) suggest, it is vital to plan well ahead of the changes employees have to face due to AI system implementation and redirect them to do more productive job tasks.

Managerial Social Capital

Formal and informal relationships top managers have with others have been identified as managerial social capital (Helfat and Martin, 2015, p.1286). According to Adler and Kwon (2002), this can help managers to obtain diverse resources and information, allowing them to sense better market opportunities and challenges.

In sum, the above literature findings indicate that organisations can promote CAs adoption and implementation success by building their top managers' Dynamic Capabilities. Many authors have also pointed out that a top management team with sufficient cognitive, social, and human capital is more likely to recognise and seize market opportunities and initiate strategic changes such as digital transformation (Helfat and Martin, 2015; Li et al., 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019). Thus, DMC could be a useful theoretical lens for this study. Top management support is critical in enhancing the incorporation of conversational AI into the business strategy. Literature suggests that transparent and visible top management support encourages positive results during the process of maximising the benefits of AI-enabled automation (Dwivedi et al., 2019).

iii) Vendor Selection

It has been stressed in a number of research studies that organisations choosing the wrong conversational AI partner to implement their first CA as a frequently acknowledged factor for project failure (Brandtzæg and Følstad 2018; Davenport & Ronanki, 2018; Wirtz et al., 2019; Kousa, 2019; Huang et al., 2020). Although many researchers have discussed the importance of choosing the right conversational AI vendor, a study conducted by Huang et al., (2020) specifically has discussed the importance of the 'strategic fit' aspect when choosing a vendor. As they argue, similar to all the other vendor selection parameters, organisations must consider how a vendor would be a strategic fit for the company's overall vision for the project to be a success. Based upon the available literature it can be concluded that a vendor's willingness to collaborate with the organisation effectively would play a vital role in accomplishing the end goal of optimising their customer service capabilities. However, while the rise in the intention

to implement CAs in various use cases has led to an increase in the number of conversational AI startups and domestic platform vendors in the market, some authors have discussed the importance of future studies to address the vendor selection process for CAs implementation as still there is no consistent methodology for choosing a suitable vendor or a platform (Kostelnik et al., 2019; Perez, 2016).

In addition, there have been relatively few empirical studies available on CAs types and how they can be utilised according to company-specific needs, and less research into how available CAs could contribute towards the success or failure of a project outcome. Nevertheless, conversational AI industry reports (Piccolo et al., 2018; Brandtzæg and Følstad, 2018; Perez, 2020) have provided cautionary indications for organisations about the types of available CAs and how they can best match for implementation purposes. As these industry reports highlight, CAs come from different types based on use cases, and there are three available CA types for organisations to begin their implementation journey; namely, 'Off-the-shelf, Cloud-based custom developments, and built in-house from scratch'. An off-the-shelf CA is built with bot-building platforms that come with templates, tools, and conversational flow builders that allow organisations to build a simple text-based CA without mastery of coding skills. These CA vendor platforms range from low-level NLP services without any machine learning capabilities to low-code less time-consuming without any customisation of the CA to match organisational specific needs (Perez-Soler et al., 2020). As many studies postulate, these types of CAs are just software without any conversational AI capabilities, and almost all the implementations fail within a few months due to its inability to effectively engage with users (Piccolo et al., 2018; Brandtzæg and Følstad, 2018; Jain et al., 2018). However, as the reports claim, today many organisations (especially SMEs) chose these CA types due to its low cost easy to deploy option and ended up abandoning their CA a few months after the launch when they get complaints from frustrated customers (Brandtzæg and Følstad, 2018).

On the other hand, studies claim that custom CAs can be customised to answer complex customer queries powered by ML and NLP technologies to evolve with its experience (Oberoi, 2019). Depending on business use cases, organisations can choose one of these CAs with a comprehensive understanding of its capabilities and limitations. Moreover, Oberoi (2019) emphasis that an off-the-shelf CA can perform basic conversations (e.g. FAQs) with a user without understanding their intent due to no trained data to answer users' personalised questions, and yet, with proper training, a custom CA has the capability to understand the customer query, do basic transactions, fetch data from the databases and many more tasks. In-

house built CAs are more popular among large organisations as it brings more benefits and flexibility for their large customer bases, and yet, some authors have stressed that this CAs type is the most complex and high-cost CA type among all available options (Perez, 2020).

Therefore, based upon the above facts it can be concluded that the organisation`s ability to carefully choosing the most suitable conversational AI vendor according to the company`s overall strategy, use case, conversational AI capabilities, and budget plays a critical role in the overall project implementation success (Ransbotham et al., 2018).

iv) Funds and Resource Allocation

Optimal allocation of funds and resources for CA projects has been identified as another vital aspect of ensuring implementation success (Mubiru et al., 2020). This requires optimal allocation of funds and resources judiciously so that the dedicated project team meets the budget and the deadline of the project. A study conducted by Mubiru et al., (2020) has identified multi-criteria goal programming based on preemptive priorities sets for project completion as a useful tool to achieve AI project implementation goals. According to Gartner (2020), there is a large disparity in pricing for cloud CA platforms, as the most common pricing models are subscription-based pricing plans requiring different budgeting requirements and budgeting strategies. Determining the implementation budget for a CA can be a complex undertaking for many organisations, especially when the AI-based CA platform involves customising and deploying machine learning in the system (Gartner, 2020).

As studies indicate, the cost of implementing an AI-based CA can range from thousands of pounds to millions of pounds, depending on factors such as use case, use case objectives, customer size, and automation level (Ismail, 2018; Mehta, 2019). In addition, AI-based CAs require continuous maintenance and improvements even after the launch to ensure the outputs and performance accuracy. For instance, according to Gartner (2019), 40% of the CAs launched in 2018 will have been abandoned by 2020 if organisations don`t have the capability to support the required resources and subsequent development. Therefore, organisations willingness to provide adequate funds and resource for their CA during the implementation and after the launch to maintain and improve its performance has been identified as an imperative factor for the project implementation success.

v) Project Management

PMI (2017) defines a project as an endeavour taken with necessary actions and steps to create a unique product or service. Project management refers to the plan, coordination, control, and monitoring of all aspects of a project to achieve implementation goals within the agreed time and allocated budget (Mir and Pinnington, 2014; Radujković and Sjekavica, 2017). Many IS implementation studies in the body of literature have identified project management as another widely discussed success factor to ensure the performance of the implementation that would lead to accomplishing its success (Radujković and Sjekavica, 2017). Research has shown that when managing a project, it requires a competent and skillful team, (i.e. a project manager and team members), tools, and techniques to meet the project goal posed by an organisation (PMI, 2000; Mir and Pinnington, 2014). Moreover, some authors emphasise that having an effective and competent project manager plays a critical role in ensuring the project's success (Radujković and Sjekavica, 2017). The project manager's responsibilities include: managing the budget and completion time and managing risk, integration, project scope, handling all the stakeholders, and maintaining effective communication during the implementation (Mir and Pinnington, 2014).

After evaluating the project management literature, Radujković and Sjekavica, (2017) presented three main categories that would contribute to project implementation's overall success. These three categories are, 1) elements of project management competence, 2) elements of the organisation, 3) elements of project management methodologies, techniques, tools, and methods. The 'Elements of project management competence' category consists of the project manager's domain-specific knowledge, emotional intelligence, and previous experience, team members' competencies, and the coordination between the project manager and the team members. 'Elements of the organisation' category consists of the organisational structure, organisational culture, organisation's market position, resource allocation, and employees' competence. 'Elements of project management methodologies' category includes the use of project management tools and software, IT support, decision-making techniques, and risk assessment tools. However, Radujković and Sjekavica, (2017) noted that these factors might vary depending on project type, organisation type and the culture, and project orientation.

However, according to Srivastava et al., (2020), AI systems implementation project management calls for a different approach in contrast with the traditional IS project

management approach as it involves big data, natural language processing, machine learning, and deep learning. As Srivastava et al., (2020) argue, conversational agents and AI systems implementation, in general, is a business project more than a technical project, although it involves a project team, data scientists, software developers in writing algorithms. Meaning, organisations that want to implement the CA need to be heavily involved to validate their company-specific data, validate the automating self-service process, and maintain the system after the launch. Thus, in order to ensure CAs implementation success among the UK e-commerce retailers, it is suggested to maintain an effective collaboration between the project team and the organisation.

vi) Strategy

Researchers have argued that organisations implementing CAs without a strategy considering longer-term implications make current CAs vulnerable in many areas and failing miserably to fulfill effective self-service expectations (Ransbotham et al., 2018; Piccolo et al., 2018; Brandtzæg and Følstad 2018; Jain et al., 2018). These studies have highlighted the need of addressing AI initiatives' complexities and emphasised the importance of having a clearly defined strategy to achieve the overall implementation goal with a comprehensive plan to succeed (Devenport & Ronanki 2018; Sun & Medaglia, 2019; Sjøberg, 2019). As some studies claim, organisations considering implementing conversational agents typically rely on vendors/technology partners, yet their CAs implementation considerations must span beyond the technical aspects (Devenport & Ronanki 2018). According to Ransbotham et al., (2018) AI implementation strategies require rapid scale up and scale down capabilities, and organisations must rapidly adapt to changes in demand to utilise the potential opportunities. Implementation strategies have been referred to as the 'how to' of achieving implementation goals incorporating multiple behavioural, technological, and organisational components (Ransbotham et al., 2018).

According to many AI researchers, a company cannot successfully deploy AI systems throughout the enterprise unless they have an implementation strategy to make sure that they have ambitious but achievable targets and a clear roadmap leading to them (Ransbotham et al., 2018; Piccolo et al., 2018; Brandtzæg and Følstad 2018; Jain et al., 2018).

vii) Change Management

Change management has been a widely cited CSF in CAs, AI systems, and IS implementation literature. Successful change management is an essential topic for all organisations, and how to achieve organisational change successfully during project implementation is identified as a central question for many senior-level managers. Research about 'change' in organisational development (OD), began with the humanitarian 'Kurt Lewin' in 1946, and Lewin is considered the intellectual father of organisational development, planned change, and applied behavioural science (Burnes, 2004). One of the early change management approaches was discussed by Lewin (1951), and in his study, he presented a three-step change model and argued that change involves a three-stage process: 'unfreezing current behaviour, moving to the new behaviour, refreezing the new behaviour'. Lewin's three-step model was the dominant change management framework for many years, and this model was reviewed and adopted by other researchers since its formulation. For example, followed by Lewin's three-step model, Bullock & Batten (1985) developed a four-stage model for managing change successfully, and these four stages consist of 'exploration, planning, action, and integration'. Building upon these early studies, the concept of managing change has been evolved over the years and as a rational, strategic, and structured process that organisations practice carefully (Gwaka et al., 2016).

As the literature findings indicate that there have been relatively few empirical studies available on CAs implementation-related change management approaches due to the infancy nature of the topic, and less research into how change management could contribute towards the project success. However, it was revealed that many researchers have discussed the importance of change management in IS implementation project success (French and Bell, 1984; Cummings and Huse, 1989; Eardley et al., 2007; Lalonde, 2011; Haddad and Kotnour, 2015). Under IS implementation related studies, change management theories under 'group dynamics perspective', and 'individuals perspective' claim that organisational change must occur at both the team level and an individual level with a focus on modifying and shaping the norms, roles, and values of their employees (French and Bell, 1984; Cummings and Huse, 1989; Haddad and Kotnour, 2015). Lalonde (2011) also confirms this claim and emphasis that when implementing projects in an organisation that involves people (and issues related to them), more creative energy must be released, and the project success must not be accomplished alone. Under the group dynamic perspective and individual perspective, IS implementation studies have suggested investing in employees by undertaking training to develop the organisation's

relevant skills as a vital part of the change management process when a project implementation occurs (Carroll and Rosson 1995; Cagliano et al., 2006). These studies have also suggested that facilitating training requirements during the implementation should be evaluated extensively regarding both its immediate and longer-term impacts. A study conducted by Eardley et al., (2007) highlights the fact that the appointment of a 'transition champion network' capable of becoming special advocates is a significant factor in increasing the likelihood of any IT/IS implementation success. Effective communication within the organisation and relevant teams was highlighted as another crucial factor contributing to successful change management during an AI or IS project implementation.

In order to provide a holistic view of the change management approach, after an extensive review of change management literature, Haddad and Kotnour (2015) proposed a taxonomy to change and presented four primary areas organisation usually must pay close attention to and the alignment required when managing change. These areas are namely: change type, change enablers, change method, and change outcome.

'Change type' refers to defining the essential characteristics of the change that is going to take place in the organisation. According to Moore (2011), the first step of defining the change type is to consider where the company is today and then evaluate what processes it needs to transform or strengthen toward managing the change. 'Change enablers' refer to the critical factors that affect change success in an organisation (Haddad and Kotnour, 2015). Change enable factors include: a clear vision for the anticipated change, top management involvement, clearly defined role and responsibilities of employees involved in change, employee education and training, knowledge and skills, resources, performance measures (Bridges and NetLibrary 2003; Haddad and Kotnour 2015). 'Change methods' refer to the actions carried out by organisational leaders when managing change. Change methods involve a specific set of processes and tools to help the top managers make decisions (Zook, 2007). 'Change outcome' refers to the consequences that bring to the organisation through change. As studies suggest, measuring change outcomes can be used to evaluate the implementation's overall success and provide management with new insight into the overall organisational performance and the system performance after the deployment (Haddad and Kotnour 2015).

2.4.6 Data Related Factors

viii) Data Quality and Big Data

The power of AI systems is heavily reliant on the collection, usage, and processing of 'Big Data', and the emergence of big data has been considered a breakthrough in technological development over recent years (Fichman et al., 2014). 'Data' can be defined as collecting facts, observations, or other information related to a particular question or a problem (Igo, 2007). PWC (2018) describe 'Big Data' as a collection of large and complex data sets of 'structured data, semi-structured data, and unstructured data' challenging to process using basic database management tools or traditional data processing applications. 'Structured data' has classified as well-defined data that can formally collect such as names, addresses, phone numbers etc. In contrast with structured data, 'Semi-structured data' does not form the formal structure of data models but is associated with relational databases or other forms of data tables. 'Unstructured data' has classified as information that either does not have a pre-defined data model or is not organised in a pre-defined manner (i.e. pictures or social media posts, recorded conversations, a word document, thousands of emails). Data helps train CAs to understand how humans think and speed up its learning process (Buren et al., 2020). As Anand et al., (2017) explain, “the more information there is to process, the more data the system is given, the more it learns and ultimately the more accurate it becomes” (p. 5). Data is the core of AI technology as the availability of massive amounts of data generated every day has been identified as one of the key reasons for many AI systems' success and development (Dwivedi et al., 2019; Sjøberg, 2019).

ix) Data Preparation

When the AI hype is brushed aside, a CA implementation involves many mundane works that underlie ML and NLP practices, including collecting, cleaning, curating data, managing training datasets, choosing or designing algorithms, and altering code-based outputs (Elish and Boyd 2018). Data cleaning (also known as data scrubbing) generally refers to identifying, replacing, incomplete, inaccurate, irrelevant data sets correcting towards machine-readable formats (Tambe et al., 2019). Although organisations might have lots of data to use for the CA, data preparation is vital if that data is not in machine-readable formats (i.e. unstructured or semi-structured) and not CAs training data material. Although deep learning can process most of the unstructured data sources, at this early stage of AI-based CAs, it is essential to prepare

the unstructured bulk data for the CAs appropriate training format (Lawnboy, 2018). The size of the organisation and its domain play a crucial role in `data availability` as smaller organisations may not have access to much data compared with large organisations (Sjøberg, 2019). However, Tambe et al., (2019) explain that not having large data sets does not necessarily mean that organisations can't use AI systems, but having large amounts of data means that an organisation can get much better benefits and accurate results from CAs and other AI systems.

x) Knowledge Base Creation

The knowledge base has defined as the “brain” of a conversational agent (Suta et al., 2020). When generating responses, the knowledge base has been recognised as the information repository the CA refers to during the dialogue management stage to ensure the most appropriate responses. The knowledge base generally contains keywords and phrases of the user inquires and the most suitable responses associated with these keywords/phrases (Reshmi, 2018). During the CA implementation phase, the knowledge base must be stored with large-scale information sources (by extracting data from various data sources) for a CA to obtain knowledge, and these information sources could be either consist of structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data sources (Reshmi, 2018). As Yan (2018) highlights, AI-based CAs retrieve information from all these three types of structured, semi-structured (i.e. labelled questions response pairs), and unstructured data sources (i.e.DocChat) to improve the fluency of the CA responses.

An adequate conversational process of a CA depends on AI capabilities and the interaction of data volume. Thus, CAs need to be designed for providing acceptable responses in the case of conversational breakdowns avoiding possible misinterpretation in dialogues (Følstad and Brandtzæg, 2017). According to Lawnboy (2018), when implementing a customer self-service CA, it is crucial to understand how people communicate in a chat environment since it is considerably different from email or telephone communications. Therefore, he suggests that companies must figure out how bulk emails with relatively long messages, telephone scripts, or any other human activities to convert into short CAs appropriate messages (as the structured company-specific data sources) when creating databases. Lawnboy, (2018) also noted that although organisations may have their existing data in a structured format (i.e. via live chat or call centre agent records), implementation teams must still go through the database creation procedures (i.e. data labelling and assign the correct category) prior to the CA launch.

2.4.7 Technological Factors

An AI-based CA is one of the most elementary and widespread examples of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and a typical example of an AI system that can do a variety of tasks ranging from tedious to more complex service counter job tasks (Adamopoulou and Moussiades, 2020). A CA as a computer programmed that responds like a smart entity through texts requires many AI subsets as the primary technological components to design and simulate conversation with human users. Therefore, this section presents the technical factors that directly contribute to maintain a human-level seamless conversation and subsequently contribute to the implementation success. These factors are natural language processing, machine learning, and data sharing and integration.

xi) Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural Language Processing (NLP), also known as computational linguistics, is a subset of Artificial Intelligence that allows computers to understand human language (Khurana et al., 2017). In various studies, NLP has been defined as a method for analysing naturally occurring human language and processing phrases and dialogues using computers to interpret text and voice, and thus classified as a field that seeks to close the communication gap between humans and machines (Khurana et al., 2017; Delen, 2013; Manning and Schutze, 1999). NLP has been identified as the heart of AI-based CAs as NLP helps CAs process the received text to interpret, comprehend, and then define a series of appropriate actions (Khurana et al., 2017). NLP has existed since the 1940s, and Warren Weaver and Andrew Donal started discussions about Natural language processing in 1946 to understand the feasibility of breaking enemy codes through machine translation in World War 2. Yet in 1957, it was found that solving this problem could get much more complicated than it seemed, and since then, it has been contributed theoretically and practically in the fields of interacting with the computer (Bachate and Sharma, 2020).

Today, NLP has been identified as a significantly important subfield of Artificial Intelligence for computer science and many other industries (Bachate and Sharma, 2020). NLP has many application areas, and among these, 'recognition management and generation of speech, natural language interfaces, machine translation, intelligent writing assistants, understanding of history and text generation, intelligent writing assistants, and speech management' can be highlighted (García et al., 2018). NLP is a complicated field since it requires a linguistic corpus, the

software tools and necessary hardware, a model of the domain in which the system wants to work, and linguistic knowledge of the language that is going to use (García et al., 2018). In addition, NLP requires different disciplines that must work together with such as computer science for method and creation of software, mathematics to identify formal models and methods, linguistics to create process and linguistic models, and neuroscience to explore the brain's mechanisms and other physical activities (Bachate and Sharma, 2020).

NLP helps the CA understand speech and text-based human commands, and an NLP unit of a CA includes two main components: *Natural Language Understanding* (NLU) and *Natural Language Generation* (NLG). NLU is one of the core components of NLP that aims to extract the context and the meaning of a user query or input. NLP extracts meaning from natural language to determine the user request's context (i.e. is this a question, suggestion, offer, or command). It identifies user intent and extracts domain-specific entities (i.e. what a user says and what actions to be taken by the CA for the query),(Adamopoulou and Moussiades, 2020). NLG refers to the NLP component that uses to prepare a natural language human-like response for the user query (sing et al., 2016). The appropriate responses are produced by one of the three models: rule-based, retrieval-based, and generative model (Hien et al., 2018).

Figure 2.7: A conceptual architecture of NLP integration in a CA

Source: Baez et al., (2020)

Figure 2.7 illustrates the NLU and NLG functionalities of a CA for the “*what is the weather like today*” user request. As the figure shows, ‘*intents*’ referred to the query or the user request

(i.e., the user's task to be performed by the CA). The user requests provided in text-based natural language are referred to as '*utterances*'. In order to identify the user intents (in this example to obtain a weather forecast) from the utterance (in this example, “what’s the weather like today?”) requires an NLP unit. The NLP unit is trained with a dataset of examples consisting of utterance-intent mappings to map utterances to intents. For instance, intents are categorised into parameters or slots (i.e. date, city of the weather forecast), and NLU must be able to infer values from utterance-intent training dataset examples. Once an intent is identified, the dialogue management component plays a crucial role to play the next action to generate the appropriate response (i.e. sends a call to the weather API). Lastly, NLG component produces the most suitable response. “8 °C, Cloudy, with 50% chance of rain” in the form of the user’s natural language (Baez et al., 2020).

xii) Machine Learning Integration

Although CAs have been identified as having significant promise, at this starting point, most CAs perform tasks in a somewhat predictable fashion (Pandita et al., 2018). The current rise of simple request-response 'decision tree logic' based CAs and its lack of performance have minimised organisations' potential to believe in the true potential of AI-based CAs and hindered the adoption and implementation of these intelligent CAs (Hu, 2019). This raises questions as to what distinguishes AI-based CAs from regular decision tree logic-based CAs.

'Human Intelligence' considers humans' ability to learn over time to adapt to their environment (Huang and Rust, 2020). Artificial Intelligence focuses on developing intelligent machines to mimic human intelligence and perform tasks such as '*learning, communicating, problem-solving, perceiving and acting*' that a human would do (Russell and Norvig, 2010). To perform such intelligent tasks, AI systems require information processing capability, logical reasoning capability, mathematical skills, and a consistent learning capability without needing much help from human developers after the deployment (Sternberg, 1999; Huang and Rust, 2020). In cognitive science and related fields, the term learning is used to express the process in which obtaining information through observation (Plamen, 2012; Oliver, 2014). Learning in humans is mostly composed of memorising, undertaking comprehension tasks, and learning from examples (Oliver, 2014). Similarly, Machine learning is the study of computer algorithms that improve automatically through experience (Rose, 2018).

In 1959, shortly after the first AI conference, AI researcher Arthur Samuel created a program that could play checkers designed to play against itself to learn how to improve, which is known as the first machine learning program (Rose, 2018). Daugherty and Wilson (2018), Classify 'Machine Learning' as the computer`s ability to learn without being explicitly programmed. Studies highlight that machine learning applications sharply contrast with traditional computer programming as standard algorithms would follow programmers` static instruction or code (automate calculation). A machine-learning system conversely can learn based on data sets (automate intuition) (Rose, 2018; Daugherty and Wilson, 2018). A more formal definition was given for machine learning by Tom Mitchell as “a computer program is said to learn from experience (E) with respect to some task (T) and some performance measure (P), if its performance on T, as measured by P, improves with experience E then the program is called a machine learning programme” (Das et al., 2015, p. 31). A machine learning agent is typically used to automatically extract knowledge and experience from the environment by learning from examples in the form of inductive reasoning (Ramezani, 2014). Inductive reasoning is a method in which the inferences are made with less confidence compared to deductive reasoning as in deductive reasoning, and the conclusion is entailed from the premises in case of a valid deduction (Ramezani, 2014).

Figure 2.8: Distinction between AI, machine learning and deep learning

Source: IBM (2018)

Machine learning is one of the branches and most essential subfields of Artificial Intelligence (see figure 2.8), dedicated to devising algorithms that allow automated learning (Ramezani, 2014). Machine learning algorithms are designed to help AI systems learn intuitively from data to find insightful information and perform a task without being explicitly programmed where to look for a particular piece of information (Huang and Rust, 2020). Deep learning (DL) is a

subset of machine learning and a relatively new set of methods that are changing machine learning in fundamental ways (IBM, 2018).

Given some background knowledge, machine learning aims to use inductive reasoning to infer new relevant information (Ramezani, 2014). Commonly, there are three main types of machine learning approaches: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning (García et al., 2018; Akerkar 2019).

Figure 2.9: Types of machine learning

Source: Adopted from Das et al., (2015)

Supervised learning – This learning method refers to training the system using data samples from the data source by assigning the correct answer or the classification (Sathya and Abraham, 2013). Meaning, this learning process is based on the comparison between computed output vs expected output and then adjusting the error for achieving the expected output (Das et al., 2015). These error and correction-learning algorithms train based on the input-output samples to identify error signals and adjust the expected output's synaptic weights. This learning method involves two main learning rules: the error-correction learning rule and the memory-based learning rule. A supervised learning paradigm is most effective for several linear and non-linear problems such as classification, prediction, forecasting and robotics etc. (García et al., 2018; Akerkar 2019).

Unsupervised Learning – This learning method refers to the system's ability to learn on its own by discovering patterns and adapting according to the system input without following an error signal to evaluate the expected system output. Unsupervised learning algorithms employ self-organising neural networks to identify hidden patterns of the unlabelled input data by dividing data into different clusters, and hence this type of learning is also called a clustering algorithm. The lack of direction provided for the learning in the unsupervised learning algorithms has

been identified as advantageous on some occasions since this learning method allows the algorithm to look back and forth at the data patterns that developers have not previously considered. One such example of unsupervised learning/ clustering is used in Google News as it groups new stories on the web and presents them as collective news stories (Sathya and Abraham, 2013).

Reinforcement Learning – The reinforcement learning method refers to the algorithm's ability to interact with its environment and learn a policy that maximises the expected outcome for a specific task. Reinforcement learning has also been defined as the training of machine learning models to make a sequence of decisions in an uncertain, potentially complex environment. This learning method employs a trial and error approach to come up with solutions to a problem through rewards and penalties (with the goal to maximize rewards) for the action it performs. This learning method has been recognised as the most effective way to utilise the machine's creativity to accomplish tasks. In contrast with supervised learning, the system is never presented with input/output pairs or explicitly corrected actions (Das et al., 2015).

Neural Networks

Machine learning has gotten a big boost recently, mainly since it works well with artificial neural networks – computer systems that are modelled after the human brain's neural structure (Rose, 2018). These are brain-inspired networks of interconnected layers of algorithms called neurons, that feed data into each other and which can be trained to carry out specific tasks by modifying the importance attributed to input data as it passes between the layers (tech republic, 2019). During the training of these neural networks, the weights attached to different inputs will continue to be varied until the output from the neural network is very close to what is desired, at which point the network will have `learned` how to carry out a particular task (tech republic, 2019).

Deep Learning (DL)

Deep learning (DL) is a subset of machine learning, and according to Rose, (2018), DL isn't an algorithm per se, but rather a family of algorithms that implement deep networks with the use of graphics processing units (GPUs) which are required to train the system in addition to clusters of compute nodes. DL works well with large amounts of data whenever a problem is too complex to understand (IBM, 2018).

Figure 2.10: Sample of a deep neural network with five layers

Source: IBM (2018)

Deep neural networks (another subset of machine learning) are neural networks expanded into sprawling networks with a huge number of trained layers using massive amounts of data. Deep neural networks have fuelled the current leap forward in computers' ability to carry out tasks like speech recognition and computer vision. Although there are various types of neural networks, 'Recurrent Neural Networks' and 'Convolutional Neural Networks' have identified the most commonly used and evolving Neural networks currently available in practice (Tech Republic, 2019). Recurrent neural networks are a type of neural net particularly well suited and used for language processing and speech recognition, in contrast, convolutional neural networks are more commonly used in `image recognition` (Tech Republic, 2019).

Deep Learning has been identified as the most recent advancement in using statistical models for conversational agents` to enhance natural language processing capabilities. The Neural Network architecture of deep learning primarily differs from traditional neural networks due to more hidden layers, with each layer consisting of more complex features (McTear et al., 2016). These deep neural network layers can learn from unlabeled data patterns and can be used for unsupervised learning environments. Deep learning methods can be used in a CA to generate POS tags of sentences (chunk text into verb phrases and noun phrases), entity recognition, and semantic role labelling (McTear et al., 2016).

xiii) Data Sharing and Integration

Some authors have discussed that to provide a seamless CA experience, data sharing and API integration with the CA plays a crucial role (Huang and Rust, 2020; Dwivedi et al., 2019; Sjøberg, 2019). As some studies suggest, poor API integration could prevent the CA from delivering an effective customer service experience while risking the accuracy of the responses. Studies such as Sun & Medaglia (2019) also noted that poor API integration prevents data from

internal company systems from being transported into the CA, potentially limiting the CA's NLP and ML capabilities (Elish and Boyd, 2018). Data sharing and system integration, therefore, are considered crucial technical factors.

2.4.8 Governance Related Factors

xiv) Data Privacy

Since CAs track user habits and behaviour with the use of APIs to perform sentiment analysis and personalised experience, it's crucial to secure the privacy and security of the data collected (Fadhil and Gabrielli, 2017). To ensure governance, some governments are introducing guidelines for the use of any type of automated decision-making system, including conversational agents. For instance, the Europe union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), introduced in Europe, not only hinders how companies can use the available data but could also result in losing the free access companies have had to rich consumer data. Through the enactment of the GDPR, the European Union mainly focuses on two principals, (1) Restrict complete automated decision making without any human intervention, and (2) Grants users a 'right to explanation' for algorithmic decisions involving them (Goodman and Flaxman, 2016). According to GDPR requirements, there must be clear data lineage and explainability to meet compliance requirements so that organisations have the ability to demonstrate how a decision about a customer has been reached (Pickup, 2019). This ties in with ethics and problematic privacy concerns that have been there among the general public since its inception. Thus, it is compulsory for organisations to ensure user privacy when implementing CAs as collection, storage, and sharing of AI technology derived large data sets raises ethical questions connected to governance, privacy, data ownership, quality, safety, and standards (Zandi et al., 2019; Dwivedi et al., 2019).

xv) System's Security

As with any AI system, ensuring data that's shared with a conversational agent remains secure has been noted as a responsibility of an organisation with paramount importance when implementing a CA (Lai et al., 2019). System security has been identified as a key component of a CA if organisations want their customers to accept the self-service provided by their CAs and increase customer confidence to engage without hesitation (Lai et al., 2019). The literature on AI systems security has grouped CAs' security risks into two groups, 1) Threats, 2) Vulnerabilities. 'Threats' refer to one-off events, including malware and DDoS attacks

(Dwivedi et al., 2019; Miller, 2019). These types of business-targeted attacks can result in organisations being locked out of their CA system and held to ransom, or hackers can threaten to expose customer data. '*Vulnerabilities*' refer to the cracks in the CA system that would compromise its security by offering cybercriminals a way into the system. These vulnerabilities could occur due to weak coding or inadequate safeguards and the system's lack of 'hackproof' nature (Miller, 2019). Thus, to ensure the CA implementation success in the e-commerce setting, organisations must work with security specialists to ensure any threats or vulnerabilities are sealed as soon as they are discovered from their CA system before and after the launch.

xvi) Transparency

When it comes to enterprise-level AI systems, while there are many ways to increase trust and transparency of algorithms, Miller, (2019) has identified two complementary approaches that will form many trusted AI systems. These approaches are (1) generate decisions (outputs from AI Systems) based on how well a human could understand the decisions in the given context, which is often calls 'interpretability or explainability', and (2) explicitly explaining decisions to people, which he calls 'explanation'. Many researchers' running hypothesis is that by building more transparent, interpretable, or explainable AI systems, users will be more equipped to understand and trust AI systems better (Mercado et al., 2016; Hayes and Shah 2017; Miller, 2019). When these AI systems become more sophisticated and independent, it is critical for human counterparts to understand the system's behaviours, the reasoning process behind those behaviours, and the expected outcomes to properly calibrate their trust in the systems and make appropriate decisions (Lee and See 2004; De Visser et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2016).

2.5 Theoretical background for Conversational Agents Implementation

In order to determine the success criteria relevant to the CAs implementation for the present study and to answer the second research question, the following section will discuss information systems (IS) implementation theories and how implementing enterprise-wide IS and its success criteria have been previously discussed in general. This review seeks to gather valuable insights on IS success criteria to provide a rich context for the present study, mainly due to the limited availability of literature in relation to AI-based CAs implementation. Subsequently, a conceptual framework will be developed based on the CSFs identified in the previous section and success criteria identified in this section to present a success model for AI-based CA implementation in the UK retail e-commerce context.

2.5.1 Theoretical Perspectives on Information Systems Success

To measure various IS implementation success, organisations are moving beyond traditional ROI-related financial measures. The IS implementation success is primarily discussed and analysed within the academic literature, and within the last decade, these success measures have been identified through different perspectives in a variety of studies. The IS success literature was initially consolidated in the 'Model of System Success' by DeLone and McLean (1992) (D&M model) and then followed by Seddon (1997)'s IS success model. These two models (figure 2.11 and 2.12) were the baseline for the later success models developed by the IS community (Petter et al., 2012; Urbach and Muller, 2012; Nguyen et al., 2015). Based on the prior studies, it seems evident that the most commonly referenced model of information system success was proposed by DeLone and McLean (1992, 2003), evaluating nearly 200 articles that measured IS success and then synthesised these measures into a model of information system success. DeLone & McLean (1992) was undertaken the development of the initial IS theory and was further updated based upon the feedback received from IS scholars. DeLone and McLean (1992) identified six factors in their findings that mainly had been used to measure IS success. These factors were: information quality, system quality, use, user satisfaction, individual impact, and organisational impact. This way of dividing the IS success into six major independent categories provided a comprehensive framework for evaluating IS success among the IS field researchers (see figure 2.11).

Figure 2.11: The DeLone and MacLean IS success model

Source: DeLone and McLean (1992)

After the publication of the first IS success model D&M (1992), some scholars argued that the D&M model was incomplete and thus must be modified, claiming that more dimensions should be included. For example, authors such as Seddon and Kiew (1994); Seddon (1997) argued that the original D&M model must be re-specified by differentiating actual and expected impacts to address the model's lack of comprehensiveness, suggesting to incorporate the additional

perceived usefulness in Davis's TAM (1989). In 1997, Seddon examined the practical applications of D&M's model, arguing that their 1992 original model was confusing (see figure 2.12). Moreover, Rai et al. (2002) showed the inability to explain IS success through the original D&M model and Seddon (1997)'s model. Sabherwal et al, (2006) conducted a study to investigate the D&M model's validity and highlighted the importance of contextual attributes in IS success.

Figure 2.12: Seddon's IS success model

Source: Seddon (1997)

The main difference between D&M (1992) model (figure 2.11) and Seddon's (1997) IS success model (figure 2.12) is the definition and placement of IS use as Seddon (1997) argues that the 'Use' must precede benefits and impacts, but does not cause them. Furthermore, Seddon (1997) considers IS 'Use' as a resulting behaviour of IS success since behaviour of the user is seeking net benefits from an information system. As Seddon claims, 'Perceived Usefulness' impacts 'User Satisfaction', and Seddon's model contains a direct path leading from System Quality and Information Quality to both 'Perceived Usefulness' and 'User Satisfaction' (Seddon, 1997).

However, as a result of the above criticisms, DeLone and McLean updated their first model presented in 1992 after ten years with a few modifications (DeLone, 2003). The primary differences between the original and the updated model are as follows: (1) the addition of *service quality* to reflect the importance of service and support in successful e-commerce systems, (2) to measure user attitude as an alternative measure of use, the addition of *intention to use*, (3) removing individual impact and organisational impact into a more parsimonious *net benefits* construct. Below updated DeLone and McLean (2003) model consists of six

interrelated dimensions of IS success: information quality, system quality, service quality, (intention to) use, user satisfaction, and net benefits.

Figure 2.13: The updated DeLone and MacLean IS success model

Source: DeLone & McLean (2003)

Seddon's Model of Success (1997) was revised and used by later studies that were more specialised in enterprise system success (Seddon et al., 2010; Urbach and Muller, 2012). However, IS Success model (DeLone & McLean, 1992) and its revision (DeLone, 2003) has evolved as predominant frameworks to structure IS success (Urbach et al., 2009). In addition, the updated D&M model has also been presented as a framework for organising IS success measurements (DeLone & McLean, 2003).

Moreover, to determine which success criteria are appropriate for CAs implementation success, this study has adopted the DeLone and McLean model for four reasons. First, many researchers have applied this model for understanding success criteria in various IS implementations (Wang, 2008; Gable et al., 2008; Urbach et al., 2009; Walther et al., 2018) with more than 5000 citations in the field of information system/enterprise system research, making this highly appropriate, given that AI systems implementation in the context of business is a class of IS/ES compared with Seddon's Model. Second, results are easy to communicate as the model has quite comprehensive categories. Third, D & M model provides a high degree of external validity as it is the most widely used IS success measured framework. Fourth, the D & M model has proven to represent AI-specific success criteria thoroughly with a specific focus on the e-commerce context.

DeLone and McLean (2003) advise researchers to select the suggested criteria of success appropriate to the context and the research problem. Hence, for the purpose of the present study, the researcher intends to observe the DeLone and McLean (2003) success model only with the focus of its three quality dimensions as the success criteria for CAs implementation. These three quality dimensions are ‘information quality, system quality, and service quality’. Subsequently, for the conceptual framework developed in figure 2.15, these three quality dimensions of the D & M model are adopted and combined with CSFs identified in the previous section.

2.5.2 Conversational Agents Implementation Success Criteria

i). System Quality

According to the D&M model, system quality refers to the characteristics of an information system (DeLone and McLean, 2003). Some authors have suggested the term ‘system quality’ of a CA refers to the effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction a user achieves while interacting with a CA as a self-service tool (Abran et al., 2003; Applin & Fischer, 2015). *Effectiveness* refers to the quality and accuracy of the conversation that helped a user achieve a specific goal (Eeuwen, 2017). *Efficiency* refers to how well organisations have applied resources to achieve user goals (Cohen & Lane, 2016; Thieltges, 2016). *Satisfaction* refers to the level of satisfaction a user has gained by conversing with a CA during the process of achieving a specific goal (Miner et al., 2016; Eeuwen, 2017). Various studies have discussed the quality attributes that must involve in these three system quality expectations. For example, some studies have highlighted the main quality attributes of *system`s effectiveness* and summarised the factors such: text accuracy synthesis, accurate commands interpretation, linguistic accuracy of outputs, overall ease of use, contains a vast amount of knowledge base and flexible interpretation of the information and passes the Turing test (Wallace, 2003; Kuligowska, 2015; Eeuwen, 2017; Ramos, 2017). Some authors have also highlighted the main quality attributes of the system`s efficiency and summarised the factors such as: delegation, robustness to unexpected user input, ability to avoid inappropriate utterances, and perform damage control on such occasions (Cohen & Lane, 2016; Thieltges, 2016). '*System satisfaction*' related quality attributes identified from the literature are: Greetings and the persona, semantic interaction by providing emotional information through expressivity and tone, make tasks more fun and interesting, the inclusion of respect, data privacy, trustworthiness (Applin & Fischer, 2015; Miner et al., 2016; Eeuwen, 2017).

ii) Information Quality

In the Delone and McLean (2003) IS success model, the information quality refers to the semantic success of the technology organisations intend to implement, which concerns the interpretation of the meaning of the receiver, compared with the meaning by the sender. The literature findings highlight the importance of information quality and emphasise the information presented to the user has to be timely, accurate, and relevant (Trivedi, 2019). In the context of CAs, most of the current CAs fail due to their lack of capability to provide relevant information at the right time while providing a seamless conversation (Trivedi, 2019). This has recognised as one of the main reasons CA users discontinue using a CA to communicate after having one bad conversational experience. Studies have used the term 'conversational' in a CA to describe systems that display more human-like characteristics to develop and maintain social relationships when performing a specific task. Similarly, the term 'conversation' in the enterprise context has generally been used to describe an interaction carried out with a customer for a transactional purpose (McTear et al., 2016).

According to the literature, understanding the subtle nuances of customer experience comprised experiential elements identified as a paramount factor for service organisations when implementing self-service CAs to co-create value with their customers (McColl-Kennedy et al., 2015; Sidaoui et al., 2020). According to Sidaoui et al., (2020), AI-based CAs that are particularly designed for customer self-service tasks call for high sentiment clarity that consists of five critical customer experience elements: thought, feeling, sensation, activity, and relation (De Keyser et al., 2020). As Sidaoui et al., (2020) suggest, an improved understanding of these elements would enable organisations to yield fruitful information exchange when they co-create the CAs self-service experience to satisfy their customer needs better. Huang et al., (2020) explain that 'Semantics and Sentiment Analysis is the heart of any dialogue system as it requires understanding the context of the conversation and understanding users from their persona, emotion, profile, and background of the dialogue content. Moreover, Huang et al., (2020) suggest that 'consistency' and 'interactiveness' must be integral parts of a CA to provide a positive information exchange and a user experience. '*Consistency*' refers to the CAs ability to respond consistently to the user's input (referring to the dialogue history) involving personalisation, stylistic generation, and coherence to the conversation context (Huang et al., 2020). '*Interactiveness*' refers to the CAs ability to respond reactively and proactively with the user. It requires the CA to have a deep understanding of dialogue context and users' emotional needs and generate dialogues as responses with a consistent personality to provide

entertainment, recommendations, chatting on exciting topics whilst providing emotional comfort (Huang et al., 2020; Sidaoui et al., 2020). Researchers have also investigated attributes expected in CAs to consider them more human-like such as self-consciousness, humour, purity, IQ and EQ, charisma, memory, social concerns, reliability, and empathy when it responds (Radziwill 2017; Zamora 2017; Xu et al., 2017; Wei et al., 2018; Liao 2018). Thus, when implementing CAs to enhance the customer self-service experience, literature findings suggest that the CAs ability to establish robust emotional connections with the user while achieving semantic success can enhance the conversational agent's information quality.

iii). Service Quality

Under the theme of service quality, numerous studies in relationship management have emphasised the importance of communicative behaviour` during customer service communications to evaluate the service provider interaction`s overall success (Palmatier et al., 2006; Lin and Lin, 2017; Van Pinxteren et al., 2020). As studies highlight, frontline employee (FLEs) encounters (during live chat, telephone, or email communications) typically comprise of nonverbal communicative behaviour (i.e. friendliness, gestures, and expressions) they would display during a conversation (specht et al., 2007; Sundaram and Webster, 2000). Service agent`s behaviour plays a key role in creating a positive first-time impression and perception towards the organisation, directly impacting building relational mediators such as trust and rapport, intention to repeat use, word of mouth, loyalty, and cooperation (Van Pinxteren et al., 2020). In service management literature, the 'relationship quality' is highlighted as an essential multidimensional determinant factor reflecting the overall relationship between a customer and a service provider.

Similarly, when implementing a CA as a self-service tool, literature has presented a number of service quality relationship determinants that organisations must consider to maintain between a CA and customer when implementing a CA as a frontline service technology. The communicative behaviour a conversation agent must follow to mimic a human-level conversation is presented in figure 2.14.

Figure 2.14: The role of communicative behaviours in service relationships

Source: Van Pinxteren et al., (2020)

Subsequently, when implementing CAs as a frontline self-service tool to emulate human communicative behaviour, some authors suggest the importance of introducing CAs as a customer service tool with a more sensitive, less mechanical appeal (Tzeng 2004; Holtgraves et al., 2007). However, researchers argue that when introducing CAs as a digital employee which builds upon “CASA” (Computers Are Social Actors) paradigm, current enterprise-level CAs do not seem to establish satisfactory relationships with customers (Fink, 2012; Everett et al., 2017; Morgan, 2017). Consequently, these findings suggest that when organisations decide to implement a CA for their frontline self-service customer service tasks, it is essential to select CAs which display communicative behaviours.

Figure 2.15: Conceptual framework for CAs implementation success

Developed by Author

In management research, CAs implementation success and its implications represent a comparably young research field (Dwivedi et al., 2019). As studies emphasise, implementing AI systems such as CAs can be extremely challenging, and there are a number of factors that can impact the outcome of such an AI investment (Duan, Edwards, & Dwivedi, 2019). Although the definition of success is subjective and can vary widely from business to business, there are some general barriers and challenges organisations may also have to consider and go through when they chose to invest in cognitive technologies such as AI. According to Duan et al., (2019), it is essential to identify Critical Success Factors (CSFs), as well as challenges and barriers organisations have to consider to succeed in such AI implementation projects. Hence the next section discusses the conversational agents' implementation challenges that would hinder the implementation success.

2.6 Conversational Agents Implementation Challenges

This section aims to investigate and identify the main challenges the UK retail e-commerce organisations face when implementing a conversational agent as a frontline technology tool. CAs implementation can hardly be characterised as an easy-to-use or easy-to-deploy system compared with other digital technologies (Lokuge et al., 2018). The literature indicates that addressing the complexities around non-technical and technical challenges the UK e-commerce retailers may face during these early days of enterprise-level CAs plays a crucial role in ensuring its implementation success (Dwivedi et al., 2019; Jöhnk et al., 2020). Similar to identifying CSFs, it requires discussing the conversational agents' implementation challenges that may arise before and during the implementation to get a more in-depth insight to achieve the present study's research aim. Hence, this section synthesises the existing CAs implementation challenges that UK retail e-commerce organisations must pay close attention to before and during the implementation to avoid the risk of project failure and to address the third research question. This section reviews existing CAs implementation challenges under two categories, namely: organisational challenges and technical challenges.

2.6.1 Organisational Challenges

The transition towards adopting and implementing CAs presents a number of organisational and managerial challenges that can create strategic implications for firms. Existing literature has reported a variety of organisational challenges that retail e-commerce organisations may face when implementing a conversational agent as an FST self-service tool. Major challenges identified from the literature include managers' lack of readiness, poor use cases and lack of

strategy, Users` expectations and acceptance, resistance to change and organisational culture, lack of AI skills and resources, and risk of losing jobs.

i) Managers` Lack of Readiness

As the first step of CAs adoption, company leaders/managers must learn to deal with this upheaval because AI is set to modify how they perform their work in the near future (Kolbjørnsrud et al., 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019; Jöhnk et al., 2020). Nevertheless, recent studies suggest that many managers are still not entirely on the same page and are still sceptical when it comes to becoming collaborative partners with AI (Kolbjørnsrud et al., 2017; Markus, 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019). Existing literature on AI systems adoption and implementation highlights that the top manager`s readiness and enthusiasm for AI vary extensively across organisations and industry sectors. Drawing on findings of a survey conducted from 1770 managers in 14 countries and interviews with 37 senior executives, Kolbjørnsrud et al., (2017) postulates that front-line managers and mid-level managers are less optimistic towards integrating AI into their daily processes in contrast to top management (see figure 2.16).

Figure 2.16: Management readiness to work with AI in organisations

Source: Kolbjørnsrud et al., (2017)

In Kolbjørnsrud et al., (2017) study, when asked whether they would trust the advice of intelligent systems making business decisions in the future, only 14 percent of frontline managers and 24 percent of middle managers took part in the survey 'strongly agreed' with the statement in contrast to the 46 percent of top management`s positive response received.

Similarly, when asked the manager`s willingness to accept responsibility for AI systems actions, only 17 percent of frontline managers and 26 percent of middle managers 'strongly agreed' to the statement. In comparison, 45 percent of top management showed the highest ranked response. Although the above study was not primarily focused on conversational agents, considering CAs as an AI system, it can be argued that middle level and front line managers` receptiveness to work with a CA in their customer service departments can be a vital factor towards the project success. Thus, it can be argued that the lack of readiness among front-line and mid-level management to relish the opportunity to collaborate with AI technology to their daily work practices is a significant challenge that could hinder CAs implementation success. This raises serious questions about how, without managers` readiness, retailers can best adopt CAs and get the most value AI technology has to offer (Kolbjørnsrud et al., 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019).

From an organisational perspective, a conversational agent's success is defined based on how well it can fulfil the use case objectives and engage with the users seamlessly during a conversation to accomplish a task (Brandtzaeg and Folstad, 2017). However, while CAs may expand opportunities and enhance digital competence for many organisations, current CAs often fail to deliver those expectations (Brandtzaeg and Folstad, 2018). Both research and industry reports suggest that most available CAs fail due to organisations lack of planning (Schuetzler et al., 2014; Chakrabarti and Luger, 2015; Wannemacher, 2016; Brandtzaeg and Folstad 2018). According to Dwivedi et al., (2019), without a clearly defined strategy, it is often difficult for organisations to determine what they want to accomplish and how to measure success in adopting and implementing AI systems.

ii) Users` Expectations and Acceptance

The effectiveness of conversational agents` implementation can only be realised through its acceptance and use by the end-users. Yet, in this early phase of its deployment, these initiatives often ignore user needs, attitudes, user experiences (Brandtzaeg and Folstad, 2018). Research on conversational AI emphasis that if the technology does not meet the users` expectations, user acceptance can be led to frustration or disappointment and even towards rejection (Piccolo et al., 2018; Brandtzæg and Følstad 2018; Jain et al., 2018). Conversational agents have been identified as having significant promise and recently faced a substantial technology push in its development (Pandita et al., 2018). Hence, Piccolo et al., (2019) pointed out that the impact of conversational agents could be even more significant if more people could have made sense of

the functioning of the CAs and if first-time users understand the interaction style with more guidance. Therefore, it's vitally important to understand the user expectations, user preferences, and user acceptance of people who use the CAs as much as organisations focusing on deploying it for sustainable growth (Følstad and Brandtzæg, 2017; 2018). This means different users' expectations and perspectives of CAs hosted in mobile apps, Facebook Messenger or Slack, a website may lead to challenges for the interaction style (Piccolo et al., 2019). Despite these expectations, current CA designs are not considered users' particular needs, preferences, and contexts, instead, most of the cloud-based CA platforms follow a presumably one-size-fits-all approach (Følstad and Brandtzæg, 2017). These off-the-shelf, ready-to-use CA platforms (without integrating AI in them) often leave a terrible first impression and a dissatisfied conversational experience among the potential target customers.

iii) Resistance to Change and Organisational Culture

Aspects of the literature have classified managing the change when implementing a CA as a significant challenge that could hinder the project's success (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018; Dwivedi et al., 2019). While technological advancements of CAs adoption can bring invaluable benefits to organisations, the implementation process involves changes that have to make in organisational structure and business processes. Without the top management's support, these changes could meet resistance from various stakeholders (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018). According to Sun & Medaglia (2019) having an organisational culture open to innovation and exploration can also contribute to pursuing a successful AI journey. Although conversational AI has been identified as a technology that can augment human capabilities, the unique strength of CAs also depends on the human effort to refine and improve its performance through continuous monitoring and investment while the system is in use (Dwivedi et al., 2019). However, refining and enhancing the CA's performance through continuous improvements has been a challenge for many organisations since the limitations of human employees' willingness to learn and adapt to the new environment in order to ensure the CAs continuous improvements. In addition, some studies argued that the impact of automating the customer service desks' specific tasks using a CA could be both positive and negative (Onnasch et al., 2014). For instance, although a higher level of automation may reduce operators' workload, it may also reduce the worker's situation awareness and create the tendency to overly rely on the conversational agent, neglecting their job responsibilities (Onnasch et al., 2014). Thus, when implementing a CA as a frontline service technology, organisational leaders need to understand

these challenges and come up with strategies to maintain the productivity of human service agents.

iv) Risk of Losing Jobs

Due to the extent of AI's popularity within the next few years, one major issue has been identified as AI's potential to improve human lives at the cost of mass unemployment (Oswald and Mascarenhas, 2018). Although implementing AI systems looks significantly beneficial and promising in the short and long run, there seem to be complexities and controversies surrounding AI that make it risky for society to lose specific jobs and ethically questionable to the community. The ethical debates of the threat of AI to substitute or replace human labour in the AI literature is real and large, and studies have highlighted the fact that at least 30% of the occupations could be automated (Oswald and Mascarenhas, 2018; Davenport & Ronanki 2018; Dwivedi et al., 2019). Employees' fear of losing their jobs to AI is another critical challenge organisations need to pay close attention to when implementing a CA to their organisation. However, such fear can also be argued by the fact that narrow AI is here to complement and augment human capabilities and do simple tedious work, but not to replace them (Daugherty, 2019). In addition, studies have highlighted that the jobs under threat are low-skill mechanical and routine jobs where the adoption of Artificial Intelligence technology could bring organisations higher efficiency and productivity benefits (Oswald and Mascarenhas, 2018).

v) Lack of AI Skills and Resources

An effective CAs adoption and implementation in the e-commerce retail setting requires employees with interdisciplinary knowledge both from technological and business disciplines (Oswald and Mascarenhas, 2018). Capgemini research, which recently ranked No.1 in the world for the quality of its research by independent analysis states, 64% of organisations lack AI skills and competence to take advantage of AI as a barrier to adoption and its implementation success (Pickup, 2019). Although companies may not have AI experts in-house, organisations capability to train the existing employees to use AI systems confidently is critical when implementing AI systems (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018; Dwivedi et al., 2019). According to the UK and Ireland Oracle's vice-principal of cloud and innovation, businesses should not expect AI technologies to magically turn their employees into data scientists. Instead, the organisational focus needs to be coupled with providing solid training on comprehending, interpreting, and analysing AI systems properly (Pickup, 2019). As a solution to address the skill gap challenge, there has been an explosion of availability of off-the-shelf

CAs with pre-built algorithms in the market with the promise of simple integration and ease of use (Pickup, 2019). However, on the contrary, some researchers argue that these off-the-shelf AI solutions rarely work well without AI-powered customisation and a lot of organisations fall into the trap of getting things done quickly at a lower upfront cost (Følstad and Brandtzæg, 2017). As a result, they end up spending years fixing issues that failed to bring the desired results (Følstad and Brandtzæg, 2017). Moreover, implementing CAs especially complex/custom CAs requires a lot of resources and monetary investments (Sjøberg, 2019). Many studies have highlighted that additional costs, resources need to use data from multiple sources, tools, and hardware to process those data can often discourage organisations from implementing CAs (Sjøberg, 2019; Shaw et al., 2019). Advance applications of ML/NLP require substantial computing power, and the more extensive the computing support, the more efficient ML applications become (Shaw et al., 2019).

2.6.2 Technical Challenges

The transition towards adopting and implementing CAs also present several technical complications that would hinder the CA project implementation success. This section has categorised and discussed the technical challenges the UK e-commerce retailers may face during their CAs implementation based upon the existing literature. These challenges include data-related challenges, user comprehension-related challenges, response generation-related challenges, and machine learning associated challenges.

i) Data-Related Challenges

Handling a large amount of inconsistent data has been identified as a significant complication for any AI system since most of the data sets are inconsistent and difficult to process (Gupta, 2017). As Gupta suggests, the underlying concepts of taking in a large amount of data and analysing it using machine learning would be a novel and yet challenging task for many organisations. Seaver (2015b) highlights that algorithmic systems, such as AI-based conversational agents, are crafted through precise attention to the context of data. This means the underlying meaning and the significance associated with datasets require converting a set of contextual and socially embedded relationships into data that can be machine-readable. Algorithms that process these machine-readable data are disconnected from meaning, seeking signals that convey information about the encoded content's mathematical properties (Elish and Boyd, 2018). As they explain, this process is about constructing and depicting statistical models without the focus to search for meaning. This barrier of algorithms' lack of ability to understand

the situations humans experience and derive the right meaning from it can make current AI systems vulnerable (Dwivedi et al., 2019). Moreover, the limited availability of conversational datasets with live user interactions when developing in-house CAs or cloud-based CAs platforms can also restrict the performance of CAs (Ram et al., 2018). As the transition to AI technology matures, these data-related challenges will need to be resolved to ensure full confidence for CAs implementation by all stakeholders.

ii) User Understanding Related Challenges

One of the main technical challenges that emerged from the CA literature is its lack of ability to understand what the user says or recognise the user query (Pryss et al., 2018). Despite the recent progress of AI, conversations with human users remain challenging due to 'Semantics issues' (Huang et al., 2020). Gupta (2017) shared a similar view and asserts that there are many complications involved with 'Human and Machine interaction' when it comes to communication at the service level. It was mainly due to human interaction's nature and complexity and the subtle ways humans interact with each other during a conversation. For instance, 'human voice, human body language, emotions, slang' all affect how two people might communicate. Thus, Gupta (2017) argues it's hard to model basic common sense in a machine or to make such inferences. Furthermore, studies have described that during a human-to-human conversation, multiple emotions are expressed, and comparatively, many background pieces of information are usually shared (Huang et al., 2020; Fadhil and Gabrielli, 2017). Therefore, these authors highlight the fact that complications may arise while trying to imitate human intuition or common sense during a conversation that can take place between a CA and a user. As Fadhil and Gabrielli (2017) postulate limitations in understanding the user also may occur due to (1) singular and plural form management and (2) synonyms, and hyponyms related to Natural Language Processing and ontology challenges.

iii) Response Generation Related Challenges

According to Fadhil and Gabrielli (2017), the ultimate vision for CAs is to mimic written or spoken human language to simulate a conversation similar to a human with a real person rather than just a simple request-response pattern CAs. However, as some studies indicate, technical challenges emerge from some of the CA's inability to provide an appropriate response to specific user requests (Pryss et al., 2018). Generating an appropriate response primarily depends on a knowledge base that contains all the information needed to provide a reasonable response to the user queries in a specific context. Yet, previous studies have highlighted that

the challenge is to create this knowledge base as it must be developed either by manual input, integration of existing databases and, and machine learning mechanisms to improve the response quality (Abdul-Kader and Woods, 2015; Pryss et al., 2018). When the conversations supported between the user and the CAs get complex, the CA's architectural design challenges can occur and usually require increasing resources to expand the CAs domain focus (Pryss et al., 2018). According to Abdul-Kader and Woods (2015), there has to be a high level of the accuracy of matching words or phrase patterns for CAs with keywords, and it is important yet challenging to give a variety of responses from the knowledge base to achieve the highest number of possible matches. These response generation-related challenges have been identified as one of the main barriers that could increase CAs and user misunderstandings. Consequently, it has led to a lack of trust in AI-based intelligent CAs adoption and implementation.

iv) Machine Learning Related Challenges

As mentioned in previous sections, AI follows multiple machine learning layers consist of 'supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning' to perform tasks learning from data without being explicitly programmed. In such a less supervised learning environment, technical challenges could exist around the moral and ethical qualities of the outputs that can create through unstructured data it captures (Dwivedi et al., 2019). For instance, on March 23, 2016, Microsoft launched a Twitter chatbot (CA) called 'Tay' powered by machine learning to understand and make interactive conversations with Twitter users. However, within 24 hours of the launch, Tay had started to make vindictive responses and derogatory remarks learning from the conversations Twitter users were tweeting. As a result, Microsoft had to completely shut down the chatbot within a short period as it became more and more racially abusive (Oswald and Mascarenhas, 2018). This example shows that machine learning algorithms' sophisticated structure with regard to data interpretation could cause the CA to make potentially catastrophic errors.

Moreover, some researchers emphasise that AI systems are prone to various biases, such as data-driven bias, gender-based bias, and interactive bias. For instance, studies note that an AI system could be written based on the programmer`s prejudices, and thus, highlight the importance of creating machine learning algorithms by specialists who avoid all sorts of biases with a clear understanding of possible outcomes and consequences (Oswald and Mascarenhas, 2018; Dwivedi et al., 2019). Complications also may arise when using a Machine Learning approach due to human errors and inconsistencies of labelled data as the conversations that

have been labelled by humans (Gupta, 2017). In addition, AI literature shows that ML systems are often referred to as 'black boxes' especially in the systems powered by deep learning that comes with more than one hidden layer of neural networks (Miller, 2019). The explanation of deep learning-driven systems' tasks is more complicated than the human explanation process (Miller, 2019). This issue has been recognised as a technical challenge for AI systems since machine learning tends to use the term interpretability rather than explainability for automated decision-making (Dwivedi et al., 2019). However, some studies have also argued that a reasonable explanation for an automated decision powered by machine learning may not have to be judged based on the same criteria that would be used to evaluate a human decision in a similar domain. But it is essential to organise at least the knowledge base and information the system processes in ways that are logical to a human (Dickson, 2019).

v) Governance Related Challenges

Interaction in natural language with various conversational agents` users is a context where privacy and ethical challenges can occur (Følstad and Brandtzæg, 2017). Since CAs track user habits and behaviour, it has been discussed that ensuring users' data privacy has been a challenge for many organisations (Fadhil and Gabrielli, 2017). A study conducted by Wirtz et al., (2019) focuses on the challenges of implementing AI systems indicates that it is imperative for organisations to address the concept of AI law and regulations to maintain governance and ensure responsibility, accountability, and privacy of their AI systems. To address the legal and policy challenges when implementing AI systems, Zatarain (2017) suggests that the current legal framework needs significant changes to protect and incentivise human-generated work effectively.

According to the emerging articles related to ethics and governance of AI, it was highlighted the fact that there`s a need to roll out such frameworks to address legal, political, and policy challenges worldwide when implementing AI systems. As Følstad and Brandtzæg (2018) argue, conversational agents are supposed to communicate with their users across genders, ages, languages, and preferences. However, Brandtzaeg et al., (2011) emphasise, some of the current CAs are typically set up to follow a one-size-fits-all approach with potential biases across gender, age, and social status while ignoring users' digital literacy, needs, and preferences. AI discrimination in some cases and issues with data bias can lead to inequality and unfairness (Wirtz et al., 2019; Sjøberg, 2019). Therefore, it was highlighted the importance of carefully considering both the data input and output when using AI since data bias could

create serious negative consequences (i.e. Microsoft TAY) (Thesmar et al., 2019; Sjøberg, 2019).

There is a growing concern in the AI community related to the explainability of AI systems, and organisations could risk reputational damage when things go wrong, especially when they are forced to rely on the 'black box' without understanding the logic behind its decision making (Sjøberg, 2019). The notion of 'explainable artificial intelligence' has seen a resurgence after having slowed since the burst of work on expert systems over three decades ago, driven by evidence that many AI applications have limited take-up to ethical concerns and a lack of trust among its users (Shams et al., 2016; Miller, 2019). According to Dwivedi et al., (2019), explainability is the ability to explain the reasoning behind a particular answer, decision, forecast, or classification, and the explainability of AI systems outputs has become an increasingly topical issue recently in both theory and practice. Miller (2019) emphasises that building AI systems capable of explanation is a challenging task, and there is still a lot of complexities around explainable AI around design and implementation. It is necessary to practice clear codes of conduct to ensure that AI benefits can be shared widely while its concurrent risks are well managed without losing human control over machines (Dwivedi et al., 2019).

Table 2.7: Conversational agents implementation challenges derived from literature

Challenge Type	Challenges
Organisational Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managers lack of readiness Users` expectations and acceptance Resistance to change and organisational culture Risk of losing jobs Lack of AI skills and resources
Technological Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data related User understanding related Response generation related Machine learning related Governance related

Developed by Author

2.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter has investigated and identified the key concepts, definitions, and theoretical bases for the main three research questions of CAs implementation benefits, critical success factors, success criteria, and implementation challenges. In this chapter, the researcher assessed the AI-based CAs implementation literature and identified the gaps in the body of the knowledge when the findings were applied to the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. Based on the review of the CSF literature, sixteen factors under four categories and three quality dimensions were identified as critical to ensure the CAs implementation success. The key findings from both the CSFs analysis and the D&M model's success criteria were then used to develop a conceptual framework to guide the research.

Chapter 3 : Methodology

The previous chapter described the underlying literature focusing on the key elements fundamental to develop a conceptual framework and achieve the research objectives. This chapter focuses on reviewing and examining existing philosophical positions and methodologies used in the field of Information Systems (IS), aiming to analyse prevailing paradigms and methodologies within the field of inquiry considering customer self-service CAs as a type of IS. As the first step, the ontological and epistemological perspectives for IS research include a presentation of positivism, interpretivism, critical realism, pragmatism, and justifications for choosing the research philosophy are discussed to establish the study's philosophical bases. In the second step, research methodologies and rationale for choosing the selected research method/research design are classified and justified.

3.1 Research Philosophy

Research is a systematic investigation and an explanation of a phenomenon in one or more ways. Research increases the sum of what is already known and also what's important for further investigation (Blaikie, 2007). The research philosophy a researcher adopts contains important assumptions about the way in which the researcher sees the world, and these assumptions will underpin the research strategy and the methods the researchers choose as part of that strategy (Saunders et al., 2009). The question of `what is known, how it is known, researcher`s beliefs and assumptions about the development of “knowledge” are generally referred to as the research philosophical paradigm (Saunders et al., 2019). To ensure the biases or perspectives are transparent, it is important to consider the beliefs, assumptions, and perceptions of the researcher and the research methodology, objectives, and output. These influences are broadly referred to as the philosophical research paradigm of epistemology and ontology (Saunders et al., 2019).

Ontology is a branch of philosophy that refers to the science of what is, structures of objects, properties, events, processes, and relations in every area of reality (Floridi, 2003). According to Crotty (1998) ontology is the study of being, and ontological assumptions are concerned with what constitutes reality or the researchers' philosophical position of how things really are and how things really work. On the other hand, Epistemology refers to assumptions about knowledge, what constitutes acceptable, valid and legitimate knowledge in a field of study, and how that knowledge is communicated to others (Saunders et al., 2011). A more concrete definition has been provided by Blaikie (2007), and he states epistemology as “the theory of

how human beings come to have knowledge of the world around them” (p.18). The relationship between epistemology and ontology is often close and interdependent, where each informs and depends on the other to address issues and assumptions of how we came to have that knowledge of reality (Hatch and Cunliffe, 2013).

Research philosophy shapes the way one can study the world and proposes how research can and should be conducted, to what extent the researcher`s involvement or detachment is required in the research, and who should conduct the research (Rubin and Rubin, 2011). Saunders et al., (2009) have classified 'positivism, interpretivism, realism and pragmatism' as four types of research philosophies that can be used in management research. These research philosophies can be seen through the eyes of ontology, epistemology, axiology, and data collection techniques (see table 3.1). These philosophical perspectives underline the way in which data is collected and analysed, and thus it is vital to overview the major IS research paradigms. Therefore, the next section will address these four research philosophies: positivism, interpretivism, critical realism, and pragmatism.

Positivism:

The positivist researcher adopts a concrete concept of observable social reality that seeks to reflect the natural scientist's philosophical stance (Denscombe, 2001). As Denscombe describes with this approach, it is assumed that, similarly to the natural world, social reality comprises regularities, patterns, and consequences. Positivism is established on the theory that human behaviour studies should be conducted in the same manner as natural science studies and thus attempts to place social research in a realm that is similar to scientific research (Collis and Hussey, 2003). To increase the predictive understanding of a research phenomenon, positivists tend to test theory using hypotheses with the assumption that the researcher remains neutral and detached from affecting the subject of the research or affected by it in turn (Remeniy et al., 1998; Myers, 2013). The positivist researcher adopts deductive, quantitative research techniques and views the object of study as independent from the researcher, and the hypotheses developed, would lead to the gathering of facts (rather than impressions) to provide the basis for hypothesis testing (Saunders et al., 2011).

On the same note, the basic positivist assumption is that: epistemologically, it is possible to collect data objectively, but ontologically, the researcher is expected to be detached from the objects of the research (Oates, 2005). According to Gill and Johnson (2010), positivist research's primary emphasis is the structured methodology, which leads to statistical analysis

through 'quantifiable observation'. However, some authors criticise positivism (Remenyi et al., 1998; Collis and Hussey, 2003; Mashat, 2005). They argue that treating the subjects as beings that are disconnected from the social environment is not possible as researchers won't be understood if their perceptions and self-activities are not examined.

Interpretivism:

Interpretivism developed as a critique of positivism but from a subjective perspective with the emphasis of humans are different from physical phenomena because they create meanings (Saunders et al., 2011). Interpretivism is a commonly regarded research paradigm, especially within the Information Systems scholars' community and, more generally, in the social sciences (Stahl, 2014). Different people from different cultural backgrounds, different circumstances, and different timelines can create different experiences and social realities to a phenomenon, and thus, interpretivism is critical to discover universal 'laws' that apply to everybody (Saunders et al., 2011). The purpose of interpretivist research is to create new, richer understandings through people's words, observations, and documents combined into a coherent picture expressed through participants' voices (Trauth and Jessup, 2000, Saunders et al., 2011). According to Saunders et al., (2009), for business and management researchers, interpretivism means looking at different perspectives from different people in organisations. According to Oates (2006), the characteristics of interpretive research include 1) multiple subjective realities, 2) Study people's different perspectives, 3) multiple interpretations, and 4) researcher reflexivity. The interpretivist researcher typically adopts inductive, small samples, in-depth investigations using qualitative research methods (Saunders et al., 2011).

Critical Realism:

Critical realism is described as another philosophical position that relates to scientific inquiry. The idea behind critical realism distinguishes the 'real world and the observable' world. Critical realists see reality as external and independent, and the 'real' cannot be directly accessible through our observation and knowledge of it. According to the critical realist, what we experience is 'the empirical' or sensations rather than the actual things. Critical realists recognise the importance of multi-level study and each of these levels (such as an individual, a group, or the whole organisation) that can enhance the researcher's understanding of what is being studied (Saunders et al., 2011). As Carlsson (2005) claims, critical realism is mainly absent from IS research, although it has been adopted and endorsed as an epistemological stance in several IS systems (Dobson, 2002; Scott, 2007).

Pragmatism:

According to pragmatism, Kelemen and Rumens (2008) assert that concepts are only relevant where they support action. According to Saunders et al., (2011), pragmatism strives to reconcile both subjectivism and objectivism, accurate and rigorous knowledge, facts and values different contextualised experiences in a non-abstract form by considering theories, concepts, ideas, hypothesis, and research findings. According to Goles and Hirshheim (2000), researchers may choose whatever methods are appropriate for the study as pragmatism may adopt a pluralist position. This means, in a pragmatist's view, it is perfectly possible to work with different types of knowledge and multiple methods within one study. Although, this does not mean that pragmatists always use multiple methods; rather, they use the method or methods for the purpose of the research (Kelemen and Rumens 2008).

3.1.1 The Rationale of the Interpretivist Philosophy

The general scenario for interpretive studies focuses on understanding the phenomena through the meanings assigned by different people with the key assumption associated with reality can be achieved through social constructions, such as language, consciousness, and shared meaning. Therefore, the researcher is considered interpretivist point of view and justifies the selection of the underlying research assumptions based upon the following reasons:

First, in this study, the researcher proposes investigating the success factors and success criteria for implementing CAs in the UK retail e-commerce sector as a self-service tool. Since CAs implementation is a new research area in the context of enterprises, the research aims to get a deeper understanding of the implementation benefits, CSFs, and success criteria affecting the implementation process and the challenges that can hinder the implementation success at the organisational level. Understanding such factors require a detailed interpretation from different organisational and technical contexts and support needed from case studies to strengthen the research outcome. Thus, there is a need for an interpretive philosophy to clarify the process to achieve the research aim and objectives.

Second, given the uncertain and complicated nature of innovation, such as artificially intelligence-based CAs, and the implementation of such systems can be better understood by examining the interpretations with relevant organisational and AI community members. Interpretivist philosophy allows the researcher to understand the different conceptions of

conversational AI systems implementation success from managers, vendors, and consultants' viewpoints while avoiding any bias.

Third, in the information systems (IS) field, interpretive studies are concerned with understanding the social context of IS. According to Madon (1992, p.21) "the interpretive nature of the object studied means that knowledge can only be acquired by understanding and interpreting the process of interaction between people in a particular social setting". Moreover, in contrast with positivist philosophy, prior IS studies discovered that the interpretive philosophy is more effective to understand the richness of a social context (Orlikowski and Baroudi, 1991).

Fourth, this study is concerned with a practical perspective on CAs implementation. This study's literature review indicates that there are many organisational, ethical, data, consultant, and vendor-related factors to be identified and their impact to be investigated in different perspectives within the organisational context. This research approach allows the researcher to investigate this insufficiently explored research area in depth. For these reasons, selecting an interpretive philosophy is considered the most appropriate and preferential choice for this study.

3.2 Research Approaches

There are two distinct approaches to research: inductive and deductive, and these approaches are concerned with how theories are used or developed (Blaikie, 2007; Saunders et al., 2009). The inductive approach is generally built and argument with the observation of data that is collected and analysed involving the identification of patterns and trends to develop a theory, whereas the deductive approach is fundamentally concerned with testing a theory (Saunders et al., 2007; Ritchie et al., 2013). According to Blaikie, (2000), the inductive approach is used to answer "what" questions while the deductive approach is used to answer "why" questions.

Taking into consideration the purpose of this thesis, the most appropriate approach to conduct this research is the inductive approach. It is essential that the inductive approach is applied in the present study to allow the researcher to explore the phenomenon due to the nature of its research objectives. Furthermore, the purpose of this research is exploratory since this study seeks to investigate the phenomenon of AI-based CAs implementation as an innovative 'Frontline Service Technology' for the UK e-commerce customer service context. As a result of the inadequacies of existing theories due to this research topic's relatively infancy nature, an

exploratory approach is considered most appropriate. Robson (2002) asserted that an exploratory study is an effective approach 'to ask questions, assess phenomena in a new light, discover what is happening, or seek new insights of a phenomenon'. Saunders et al., (2009) claim that exploratory research involves searching the literature and including findings of the interviews conducted with the 'experts' in the subject. By adopting the exploratory approach, this thesis follows the five characteristics of the process of inductive inquiry described by Creswell (2008), namely: initial information collection, semi-structured questions in interviews, identification of patterns through data analysis, examining themes identified in the patterns in a broad view and make suggestions, recommendations and theories based on the research experience and the literature.

3.3 Research Methods

This section is aimed to clarify the research approach and provide justifications for using the qualitative methods approach as the most suitable research method for this study and its context. This section also presents the possible choices for research methods that could be used to conduct research and discuss the methodological approaches academics use within the Information Systems research.

Quantitative Method

The quantitative research method is defined as a systematic investigation conducted in an empirical form of a phenomenon by testing theories examining the relationship among variables, measured typically on instruments, analysed data using statistical, mathematical, or computational procedures (Bryman, 2004; Creswell, 2009). Bryman (2012) defined the quantitative method as a research method that emphasises quantification in data collection and analysis. Quantitative research is undertaken to develop and employ hypotheses and/or mathematical models and allows research questions to be tested through selected samples to generalise findings accordingly. One of the main quantitative research features is that the study population's results could be relevant and linked to the entire population. Thus, conclusions derived from the study could be generalisable for the target audience's whole population (Sarantakos, 1998).

According to Creswell (2009), quantitative researchers usually test and validate well-known theories deductively and generalise and replicate the findings using statistical procedures (while making assumptions by controlling the possibility of alternative explanations, avoiding

biases). The quantitative research method allows the researcher to test the research questions by collecting a selected set of samples, analysis, interpretation, and illustration of findings through numerical data (Ajzen, 2005; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). The term “quantitative” and “positivist” has been used interchangeably in IS research, and quantitative method identified as one of the preferred methods among IS and AI researchers (Milward and Provan, 1998; Liang et al., 2019; Alhashmi et al., 2019) as it provides more explanation in statistical terms compared to qualitative methods.

Qualitative Method

The term 'qualitative research' refers to the type of research that produces findings not arrived at by statistical procedures or other means of quantification (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). Qualitative research methods help social science researchers study social and cultural phenomena by examining the natural environment in the context of the meanings people attach to them (Baskerville and Wood-Harper, 1996). The qualitative research method is defined as the type of research interested in analysing the social issues or events' subjective meaning by collecting non-standardised data in the context of participants' surroundings such as lived experiences, behaviours, emotions, feelings, organisational functioning, and cultural phenomena (Flick 2014; Silverman 2015; Rahman 2016). The qualitative method explores the “why” and “how” research questions, not just the “what”, “where”, “when” or “who” through detailed exploration of the situation with access to large amounts of “hard data” (Yin, 2014). Denzin and Lincoln (1994) claimed that the qualitative research approach is multi-method in focus (concerned with multiple perspectives), without being limited by pre-determined categories of analysis. The qualitative method is employed to achieve deeper insights into issues and provide information processing in a specific and in-depth manner (Bachman 1998; Chalhoub-Deville and Deville 2008). Yin, (2011) noted five features of qualitative research, and these features are: i) studying the meaning of people's lives, ii) covering the contextual conditions within which people live, iii) representing the views and perspectives of the people in a study, iv) striving to use multiple sources of evidence without limiting to a single source alone, v) develop insights into existing or emerging concepts that may help to explain a research phenomenon. A number of researchers have outlined the main advantages and disadvantages of quantitative and qualitative methods, and they are presented in table 3.2 below.

Table 3.1: Advantages and disadvantages of quantitative and qualitative methods

	Quantitative Research	Qualitative Research
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statistical analysis - Structured methods - Study sample reflects a larger population - Results can be generalised - One of the popular methods in IS research - Less time consuming and Economical - Based on the positivist paradigm of measuring variables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inductive data analysis - Produces detail description of participant's feelings, experiences and opinions - Enhance description and theory building - Employed to achieve deeper insights - Holistically understands the human experience in a specific setting - Based on interpretivism paradigm to understand different meanings of individual cases or events - Data collection is subjective and detailed - One of the popular method in IS research
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Misses subjective aspects of human existence - The positivism research paradigm leaves out the common meanings of social phenomenon - Provides the overall picture of the variables rather than considering the information deeply - Overlooks the respondents' experience and perspectives in highly controlled settings - Not helpful when generating theories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leaving out contextual sensitivities in some occasions - Focused on the participants' feelings, experience rather than other imperative issues in the context - Small sample size - Data analysis and interpretation comparatively more difficult - Subjective and non-scientific - Analysis of the cases taking a considerable amount of time - Lack of hard data or clear measuring

Source: Denzin & Lincon (1998); Blaikie (2007); Creswell (2009); Rahman (2016)

Mixed-Method

The mixed-methods approach is generally used when a study wants to adopt both the qualitative and quantitative methods when planning the research design (Saunders et al., 2009; Gunasekare 2015). A mixed-method approach allows the researcher to comprehend a research problem better using quantitative and qualitative research procedures simultaneously or one after the other (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Although both these methods are used in a mixed-method study, qualitative data are analysed qualitatively, and quantitative data are analysed quantitatively as separate constructs (Saunders et al., 2009; Gunasekare, 2015). Given the strength of using a mixed-method approach to better comprehend a research problem by adopting a mixed-method, some challenges are also essential to acknowledge. For example, this method reflects two contradicting ontological and epistemological philosophies, and this affects the researcher's views on how reality exists. The second practical challenge is the issues a researcher faces when moving from one approach to another while maintaining the approaches' unique characteristics (Lee 1991; Mingers 2001; Gunasekare 2015).

3.3.1 Justifications for Choosing the Qualitative Research

As Silverman (2015) suggests, qualitative research's essential strength is that it enables the researcher to comprehend the meanings people express on their feelings, experiences,

perceptions, and thoughts focusing on actual practices on-site/organisations. Myers et al., (2013) highlight that qualitative research is more suitable for the in-depth study than studying many entities more selectively to enhance the phenomenon under investigation deeper with the cases with few entities (i.e. people, organisations, and systems). The quantitative research method is inappropriate for this study as the study will include interviews with experts to investigate their AI-based CAs implementation experience.

For the present study, the investigation will require rich empirical data in order to provide a better understanding of the AI-based CAs` self-service use case benefits, to investigate implementation CSFs, success criteria, and the challenges that UK e-commerce retailers may face during the implementation process due to the relative newness of this technology in the selected research context. In addition, while CAs potentially expand cost and time-saving opportunities for UK retailers, at this early stage, CA implementation projects among the UK retailers frequently fail (Brandtzaeg and Folstad, 2018; Adam et al., 2020). Although AI-based CAs are regarded as in their infancy to the UK enterprises, the implementation practice is less likely to flourish, especially in the UK retail e-commerce setting without in-depth and rigorous research. The term 'interpretive' research is used with 'qualitative' research recurrently and interchangeably to investigate and analyse the findings in-depth, without restricting the researcher to gain new insights (Galliers,1992). Creswell (2007) also described qualitative research as 'interpretive, humanistic, and naturalistic', and thus it can be concluded that interpretative philosophy best matches when conducting a qualitative study.

Marshall and Rossman (1999) have presented several types of studies where the application of qualitative method approach is appropriate, namely: i) Research that examines in-depth complexities and processes, ii) The study under investigation is little-known innovative systems or phenomenon, iii) When a study seeks to explore where and why policy, iv) Research that cannot be carried out experimentally for practical or ethical reasons, v) Research on informal and unstructured linkages and processes in organisations, vi) The main variables and essential concepts of a study have yet to be identified. Based upon Marshall and Rossman (1999) qualitative research categories, the following points have been depicted to justify the need to adopt the qualitative methods for the present study: 1) AI-based CAs are an innovative FST self-service tool for most parts of the UK retail e-commerce organisations, 2) AI-based CAs implementation process involves informal and unstructured processes in organisations that are worthwhile to investigate in-depth, 3) This study investigates a limited phenomenon that is insufficiently explored.

Moreover, the qualitative method is one of the most popular methods adopted in IS implementation research (Conboy et al., 2012). It also can be a rich source to investigate phenomena related to Information Systems (IS) and empirically study these problems to discover solutions using inductive data collection methods (Conboy et al., 2012). Therefore, the qualitative methods approach can directly impact the researcher`s ability to understand the rising viewpoints of the participants and collect rich information regarding this dynamic and complex research phenomenon. Furthermore, after careful consideration of the epistemological standpoint discussed previously, to achieve the research aim and objectives of this research, the qualitative method was identified as the most appropriate approach for this research, and the considerations for this choice are presented below:

First, chapter one highlighted that the AI-based CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce setting is not well researched and insufficiently explored. As the nature of a qualitative study is multi-method, it enables the researcher to make an appropriate plan to gather rich and in-depth data by investigating the study questions and discovering solutions using inductive data collection methods. These methods include but are not limited to, i.e. interviews, observations, interventions, and archival material.

Second, this research study proposes to investigate AI-systems implementation in relation to organisational and technical perspectives. Current research focuses on organisational senior managers` and conversational AI technical experts` viewpoints and perspectives to generate an in-depth understanding to achieve the research objectives. Adopting qualitative methods allows the researcher to investigate the research phenomenon by interviewing and observing different organisational case studies that suit this research study's purpose.

Third, it is clear from the first chapter that AI-based CAs implementation in the UK retail e-commerce setting as a frontline service technology is a complex innovation. Thus, this study requires contextual data to provide in-depth and insightful interpretations as the objectives under investigation are complex and subjective. The qualitative approach offers contextual details for the present study and is considered the most appropriate approach for this study.

In summary, considering all factors, the researcher has provided justifications for choosing the qualitative method as the most suitable approach for this study, and the following section discusses the research strategy adopted and justified the rationale behind that selection.

3.4 Research Strategy

The present study has applied an exploratory form of the research strategy using case studies since it's the most suitable data collection method for the phenomenon under investigation (Myers, 2009; Yin, 2012; Yin, 2017). As per the view of Yin (2013), the case study method is significantly beneficial when conducting an in-depth investigation in its natural setting as it allows to expand the researcher's understanding by combining the literature with new empirical insights. As Yin emphasised, the case study strategy is mainly useful when studying issues with less researched, and AI-based CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce setting is an insufficiently explored research area. In addition, the case study strategy, followed by the interpretive paradigm, has been recognised as the popular research strategy when conducting IS empirical research (Myers, 2009).

According to Yin (2012) case study focuses on a specific contemporary phenomenon to be investigated in a real-life context, using multiple evidence sources. Simon (2009) describes that a case study exploration can be addressed in a single instance from multiple perspectives. In social sciences related studies, case study examples can be a company, a department in an organisation, a person, a project, a policy or regulation, an institution, an IT system (Yin, 2017). Case studies are more beneficial when the researcher seeks to explain contemporary circumstances which require an extensive level of knowledge of some social phenomenon (i.e. to investigate 'how' and 'why' some social phenomenon works) (Yin, 2017). Johannesson and Perjons (2014) have presented a number of the case study characteristics, namely; (i) focus on one instance, (ii) Natural setting, (iii) focus on depth, (iv) relationships and processes, (v) multiple sources and methods.

In the present study, the 'multiple cases' option was identified as the preferred case study choice in contrast with a 'single case' choice (Yin, 2013). According to Flick (1998), multiple cases involve a recursive sequence of evidence collection that reiterate at different times to prove the rationale behind the underlying concepts identified in theories, since in the qualitative research methodology, the process of research is not straight or linear. Further, Yin (2013) and Flick (1998) emphasised that multiple case studies are more feasible in the qualitative research methodology to gather recursive evidence at different times without restricting it to a one-off time.

Figure 3.1: Multiple case study procedure

Source: Yin (2017)

The multiple case study method was identified as the preferred choice, and the rationale for selecting this method is summarised below:

- i) The researcher seeks to gain an in-depth understanding of the AI-based CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce setting. Multiple cases represent replication of evidence that allows for the development of rich theoretical knowledge and new insights for this less-explored research context.
- ii) Multiple case study method using seven UK organisations can provide an extensive and in-depth description of these research objectives through a recursive sequence of evidence collection that reiterate different UK retail e-commerce organisational environments.

George and Bennett (2005) highlight advantages of using the case study method include 'the potential to achieve high conceptual validity, ability to closely examine the research area in the context of individual and multiple cases, and the capacity for addressing casual complexity'. Although the case study method has been identified as the most suitable strategy for this study, it is also vital to note that field research is not without its limitations due to how the case study reports are interpreted. Usually, limitations may occur with the conclusions' internal validity as researchers have no control over independent variables during the case study data collection process. Humphrey's (2001) view multiple case study strategy entails a recursive sequence of evidence gathering that is repeated at various times to prove the logic behind the underlying concepts described in theories. Hence, despite these limitations, the multiple case study method

enables the researcher to get rich in-depth insights and achieve high conceptual validity for the phenomenon under investigation (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014; Yin, 2017).

3.5 Research Plan

This study's research plan was determined by the research objectives underpinned by the interpretivist philosophical paradigm as articulated in section 3.1.1. This research was administered through a constructive plan consisting of three main phases. Phase one began by collecting background information on the context and rationale of the research topic and identifying the research aims and objectives. Then the study was followed by a critical literature review of AI, AI-powered text-based CAs and, the literature on, a) to investigate CAs benefits and implementation challenges, b) its implementation-related CSFs and success criteria. This resulted in the development of the proposed conceptual framework. In phase two, the detailed methodology was identified and discussed. The execution of the fieldwork will be conducted using UK e-commerce organisations that have implemented AI-based CAs as a self-service frontline technology (using semi-structured interviews, observation, documents) with the data analysis to finalise the results in this phase. Lastly, in phase three, the data analysis will be discussed with a revised research framework to present the final results, the conclusion, and then the future research will be presented.

3.6 Data Collection

3.6.1 Primary data collection

In the present research study, the primary data collection method was semi-structured interviews. Saunders et al., (2007) defined a semi-structured interview as an interview method that the interview is taking place with a set of question themes in hand, but the interviewer has the flexibility to adjust the order in which questions are asked and arrive at new questions based upon the context of the conversation flow during the interview (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014). As this method permits additional ad-hoc questions to add to the interview participant's responses, this method was considered more valuable for the type of rich data required for the research objectives under investigation (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014). Moreover, semi-structured interviews allow the researcher to be more flexible regarding the question themes at hand and enable the researcher to be more focused on the interviewees (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014). In the context of this study, adopting semi-structured interviews for primary

data collection allows to bring unknown issues to the fore and extract the expert knowledge of the interview participants during the interview process.

Under the present study, seven case studies were conducted with each consisting of two 'Managerial Level' and 'Technical Level' interviewees. These case study organisations were selected based upon convenient (non-random) sampling (Oates, 2005) from a database created by the researcher while attending London AI technology conferences, AI vendor trade exhibitions, LinkedIn connections, and conversational AI platform websites.

Classification of the case studies and Semi-structured interview participants

As mentioned in the above section, seven UK case studies were conducted for the present study, each with two interview participants. The criteria followed for the selection of these seven UK organisations are:

- 1) UK Organisations (with a specific focus on UK retailers) who have an online e-commerce presence and implemented a CA successfully as an FST customer self-service tool for their particular customer self-service tasks.
- 2) CAs implementation currently is at the post-implementation phase and already using the CA to engage with customers in their chosen platforms.
- 3) Researcher has access to these organisations and conducts semi-structured interviews with 'Managerial Level' and 'Technical Level' who actively took part during the implementation process.

In this study, convenient sampling was involved by interviewing the available and most convenient person (s) to act as case study interview participants. For example, for a Managerial Level participant, job roles included 'company directors, account managers, marketing managers, business development managers, chief technological strategists, company IT managers, etc.' who have directly contributed to their CAs implementation projects. Technical Level participant job roles included 'product managers, AI consultants, project managers, and CA developers etc.' who have acted as conversational AI experts during the implementation. Twenty-four potential interview participants (technical level and managerial level) in 13 organisations were initially approached, and a research invitation email was sent for these selected organisations. Based on the positive responses received from 19 participants of nine organisations, participant information sheets and consent forms (See the Appendix section) were sent to them via email to decide whether they wish to participate in the study. Fifteen

potential participants responded and confirmed their participation from seven organisations, and all the interviews were held during a time frame of 30 - 60 minutes. Their company details and the job roles are illustrated below.

Table 3.2: Interview participant codes

Case Study	Nature of the Business	Organisation Size	Interview Participants	Participant ID
Company A	E-Commerce Fashion Retailer	SME	Managerial - Lead Technological Strategist	LTS01
			Technical - Project Manager	PM01
Company B	E-commerce Retail Uniform Supplier	SME	Managerial - Senior Manager	SM02
			Managerial - Account Manager	AM02
			Technical - AI Consultant	AIC02
Company C	E-commerce Wholesale Retailer	SME	Managerial - Business Development Manager	BDM03
			Technical - Project Manager	PM03
Company D	E-commerce Meal Kit Retailer	SME	Managerial - Company Director	CD04
			Technical - AI Chatbot Developer	ACD04
Company E	Hardware Products Retailer (Online and Brick and mortar)	SME	Managerial - Head of Customer Care	HCC05
			Technical - Product Manager	PM05
Company F	E-commerce Wholesale Gift Supplier and Retailer	SME	Managerial - Chief Technology Officer	CTO06
			Technical - Chatbot Developer	CD06
Company G	Luxury E-commerce Travel Company	SME	Managerial - IT Manager	ITM07
			Technical - Project Team Leader	PTL07

Source: Developed by Author

3.7 Qualitative Data Analysis

Data Analysis Assumptions

These seven case studies' methodological assumption was that the selected technical and managerial participants would provide accurate data and responses in the interviews based on the experience they have gained during their CAs implementation. It was presumed that the answers were provided to the best of the participants' knowledge, and the data gathered accurately reflected their perceptions and views. It was also assumed that the analysis's empirical findings would be unbiased as the semi-structured open-ended approach was adopted during the interviews.

3.7.1 Data Coding

Data collected through semi-structured interviews were coded using pre-defined constructs under the research questions. The data analysis software NVivo 12 was used to help organise, analyse and derive insights from responses obtained. Data analysis was conducted based on the three main research questions, and these pre-defined constructs were:

First section: CAs implementation benefits

Second section: CAs implementation related critical success factors

Third section: Success criteria for CAs implementation

Fourth section: Challenges in CAs implementation

3.7.2 Using the NVivo Software

NVivo software is used for qualitative data analysis and was designed by Tim Richards in 1999 for the purpose of themes and sub-themes identification to achieve the desired objectives of qualitative investigations. NVivo is a valuable tool in analysing text as well as pictures, videos, and graphs. Advantages of using NVivo in qualitative research are, a) NVivo assists in organising and classifying un-structured and non-numerical data, b) content analysis, ethnography, grounded theory analysis techniques are supported in NVivo, c) availability of an extensive range of data sources that are supported in NVivo.

As previous studies show, there are no specific rules or conventions for analysing or interpreting qualitative data (Miles and Huberman, 1994). Making sense of massive quantities of data can be challenging and a highly intellectual task. Yet, analysing can be more feasible

by sorting the data into what is important and what isn't, looking for patterns, and communicating the information in a logical way (Patton, 2003). Hence in this study, the content analysis technique was conducted using NVivo software following the previous section's pre-defined constructs. The content analysis of interview data was presented in the form of answers given by the participants to the semi-structured interview questions asked by the researcher and then transcribed into pre-defined constructs (mentioned in section 3.7.1) that could be coded and categorised further breaking down into sub-themes that were emerged. During this process, the first step of the analysis was to read each interview transcript multiple times before the data was used for analysis purposes. It allowed the researcher to get a considerable level of understanding of the context of the data prior to the content analysis process.

For the purpose of content analysis, this study adopted the step by step guidance highlighted by Flick (1998), and these steps are: i) Group similar data sets and eliminate the less relevant, ii) define the terms presented in the data, iii) identify a formal structure of the data sets and code according to themes and sub-themes. The NVivo software was first used to identify the main themes and sub-themes that arose from the semi-structured interviews with the participants. Initially, using NVivo to analyse data allowed the researcher to manually inspect organised data and gain a thorough understanding of the rationale and context of the nodes and child nodes that appeared.

Figure 3.2: Tree nodes in NVivo

Source: Developed by Author

Figure 3.3: Coding strips imported from NVivo

Source: Developed by Author

Figure 3.4: Word frequency generated from NVivo

Source: Developed by Author

3.7.3 Reliability and Validity

The case study approach usually comes under internal validity, external validity, and construct validity (Yin, 2013). In the present study, internal validity was maintained by ensuring interview questions are clearly written and linked with the research aim and objectives, and by

choosing appropriate organisations (according to the pre-defined constructs mentioned in section 3.6.1) for case studies that enabled the researcher to find in-depth, context-specific data for the developed semi-structured interview questions. Through this approach, systematic collection and management of data were ensured. The external validity was achieved by explaining the data analysis results through applying it to similar CAs implementation customer service use cases in other industries. Construct validity was achieved by using more than one source of evidence for the study without focusing on one or two biased responses.

According to Weber (2004), research is reliable if researchers can demonstrate interpretive awareness. Interpretive researchers must demonstrate that they are aware of the subjectivity they bring to the research process and that they have taken steps to address the consequences of that subjectivity in their research. The term 'reliability' is used to describe the degree to which a measurement is stable and performs well. In qualitative research, reliability must be achieved through an in-depth understanding of the participants' different opinions when presenting the results of the findings. In the present study, the reliability was maintained and achieved by doing an in-depth investigation using seven UK retail e-commerce organisations, without restricting to one or two case studies. Triangulation of this study was conducted by collecting evidence from different individuals without limiting it to one particular group. As presented in table 3.3, this study has gathered data from both managerial and technical level study participants who have played various roles during their CAs implementation process. Moreover, research triangulation was achieved by comparing all the responses received from different levels of study participants of the seven case studies; using publically available information and documents about these case studies, and comparing and contrasting the findings with CAs implementation-related studies.

3.8 Research Ethics

High-quality research must be methodically opined by addressing ethical concerns, and all researchers, irrespective of the choice of methodology, should be abiding by ethical norms (Gratton and Jones, 2010). For the purpose of the present study, ethical approval was given by the University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee under clearance ID 7873 and the entire research has been followed the ethical guidelines mentioned in the UWS Handbook of Research Ethics published in 2018.

Furthermore, based upon the ethical considerations established by May (1997), the following points have been depicted to enhance the ethical considerations of the present study:

- 1) To follow the societal norms in the research and understands the researcher`s responsibility towards society.
- 2) To obtain the consent to be questioned during the interviews by the study participants.
- 3) To conduct all the interviews and ask semi-structured questions with sincerity.
- 4) To maintain professional decency at all times during the interviews.

Moreover, the researcher assured the confidentiality and anonymity of the data collected as follows. All of the responses gathered during the interview were stored in a password-protected location and were only used for data analysis purposes. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the process. Company identities did not mention by their names and were given a specific letter (i.e. Case A, Case B, and Case C etc.). Individuals who participated in this study did not mention using their name and only mentioned using the participant IDs created using their job titles (i.e. LTS01, SM02). All of the information gathered during the interview process (documents, digital files of the interviews, transcript interviews, and so on) were stored in a secure/password-protected location that only the researcher has access to.

Chapter Summary

This chapter presented details of the philosophical assumptions, research methodology, design for the data collection, and analysis adopted for this study. The chapter first discussed four major philosophical paradigms namely: Positivism, Realism, Interpretivism, and Pragmatism to create a background understanding, and then provided the rationale for choosing the interpretivist philosophy for the present study. The chapter next discussed the available methodological approaches for IS research namely: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods to create a background understanding, and then the rationale for choosing the qualitative method was discussed and justified. The chapter then discussed the semi-structured interview technique employed for the empirical data collection process using the case study approach. The data analysis process followed by the content analysis using the NVivo 12 software was then discussed and presented with example figures depicted from NVivo software during the data analysis. The next chapter provides the company backgrounds of all the seven case studies.

Chapter 4 : Case Study Backgrounds

4.1 Case Study 1: Company A

Company A is a UK-based value-focused online retailer that caters to the global female market aged 16 to 34 with affordable trend-led fashion needs such as clothing, shoes, accessories, and beauty products. The company has built one of the fastest supply chains in the UK e-commerce market, allowing them to offer a dynamic online shopping experience to its growing millennial female customer base. The online retailer has seen rapid growth in the UK and has expanded into Europe since its launch. By committing to enhancing their customer experience through technology on a regular basis, the company aspires to become a leading multi-channel e-commerce retailer where customers can seamlessly shop via the web, social media, and mobile app.

The company believes that providing excellent customer service is a necessity for an any-e-commerce retail store. They are also particularly focused on the audience that's already interested in their products, i.e. Facebook page and website visitors who engage with both the platforms looking to purchase products but need time and/or assistance to make the final decision to complete the transaction. To address both these needs, adopt conversational AI technology and implement a CA was identified by the management as the most suitable option. In addition, the company also wanted to prioritise having 'chat' in front as it has been identified as the preferred communication channel among their target millennial customer base. In recent years, the company's growth strategy has shifted away from entering new markets and instead of focusing on creating more personalised shopping experiences for their growing online millennial customer base. Company A believes that Artificial Intelligence is going to play an essential role in their digital strategy. Hence, their aim was to revitalise their value chains, creating a better-personalised service for customers and generate more value for the company through AI. Their goal of adopting a CA is to give their customers easy access to the information they need with a more personalised touch.

Primary users of this CA are the company's Facebook page and website visitors, and thus the CA has integrated into Facebook messenger and the company website. Primary data for this case study was collected by conducting two interviews with the company's Lead Technological Strategist (LTS01) and the Project Manager (PM01), who was leading the implementation

team. In order to get in-depth insights into the phenomenon under investigation, both top management (LTS01) and technical level expert (PM01) were involved as participants in the interview process.

Table 4.1: Company A summary of the conversational agent

Use Case	To Enhance Marketing and Customer Service Experience
Target Market	B2C
Target Users	Online Shoppers
Chatbot Type	Text-Based
Platform	Facebook Messenger and Website
Implementation Status	Successfully Completed

Developed by Author

4.2 Case Study 2: Company B

Company B is a leading e-commerce corporate uniforms supplier to a wide range of industries from transport, aviation, tourism, leisure, and hospitality, serving large and small businesses in the UK. The company was originally founded in 1895 in the East End of London and has a reputation in quality manufacturing within the Corporate Clothing Industry with over 100 years of experience in the market. Today the company has sites in the UK and overseas with offices in China and Indonesia along with a strong supply chain worldwide. As the official uniform supplying partner, company B has to provide uniforms to each of their customers` average number of 3500 - 4000 employees throughout the year for their uniform needs. With the recent expansion of their customer base, the company had been looking for ways to upgrade communication between the company and its customers and identified the adoption of a CA as an excellent solution for the customer service challenges they were facing. However, with the recent expansion, their biggest challenge was to respond to hundreds of daily order queries without a delay while dealing with other critical operational issues. Thus, company B`s primary goal behind implementing a CA was to overcome their customer service challenges, partially automate their customer engagement process and improve the overall organisational performance.

The company has first deployed the CA targeting one of their largest customers as a pilot project with the intention to expand it further gradually for their other corporate customers based upon the pilot projects` level of success. The primary users of this first phase of CA are 4000 employees working for the selected customer. The main focus of implementing a CA was to assist these employees in placing uniform orders, getting updates about their outstanding uniform orders, and arranging returns/exchanges. Company B has separate, dedicated internal e-commerce websites for all their customers, and thus the internal e-commerce website of the chosen customer had identified as the platform to integrate the CA.

This case study's primary data was collected by conducting interviews with a Senior Manager (SM02) who`s been working in the company since 2013, an independent AI Consultant (AIC02) who guided the company throughout the implementation process, and the chosen company`s Account Manager (AM02). Both the interviews were conducted face to face on separate occasions. Company B`s CA was launched in June last 2019, and at present, the system is in its post-implementation phase. All the interviewees were happy about the CA's performance and agreed that the implementation was a great success as a pilot project.

Table 4.2: Company B summary of the conversational agent

Use Case	To Enhance Customer Service Experience
Target Market	B2B
Target Users	Employees of their largest corporate customer
Chatbot Type	Text-Based
Platform	Internal E-commerce Website
Implementation Status	Successfully Completed

Developed by Author

4.3 Case Study 3: Company C

Company C, founded in the 1980s, is an online B2B wholesale retail clothing and workwear distributor located in the UK. The company has stocks of over 100+ different brands, including Adidas, Nike, American Apparel, and is one of Europe`s fastest-growing online B2B wholesale companies in the clothing retail distribution market today. The business, which trades in more than 50 countries worldwide, has continued increasing exports, especially into European Markets, increasing their B2B customer base and setting up new operations on the continent. The company's vision is to become the European market leader for the B2B retail wholesale consumer clothing and workwear distribution.

Company C`s primary purpose in implementing a CA was to introduce customer self-service and empower their customers to resolve selected inquiries on their own. Use case objectives were to automate the purchase order placing process and provide an instant answer for their customer`s backorder inquiries. Their CA's primary users are regular customers who have a registered business account with the company, and the company website had chosen as the platform to host the CA. Study participants explained that before introducing this CA, despite the fact that their customers could easily get product details such as offers, prices, available quantities, and product colours by logging into their business account, they still had to contact the customer service department to place purchase orders and to get backorder updates. The company was struggling to keep up with the daily busy ad hoc customer support centre operations, overloaded by inquiries that resulted in longer waiting times. Thus, the management was decided to leverage AI technology to reduce long customer wait times and ease customer support agents' daily work pressure.

This case study's primary data was collected by conducting two interviews with one of the company`s Business Development Managers (BDM03) and the Project Manager (PM03), who was leading the implementation team. To provide information from different perspectives, both top management (BDM03) and technical-level experts (PM03) were involved as participants in the interview process. The CA was launched in 2019, and at present, the system is in its post-implementation phase.

Table 4.3: Company C summary of the conversational agent

Use Case	To Enhance Customer Service Experience
Target Market	B2B
Target Users	Business Account Holders
Chatbot Type	Text-Based
Platform	Company Website
Implementation Status	Successfully Completed

Developed by Author

4.4 Case Study 4: Company D

Company D is an online subscription-based meal kit retailer based in London. The company provides weekly and monthly easy-to-cook recipe kit boxes that include choices over 100, (i.e. healthy, restaurant quality, and easy-to-create) meal recipes. Their business model entails preparing ingredients for customers' preferred recipes and delivering them to customers, who must then cook the meal using recipe cards. The company was founded in November 2018 and currently operates its business for the London household market. Their target market is London-based consumers who don't have time to shop for groceries and yet prefer a home-cooked meal over fast food home deliveries. The company's vision is to provide healthful and convenient meal kits to their target consumers and bridge the gap between home-cooked meals and takeout.

Meal kit box subscription services have grown in popularity, particularly among time-pressed and tech-savvy customers. They are attracted by the ease with which they can pay for their meal kits using online services and apps at the touch of a button. However, despite their increasing demand, the company has been experiencing massive growth in sales since March 2020 as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. The introduction of lockdown and social distancing regulations have opened the door to an unprecedented level of demand and has transformed company D's role drastically as a meal kit box delivery service in London. As a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, the company has been receiving a high volume of incoming messages. They needed to hire more customer service agents to monitor emails and incoming Facebook messages, and phone calls around the clock to keep up with the demand. Slow response time for these messages was a challenge for the company as it took their support team more time to get through all the necessary steps to resolve each customer issue received from these messages. Their customer support team was overworked and could never get ahead, and the customers themselves were frustrated with the long wait times.

Company D's primary purpose in implementing a CA was to partially automate some of their customer service tasks and encourage self-service for their customer support inquiries. They are currently using the CA to perform tasks such as 'manage subscriptions, place orders, provide order updates, and help customers track their order delivery'. The primary users of this CA are their subscribed meal-kit shoppers. The company website and Facebook messenger app had chosen as the platform to host the CA. This case study's primary data was collected by conducting two interviews with the Company Director (CD04) and the AI Chatbot Developer (ACD04), who was leading the implementation team. To provide information from different

perspectives, both top management (CD04) and technical-level experts (ACD04) were involved as participants in the interview process. The CA was launched in May 2020, and at present, the system is in its post-implementation phase.

Table 4.4: Company D summary of the conversational agent

Use Case	To Enhance Customer Service Experience
Target Market	B2C
Target Users	London Based Meal Kit Shoppers
Chatbot Type	Text-Based
Platform	Company Website
Implementation Status	Successfully Completed

Developed by Author

4.5 Case Study 5: Company E

Company E is a UK-based trade tools, accessories, and hardware products retailer founded in 1999, which targets DIY (Do it yourself) and trade professionals. It offers over 2000 products from power tools, cables, specialist goods for plumbers and many other various trade professional accessories at better prices. These products can be ordered over the phone or online for next-day deliveries and pick up from the store through click and collect service. In 2014, company E launched its mobile app and website, enabling customers with an easier shopping experience and introducing a 'click and collect' service, allowing the customers to pay securely online and collect their orders in-store within minutes. Since then, sales have increased by 250%, and with this success, the web and mobile app has been extended to a broader products range available online, and the contact centre extended their opening hours to deliver a 24/7 service.

As the company began to experience tremendous sales growth with e-commerce omnipresence, it soon became flooded by increasing customers. With the expansion of its e-commerce omnichannel presence, one of its biggest challenges was their live chat service's high maintenance and operational cost. The company soon realised that when most of their customers were unable to find shipment delivery updates or arrange their returns online, eventually the unsatisfied customer would contact them, and that drove up to their customer service maintenance cost as their live chat interaction was growing at a fast pace. In addition, longer waiting time led to various customer complaints and overall dissatisfaction with their customer service. To address this issue, the company has spent the last few years reshaping its technology to serve their customers better. In 2018, they took the first step to partially automate its customer service using a CA. Company management's willingness to adopt digital initiatives to serve a better customer experience has been highlighted as a critical factor for their continued growth in the market.

Company E's primary purpose of implementing a CA was to partially automate the customer engagement process with a focus of using it as an e-commerce FLE tool to assist customers to 'check inventory status, provide delivery status updates and to process returns and exchange requests'. This CA is an upgraded version of their live chat agent, as the company wanted a solution to provide customers with quick access to online self-service without leaving them in a waiting line to get in touch with a live agent.

Primary users of this CA are App users and website visitors, and thus the CA has integrated into their official company app and website. This case study's primary data was collected by conducting interviews with the company's head of customer care (HCC05), who started the position 14 months ago in the company, and the product manager (PM05) who acted as a bridge between the company and the project development team. Both the interviews were conducted via the zoom meeting app on two separate occasions. The CA was launched in February 2018, and at present, the system is in its post-implementation phase.

Table 4.5: Company E summary of the conversational agent

Use Case	To Enhance Customer Service Experience
Target Market	B2C
Target Users	DIY and Trade Professional
Chatbot Type	Text-Based
Platform	Company Website and Mobile App
Implementation Status	Successfully Completed

Developed by Author

4.6 Case Study 6: Company F

Company F is a UK based online retail wholesale gift supplier that design, develop and distribute quality gifts, accessories and decorative items to retailers across the UK and Europe. Since its launch in 2010, the company has grown rapidly over the past ten years, and today the company has recognised as one of the UK`s leading wholesale giftware suppliers and importers. Their vision is to become the go-to supplier of contemporary trend-led products and traditional bestsellers for their customers while making the task of purchasing an easy and enjoyable one. The company has an impressive customer base in the UK and across Europe, and as an e-commerce company, they have spent the last few years reshaping the technology to serve their customers better.

With the continuous market growth and product range expansion, the management realised that they would need a far more sophisticated solution to create an even better customer experience for their UK and Europe customer base. Especially with the recent Europe market expansion, the management recognised that communicating with Europe customers effectively with their native languages as a challenge to their live chat agents. In addition, they also recognised that their live chat team`s limited availability (Monday to Friday 7 am – 9 pm) was not enough to provide an unparalleled customer service experience for their customer inquiries. The management was aware that the speed at which their customers get access to information they seek helps them to speed up their decision-making process, and if not on many occasions, they may find an alternative solution. For these reasons, the idea of implementing a CA was brought to life to extend their 14 hours Monday to Friday live chat availability to 24 hours, 7 days. In addition to the 24/7/365 availability, they wanted to launch a CA incorporating English, French and German languages as chat options for customer service so that their customers could contact them at their convenience with their preferred language.

Company F`s purpose behind implementing this CA was to expand its customer service support beyond office hours and to communicate with its European customer base in their preferred language. The company focused on using this CA to perform self-service tasks such as – to create custom and volume-based discounts, check inventory, purchase products, and having easy access to policies and terms. Primary users of this CA are wholesale customers who visit their e-commerce website to place orders and seek live chat support to resolve their queries. Therefore, the CA has integrated into the company`s e-commerce website. This case study's primary data was collected by conducting separate phone interviews with the company`s Chief

Technology Officer (CTO06), who has been working in the company since 2017 and managed the implementation process with the vendor`s team, and the Chatbot Developer (CD06) from the project team. The CA was implemented in August 2018, and at present, the system is in its post-implementation phase.

Table 4.6: Company F summary of the conversational agent

Use Case	To Enhance Customer Service Experience
Target Market	B2B
Target Users	Wholesale Gift Buyers
Chatbot Type	Text-Based
Platform	Company Website
Implementation Status	Successfully Completed

Developed by Author

4.7 Case Study 7 - Company G

Company G is a member's only online British travel company selling discounted luxury hotels and holidays in the UK and abroad through its website and mobile app. Company G operates their hotel stays and trips for exclusive members-only rates in United States, Switzerland, Netherlands, France, Italy, Denmark, Germany, Norway, Spain, and Belgium from UK headquarters. Their vision is to provide an exciting, enjoyable, and stress-free holiday experience for their members through exclusive hand-picked best hotels and holiday offers. Every week the company runs short 'flash sales' lasting around two weeks, and as many as 200 sales deals are going on at any one time in their website and mobile app.

After launching their mobile app in 2017, the company soon realised that many of their members are using the mobile app to make it faster and easier to find deals and to pre-plan their holidays. Hence, the company management was increasingly looking for new channels to reach their existing members and potential new members in ways that appeal to their need for convenience, speed, and user-friendly digital experience. Company G believes that with their extensive market research, conversational AI-based travel planning, and personalised recommendations with self-service features are expected to play an essential role in the retail travel industry in the near future. Therefore, the company has decided to invest in conversational AI technology and implement a CA to provide an exceptional customer service experience.

Company G's primary purpose in implementing a CA was to assist their members to pre-plan their holiday and provide instant answers to most of their inquiries. They were focusing on using the CA to assist their members to provide personalised holiday recommendations, book the chosen holiday package, and make changes to their holiday package on their own.

Primary users of this CA are exclusive members who visit their mobile app to pre-plan their holiday, cancel or update their holiday package or seek support from a live chat agent for their inquiries. This case study's primary data was collected with the company's IT manager (ITM07), and with one of the Project Team Leaders (PTL07) from the implementation team. The CA has been implemented in April 2019, and at present, the system is in its post-implementation phase.

Table 4.7: Company G summary of the conversational agent

Use Case	To Enhance Customer Service Experience
Target Market	B2C
Target Users	Members
Chatbot Type	Text-Based
Platform	Mobile App
Implementation Status	Implementation Phase

Developed by Author

Chapter 5 : Analysis of Results

In the previous chapter, seven UK-based case studies of successfully implemented conversational agents have been examined. This chapter aims to present the findings and analyse the data collected through the semi-structured interviews of the seven case studies. The analysis of results is structured into three sections, and these three sections were developed in accordance with the objectives and research questions of the study. The first section of this chapter presents the analysis of results for the thesis's first research question: What are the UK retail e-commerce customer self-service conversational agents implementation benefits. The second section addresses the second research question: What are the CSFs and the success criteria that are significant for AI-based conversational agents' implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce sector. The third section seeks to find answers to the third research question: What are the challenges the UK retail e-commerce organisations are facing when implementing AI-based conversational agents. The purpose of this comparative analysis is to examine and present all case study participants' views and understanding with regard to the research questions of this study. The comparison of seven case studies has provided a generalised knowledge and clear understanding of the knowledge this study seeks to find through research questions.

5.1 Conversational Agents Implementation Benefits

The first research question listed in the introduction above seeks to elucidate the benefits these seven UK e-commerce retailers were achieved through successfully implementing conversational agents to fulfil their customer service use cases.

For company A, the primary objective of implementing their CA was to provide a personalized B2C customer service experience for their Facebook and Website visitors. The goal of choosing this use case was to engage with these potential target audiences and assist them with their general product-related inquiries. This conversation experience aims to mimic the way the shopper might chat with a human employee to get product details, advice, and recommendations. Lead Technological Strategist (LTS01) explained the purpose behind choosing this use case and adopting conversational AI technology for their daily business operations, and he quoted:

“Artificial intelligence is going to play an important role in our digital strategy. Our aim is to revitalise our value chains creating a better personalised service for our customers

and of course create more value for our company. [...] The goal of adopting a chatbot is to give our customers easy access to the information they need with a more personalised touch (Lead Technological Strategist, Company A).”

The above semi-structured interview extract had with Company A's LTS01 shows that integrating their digital strategy with artificial intelligence was the focal point of implementing a CA with a specific focus to be more agile and innovative. LTS01 was convinced that AI-enabled self-service CA could bring themselves closer to their digital native customer and provide more value through every touchpoint. Company A's managerial participant revealed that getting valuable deep insights about their customer needs and expectations is a key benefit of their CA implementation. As LTS01 noted, compared with the website CA, their millennial customer base has been showing more receptiveness to converse with their Facebook messenger's CA and most of these insights are coming from their Facebook customer base. In addition, it was also revealed `ability to provide personalised offers to their customers, faster information exchange rate, ability to capture new customers, as other benefits company A has achieved through their CA implementation.

Company B's CA implementation objectives were to overcome their customer service challenges, partially automate their customer engagement process, and improve overall organisational performance. Their main focus was first to implement a CA with only one of their customers as a pilot project and expand its operations gradually based upon its success. Their pilot project's CA's capabilities were designed to fulfil their largest corporate customers service tasks, i.e. place uniform orders, provide updates about their outstanding order status, and arrange return/exchanges. All the interviewees were happy about their CA's performance, and based on the benefits it has been already provided, they all agreed that the implementation was a great success as a pilot project. It was revealed that one of the main benefits of the implemented CA as their faster response rate. According to their managerial level participant SM02, as a result of their CA's 24/7 self-service, for the same queries that usually took 1-2 full working days to respond through an email, now takes only a few minutes. Consequently, their instant response rate to customer inquiries has gone up by 30%. This surge has mainly been caused due to the target users' ability to get their uniform updates even on weekends and after office hours at their convenience. After the CA launch, company B's has been receiving fewer emails regarding their uniform-related queries. It was revealed to have positively impacted their employees` daily performances.

Company C's objective to implement their B2B conversational agent was to introduce customer self-service and empower their customers to resolve selected inquiries on their own. Their conversational agent's capabilities are to automate the purchase order placing process and provide an instant answer for their customer's backorder inquiries. Company C's managerial level study participant, BDM03 explained that before the launch of their CA, although their customers could easily get product details before placing an order by logging into their business account, these customers still had to contact the customer service department (via emails, and over the phone) to place purchase orders and to get backorder updates. The company was struggling to keep up with the daily demand on their customer support centre – overloaded by inquiries that resulted in longer waiting times. Subsequently, they decided to leverage conversational AI technology to reduce long customer wait times and ease the work pressure from support agents. It was revealed that company C's primary benefit of implementing their CA as taking the pressure off from their employees' daily workload. It was also revealed that their employees do not have to repeatedly work over the same task as the CA handles most frequently received purchase order requests and backorder updates.

Similar to company C, company D's objective to implement a CA was also to encourage self-service for their customer support inquiries. Their CA's use case objectives were to provide self-service support for specific tasks, i.e. 'managing customer subscriptions, place orders, provide order updates, and help customers track their order deliveries'. The primary users of this CA are their subscribed meal-kit shoppers. The purpose of company D implementing a CA was noted from the below words:

“As a meal kit delivery service, we needed to respond quickly to COVID – 19 to ensure to deliver customer demand during this hour of need (Company Director, Company D).”

As the above quote demonstrates, slow response time for customer inquiries was a challenge for the company since the COVID-19 crisis started. It was revealed that it took their support team more time to get through all the necessary steps to resolve each customer issue received from these messages. The company had been receiving a high volume of incoming messages. Their customer support team was overworked and could never get ahead, and the customers themselves were frustrated with the long wait times. As a solution, company D's management started exploring how they could use a CA to release the pressure from the customer service team partially and reduce wait times, the idea of implementing a CA to handle their high volume messages was born. According to CD04, their CA implementation's primary benefits

were 24/7 availability and the ability to provide faster responses to their customers. For instance, CD04 revealed that their average response time to customer inquiries was eight hours before the demand surged after the lockdown, but now they have the ability to provide instant answers for the most popular customer queries such as delivery status and order updates. Respondents also revealed that having a 24-hour customer support service with a faster response rate as a huge advantage.

Company E's primary objectives of implementing a B2B customer service CA were to assist customers in checking product inventory status, provide delivery status updates, and process return and exchange requests. The introduction of a conversational agent is an upgraded version for their live chat agents as the company was facing high maintenance and operational cost of their live chat platform with the expansion of their e-commerce omnichannel presence. Company E's primary focus was to utilise both communication channels to provide an efficient customer engagement process. Since the company wanted to use conversational AI technology and its employees as collaborative partners, the company didn't focus on eliminating its live chat agent service. Instead, the focus was on the CA's presence to introduce it as the first option to communicate when a customer has frequently asked queries from their live chat agents, i.e. inventory status updates and questions about their order delivery or returns. And for other queries, they were encouraged to contact a live agent. With this approach, the CA collects specific information to understand the query and responds based upon the user's request.

According to the company's head of customer care HCC05 their CA's implementation benefits are: increased customer engagement rate and an improved overall customer service operations. For instance, HCC05 noted, during the first six months of launch in 2018, engagement with the CA on the mobile app and website was 25%. In 2020, their customer engagement with the bot stood at 55%. He further noted that their CA's engagement with their customers has reduced customer service operational cost by 20% and overall efficiency in helping customers with order delivery updates and returns.

Company F's B2B customer service CA implementation objectives were to expand their customer service support beyond office hours and to communicate with their European customer base in their preferred language. This conversational agent's self-service capabilities are - to 'create custom and volume-based discounts, help retail buyers check inventory status instantly, purchase products, and easy access to policies and terms'. The main benefits of implementing company F's conversational agent were highlighted as the 24/7 availability to

engage with their customers and capture a broader European customer base overcoming the language barrier. For instance, company F's managerial level participant CT06 revealed that the language barrier was a challenge for their customer service agents since the company also has a large European customer base. Their multilingual conversational agent's ability to converse with users in English, French and German languages has been an invaluable benefit they have been experiencing as a result of their CA implementation. It was also revealed a positive sales growth within the first six months of their CA's launch.

Company G's primary objectives to implement their B2C customer service CA were to actively engage with their exclusive members to help them pre-plan their holiday and provide instant answers to most of their inquiries. Capabilities of their CA are to 'assist their members in delivering personalised holiday recommendations, book the desired package, make changes to their holiday package on their own'. The main benefits of implementing company G's conversational agent were revealed as the ability to deliver personalised holiday recommendations, the ability to converse with international customers through their multilingual conversational agent, faster information engage, and enhanced customer loyalty.

Table 5.1: CAs Implementation objectives and benefits

Case Study	Use Case	Objectives and Capabilities of the CA Implementation	Benefits Achieved
Case Study A	B2C Customer self-service CA	Objective: To engage with their target customers and assist them with general product-related inquiries. Capabilities: to provide product details, offer special offers and recommendations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Getting valuable deep insights about the target customer • The additional revenue stream from personalised recommendations and offers • Ability to capture a broader customer base towards their brand
Case Study B	B2B Customer self-service CA	Objective: To integrate Artificial Intelligence into their digital strategy. Capabilities: Automated order placement process, process return and exchange requests, order status updates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The service counter-response rate has gone up by 30% • 24/7 self-service availability • Significant improvement in employees daily performances
Case Study C	B2B Customer self-service CA	Objective: To partially automate the customer engagement process. Capabilities: To place purchase orders, provide backorder updates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking the pressure off from customer service employees • Reduced waiting time and faster responses • Fewer customer complaints
Case Study D	B2C Customer self-service CA	Objective: To encourage self-service for customer inquiries. Capabilities: To manage subscriptions, place orders, provide order status updates, track order delivery.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24-hour automated customer support service • Better team productivity • Customer service cost reduction
Case Study E	B2B Customer self-service CA	Objective: To introduce a CA to work with the live-chat agents as a collaborative partner. Capabilities: to check inventory status, provide delivery status updates, to process returns and exchange requests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 55% rise in customer engagement with the CA within the first year of the launch • 20% customer service operational cost within the first year of the launch • 24/7 customer service
Case Study F	B2B Customer self-service CA	Objective: To overcome the language barrier they have with their European customers and provide 24/7 availability. Capabilities: To offer custom and volume-based discounts, provide quotations, check inventory, place orders, access company policies and terms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to converse with their French and German language through their multilingual conversational agent • Ability to capture a broader European customer base overcoming the language barrier • Sales growth
Case Study G	B2C Customer self-service CA	Objective: To enhance the customer engagement process during their customers` holiday booking journey. Capabilities: to provide personalised holiday package recommendations, book holiday packages, multilingual conversational ability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to deliver personalised holiday recommendations • Ability to converse with international customers through their multilingual conversational agent • Faster information engage / Enhanced customer loyalty

Developed by Author

5.2 Critical Success Factors

The last section discussed the rationale for choosing use case objectives for implementing AI-based CAs and the benefits these companies obtained from adopting conversational AI technology by the participated organisations. This section reflects the case study participants' views on the critical success factors contributing to their CAs implementation success. These factors are broadly classified into three categories based on their relevance, as follows: Organisational factors, technological factors, and governance-related factors.

5.2.1 Organisational factors

i) Top Management Support

During the interview data analysis, two sub-themes emerged under the 'Top Management Support' category, which will be discussed in this section. These themes were: willingness to adopt AI as an innovation, adequate knowledge about AI-based CAs, and management support after the launch.

Willingness to adopt AI as an innovation

Some participants specified that their implementation would not be successful if it weren't for their top managements' openness and willingness to adopt new technology such as conversational AI for their business operations. For instance, company B's management level study participant SM02 quoted:

“Our company director is always open to adopt new technologies depends on its usefulness, and he's usually very keen to bring innovative ideas to his company's business operations. His enthusiasm was a crucial factor for other managers in the company to believe in AI technology (Senior Manager, Company B).”

A similar view was shared by company G's managerial level participant ITM07. She emphasised that their top management was willing to adopt conversational AI technology mainly because they were convinced about an AI-based CA's (chatbot) capabilities benefits it can bring to their organisation. He quoted:

“[...] yes yes, we were convinced that the key advantage of adopting an AI-based chatbot is in its ability to sort through the vast amounts of data accurately within a very short period of time. It also has the ability to give our members (chatbot users) a clear picture of

what is going on in real-time while getting self-service customer support (IT Manager, Company G).”

Company E and F's managerial level participants also agreed that they were open to using the conversational AI technology as they were searching for a technology that could engage with their customers 24/7 due to the limited availability of their live chat agents.

All the above participant comments revealed that the majority of the top managers were convinced about the potential benefits of implementing their CA as an innovative addition to their customer service operations. Data analysis also revealed that although the 'innovation adoption' was discussed as a separate CSF in the conceptual framework derived from the literature, according to participant responses, innovation adoption can be considered as a sub-theme under the top management support.

Adequate knowledge about AI-based conversational agents

Analysis of the study participants' feedback revealed that top managements' adequate knowledge they have about AI technology and how AI-based CAs work as a critical factor that would determine the success or failure of a CA implementation. The majority of the technical level participants emphasised the importance of top management having a clear idea of the customer service use case and its objectives before embarking on an AI-based CA implementation initiative. Responses received from participants such as PM03, SM02, ACD04, and ACD06 indicate that before embarking on a CA journey, companies must understand which AI features perform what types of tasks in a CA, and the strengths and limitations that have involved with each feature. In addition, data analysis revealed that prior to making the CA adoption decision for their customer service tasks, companies must understand the difference between rule-based and AI-based CAs with their capabilities and also what it takes to maintain and improve the performance of a successfully implemented CA after it goes to the public. For instance, company C's technical level participant PM03 highlighted that at first, some of company C's senior management team didn't have a clear vision or fundamental knowledge about AI-based CAs. As he stated, although the top management was excited, they didn't have a clue what they were doing or what to expect apart from the abstract idea they had about CAs. PM03 further noted that before companies begin the implementation process, it is required to spend more time and effort to do their research about CAs and the ROI for their company since conversational AI technology is new in a lot of ways and not an easy thing to grasp mentally.

In addition to technical participants, a similar view was shared by a managerial level participant in regards to not having adequate knowledge about CAs and noted that their lack of knowledge about AI features and its technological capabilities as a barrier during the decision-making process when choosing the objectives for their use case. For instance, company B's managerial participant SM02 noted:

"[...] you know, we wanted to do things right with our pilot chatbot project using AI features. But to begin with, we didn't know what features to look! Not even our IT team didn't have a clear idea about how effectively machine learning can be used in our chatbot. To be honest we just followed the hype! So we had to completely rely on our AI consultant and vendor to decide the key features of the use case. Seeking experts' advice and guidance is obviously the most sensible thing to do, but it would have been better if we knew what we were getting into in advance (Senior Manager, Company B)."

This statement demonstrates that company B's senior managers' lack of knowledge about their AI-based CA was a key issue for the company during the decision-making stage. This example also shows that by following the AI hype, company B has not considered not only factors such as how to fully unlock the benefits of AI for their customer service use case, but also how their decision to adopt an AI-based CA will need to enhance their employees' skills and capability to create an empowered AI savvy workforce. Therefore, these findings suggest that an organisation's readiness to invest money in conversational AI technology is simply not adequate to ensure the success of its CA implementation. Instead, top managers of organisations must have a clear vision and a fundamental understanding of the technology without blindly following the AI hype. Therefore, based upon the empirical data, it can also be argued that organisations must also conduct a holistic organisation-wide analysis to mitigate the impact this technology could create for their employees and customers without blindly follow the AI hype.

Continuous support after the launch

Top management support after the CA launch was another sub-theme identified through the data analysis, and particularly, technical-level participants highlighted the importance of this sub-theme. The majority of the technical level respondents revealed AI-based CAs require continuous improvements after the launch if organisations are looking to ensure the overall project success and achieve their desired ROI. Company A, B, C, and E's technical level respondents were happy about the top management support and commitment they were

receiving after the launch. These participants emphasised that their top management's 100% support and commitment during the implementation and after the launch directly impacted to deliver results they promised to deliver during the initial discussions.

On the contrary, it was found that in some case studies, a few top managers gave their full attention to the project during the implementation stage and yet not considered the improvement and enhancement of their CA's daily performance as an important area to ensure the success of their CA after the launch. For instance, company D's technical level participant ACD04 noted:

“There was a lot of enthusiasm in the beginning. But after the chatbot went live to the users, their interest declined. For a chatbot with AI, improvements after the launch is a critical area that organisations must consider since machine learning works better with live data and experience the platform gets through daily user interactions (Chatbot developer, company D).”

A similar view was also shared by company F's technical level participant ACD06 and highlighted the issue of their top management not looking for continuous improvement or spend money to maintain a high level of performance of their CA. He quoted:

“[...] well they approved the project, worked with us to get the job done! But now, they don't do any follow-ups or upgrades with us as they are so busy.[...] This is the problem because they don't understand how important it is to monitor and improve the performance of their chatbot (Chatbot developer, company F).”

As both these statements provide evidence, AI-based CAs implementation projects do not just complete after the launch in contrast to the experiences organisations have with most of their previous IS projects implementations. These respondent extracts also demonstrate that in practice, implementation of an AI-based CA is a continuous process since, after completion of the implementation phase, the launch phase (post-implementation phase) starts. Therefore, it is required to provide equal attention during both these phases to ensure a CA project implementation success. These findings indicate that the most challenging part of an AI-based CA project begins after the launch as the live interaction data can show how accurately their CA can provide answers to user queries. As ACD06 explains in the above statement, top management can't just abandon their CA after the launch since the project success can be only measured based upon how satisfied their customers are with their self-service chat experience. Yet, if organisations fail to monitor and improve their CAs after the launch, within a few months, CA wouldn't be able to engage with its users as expected. Therefore, data analysis

suggests that getting the top management's active involvement and commitment is a critical factor not only during the implementation phase but also after the launch to avoid project failures.

ii) Vendor Selection

To undertake the project, company A had outsourced a specialist conversational AI project team to design, develop and implement their CA in-house. Company A's managerial level participant LTS01 explained their company's reasons for choosing to build an in-house CA and noted:

“Resource and funds assessments were discussed during the initiation stage. Our options were either to choose a cloud-based platform or build it in-house. We decided to build an on-premises one because we already had many resources and infrastructure needed with our previously implemented systems.[...] although the initial cost was high to build it with a specialised team, this was the suited and most secure option for us when it comes to our customer base size, our company's sensitive data protection and also to maintain the full control over the vendor (Lead Technological Strategist, Company A).”

The above statement indicates that building CAs in-house requires more complex back-end programming and it is vital to seek well-experienced CA developers to accomplish this task. LTS01's responses noted when building their in-house CA, their project required highly professional conversational AI and programming skills. During the interview, an insightful analogy was used by LTS01 to describe an AI-based conversational agent. As he stated, 'AI-based CAs are like children and learn based on the examples it is exposed to'. Therefore, he revealed that building the knowledge base from scratch was challenging and complicated for them as it needed a large database to provide a learning environment for machine learning and build up the system capability to provide appropriate responses to user requests.

For company B, the vendor was recommended by their AI consultant, who has worked with him in his previous CA projects. After thoroughly assessing the most suitable CA type for their business need, such as - assessing the technology infrastructure and funds needed for a cloud-based deployment or building it on-premises, they decided to opt-in for a pre-built, customisable cloud-based CA for scalability and affordability reasons.

Similarly, companies C, D, E, F, and G made a decision to go with pre-built, and customisable AI-powered CA solutions with UK's leading SaaS platforms, mainly because, to build AI-

based CAs in-house involves a longer deployment time, huge initial investment with complex back end programming. Company E's managerial participant HCC05 elaborated the decision of choosing a pre-built customisable CA, and he quoted:

“When choosing a vendor for a customisable chatbot platform, we had to thoroughly assess to understand the pricing structure, resources needed, the scope of work and how the requirements will be met during the implementation process, the terms and conditions, expiry and renewal dates etc. These assessments helped us to ensure that we are driving the maximum value from the chatbot platform (Head of Customer Care, Company E).”

This quote clearly shows that the preferred CA deployment type to embark on company E's first conversational AI project is a prebuilt, customisable CA platform from a reputed vendor. However, semi-structured interviews also indicated these organisations choosing a pre-built cloud-based or build a CA from scratch in-house had depended on factors such as company size, customer base, advance back end systems, specialised conversational AI experts in house, and security reasons.

During the interview data analysis, three themes emerged under the `Vendor Selection` category, and these themes were: Conversational AI specialisation with similar use cases, previous experience with implementing AI-based CAs successfully, and delivering ongoing success and future development.

Conversational AI specialisation with similar use cases

When choosing company A's project team to build their CA in-house, two conversational AI specialised companies were given a chance to demonstrate their domain experience, capabilities, and price packages. After careful consideration, they had outsourced a project team from a London-based leading start-up company to build the CA considering factors based upon their previous in-house build conversational AI project implementation experience in the UK retail e-commerce setting and project team's specialised capabilities.

To choose a vendor with conversational AI specialisation with similar use cases, company C and D had asked for references from their shortlisted vendors who had done similar projects with companies in the same industry and spoken to those companies specifically to ask about their experience working with the vendor.

When company E started looking to choose a suitable vendor, they have seen a lot of hype in the market, and they have seen vendors who were promising Artificial Intelligence in their

systems that were ready to go out of the box with false promises. Their managerial level participant HCC05 noted,

“[...] When we had the opportunity to test one of the vendor`s CA platforms, we found out that even with small changes in wording their system would be stumbled. So we had to keep searching for a suitable vendor (Head of Customer Care, Company E).”

It can be said that this statement confirms the popularity of the off-the-shelf easy to deploy CA platforms in the market and the importance to identify these vendors through a thorough assessment. The above statement also provides evidence that these types of ready-to-go CAs are not suitable for a UK e-commerce retailer who wishes to implement a CA to engage with their customers as a self-service tool.

However, while most of the managerial participants strongly emphasised their focus on working with a well-established SaaS vendor platform to embark on their first conversational AI project, a different view was shared by company F`s managerial level participant, CT06. As he explained, his company decided to work with a small start-up conversational AI company because of the discounted price package they offered and after being convinced with their capability to deliver an innovative conversational AI experience for their target customers. For instance, CT06 quoted:

“Our vendor demonstrated us how to customise our customer service chatbot to deliver personalised content based on different access points. [...] how to encourage customers to have interactive conversations through our website user account loggings and within public areas such as our Facebook page. Many other chatbot capabilities were discussed during their first presentation too. That one hour presentation was extremely useful for us to comprehend how to approach our customer. We knew they are a new start-up but they blew us away. They were confident and knew exactly what they are doing (Chief Technology Officer, Company F).”

This statement adds more parameters to the above argument. It suggests that UK e-commerce retailers could partner with conversational AI start-ups instead of only focusing on well-established vendors when looking for a conversational AI partner. However, although these young vendors might bring more value and benefits for CA implementations, due to the popularity of poor off-the-shelf CA vendors in the market, it is advisable to gather substantial evidence on required vendor credentials.

Previous implementation experience

More evidence was adduced to consider when choosing a vendor, and another sub-theme identified from the data analysis was the vendor`s previous experience with implementing AI-based CAs successfully. For instance, company A`s managerial participant LTS01 highlighted that they were looking for a vendor with a proven record of successful AI systems and particularly CAs implementation who could bring real value from AI technology to their business. Company B, who initially followed the hype with a little knowledge about conversational AI also had a similar view. Their managerial level participant SM02 noted that they wanted to feel comfortable saying to the vendor that they are new to this technology and have no idea how it works.

Moreover, company F`s managerial participant CT06 revealed how their vendor guided them to use their existing content repository in use with their live agents and integrate it into the knowledge base rather than spending time and more money transferring all the data to a separate knowledge base. This shows that vendors this level of understanding of customer needs and knowing exactly what to do with a company`s existing resources come from their previous experience by successfully working with many customers with similar situations.

iii) Funds and Resource Allocation

The majority of these case study organisations had gone through a critical assessment to evaluate the most suitable CA option for their company, i.e. either to choose a cloud-based SaaS platform to customise their CA or to build it from scratch. When defining the funds and resource requirements many organisations had taken into consideration of factors such as `customer base size, use case objectives, level of customisation, budget, available resources in-house and security concerns`. During the semi-structured interviews, many comments indicate project delivery time frame as a prevailing issue that some of the case study organisations had to go through to complete their project within the allocated funds and resources. According to company A`s technical level respondent PM01, it took eight months to complete their in-house built CA project from the planning phase to the launch date. However, they had to spend two extra months for the project completion than the initially planned six months` time frame due to some difficulties they were experiencing during the testing phase.

According to the respondents, company E, F, and G`s implementation process had taken 8, 10, and 13 weeks to complete their SaaS customised CA implementation process. For instance, to launch company E`s CA, their vendor had taken eight weeks, and company F and G`s project

team had taken 10 and 13 weeks respectively to complete the project as initially planned. Company D had taken only four weeks to complete its implementation process due to the urgency and had decided to improve its performance after the launch. This highlights the shortest time frame taken to a SaaS-based CA launch in contrast to all the other companies. Company D's managerial level respondent revealed that they had to act fast due to the urgency and to release a live CA for their customers as a result of the covid-19 pandemic's business spike in-home deliveries.

However, company B, C, and E's project completion had been disrupted from the initial plan as the project team had to overcome a few obstacles. For instance, according to the respondents, part of the knowledge base that wasn't ready on time was company B's reason for this delay. Prior to integrating their CA into the company's ERP system, they had to ensure that all the data records such as employee's names with correct spellings, workplace addresses, employee job numbers are all accurate and machine-readable. To cross-check and clean data of their 4000 employees (Employees of the company who choose to run their pilot with the CA) had taken extra 8 weeks than initially planned.

Company C's reason for the project completion delay was revealed as the unsettled project scope. According to their managerial level respondent BDM03, they have had too many changes along the way, especially with the initial objectives. In addition, company E had faced delays during content creation and testing phases. However, this testing delay was not encouraged by their vendor. For instance, company E's technical level participant PM05 noted that their client (company E) decided to keep improving their CA performance without releasing it live as they were not satisfied with the testing results and the CA's response accuracy.

These findings show that only four organisations have completed the implementation projects according to the planned implementation timeframe, allocated funds, and resources. Respondents noted that their well-planned funds and resource assessment and allocation at the beginning of the project, not changing the project scope, choosing a well-reputed vendor for the CA, and having an effective project team as main reasons their organisations managed to complete the project as planned within the budget.

iv) Implementation Strategy

Data collected from the interviews point to a number of sub-themes under the 'Implementation strategy' that organisations must focus on regardless of the deployment type.

Many respondents highlighted that their 'implementation strategy' started to show positive results after the launch. These sub-themes were: use case objective analysis, target audience, the scope of the automation, and the platform to launch the CA.

Use Case and Objective Analysis

'Use case and objectives analysis' was a sub-theme discussed by many participants as an important area to discuss under implementation strategy discussions. Most of the respondents' feedback summarised several critical areas to discuss in relation to use case analysis. These areas are: 'which areas should organisations prioritise to introduce a self-service CA, objectives of the use case for introducing a self-service CA suitable for their customer demographics, and choosing this use case what organisational problem they can solve'. Analysis of data shows ill-defined objectives of a CA project have the risk of leading the organisation to a scattering choice of functionalities. Some respondents provided evidence to highlight that unless organisational leaders don't have a holistic view of CAs' value and how to utilise its capabilities to achieve the company's overall strategic goals, its implementation failure will be much greater. For instance, company B's technical level participant (SM02) emphasised the organisation's ability to articulate the feasibility of the chosen use case's goals and how the conversational AI technology adoption aligns with the overall business strategy plays a vital role to get ROI from its deployment.

Furthermore, this argument was supported by company A's technical level participant PM01. He revealed that during implementation strategy discussions, organisational leaders' ability to express the business goals clearly and coherently to the project team and the support received to galvanise resources for the project as vital components contributed to their project success. Company E and F's technical level participants also sustained the point. Technical respondent of the company F, PM06 said that,

"[...] we know the technical side of a conversational agent. But only managers know about their business model, their customers, and business problems they have inside and out. So we must get to know about the client's objectives of the use case clearly and their customers' expectations in a deeper level to deliver results (Project Manager, Company F)."

This comment demonstrates that using case and objective analysis during the strategy discussions is not something the project team could do independently. Combining PM06's statement with the above responses highlights that the focus of a CA adoption must not centre only on Artificial Intelligence technology but also be driven by the organisation's overall

business strategy and business value. To sum it up, data analysis showed the importance of organisations' ability to articulate the use case and its objectives to the project team, and having a holistic view of the expected benefits before the implementation process helps to define a cohesive implementation plan.

Scope of the Automation

Based on the feedback received from many respondents, there is strong evidence that during these early days of text-based enterprise-level CAs, setting up the CA's scope as a critical area to consider their strategy discussions. This means critically evaluating factors such as: 'defining what customer service tasks e-commerce retailers can automate and what sorts of customer service tasks organisations must not focus on to automate, what are the main tasks companies can implement their CA to accomplish', etc. For instance, company E's technical level participant revealed that they first wanted to focus on the most popular customer problems to serve from their customer service CA and then expand its scope. Similarly, company B's technical level participant AIC02 explained that during the strategy discussions, the project team and the top management had to discuss the scope of their first version of the CA and how they are going to introduce it to the customers. After discussions, they have concluded to first deploy the CA to only one of their customers as a pilot run, limit the CA's capabilities only to few selected tasks (i.e. to place orders, get order status updates, and process return and exchange), and train the bot to do those tasks exceptionally well. Setting up the project scope was explained by the AIC02 as quoted:

“[...] obviously it's a very difficult task to program the chatbot to answer every possible question under the sun initially at once [laughter]. So our goal was to understand user expectations clearly and define what our chatbot can help with and what it can't, then focus on doing those expected tasks really well (AI Consultant, Company B).”

The above statement provides a clear example for organisations who are embarking on their first conversational AI project to consider starting with a narrow scope to focus on automating those tasks to ensure the intended outcomes. To get the best results, this might also mean starting with a pilot project to test and refine the CA first before expanding it out further. Some participants also revealed that during the planning stage, the project team had discussed the estimation of the volume of customer service queries that can be automated. They have looked into factors such as monthly customer support volume, the percentage of the repetitive queries from the monthly customer support volume, and any expected spikes in the volume during

different seasons, etc. Data analysis illustrates that all seven case studies have used their customer service CAs to perform only up to 2 to 5 specific job tasks ranging among 'providing personalise recommendations, placing orders, order updates, manage customer accounts, process return, and exchange, track order deliveries and to check inventory status'.

Some Technical level respondents revealed the negative effects of not having a clear project scope. For instance, PM05 noted that getting new requests and top management changes in the middle of the implementation hindered their project delivery up to some level. He emphasised the importance of communicating a clearly defined and agreed project scope with the organisation during the planning stage to avoid disputes, disappointments, and additional costs.

Target Audience

Defining the target user or considering the most suitable audience who will be the CA's primary users is another sub-theme identified from the data analysis under the implementation strategy. During the strategy discussions, some respondents revealed the need to identify their ideal CA user who would use a customer self-service option to engage with the organisation, observe these users' specific needs and expectations before determining the level of customisation required for the CA. Company C's technical level respondent PM03 mentioned the importance of focusing on customer demographics when deciding the CA's target user. For instance, someone on social media (i.e. Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter) is more likely to ask a different question compared to a user who has already downloaded the company app or frequent website visitors since they are more knowledgeable about the service or products that brand offers. Moreover, findings revealed that using the most suitable language to communicate with the primary user by considering their communication method could also be significant for a seamless chat interaction. For example, a CA that uses 'slang' or using three-letter acronyms might not be the right tone for a more conservative audience. Therefore, PM03 pointed out the importance of understanding the demographics of the users of the chosen platform and program the CA interactions accordingly.

More feedback was received from other participants regarding the target audience. Company B's technical level participant AIC02 explained user-centricity as one of the crucial factors for their customer service use case during the implementation strategy planning. As he described:

“First step was to consider our user's expectations, their demographics and pain points they normally face when they reach out to us with their queries. Customer-centricity is a crucial factor to consider as this is a customer service chatbot (AI Consultant, Company B).”

This statement demonstrates the construct of targeting the right user to solve their problems by focusing on their specific needs instead of targeting a wide demographic to avoid CA failures and user disappointments. Subsequently, having a defined target audience with unique insights such as their 'interests, behaviour, geography, and technology used' offers organisations an in-depth understanding of the requirements when creating the CA's content base.

Platform to launch the CA

Many respondents believe identifying the right platform to launch the CA must be vital in implementation strategy discussions. According to Company C's technical level respondent PM03, launching the CA in the wrong habitat is one of the main reasons for current CA project failures. More evidence was received to echo this fact from company E's technical level respondent PM05. He stressed that their client initially only wanted to launch their CA to the company website but was not focusing on their company App. However, PM05 noted that the company would miss half of their target users by only focusing on launching their CA on the company website since more than 50% of their customer account holders were using the company app.

This argument was confirmed by company A and F's managerial participants LTS01, CTO06 and noted:

“Our audience is most reachable on Facebook and website [...] The first phase was launching the chatbot to our Facebook page and incorporate it for our online sales and customer service engagements. The second phase was launching it to the website target audience, and the third phase Instagram (Lead Technological Strategist, Company A).”

“[...] we had to define the audience and then explore our engagement channels to access that audience. I mean, if it's social media only, mobile or web-only or to focus on all three platforms. But most of our users access the service via the web and a small percentage use the Facebook and mobile app (Chief Technology Officer, Company F).”

Both the above statements add more validity to the argument of launching the CA in the wrong habitat is one of the main reasons for current CA project failures. Therefore, it emphasised that choosing the right platform to launch the CA where companies meet their target audience is critical to the project's success.

To sum up, company A's study participants revealed that during the planning and strategy discussions, the top management and their project team had considered 'use case and overall

objectives of the project, choosing the most suitable hosting channel for the CA, personality of the CA, organisation's data readiness, ways to manage the change, how to conduct employee training and education, and user experience factors of their CA' as general key areas of their implementation strategy. Responses also asserted the utmost importance of addressing all the mentioned key areas during strategy discussions as they were building their CA in-house. Top management and other company's relevant shareholders were involved in the planning and strategy setting.

Similarly, pre-built customisable AI-based SaaS CAs chosen by companies B, C, and E had also adopted a strategy to avoid pitfalls during the deployment. Respondents remarked that there had been a combination of factors such as understanding the target audience needs, user-centricity, and scope of the automation in their strategy discussions to have led their CAs to meet the desired expectations. Key decision-makers such as company directors and senior managers, project manager, team members, and key employees from relevant departments were included during the planning stage to gather their views and business knowledge. In contrast to the above companies, understanding the importance of having an 'implementation strategy' was lacking in some of the case studies. For instance, company D's respondents remarked that they hadn't spent much time planning or focusing on a strategy due to the urgency of the deployment. Their main focus was on content creation for their knowledge base during planning meetings while leaving the rest to the vendor. Company G's respondents also revealed that they didn't have a specific strategy and just followed the instructions provided by their vendor. However, company D's managerial level respondent CD04 agreed that if they had spent more time planning for an implementation strategy and understanding their CA's usability without just rushing towards completing the project, they would have avoided many issues they are currently facing with their chatbot.

v) Project Management

Considering the complexity of AI-based CAs implementation, many participants identified project management with high importance. Sub-themes emerged based on the participants' responses for project management, and those sub-themes were 'Project team and planning and project handover'.

Many responses received revealed that having a dedicated project manager who managed the project team and resource requirements for project delivery was a vital part that contributed to their project success. However, it was found during the analysis that although all the case

studies had dedicated project managers and team members, their engagement and responsibilities differed based upon various factors. These factors were highlighted as going for a SaaS pre-built CA and customise it or build it in-house from scratch, the use case, project scope, delivery time, AI features, and the budget.

Project Team and Planning

As company A had built an in-house CA with an outsourced project team, their management level interview participant LTS01 revealed that it was imperative to have a fully dedicated, domain expert project team to successfully deliver such a sophisticated project. Their project team was fully committed only to this project without distractions from any other projects, and the availability and the flexibility of the project team have contributed to building an effective partnership between the organisation and the project team. Company A's project team consisted of members, including the project manager, developers, copywriters, conversational flow designers, and selected company A's employees. The project manager was responsible for communication, setting up the strategy, team members, and top management, delivering resources with management support, managing meetings, employee training, CA testing, keeping project logs, and documentation. The project manager emphasised that strategic planning, skilled team members, resource allocation, and clear communication are critical areas to consider when building a CA in-house.

Company B's technical level respondent AIC02 pointed out that the size of a customisable CA project team can be varied depending on the factors such as context, the scope of action, and the use case objectives in which the CA project takes place. AIC02 illustrated Their project team combination, and there was a dedicated team from the vendor's side as well as the organisation side in the project team. In company B's project team, a senior manager and two administrators were fully dedicated to data preparation and to support the team with all the other information needs representing the organisation. From the vendor's team, there was a project manager, two developers, and a copywriter. Company E's technical level participant PM05 also emphasised that team coordination is crucial even for a customisable SaaS CAs implementation project. For instance, each member's defining roles within the project and creating new positions if required, are highlighted as essential areas to consider. Another factor highlighted under the respondents' project team was having well-experienced employees from relevant departments in the project team to work together with the vendor. Incorporating well-experienced employees in-depth knowledge about the company and customer expectations for

the implementation identified as a vital factor to consider during the planning, strategy setting, and database creation stages.

The project planning process elaborated by company B`s AIC02 and quoted:

“[...] Planning was undertaken focusing on each stage of the implementation during the first two weeks, and we had clear project implementation schedules. We also had a strategy in hand to avoid bumps along the way with a road map for each step of the project getting involved with relevant stakeholders at each stage as it happened (AI Consultant, Company B).”

The above statement provides evidence for the constructs of having a `clear implementation strategy, setting up a realistic timeline for each milestone, planning and project road mapping, clear communication strategy` as vital components to consider during a project planning process. To add to the above statement, the majority of the project managers who responded during the interviews also noted that procedural controls such as; setting key roles and responsibilities within the project team, coaching team members, brainstorming sessions, well planning and clear strategy setting, setting effective joint communication plans, status reviews, tracking their project milestones at each step were integral parts of their project planning and management process.

All the organisations have used face-to-face meetings, skype meetings, regular phone calls, and emails to communicate with the project team members (between the vendor`s team and the company) to discuss urgent matters as well as planned schedules. Face-to-face meetings were highlighted as the most used communication method during the implementation phase, while telephone calls, group meetings via skype, and regular emails were highlighted as the most used communication method after the launch.

Successful Project Handover

More feedback received regarding project management from the data analysis and 'vendors` project handover ability after the launch' was identified as a critical contributor for a CA implementation success. Company E`s technical level respondent/project manager PM05 revealed that they started planning for the project handover process at the very beginning. For instance, he revealed that as the project manager, he began to document everything clearly from the beginning and started preparing selected company employees for their responsibilities from the planning stage.

On the contrary, company D's managerial level respondent CD04 had a negative experience with their project handover. He expressed his frustration and stated:

“To be honest, at first, we were overwhelmed by the amount of information they just presented us after the project completion. It was like we had so many documents with technical terms to follow but we didn't know what exactly to do or what questions to ask from them. We weren't prepared for it (Company Director, Company D).”

The above statement indicates the importance of looking at the vendor and the project team's competence of the project handover method when choosing a vendor. However, as the data analysis suggests, successful project handover is not only a vendor's responsibility, and organisations must also play a key role to ensure their roles and responsibilities after the launch. A few technical-level participants noted that they encourage their clients to have several employees to read project documents and ask questions where they don't understand something.

vi) Change Management

Participant responses suggest organisations must take extra effort to get employees and customers on board for the adoption of their conversational agent by proving the benefits they get by using AI-based CAs. The analysis of interview responses emerges that 'internal and external change management and effective communication' as two main areas the majority of the companies have focused on when managing change that came with their CAs implementation.

Internal and External Change Management

Data analysis indicates that participants had viewed portraying a positive image on the idea of adopting AI technology and the importance of highlighting the advantages of using a CA among staff members as a key internal change management approach to get employees on board with the project. Some managerial level participants (SM02, HCC05) reported that initially, there was a certain degree of resistance within the organisation for partially automating their customer service tasks.

To address internal change management needs, the majority of the companies had taken steps to create a positive momentum among their employees by involving them with various project tasks such as seeking their expert knowledge during strategy discussions, by appointing key employees as implementation project team members, and also by involving selected employees

for content and knowledge base creation. Some of these tasks were split based upon these employees` job flexibility, while others were given fixed task assignments with more established routines. Company E`s managerial participant PM05 revealed that to get employees on board, they took time during the pre-implementation phase to conduct an internal survey to understand employees` receptiveness towards adopting advanced technology like AI and willingness to work with a CA.

Most of the companies had conducted training initiatives such as group presentations, one-on-one training sessions, workbooks distribution, and informative email campaigns to provide their employees with the fundamental knowledge they needed to work with their CA. Company D`s respondent revealed that they engaged available employees from different departments to check CA`s responses if they are slow, inaccurate, or offensive. Getting some employees to engage with the CA for testing internally before the launch had helped them identify issues. This team had also gained experience serving as experts to assist other employees down the line. In addition, company B had conducted user training and customer service employees training to handle specific queries when the CA handovers to them were undertaken. Their vendor had also provided training to two IT executives to monitor chats, error messages, the wait time between messages, and the overall analytic dashboard.

Some respondents discussed the job redesign and created new job roles in their organisation as part of their change management strategy to utilise their internal resources adequately. For instance, company A`s managerial level respondent LTS01 stated they had to hire three full-time conversational AI experts to maintain and improve the CA performance upon project completion. He also stressed their job redesign approaches for some job roles, and he quoted:

“This chatbot is not only going to change the way we interact with our customers but also it is going to create more roles and opportunities within the company. So we had to think about ways to redesign some of our customer service and marketing agent`s job responsibilities to make them effectively collaborate with the chatbot in both the departments (Lead Technological Strategist, Company A).”

However, although job redesign was a focal point for some of these organisations, a few of the participants noted that they didn`t pay much attention to that during the planning stage. As a result, there had been disagreement over who should take over and changes to work procedures. This example demonstrates the lack of a succession plan and clear job redesign handover could interrupt the success of the project after launch. In addition, primary data suggest, internal

change management may accomplish successfully through communicating the company vision and the implementation of a precise action plan, combining listening to employees, assigning tasks for project activities, teaching, training, and by bridging the skill gap through recruiting new employees if required.

Based on the data analysis, there is adequate enough evidence to argue that although implementing a CA can be a lucrative addition to the UK e-commerce retailers, only by managing both internal and external change proactively with a constructive change management strategy CAs could benefits and ROI for their investments. To manage the change externally successfully, some companies had sent emails to their regular customers who have a registered business account by introducing the CA enclosing key information such as its purpose, steps by steps, and instructions on how to use it.

Effective Communication

The majority of the responses received indicated a strong link between effective communication between the relevant stakeholders and implementing their CAs successfully. Some managerial level participants (SM02, HCC05) reported that initially, there was a certain degree of resistance within the organisation for partially automating their customer service tasks. As they stressed, this employee resistance mainly stemmed from the lack of understanding and general misconceptions of the technology. Employee resistance for partially automating customer service tasks appears to be primarily linked to some employees` lack of confidence to work with sophisticated technology such as AI and concern over job security.

Findings from interview data also show that an AI messaging platform is not just “*if you deploy it, they (users and employees) will just adapt*” (PM05)”. Instead, it requires a more strategic and holistic effort across the organisation.

Figure 5.1: NVivo relationship map of the organisational CSFs

Source: Developed by Author

The map extracted from the NVivo 12 software shown in the above figure demonstrates the relationship between the themes and sub-themes identified under the organisational CSFs influencing the CAs implementation success in the UK e-commerce customer service context. As discussed in the above section, six organisational-level CSFs were identified from the semi-structured data analysis, and these six CSFs were further sub-divided into 13 sub-themes.

5.2.2 Technological Factors

vii) Natural Language Processing

Company B's technical level respondent AIC02 revealed that conversational issues mostly begin when a CA is only built with pre-defined answers. For example, he highlighted that when a user's requests don't match with the pre-defined answers, the CA usually replies to the user with the message "sorry, I did not understand". Therefore, he emphasised the importance of infusing NLP with a CA to avoid such user disappointments. Another technical level participant noted that they continuously focused on improving their CAs capability to understand intents and extracting entities with a variation as this NLP capability provided their CA to manage complex and multi-intent conversations. Some participants revealed that NLP was a critical technical factor for them when customising their CA as they particularly focused on their chat interface to have dialogues instead of menus and buttons selections.

Company A's technical level respondent PM01 emphasised that to build proprietary NLP/NLU components in domain-specific CAs like their in-house built project, it was essential to go beyond standard features available in common APIs such as Dialog flow or IBM Watson. He highlighted the importance of adding more NLP expert knowledge and similar resources when building the knowledge base. Company B's technical level participant AIC02 also noted even with customisable CAs, the importance of having a self-learning conversational AI capability in their CA with advanced AI features with API connectors that can integrate with their CRM system. Company C and G's technical level respondents echoed that statement and noted NLP was a must to provide an enhanced conversational and personalised user experience.

viii) Machine Learning

Company B's technical level respondent AIC02 elaborated the CA's functionality during the interview, and he noted that an AI-based CA's job is to receive the user query, interpret it, analyse and contextualise the user input to determine the most appropriate answer and then provide an answer as the output value. Similarly, the project team leader (PLT07) of company F echoed AIC02's statement and added that there must be a few key components in an AI-based CA to process the input and understand user sentiments and emotions during a conversation. These features are namely: natural language processing (NLP), natural language understanding (NLU), and machine learning (ML), Predictive analytics, sentiment analysis.

PTL07 noted the importance of incorporating machine learning into the CA when choosing a customisable platform or implementing an in-house build CA. He also highlighted to avoid one-size-fits rule-based CAs if organisations are serious about introducing an intelligent CA as an FST.

Some technical level participants highlighted another critical factor of not losing control of the CA by not allowing it to come up with 100% independent answers on its own when interacting with its users. For instance, company E's PM05 noted:

"[...] Our chatbot platform has the hybrid model approach. We believe the hybrid model approach is the most suitable chatbot type for customer self-service because it has key advantages and the chatbot behavior can be aligned with business expectations (Project Manager, Company E)."

The above quote demonstrates that a hybrid approach consisting of rule-based and machine learning applications can offer organisations more transparency for their output while

delivering more consistent, complex, and personalised conversational solutions as a frontline service technology.

Another technical level participant noted that their CA gets smarter day by day as it continuously learns from the previous chat history, by gathering user information and connecting all the data points from other organisational databases to provide intelligent answers for user requests. He further explained that their CA's self-learning capability stems from the Machine Learning component infused in the system. A study participant who was coming from a strong CA's development background revealed during his interview that one of the main goals of a CA is to maintain the conversation seamlessly as possible with a human user. As he noted to achieve that goal Machine Learning plays a huge role.

The majority of the managerial level case study participants did not have much knowledge of the technical aspect of their CAs and thus didn't receive much feedback regarding the technical factors of their CA during the interviews. Similarly, the majority of the managerial level participants also revealed that their IT department also did not have adequate knowledge about NLP and ML functionalities and highlighted it as a critical issue they had to face during the implementation process.

ix) Human Handover

In this early phase of CAs deployment, there are always many situations when a CA simply cannot complete an inquiry. While CAs can efficiently and effectively address some tasks, participant responses show the importance of having the human handover option in a CA to avoid frustrating situations during a conversation. For instance, company C's technical level participant PM03 quoted:

"[...] If our bot can't answer a specific query, it lets know the customer that a customer service agent will get in touch with them through the phone or email (based on their preferred communication mode), instantly or within the next 3 hours depends on the customer service agents' availability (Project Manager, Company C)."

The importance of having a customer service agent in the loop was also discussed by company D's CA developer PTL07. As he noted, the CA must have the ability to create a ticket to notify an employee in real-time that a customer has a query the CA can't answer and needs their immediate attention. He also emphasised the importance of a CA's ability to connect those queries to an employee in the correct department, with the conversation's information up until

that point so that the employee can get the conversation history and the customer doesn't have to repeat themselves.

Providing more evidence, company G's technical level respondent PTL07 noted that identifying what to automate and which inquiries to hand off to human support is vital to consider during the implementation. These examples illustrate when using a CA as a frontline technology to maximize the self-service customer experience, it is essential to build trust among its users by providing easy access to a human employee if the user requires more information.

x) CA Analytics

Data analysis revealed that the role of 'Conversational agent's analytics' as an integral part of ensuring the project's success due to its vital role in measuring performance with its user interactions. During the interviews, it was highlighted that monitoring the conversation history of live user interactions after the launch is crucial to measure the KPI of the established self-service parameters of the use case objectives. Some respondents noted that setting up quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) allows these organisations to evaluate their CAs performance effectiveness. Some of these KPIs mentioned during the interviews were: CAs activity volume (to evaluate the number of daily weekly interactions), the bounce rate of the CA (meaning the number of conversations sessions the CA failed to accomplish during their intended customer self-service tasks), human handover rate, retention rate (to evaluate the number of users have repeated conversations sessions within a specified time), CAs response volume, CAs conversation length, goal completion rate, interaction and non-responsive rate and user complain rates. The majority of the technical level respondents' feedback indicates that their CA implementation's real success depended on the CA's performance after the launch.

Figure 5.2: NVivo map of the technical CSFs

Source: Developed by Author

5.2.3 Governance Related Factors

xi) Data Privacy

Study participants' comments indicate that essentially a CA has the potential to collect a large variety of customer data and for this reason, CA platforms and companies that use CAs have a responsibility to ensure data protection measures are designed and implemented according to the government rules and regulations. Analysis of the semi-structured interview responses indicates that all the organisations of this study had taken GDPR measures seriously to ensure their CAs governance and avoid legal complications that may arise after the launch. For instance, company A's project manager PM01 noted the involvement of their legal and security teams from the project planning stage to craft a conversational privacy policy and security infrastructure that protect their users' data while making data available for improving the system. To address the privacy and data security needs of company B, E, F, G CAs users, in their privacy policy, they have stated critical information such as 'what information is being collected, why is it being collected, for how long it will be used, who will it be shared with and how can they withdraw from the agreement, etc'.

xii) System Security

Some participants revealed that their conversational interface was heavily involved with security processes compared with their other IT project implementation as they are working with real-time customer data. There was a general consensus among many participants about the importance of regular mandatory updates of their chat interface to avoid data and security breaches. However, some participants were not very happy about the hidden cost involved with these updates, as they were not well informed by their implementation partner about these requirements. Company D's managerial participant CD04 shared his data security concerns and according to him, he was a bit concerned about the data security of their users as he thinks subscription-based chat platforms could make him feel unsafe and sees this as an issue.

xiii) Transparency

Company C's technical level participant PM03 reported an interesting finding in regards to the transparency of the e-commerce CAs. As he pointed out, it is important to let their CA users know that they are communicating with a machine, not with an actual human, and provide them the option to choose their preferred communication method. PM03 also noted the consent approval requirements to begin a conversation with their CA users and quoted:

“[...] A user has to agree to terms of service to ensure that they are aware of the personal data collected from our chatbot and the purposes that data is being used for. You know according to GDPR, users have the data ownership and have the right to request the erasure of the personal data related to them (Project Manager, Company C).”

The above statement demonstrates that organisations are responsible for informing the user about their data privacy concerns and ensuring that all personal data will be processed consensually and lawfully in a transparent manner. In addition, by requesting opt-in permission from their CA users to use their data instead of the opt-out system, it had been up until recently helps the user decide what information they are happy to provide and what not to provide. PM03 further elaborated why the users have data ownership and have the right to request the erasure of their personal data (according to article 17 of the GDPR). For instance, some CAs could identify and remember users` personal details such as names, home addresses, email addresses, phone numbers, IP addresses that a user does not wishes to share for any other purposes. Therefore, before a chat session begins, it is important to encourage customers to read and understand the privacy and data policy and provide customers with the option to pull their most important personal data after a user has actively conversed with a CA.

Most of the respondent comments were related to the governance-related challenges they were experiencing when implementing their CAs. Therefore, a further analysis related to the comments received has been provided in the `governance challenges` section.

5.3 CAs implementation success criteria

The last section discussed the CSFs identified from the data analysis that has contributed to implementing these case study organisations` CAs successfully. This section investigates the study participants` views on the CAs implementation`s success criteria identified from DeLone & McLean, (2003) success model. These success criteria are information quality, system quality, and service quality.

5.3.1 Information Quality

Data collected in the interviews point to two sub-themes that directly contribute to enhancing the 'Information quality' of a CA that organisations must focus on regardless of the deployment type. These sub-themes were: Knowledge Base Creation and Sentiment Analysis.

Knowledge Base Creation

Data analysis shows that although the noticeable element of conversational AI is the technology itself, 'content' that generates the outputs for user requests also plays a major role in a CA to enhance the quality of the information it provides as responses. The primary data suggest that a CA's knowledge base must have a wealth of knowledge to provide comprehensive, context-specific answers in information form to user queries. Notably, during the data analysis, respondents' extracts evoked the phrase "Garbage in, garbage out" used by many AI practitioners. This means an AI-based CA is only as good as the data it's trained upon. During the analysis, many views and ideas were presented by technical-level respondents about the information quality of their CAs. For instance, company G's technical level participant quoted:

"AI-powered chatbots are like children. They learn by example. A chatbot learns based on the examples it is exposed to. So it was really important to incorporate customer service and marketing teams' knowledge and experience in addition to the available databases to create content for this chatbot (Chatbot developer, Company G)."

In light of the above statement, this respondent example demonstrates the CAs knowledge base creation's significance in creating a maximum effect on conversational flow to satisfy the users' purpose. The above comment also suggests that depending on the conversation's task and complexity, the CA needs to be trained with company-specific dynamic data sets to provide appropriate responses to the users. The majority of the technical level respondents' feedback received also contributed to back this argument. As they noted, when introducing a CA as a self-service frontline tool, it is imperative to gather data from the company's customer service data sources to design the conversation flow specific to the industry and use case objectives when building in-house or customising a CA.

The majority of this study's technical level participants revealed the content creation approach they had taken to integrate into the knowledge base. The summary of the responses received as follows. For the content creation and conversation design for their customer self-service CA, most of the project teams' starting point was to gather data from their customer service agents, emails, phone records, and ERP, CRM databases. Such extracted data included the types of questions customers previously have asked, the effort and time needed for customer service agents to resolve those queries, and then 'tags' were created from the information gathered from those data sets (to identify the possible user queries). The next approach was to create content to generate responses (CA outputs for those specific queries). During this content creation

process, project teams' main focus was on their CAs to generate responses with a structure reminiscent of what customer support agents might answer in real-time to those identified customer queries and then create labels using the tags attached to extracted dynamic datasets to train the CA. Moreover, data analysis highlights that most of the organisation's task-specific content that the customer service CAs require is already being created extensively through telephone conversation records conducted by customer service teams, live agent chats, email conversations, or social media direct messages. Re-purposing this existing content in a format that is understood by a CA is a crucial task the project team must conduct by collaborating with key employees in relevant departments. Some participant responses received indicate that project teams should ensure that they gather relevant, accurate datasets and then clean them thoroughly before using it for training purposes as data quality plays a critical role in delivering information quality. However, these participants noted that content creation was a highly intellectual and challenging task.

More feedback was received regarding the importance of database creation to ensure information quality. For instance, company A's PM01 quoted:

"[...] Database creation is a huge part of the puzzle and essential to provide a painless user experience. If the database is created poorly, users could potentially be ended up with an extremely bad experience (Project Manager, Company A)."

The above comment seems to provide evidence that the success of AI-based CAs as a self-service tool relies heavily on having the right content and presenting that information to the user at the right time clearly and concisely. The above comment also suggests that a painless user experience stems from the intelligence in the CA system to generate context-specific answers and information. Company E's and F's technical level respondents (PM05, ACD06) provided more evidence for the above argument. They noted that their CAs knowledge base provides a platform for the system to provide intelligent responses to user requests. To maintain the CA's intelligence as an essential substance of self-service, ACD06 also noted that they keep updating the knowledge base with new and pre-existing data using daily analytics (i.e. for new intents recognition and journey mapping). Moreover, participant ACD04's responses indicate that when organisations choose SaaS customisable CAs from vendors, they should ensure that these CA platforms consist of knowledge bases that could understand user languages based on their demographics, especially representing their enterprise sector (ACD04).

Sentiment Analysis

As the name suggests, sentiment analysis refers to the CA's ability to identify the users' sentiment (view or opinion that is held) during a conversation (Bachate and Sharma, 2020). According to the data analysis, some technical level respondents such as AIC02, ACD06, PM05 noted that a CA's goal is to create a conversational interface that is as human-like as possible that doesn't sound or behave like a robot. As these respondents noted, when delivering responses and information for a user query, at least up to some extent, the CA needs to understand user intents' language, context, and the tone of the message. To achieve this objective, it was revealed that sentiment analysis is the tool that can be used as it automatically extracts both the context of the user intent as well as the feeling from the same message.

5.3.2 Service quality

This section discusses the sub-themes identified during the data analysis that comes under 'service quality'. The majority of the study participants discussed the '*personality of their CAs*' as an essential service quality-related success criteria they considered during their CAs implementation. The findings are as follows:

Defining the CA's personality during the implementation was one of the most discussed themes captured from interview data in relation to service quality. Data analysis indicates that the project team and organisational leaders' competence to think about the CA's personality they want to expose to the target user when introducing it as a self-service tool is considered as a crucial factor by some study participants. In supporting this, company A's technical level participant PM01 expressed that deciding the personality of their CA was a significant part of that would reflect their CA's system quality, and he quoted:

“A chatbot is not only a technical thing in customer service. But what the user is seeing or experiencing is the personality of a chatbot. Many companies don't consider this. But if you want it to partially replace a human employee, you better think of ways to make it like one as much as possible. The way a chatbot is doing a dialogue, its tone of the text message, the language, and the way it's effectively interacting with the user shape the personality of a chatbot [...] So this is a very important aspect for the service quality [...] (Project Manager, Company A).”

Moreover, company A's management level participant LTS01 also shared a similar view about the importance of syncing the CA's character with the organization's corporate identity. He quoted:

"[...] The personality of the chatbot should really in sync with the corporate identity of the company. When a customer is messaging to our chatbot, they are messaging with our company, and the way they receive the chatbot is the way they see the company. It's like a website. If you have a website for your company that is known as the window of a company into the world Right? A chatbot is exactly the same, and that's why we wanted to think carefully when designing the correct character of the chatbot (Lead Technological Strategist, Company A)."

As it seems, defining the personality type of company A's CA that matches their target audience while focusing on the brand tone they wanted to associate with the CA was one of the focal points during their implementation process. Both the above comments provide further evidence and add more to the argument of defining the CA's personality while focusing the brand tone on the e-commerce retailer when focusing on improving the service quality of the CA. These findings suggest a CA would have to be perceived as an appealing and valuable offering to its users for the brand to associate with its target audience.

Furthermore, HCC05 and CTO06 show that CA's meta aspects as a conversational interface defining the company's branding guidelines could create a positive CA user interaction and service quality. Company E's managerial level participant HCC05 revealed that they wanted to focus on branding without using the simple, standard CA offered by the vendor. They have communicated to the project team about the branding guidelines they wanted to incorporate into the CA, such as picking the right name, logo, and colour scheme following their branding guidelines when customising their CA. HCC05 also revealed that focusing on the branding aspect effectively helps its users to recognise, remember their CA as a high-quality self-service tool, and come back to use its services. Company F's respondent, CTO06 also discussed another interesting point to consider when defining the CA's personality. The character they wanted to reflect through the CA (i.e., whether it should be formal or informal, excited or calm, fun or boring to match their customer base) with their UX experts and designers.

Also, another technical level respondent, PM01 stressed that they were having a particular focus on designing conversations more friendly and approachable while adding empathy to imply a more human-like interaction with users. He quoted:

“Users can imply a lot about the personality of a chatbot simply through the words and sentences a chatbot presents during a conversation. Primary users of this chatbot are millennial women who want to empower them through their fashion choices. So our conversation designer considered the most appealing language that can resonate with the user to train the chatbot (Project Manager, Company A).”

The above respondent extracts and analysis of these data demonstrate that introducing an AI-based CA with a well-defined personality considering nuance aspects such as words and dialogues can foster a friendly tone to the text messages reflect target users` persona can enhance the service quality.

5.3.3 System Quality

This section discusses the sub-themes identified during the data analysis that comes under 'system quality'. The majority of the study participants discussed the '*usability testing*' of their CAs as an essential system quality-related success criteria they considered during their CAs implementation.

Company A and B`s interview participants expressed the importance of discovering the viewpoints and requirements before the launch from their end-users to help the project team to explore the CA`s features and its usability with depth. Company A`s project team had tested their CA using a sample population of their target audience to discover their view on the CA's overall usability, and then the feedback received was incorporated to make the necessary improvements before the launch. According to company A`s PM01, user testing was identified as a crucial factor in their CA implementation success. Company A had used testers to get feedback on the usability of the CA, describing their experience. As PM01 noted:

“Our audience is most reachable from Facebook and website. Defining the audience and then seek people who meet those criteria from both the platforms for user testing was a crucial part of this implementation success (Company A, Project Manager).”

The above statement provides more evidence of the user testing's importance as it has helped company A to obtain valuable insights to enhance their CAs service quality. As PM01 revealed, some of these insights were about how receptive the target users for the company A`s CA, how the conversational floor works, how long a customer prefer to carry out a conversation, how emotionally they get connected with the CA, percentage and success rate of specific task completion without a human handover.

Similarly, company B had also conducted usability testing of their CA, involving a selected group of target users. The feedback received was taken to modify the model before the launch. Company C's PM03 described the value of usability testing during their implementation, and he quoted,

“Getting feedback from the live testing initiative gave us the visibility into how the rest of the chatbot users might react and the overall system quality (Company C, Project Manager).”

Company C had tested their CA prior to launch with users from a select external group, using a pre-determined usability testing protocol to test and evaluate task completion ease, detect system errors, and assess participant views on the CA. These usability issues identified by subsequent participants were considered unique if previous participants had not been identified as having the same issues. All the unique issues and opinions then were taken to improve the CAs system quality before the final launch.

PTL07 shared another insightful view, and he noted that at this early stage of CA developments, not having a clear definition to decide what constitutes a good behaviour of a CA and what is a good dialogue that would reflect the system quality as an issue they were experiencing. They had started exploratory testing soon after their CA launch manually to see how it behaves with different user inputs while closely monitoring the daily conversations CA produces to understand how the CA system reacts to user requests.

Figure 5.3: NVivo relationship map of the CAs implementation success criteria

Source: Developed by Author

5.4 CAs Implementation Challenges

When implementing a CA as a customer self-service tool, similar to the success factors contributing to the implementation success, such complex projects call on an organisation to follow steps to avoid pitfalls that could jeopardize the whole initiative. Similarly, failure to address unexpected problems and roadblocks during an AI-based CAs implementation could very well lead to undesirable consequences. In this section, a list of challenges is presented that could appear during different implementation phases collected from interview respondents. The challenges that emerged from the interviews are analysed under three main categories. These categories are organisational challenges, technological challenges, and governance-related challenges.

5.4.1 Organisational Challenges

i) Vendor management challenges

According to empirical evidence, many of the case study organisations have not gone through any sort of AI project implementation previously and have initiated the project from zero knowledge while highly depending on the vendor. Therefore, after analysing the semi-structured interviews, it was revealed that these organisations had faced several challenges when dealing with their conversational AI vendor. From top management level participants` perspective, these vendor management related challenges were – top management`s lack of knowledge to choose the most suitable vendor and the SaaS CA platform; having to fully rely on their chosen vendor when making critical decisions regarding their CA; accommodating an effective relationship with the vendor; lack of transparency in some cases; conflict of ownership and not having a standard pricing model. These challenges identified from the data analysis are elaborated as follows:

According to many managerial respondents, their lack of understanding about conversational AI technology and conversational agents when choosing the most suitable CA platform for their organisation revealed as one of the highly quoted challenges they were facing during the implementation phase. To overcome this challenge, company A and B`s managerial participants LTS01, SM02, AM02 noted that they had to seek professional support by getting consultant guidance when choosing a reliable well-experienced vendor. Other companies had gone through a thorough assessment (as explained in the CSFs analysis section) when choosing the most suitable Cloud CA platform partner.

It was also revealed that accommodating an effective relationship with a vendor they had not previously worked with was identified as a challenge by some managerial level respondents. For instance, company F's managerial participants revealed that although they took a gamble and chosen an impressive London-based conversational AI startup as their vendor, there seemed to have had some unprofessional behaviours among the vendor's team members compared with other IT partners company F had previously worked. Another vendor relationship-related issue was discussed by company C's managerial participant BDM03. He noted that their vendors' lack of transparency and lack of communication effort to reveal the hidden costs involved with various tasks upfront was highlighted as an issue they experienced during and after the implementation. Consequently, company C had exceeded its project budget because of the hidden cost piled up from their customisable CA interface. Therefore, not having a standard pricing model for CA projects is considered a challenge for some organisations.

Similar to managerial level participants, technical level participants also highlighted some organisational challenges they were facing during their project implementation. Company B and F's technical level respondents (AIC02, CD06) stated that a lot more communication effort was needed between the client (organisation) and the vendor's project team as many misunderstandings were arising from lack of adequate technical expertise within the organisation. For instance, company F's technical level participant noted:

“During the database creation, one of our biggest challenges was to help managers and their team members to learn the nuances of creating relationships through written words. They were used to creating relationships through in-person interactions (CA developer, company F).”

The above statement supports the fact that effective communication and a positive relationship between the vendor and the organisation play an essential role in the project's success and yet a challenging task to accomplish during the implementation process. To address this challenge, company F's technical team had built out a conversation guide and leveraged Live Person's MCS (meaningful connection score) toolkit to teach relevant managers and appointed company team members to have effective customer service conversations digitally, to analyse and course-correct conversations in real-time. In addition, some technical-level participants mentioned their clients' lack of flexibility in continuous resource allocation for subsequent improvements was a barrier to deliver desirable results.

ii) Employee misconceptions and lack of trust-related challenges

Similar to the findings from the literature, data analysis revealed that some of the case study organisations' CAs implementation was controversial among some of the employees due to the general notion they had about AI technology. For instance, company B's managerial participant SM02 mentioned some of their employees were worried about losing their jobs mainly because they are too old to learn and won't be competent enough to work with a complex technology like AI. To address this issue, management had shared emails among employees with background details about the purpose of adopting conversational AI technology, how the CA works, and the benefits employees get by collaborating their work with the CA. Company E's managerial level respondent HCC05 also echoed the same fact mentioned by SM02. He noted that some of their staff members showed non-responsiveness and reluctance towards partially automating their customer service tasks and work as collaborative partners with a conversational agent. Those same employees also have shown hesitance towards the company's training as they were not mentally prepared for the transition and acceptance of a new system. HCC05 also emphasised that resistance was coming from their older workers to work collaboratively with their CA, especially when handling queries handed over to them by the CA.

These findings provide evidence that employees of the e-commerce retailers who operate their businesses fully online (Company A, C, D, F, G) seem more receptive towards AI-driven technology transformation compared with employees working in companies (B and E) focused on hybrid retail business operations (brick-and-mortar and e-commerce). The findings demonstrate that employees working in the companies which are making a shift from hybrid retail operations to a more e-commerce presence to expand their online shopping capabilities may show a strong resistance towards AI's actual capabilities and frequently have misconceptions about it. These employee misconceptions can range from a direct threat of losing their jobs to AI technology and CAs are complex systems to learn. Getting employees on board with the project during the implementation and after the launch has been identified as a challenging task for some companies during the data analysis since it entails reassuring people who are uncomfortable with any kind of change and modifying their deeply rooted habits.

iii) Lack of AI skills and knowledge within the organisation

Nearly all participants conceded that ‘Lack of AI skills and knowledge’ among their employees in their IT departments and customer service departments as a challenge they faced during implementation and post-implementation phases. Many study participants acknowledged that conversational AI is a complicated and sophisticated technology that requires extensive training for their IT staff to ensure the functionality and continuous improvements of their CA. For in-house built company A’s CA, their managerial level participant LTS01 noted the importance of having a well-trained, competent, full-time, and part-time team in the IT department to monitor, analyse and improve their CAs daily performance. Lack of skills and inhouse knowledge as an organisational challenge described by LTS01 from the following words:

“[...] The most important question was how we are going to ensure our chatbot is providing accurate answers, maintain its functionality and utilise the data we get from daily user interactions to improve AI capabilities after it goes live. In order to do this, we had to hire full time and part-time conversational AI experts to the company as well as provide extensive training to our existing IT staff members. [...] It was indeed a challenge because we had to spend a lot of money for new staff and a lot of hours to train IT staff (Lead Technological Strategist, Company A).”

This response can be analysed as building a conversational agent from scratch, despite its benefits, can be a complex and challenging undertaking even after the launch for many organisations. The above statement provides evidence that, unlike pre-build cloud-based CA platforms, in-house built CA are required to have a full-time team with conversational AI expertise to monitor and maintain their CAs performance around the clock to avoid system issues.

In addition to in-house build conversational agents, ‘lack of knowledge within the organisation’ was also highlighted as a challenge among other case study organisations using cloud-based CA platforms. For instance, a few companies that used customisable cloud CA platforms had included company IT executives as permanent project team members to provide them with sufficient training experience. These selected IT executives were trained to handle and monitor the CA’s day-to-day operations since getting vendor’s support for every little issue after the project completion was involved with a substantial extra cost. However, these IT executives’

lack of presence and attention to the company's other IT matters during the implementation period had caused some disruptions to their daily operational activities.

5.4.2 Technological Challenges

Summing up all participants' narratives on technological challenges, most participants noted the 'data preparation, dialogue training, low-performance rate, integration complications, users' poor language use' related challenges as the primary technical challenges they were facing during and after the implementation. These challenges are discussed in the below section.

i) Data Preparation Challenges

Notably, many participants (ACD04; ITM07; PT07) revealed that data preparation was a challenging and highly intellectual task during the implementation. For instance, company C's technical level participant PM03 noted that data needed for their conversational agent's knowledge base took them more time to gather and prepare datasets following the required standards. As a result, the project team had to allocate more additional time to define the entities, intents, and conversational agent's responses when customising their cloud CA with the company-specific data due to its importance.

More feedback supporting to highlight the data preparation challenge received from company B's technical level participant AIC02, who said:

“We had to spend additional eight weeks to clean our employee data. During the data preparation, we found out that about 20% of employee data is not accurate. We found out spelling errors of their names, wrong delivery location records, and also employee number errors. [...] for example, we found out when first created the employee record in the system, some of our client's data entry operators had keyed in O (capital O) instead of 0 (Zero) for the 'S0' employee code before their four-digit employee number. And as a result, employee details didn't match against the ERP system's database. [...] Getting all these lists of employee names, employee numbers, addresses and delivery locations from customers and then cross-checking each and every single employee's record with our internal database was a massive task (AI Consultant, company B).”

Above technical level study respondent has provided valuable and more in-depth insight into the complexities surrounding the data preparation process they had to go through during the implementation. The above statement provides evidence that even during their pre-built cloud platform implementation, they had to deal with many mundane tasks related to the

customisation process while paying precise attention to the context of data sets that would match with their data inputs. If company B had integrated their company data based on the CAs knowledge base without any data preparation, the 20% of employees with inaccurate data would not have been able to have a seamless conversation when they converse with the conversational agent. The above statement has shown a vital issue why most of the current CAs fail to provide answers accurately for their user requests.

In contrast to company B taking additional time and effort for the knowledge base creation, while other companies acknowledged its importance, data analysis also revealed that some companies hadn't paid much attention to the knowledge base creation or dialogue training during the implementation. For instance, company D's technical level participant noted that getting an insufficient amount of quality training data for 'dialogue training' during the implementation was a challenge they had to deal with the client as a vendor. As company D's technical level participant CD04 noted, their client (company D) didn't want to spend money on required resources or additional time for dialogue training. As the project's conversational AI expert, he wasn't pleased about not getting enough resources and support from the company and highlighted that their CA only had three-four versions of dialogues but not hundreds of different versions. Based on the case study responses received from both the technical and managerial level respondents of company D's case study, it was revealed that company D's CA as the least performing conversational agent in this study.

ii) Low-performance rate

when it comes to response accuracy and CAs comprehension capacity for user requests as one of the leading technical challenges they are currently facing during the post-implementation phase. Most participants acknowledged that still, their CAs are unable to provide answers to all the queries seamlessly. Extracting entities and intents from a user request to comprehend the query and then navigate between contexts and subconversations has been identified as a challenging task. For example, company G's technical level participant PLT07 noted:

“In reality, you can rarely see a single intent in a human conversation. Humans are really good at having conversations where the goal shifts from one thing to another. This shows how far we have to think and go when determining intents and entities for a chatbot.”

Company B's technical level participant AIC02, who has a wide technical knowledge about conversational AI expressed that lack of response accuracy is an expected challenge of an AI-based CAs during the early days after the launch. Therefore, as he stated, it is imperative to

closely monitor the CA's performances and provide more training data sets while the bot learns from its own experience.

To overcome the low-performance rate, many respondents reported they are continuously monitoring their CA performance and working with their in-house conversational AI team to improve their CA performance. Company F's CTO06 suggested another solution. He noted when choosing vendors for pre-built CA interfaces, it is important to prioritise vendors who give more attention and effort to develop flexible, proactive, and intelligent algorithms with more intelligent capability to interpret user messages.

In addition, LTS01 stressed that still, their CA is unable to understand the context of some of the conversations, and also he believes that their CA must have the ability to respond to 'small talk' and handle random questions at least up to some extent. Their CA has failed to provide appropriate responses to random questions, and he sees it as an issue. He further stressed to overcome this issue they are continuously expanding the training data for intents to understand different ways a user would interact with their self-service CA. This shows the need for enterprise CAs with AI to be trained to have a conversation with the user rather than restricting the conversation to predefined questions and responses.

iii) Poor Language Use

BDM03 noted the 'User language and the way target customers present their query to the CA (poor language use)' as a technical challenge of their CA. He believes still many users have no idea how these CAs operate and how to interact with them. BDM03 quoted:

“Most of the time people attempt to describe instead of necessarily simplifying it without thinking whether the bot would be able to understand it or not.”

Another issue raised by some participants is that not having a clear definition of what is a good dialogue or for what is the acceptable behaviour of an AI-based CA. For instance, company F's managerial level participant CTO06 stated that they started to notice that their end-users were keying in totally different sentences/words to ask the same things differently. He further noted, when they were training the CA they did not consider that aspect much. Thus, they had to do some user tests manually to identify how the CA behaves with different inputs and then closely monitor the CA's conversations history to understand how the CA was reacting to users.

5.4.3 Governance Related Challenges

Data security has been recognised as a challenge by many managerial and technical participants during implementation, mainly when dealing with customers' personal information. Although choosing a SaaS CA platform was the preferred choice for many organisations for deployment, ensuring the security standards and policies on the selected CA platform hasn't always been an easy task for organisations due to the CA platform ownership issues. According to the semi-structured interview responses, the 'Conflict of ownership' was an issue organisation didn't see coming during the implementation. Conflict of ownership seemed to have arrived when the vendor has full ownership of most of the customisable CA platforms, but organisations prefer to have more control over them. For instance, according to company D's managerial level participant CD04, they were concerned about their customer data security. They thought public/vendor own cloud databases are less secure than the company's private databases. Company C's managerial participant BDM03 also echoed CDO4's statement and noted his concern about not having a choice but to follow the vendor's instruction on several mandatory updates to their CA within a brief period. This has cost them unexpected additional costs during the post-implementation phase thus far.

User hesitance to provide personal details or provide consent when engaging with the CA due to lack of trust and privacy concerns was another governance-related challenge highlighted by the respondents. For instance, LTS01 stressed encouraging their potential and existing customers to use the CA across both the platforms (Facebook messenger and website) as a huge challenge soon after the launch. To encourage customers to trust and use their CA, it was revealed that the company had to update and introduce a transparent, easy-to-access data and privacy policy. In addition, interview participants showed 'maintaining the security and privacy' of their CA as a challenge. BDM03 noted that their company is always focused on maintaining the CA's input databases' security to avoid the loss of users' information or sensitive corporate information. Therefore, compare with their other IS systems the company had to set up heavy security processes to prevent hacks and data breaches.

In addition, responses received from company B's managerial participant SM02 revealed their lack of understanding about data protection requirements (such as GDPR) of their CA during the pre-implementation phase as a challenge. The company had to fully rely on the vendor consultant guidance to fulfil those requirements. Also, SM02 had spent some time researching their company's responsibility to understand the use of conversational AI technology.

Figure 5.4: Implementation challenges – coding by items

Source: Developed by Author

5.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented an analysis of the qualitative data collected from the case study interviews that have been described in chapter four. All the main themes and sub-themes found to be important were classified according to the research questions. Therefore, the data analysis of this chapter was grouped into four main categories: CAs implementation benefits, CAs implementation CSFs, CAs implementation success criteria, and CAs implementation challenges in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. There is strong evidence indicating that the majority of the case study organisations were happy about their implementation success and the benefits they have achieved. CSF-related data analysis revealed that there is no strong evidence to categorise data-related factors as a separate CSF category since it appeared to be more suitable as a part of the `knowledge base creation` that has been presented under the information quality dimension. Moreover, data analysis also indicated more parameters for CAs implementation challenges and these findings will be discussed in the next chapter.

Chapter 6 : Discussion

This discussion chapter presents the findings of the analysis of the data collected in order to identify the link between the evidence gathered in the literature review and the conclusions obtained in this study. In the previous chapter, data classification was summarised, which outlined the empirical findings without going into detailed analysis. This discussion and outcomes chapter provides a detailed analysis, presenting an overview of the results as a summary relating them to the literature findings. The outcomes of this chapter are based on the first three research questions. Section one discusses the UK retail e-commerce customer self-service CAs use cases implementation benefits. Section two discusses the critical success factors and the success criteria that are significant for CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. Section three discusses the challenges the UK e-commerce retail organisations are facing when implementing CAs as a customer self-service tool. Subsequently, the case studies and comparative analysis findings suggested a need for modification of the conceptual framework model proposed in figure 2.15 in chapter two. Thus, the findings of the CAs implementation CSFs and success criteria with the revised conceptual framework are presented in this chapter in figure 6.1.

6.1 CAs Implementation Benefits

This section discusses the data analysis findings in regards to the benefits these seven UK e-commerce retailers achieved by successfully implementing CAs to fulfil their customer service use cases. Based on the data analysis, *'24/7 customer service availability and the ability to provide faster response rates'* have been identified as the most discussed CAs implementation benefits by the company B, C, D, E, G managerial level study participants (see table 5.1). Previous studies such as Ikumoro and Jawad, (2019) and Adam et al., (2020) also discussed these two benefits as significant. Both these studies have highlighted that implementing a CA allows customers to engage with the company 24/7 through their preferred communication channel for a specific query (i.e. Facebook, website, company app) instead of writing an email or making a phone call and then wait in line for a response.

'Taking the pressure off from service agents and better team productivity' also show as benefits the majority of the organisations have achieved by implementing their CAs. This finding was also supported by previous studies such as Gnewuch et al., (2017), Daugherty and Wilson (2018). The study findings also have provided evidence to agree with Daugherty and Wilson (2018)'s claim that "by giving humans to do what they do best while giving AI systems to do

tedious grunt tasks, organisations are set to achieve an unprecedented level of productivity while saving cost” (p.23). As the data analysis revealed, managerial study participants believe that there has been a positive change among their service agents after the CA launch. *'Getting valuable deep insights about the target customer, the ability to provide personalised offers and recommendations'* were other benefits highlighted in the data analysis that supported the literature findings (Chung et al., 2018; Gao, et al., 2019; Hoon et al., 2020; Rese et al., 2020).

However, the present study findings highlight a few more significant benefits these case study organisations have achieved through their CAs implementation, which previously hasn't been discussed in the body of knowledge. One of these benefits is the *'ability to communicate with international customers from their preferred language'*. For instance, company F and G's managerial respondent noted that by implementing a multilingual CA, they now have the ability to engage with their French and German customers without hiring French or German speaking employees. This has enabled these organisations to capture a broader European customer base by overcoming the language barrier. *'Fewer customer complaints and enhanced customer loyalty'* were also shown as the benefits of the present study findings.

In addition, results also suggest, when discussing the implementation benefits, the findings showed a strong connection between their customer service CAs' use case objectives, capabilities, and the benefits these companies have achieved. The empirical evidence suggests that although all the case study organisations have implemented a customer self-service CA, the objectives and capabilities of the implemented CAs were drastically different and required a high level of customisation during the implementation process based upon their business models. The findings highlight that in order to achieve the implementation benefits and ROI, the majority of these case study organisations had focused on choosing the most suitable self-service tasks to perform using their CAs during strategy discussions without blindly launching to the public. As the empirical data suggest, it was critical for these organisations to allocate more time and effort to define the CAs implementation objectives and capabilities while considering their company-specific customer pain points, the frequently asked questions, when and where customers need human service agents' attention during a conversation, when the CA should decide the query handover to a human, and the average time it takes to complete a specified self-service CA task. The present study's CAs implementation objectives and their company-specific CAs capabilities were presented in table 5.1 in chapter five. As the table shows, these CA capabilities are - to place orders, provide order status updates, provide

personalised service and offers/ recommendations, track order delivery and updates, check inventory status, multilingual conversational ability, and process returns and exchanges.

6.2 Critical Success Factors

This section aims to discuss the three main CSFs categories identified from the data analysis that are significant in CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce context. These three CSFs categories are organisational, technical, and governance-related factors and these identified factors are discussed in the following sections.

6.2.1 Organisational Factors

As one of the CSFs categories identified in this study, this section discusses the critical organisational factors affecting AI-based CAs implementation success. These factors include top management support, vendor selection, strategy, funds and resource allocation, project management, change management. These factors are discussed in the following section.

i) Top Management Support

The success of AI systems implementation largely depends on top management`s readiness, commitment, and support (Markus, 2017). As the literature suggests, transparent and visible top management support encourages positive results during AI-enabled systems implementations (Markus, 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019). Overall, in a similar vein, most of the respondents agreed about the importance of top management commitment and support and described how their support has successfully contributed to achieving their CAs implementation. Both managerial and technical-level respondents noted that top management`s active involvement and participation at all stages of the project, during the implantation and after the launch, directly contributed to their project success. However, findings show that top management commitment and involvement in two critical areas have directly contributed to their CAs implementation success. These two areas are gathering adequate knowledge about conversational AI technology before blindly follow the hype, and providing continuous support after the launch.

Many studies have discussed the importance of having adequate knowledge among top managers to implement CAs as an essential factor to ensure implementation success. For instance, researchers such as Brandtzaeg and Folstad (2018) also agreed on this finding and claim that despite high expectations, many organisational leaders` lack of understanding and

competence in implementing CAs have been identified as one of the major reasons for implementation failures. From specific responses received, there is a strong belief among technical-level respondents that top managers getting the fundamental education about conversational AI and CAs before quickly jumping into implementation decisions could be significant for the project's success or failure. Based on these technical level participants' responses, it was clear that some of their clients didn't know what to expect and the implementation use case objectives initially. Therefore, these findings suggest that an organisation's readiness to invest money in conversational AI technology is simply not enough to ensure implementation success. Instead, top managers of organisations must have a clear vision and a fundamental understanding of the technology without blindly following the AI hype.

To add to the findings, some technical-level respondents also discussed the top management's ability to conduct a benefits and risks assessment of adopting a novice technology such as AI to a company. Meaning, organisations must also conduct a holistic organisation-wide analysis to mitigate the impact this technology could create for their employees and their customers. As respondents highlight, this is mainly due to the fact that conversational AI technology is a new and different concept from other enterprise systems they have previously worked with, and if implemented properly, organisations can obtain fantastic first-mover benefits, but at the same time, if things go wrong, it can damage the company reputation.

In addition to the top management having adequate knowledge to embark on the implementation, this study revealed some significant findings that hadn't been discussed in the literature. As the analysis was shown, top management having a combination of 'commitment, excitement, and engagement' towards their CA after the launch can be considered as a vital factor to ensure the implementation success. Study findings indicate that the most challenging part of an AI-based CA project begins after the launch as the live interaction data can show how accurately their CA can provide answers to user queries. However, if organisations fail to monitor and improve their CAs after the launch, CA wouldn't be able to engage with its users as expected within a few months. Therefore, data analysis suggests that getting top management support is a critical factor not only during the implementation phase but also after the launch to avoid project failures. However, there were limited studies that have discussed the importance of 'top management's continuous support' after the launch.

ii) Vendor Selection

Analysis of the responses revealed that an AI-based CA implementation's success could also depend mainly on the vendor's experience, reputation, and expertise, as choosing the wrong one will lead to an ROI failure. Primary data indicates having AI technology means nothing if it's not implemented and maintained appropriately according to the e-commerce retailer's specific business context. Several studies echoed this finding and confirmed the importance of choosing the right conversational AI partner to implement their first CA (Brandtzæg and Følstad 2018; Davenport & Ronanki, 2018; Wirtz et al., 2019; Kousa, 2019; Huang et al., 2020). In addition, studies claim that when it comes to getting the most from conversational AI technology, building or customising the CA, integrating, installing, maintaining, and expanding its performance plays a vital role (Brandtzæg and Følstad, 2018). Similarly, the findings show that case study organisations have selected their CAs implementation vendor primarily based on two factors. These factors are: conversational AI specialisation with similar use cases and previous implementation experience.

The study finds that when selecting a vendor, it's more beneficial for considering their specialisation experience in the industry with similar use cases. Finding shows vendors' familiarity with the company's industry and specific use cases means they already have first-hand knowledge about designing and deploying the CA that delivers the best experience for its users as they understand sector-specific terminology what content is best suited for e-commerce self-service. In addition, responses revealed having specialisation and experience in similar use cases means the vendor has enough knowledge to explain to a company what integrations are necessary to automate user journeys. Also, the vendor should be able to guide a company concerning what is involved with deploying their CA on a variety of channels such as company website, messaging platforms (i.e. Facebook, WhatsApp), or mobile app. This is why Huang et al., (2020) suggest that organisations must consider how their vendor would be a strategic fit for their overall company vision and how vendors could guide them towards it with their experience and knowledge.

Besides that, findings indicate that most of the case study organisations didn't want to select just an AI vendor. Instead, they were looking to work with vendors who could provide knowledge throughout the entire process and become a trusted partner. As the majority of the case study organisations IT departments didn't have an in-depth understanding about CAs, it shows these companies believed that vendors with successful CAs implementation experience

could understand organisational specific needs, evaluate their ROI expectations, and suggest enhancements and new ideas for use cases. However, only one organisation had partnered with a young and promising London-based conversational AI startup based upon their substantial evidence on vendor credentials. As implementing domain-specific text-based CAs in enterprises is still new and evolving, there were limited studies that have discussed the vendor selection guidelines in-depth.

iii) Funds and Resource Allocation

The study findings reveal that the budget and resource allocation (depends on organisational needs) significantly impact a CA project implementation success. As it appears, most case study organisations had some serious budget issues as a result of exceeded planned time for the project completion and due to the changes made to the original project scope.

Evidence from data analysis indicates that once a company decides to adopt a CA for their customer service frontline, top managers' key focus must be on three main areas that will help them determine the budget and the required resources for their CA project. These three key areas are 'the CA platform, implementation process, and potential compliance cost'. Evidence gathered from data analysis indicates that asking the right questions from the vendor or the CA platform provider can be highlighted by the respondents as the first critical area to determine to provide adequate funds and resource allocation requirements of the implementation. These fundamental questions are: 1) the delivery method of the CA and the cost and resource involvement for each option (SaaS vs build inhouse), 2) how the CA is licensed and the ownership related questions, 3) How these pricing metrics will be affected when using Application Program Interface calls (API calls), 4) How the pricing metric will be affected based on the user volume, 5) evaluation of the total cost involves with building a CA from scratch versus choosing the customised option.

The implementation process related to cost assessments involves choosing the most suitable service, choosing the implementation team, seeking strategic consulting services, data security requirements, public cloud licensing requirements, setting up strategies, implementation scope, conducting pilot runs, and testing the CA, etc. The focus of the 'potential compliance cost' involves in the project is the third area responses highlight that organisations must also consider thinking beyond the CA platform and implementation costs and scale the budget and resources for organisational-wide CA adoption driving activities. These activities include workflow redesign, employee training, skill development, create an AI-savvy work environment, and

organisational-wide change management initiatives. As implementing domain-specific text-based CAs in enterprises is still new and evolving, there were limited studies to back these findings in the literature.

iv) Project Management

The findings show that having a dedicated project manager who managed the team, resources requirements, and project delivery for both in-house build and SaaS customisable CAs was crucial for the implementation. The current study found three key areas respondents mentioned they were concerned about related to their project management. These three areas are project team, planning, and project handover. In addition to including well-experienced conversational flow designers in the project team, findings also revealed the importance of adding well-experienced customer service/frontline employees to work with the project team closely due to the in-depth knowledge they have about the company and customer expectations. These employees' knowledge and experience have played a key role during the strategy setting and knowledgebase creation. This finding is also in accordance with Srivastava (2020), and as he claims CAs implementations, in general, is a business project more than a technical project as CAs knowledge base must be heavily involved with company-specific data when introducing a CA as a self-service FLT tool.

In addition, it was revealed that project handover after the launch was an issue for some specific organisations. Therefore, findings suggest that organisations that especially go with SaaS AI-based customisable CA platforms must prepare for the project handover at the very beginning to avoid confusion and conflicts. As it appeared from the findings, a successful project handover is not only the vendor's responsibility with CAs implementations. It is also an organisation's responsibility to prepare their selected in-house employees to work closely with their CAs after the launch to handle daily monitoring tasks. This finding is also supported by studies such as Pickup (2019). As Pickup's study suggests, when implementing AI systems, organisations should not expect their employees to turn into data scientists magically. Instead, the focus must be on providing solid training on comprehending, interpreting, and analysing AI systems properly.

v) Implementation Strategy

Data collected from interviews captures a construction of strong relevance and importance of having a clearly defined strategy to influence an AI-based CA implementation outcome's

success. The literature also confirms this finding, and many researchers have been identified that organisations implementing CAs without a strategy make current CAs vulnerable in many areas and failing miserably to fulfil effective self-service expectations (Ransbotham et al., 2018; Piccolo et al., 2018; Brandtzæg and Følstad 2018; Jain et al., 2018). For the most part, 'strategy' was discussed by participants in relation to organisational decisions they had taken for the general key areas that needed attention during the planning stage. The data analysis findings indicate four key areas these case study organisations have focused on during their implementation strategy discussions. These areas are use case and objective analysis, the scope of the automation, target audience, and the platform to launch the CA.

All the comments received from semi-structured interviews demonstrate that the organisation's preparation, similar to the time and money they invest in a conversational AI deployment project as a critical factor to avoid many CA-related issues they face after the launch. The companies (A, B, C, E, F) who had taken their time to define the target audience and evaluate the most suitable platform to launch their CAs during the implementation strategy discussions highlighted it as one of the significant reasons for their project success. Conversely, company D and G's managerial and technical level participants didn't specifically mention the special attention they had pay towards the target audience or platform selection during strategy discussion. Company D's reasons for not taking time and effort to define their target audience and the platform at the early stage of the implementation were 'Not having adequate time to spend for planning and their vendor not emphasising the importance of getting an in-depth insight about their CA user'. However, company D's participants revealed some of the major issues and complaints they were experiencing from their customers about the CA after the launch.

The logic that informs from the study findings is that coming up with an effective implementation strategy is similar to having a flashlight in a tunnel, meaning, although organisations can't see the full picture of the results, they can be fairly confident that they are progressing towards introducing an effective self-service CA to their customers. Implementation preparation is a common phase shared by most IS-related projects from organisational and project factors. Yet, the study findings demonstrate that the 'Implementation strategy' of a conversational AI project was positioned implicitly as something that organisations should be articulated more distinctly based on different factors such as the deployment type (i.e. build in-house from scratch or use a pre-built customisable platform), organisation size, customer base, use case, and its objectives as well as the level of automation

of the CA rather than following same principles usually vendor`s apply to every project. This finding was also supported by literature; as Etlinger (2017) argues, CAs implementation considerations must span beyond the technical aspects without heavily rely on the vendor. Similarly, the findings suggest that whilst organisations focus on conversational AI technology, the focus must also be on how to reach the users and how to satisfy their e-commerce shopping needs.

vi) Change Management

This study's findings show that most organisations have used different change management strategies to manage the organisation-wide change that came up with their CA implementation. As the findings highlight, the introduction of an AI-based CA as a self-service tool to their e-commerce service counter had created a significant effect within the organisation and outside the organisation. Therefore, to manage the changes that were coming with these companies` project implementation, findings show that most of these companies have focused on two critical areas as focal points. These two areas were internal and external change management and effective communication. When dealing with internal change management, some of the case study participants had viewed the importance of portraying a positive image among their employees on the idea of working with AI technology. In order to achieve this goal, some companies had shared informative email campaigns explaining the benefits a CA would bring to their employees, involving key employees for the knowledge base creation and to the project team, whilst some other companies had conducted internal surveys to understand their employee concerns. The study findings suggest that portraying a positive image as an essential change management strategy to avoid the organisation's resistance to collaborate with AI when serving their customers. Despite the benefits CAs implementation brings to the organisations, findings also indicate that job redesign and creating new job roles to work along well with the CA play a significant role in achieving the maximum ROI after the CA launch. However, although job redesign and providing relevant training to their employees was a focal point for some organisations, a few organisations were found without a clear succession plan during the implementation. It was revealed that this had led to some disagreements among customer service and admin employees over who should takeover which jobs. These findings are in accordance with change management theories under 'group dynamics and individuals perspective' (Cummings and Huse, 1989; Haddad and Kotnour, 2015) discussed in the literature. As these theories claim, organisational change must occur at both the team level and

an individual level, focusing on modifying and shaping the norms, roles, and values of their employees.

6.2.2 Technological Factors

According to Adamopoulou and Moussiades (2020), the design and development of an AI-based CA involve a variety of AI subsets (NLP, ML, DL) and techniques. As many studies highlight, in order to enhance the CAs ability to maintain a seamless conversation and deliver a positive user experience, AI technology plays the most crucial role (Ramezani, 2014; Rose, 2018; Deng and Liu, 2018; Zhou et al., 2020). For instance, NLP helps the CA to understand text-based human commands by the natural human language and then generate the most suitable response for the user request from that same user language (Lester et al., 2004; Nuruzzaman and Hussain, 2018, Levy, 2018, Masche & Le, 2018). ML in a CA enables the system to better respond to the user by analysing training datasets and making accurate predictions using data (Rose, 2018; Ramezani 2014; Oliver, 2014). Dialogue management helps the CA to determine conversational behaviour according to user requests (McTear et al., 2016). Data Sharing and Integration allows the CA to integrate with the company databases and provide real-time updated responses (Adamopoulou and Moussiades, 2020).

Similarly, it has been found in this study that there is a consensus among technical level respondents about the critical role and the importance of NLP and ML. However, data analysis revealed that the 'data sharing and integration' CSF identified in the literature under the technical category is a directly relevant component to the 'knowledge base', which has been discussed in the following section under the implementation success criteria. Thus, based on the study findings, there wasn't enough evidence to consider 'data sharing and integration' as a separate CSF which was initially identified as a CSF in the literature.

Interestingly, however, in addition to these CSFs identified in the literature, two additional factors were identified from the study findings related to CAs implementation project success. These two CSFs are 'human handover and CA's analytics'. As the findings suggest, in this early phase of AI-based CAs development, when introducing a CA as an FST self-service tool, there could always be many situations when a CA simply cannot complete a user request. Therefore, study findings indicate that while CAs can efficiently and effectively address some tasks, the importance of having a human service agent in the loop option to avoid frustrating user experiences during a conversation. According to some technical level respondents, when implementing CA's for customer service tasks in the e-commerce setting, it is essential to build

trust among users by providing easy access to a human employee and resume the conversation within a specified timeline with a human agent. There wasn't much literature to back this finding as none of the previously discussed CA implementation studies had not addressed the importance of CAs ability to pass queries to a human and 'human handover' as a critical factor to implementation success. However, the concept of CAs working collaboratively with human employees also emerged from the study findings, and this finding was also supported by a few studies such as Daugherty and Wilson (2018), Jarrahi (2018), Dwivedi et al., (2019). They argue that AI systems should be designed to complement and augment each other's capabilities by giving tasks what both parties do best in contrast to creating a fully automated customer service department.

In addition, the importance of CA Analytics was mentioned by many technical level participants as an integral technical part of ensuring the CA implementation project success. The study findings highlight that CA analytics helps organisations to monitor the conversation history of live user interactions daily, measure performance against company-specific KPIs, and identify usability errors and improve the CA's performance. Although CA analytics come into play after the launch, findings indicate that CA implementation's real success depends on how e-commerce retailers pay attention to the implementation phase's analytics requirements. However, CA analytics appeared to be a less-discussed area in the literature.

6.2.3 Governance Related Factors

This study's findings show that due to the nature of easy-to-use and rapid exchange of instant messages between the users and the CA, companies could attain a vast amount of real-time data from interactions with users. For this reason, it was revealed that businesses that use CAs and vendors that provide CA platforms have a legal responsibility to maintain their General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR). Meaning, organisations that deploy CAs and vendors who have ownership of CA platforms are not allowed any data breaches with their users' data and must be GDPR compliant. Therefore, the study participants highlighted maintaining data protection responsibility as a critical and yet challenging task during the implementation and after the launch. However, the findings highlight that the majority of the case study organisations' lack of knowledge about their CA's governance-related requirements as an issue they didn't pay much consideration when they made the CA adoption decision. For instance, it was revealed that most top managers were unclear about the GDPR requirements, what data their CA collects, and what their responsibilities as an organisation have to practice. As six of

these companies were using pre-built customised CAs from service providers, these case study companies were heavily relied on their vendor's guidance to maintain the legal requirements. Moreover, some organisations involved expert legal and security teams in crafting their conversational privacy policy and security infrastructure needed to confidently introduce their CA as a self-service FST tool.

To sum up, there was substantial evidence to agree that ensuring case study organisation`s CA users' data privacy as an integral part of their overall CAs implementation success. This finding was also supported by the existing literature. Many studies previously have discussed the importance of data protection responsibility (Fadhil and Gabrielli, 2017; Zandi et al., 2019; Dwivedi et al., 2019; Pick up 2019). In addition to privacy and security, an interesting finding was revealed in regards to the transparency of the CA. Some respondents strongly believed that it is ethically important to let the CA users know that they are communicating with a machine, not with an actual human, and provide the user with the option to choose their preferred communication method. Therefore, the present study findings suggest that the goal of an AI-based CA implementation must be around achieving its plethora of benefits without losing control to the AI technology.

6.3 CAs Implementation Success Criteria

This section aims to discuss the key CAs implementation success criteria identified from DeLone & McLean (2003) success model in chapter two and empirically investigated findings in chapter five. In order to answer the third research question, this section discusses the CAs implementation success criteria relevant to the UK retail e-commerce customer service setting. These criteria were classified into three categories based on their relevance, as follows: information quality, service quality, and system quality.

6.3.1 Information Quality

This study found that most case study organisations have focused on two main success criteria to enhance the information quality of their CA during the implementation. These two success criteria are sentiment analysis and the knowledge base of the CA.

Sentiment Analysis

As the data analysis findings indicated, integrating sentiment analysis for a CA plays a vital role when organisations implement a CA to extract the user's positive or negative polarity.

Although many technical participants agreed that analysing their user's sentiment is still an issue and a challenging task for their implemented CA, they also highlighted the importance of gradually improving the CA's sentiment analysis capability must be a top priority to enhance the information quality.

The literature supported this finding, and authors such as Bachate and Sharma, (2020) have also discussed the importance of analysing the sentiment expressed in a written text by a user during a CA conversation and measuring the satisfaction level of the user-CA interaction. Furthermore, some studies have highlighted that during the self-service counter interactions, customers are more often reluctant to share their sentiment with firms, and thus, companies are unable to instantly recognise dissatisfied customers (unless they receive a formal complaint) and react fast enough to respond to unhappy customers in order to avoid bad self-service customer experience (Feine et al., 2019). They further argue that failure to react and respond to CAs user's sentiment can result in lost customers, negative word of mouth for the brand, fewer profits, and a less brand loyal customer base for the organisation. McTear et al., (2016) also added their views towards the present study's finding and mentioned that application of sentiment analysis in e-commerce CA service encounters has the ability to provide rich, informative signals for organisations since the written language is influenced by emotions, thoughts, and intentions of their target users.

Knowledge Base Creation

The study findings indicate that a customer self-service CA's knowledge base plays a significant role in enhancing the quality of information it presents as responses to user queries. The data analysis highlights that even for a domain-specific customer service CA, it is crucial to have a wealth of knowledge to provide comprehensive and context-specific responses. This finding is consistent with DeLone & McLean (2003), and they state that the information quality must be able to enhance the desirable characteristics of the system outputs. Meaning, the system outputs must be understandable, relevant, accurate, and complete. This present study finding was also supported by the CAs implementation related studies such as Suta et al., (2020) and Reshmi (2018). They have defined the knowledge base as the brain of an AI-based CA and postulate when generating responses, the knowledge base is considered as the information repository the CA refers to ensure the most appropriate responses.

The present study found that most managerial and technical level participants believed the 'content creation' for the knowledge base was a highly intellectual and challenging task they

had to experience during the implementation. Some technical level respondents gave an interesting analogy of 'a child's brain' to an AI-based CA. As the respondent (PTL07) explained, these types of CAs learn by example, and therefore, the information quality is only as good as the data it's trained upon. Thus, data analysis indicates that depending on self-service use case objective and tasks, CAs need to be trained with company-specific dynamic data sets, in addition to integrating the system to the company's CRM, ERP, and public customer service databases to enhance the CAs information quality. Findings of the data analysis show the importance of expanding the knowledge base determines the quality of the information the CA provides as intelligent responses for user queries. It was revealed that the CA determines what responses to deliver and what action to take next, based upon the knowledge gathered as it helps the CA to learn and evolve over time using its knowledge base. This result is in accordance with Reshmi (2018), and she claims during a CA implementation, the knowledge base must be filled with a large scale of various information sources to improve the information quality and fluency of the responses.

The findings also highlight that when creating company-specific content for a customer service CA, the content that is required to train the CA is already being created in company databases such as – live chats history, telephone conversations, email conversations, and social media comments. However, re-purposing these unstructured big data sources into a CA readable context was revealed as a highly intellectual and time-consuming task. This finding was supported by the literature. According to Lawnboy (2018), when implementing a customer self-service CA, it is crucial to figure out a way to exchange information in a chat format that was previously done using emails or over the phone.

6.3.2 Service Quality

This study found that most case study organisations have focused on the personality of the CA as the main success criterion to enhance the service quality of the system during the implementation. Findings of the data analysis provide enough evidence to claim that it's crucial to reflect a CA's personality through the way the system presents a dialogue, the tone, and the language of a response while incorporating the company's corporate brand identity. This result also confirms the findings of other studies such as Specht et al., (2007), Sundaram and Webster (2000), in which it was found that service agents behaviour plays a key role in creating a positive first-time impression and perception towards the organisation, intention to repeat use, word of mouth, loyalty, and cooperation. According to some technical participants, when a

retail e-commerce organisation wants to partially replace a human employee to do the customer service tasks, it's essential for organisations to think of ways to make the CA a suitable replacement. As the study findings show, the majority of the case study organisations have focused on introducing the CA as a brand ambassador more than a technical device when presenting it to their customers through their chosen platform. Similarly, studies such as Van Pinxteren et al., (2020), Holtgraves et al., (2007), Tzeng (2004) suggest that it is essential to emulate a more sensitive human appeal and a less mechanical appeal when implementing a CA as a frontline self-service tool.

6.3.3 System Quality

DeLone & McLean (2003) defined system quality as an information system's desirable characteristics, such as ease of use, flexibility, and response times. In order to achieve these characteristics, the study findings show that the majority of the case study organisations have focused on 'usability testing' as the main success criteria to enhance the system quality of their CA during the implementation. There is a strong consensus among the managerial and technical level interviewees on the importance of a CA's usability testing to improve the system quality prior to the launch. The study findings indicate that case study organisations have taken a variety of approaches to conduct usability testings with their target audience to get insights such as system errors, participants' views on the CA's conversation experience as a self-service tool, and their level of satisfaction. All the issues and feedback had taken into consideration to improve the overall system quality of the CAs during the implementation by many organisations. Many studies have discussed IS's quality attributes such as 'effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction' in general (Eeuwen 2017; Miner et al., 2016; Cohen & Lane 2016; Thieltges 2016). However, limited studies have discussed the importance of the 'usability testing' of a CA as a system quality success criterion.

While a few organisations had considered the usability testing as a top priority by discussing feasible step-by-step approaches during their strategy discussions, some organisations had done the system testing on an ad hoc basis without a clear plan in place. Consequently, those organisations who tested their CAs without a clear plan had gone through various issues such as not having enough time to arrange external groups for testing, not having adequate resources and allocated budget to run the testing phase successfully.

Another interesting finding of the study was that while most technical-level study participants believed the importance of usability testing during the implementation, they also noted that

improving the system quality is a continuous process and doesn't stop after the launch. As the AI-based CAs learn based on experience and live interactions, the study findings suggest that it is imperative to focus on usability to maintain the CA's system quality around the clock.

6.4 CAs Implementation Challenges

This section is aimed at discussing the CAs implementation challenges identified in the present study. In order to answer the fourth research question, the findings of this study show three major implementation challenges categories. These categories are 'organisational challenges, technological challenges, and governance-related challenges'. These categories are discussed in the following sections.

6.4.1 Organisational Challenges

According to empirical evidence of this study, many of the case study organisations have not gone through any sort of AI project implementation previously and have initiated the project from zero knowledge while highly depending on the vendor. Therefore, after analysing the semi-structured interviews, it was revealed that these organisations had faced several challenges when dealing with their conversational AI vendor. From top management level participants' perspective, these vendor management related challenges were – top management's lack of knowledge to choose the most suitable vendor and the SaaS CA platform; having to fully rely on their chosen vendor when making critical decisions regarding their CA; accommodating an effective relationship with the vendor; lack of transparency in some cases; conflict of ownership and not having a standard pricing model. Similarly, technical level participants also had similar challenges issues with organisations as they were not happy about the way some companies didn't want to add more money and resources to enhance the performance of the CA after the launch. Many authors support this finding of managers lack of knowledge as an issue, and according to them, company leaders/managers must learn to improve their understanding as AI is set to modify how they perform their work in the near future (Kolbjørnsrud et al., 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019; Jöhnk et al., 2020). However, vendor-related challenges were a newly emerged challenge to the body of knowledge as previous studies have not discussed this issue in the literature.

In addition, similar to the findings from the literature, data analysis revealed that some of the case study organisations' CAs implementation was controversial among some of the employees due to the general notion they had about AI technology. The study findings

demonstrate that employees working in companies that are making a shift from hybrid retail operations to a more e-commerce presence to expand their online shopping capabilities may show a strong resistance towards AI's actual capabilities and frequently have misconceptions about it. These employee misconceptions can range from a direct threat of losing their jobs to AI technology, and CAs are complex systems to learn. Getting employees on board with the project during the implementation and after the launch has been identified as a challenging task for some companies during the data analysis since it entails reassuring people who are uncomfortable with any kind of change and modifying their deeply rooted habits.

Nearly all participants conceded that 'Lack of AI skills and knowledge' among their employees in their IT departments and customer service departments as a challenge they faced during implementation and post-implementation phases. Oswald and Mascarenhas, (2018) supported this finding and postulates that an effective CAs adoption and implementation in the e-commerce retail setting requires employees with interdisciplinary knowledge both from technological and business disciplines. These interview respondent extracts of challenges in regards to lack of AI skills and knowledge within the organisation also supported by the literature findings (Pickup, 2019; Dwivedi et al., 2019). To address this challenge both these previous studies highlighted the importance of preparing their existing employees to work with their AI system after the launch and recruit full-time AI professionals if they can't find in-house talent to ensure the system's overall success after the launch.

6.4.2 Technological Challenges

Summing up all participants' narratives on technological challenges, most participants noted the 'data preparation, dialogue training, low-performance rate, integration complications, users' poor language use' related challenges as the primary technical challenges they were facing during and after the implementation. Even though these technical challenges were already acknowledged in previous studies by Seaver (2015b), Gupta (2017), Preyss et al., (2018), Hung et al., (2020) all have generalised their findings to AI –systems implementation challenges, but not specifically for CAs implementation.

6.4.3 Governance Related Challenges

Data security has been recognised as a challenge by many managerial and technical participants during implementation, mainly when dealing with customers' personal information. Although choosing a SaaS CA platform was the preferred choice for many organisations for deployment,

ensuring the security standards and policies on the selected CA platform hasn't always been an easy task for organisations due to the CA platform ownership issues. According to the semi-structured interview responses, the 'Conflict of ownership' was an issue organisation didn't see coming during the implementation. User hesitance to provide personal details or provide consent when engaging with the CA due to lack of trust and privacy concerns was another governance-related challenge highlighted by the respondents. Lack of knowledge companies have about their CAs GDPR compliance requirements was also highlighted as a challenge under this category. These findings related to governance-related challenges that have emerged from the present study have not seemed to previously discussed by previous studies.

6.5 Modification of the Conceptual Framework

The proposed conceptual framework was developed in chapter two to understand how AI-based CAs can be implemented successfully in the context of UK retail e-commerce customer service. The framework was evaluated and assessed for feasibility in chapters five and six based on the methodology developed in chapter three using seven UK retail e-commerce organisations that have successfully implemented a CA for their customer service purposes. Based on the evidence of these seven case studies, the conceptual framework proved somewhat feasible during the comparison between the practical CAs implementation success and the literature findings proposed. However, through the data analysis in chapter five, it has been found that there is a need for modifying some aspects of the conceptual framework to provide a more comprehensive overview of AI-based CAs implementation success. The modified conceptual framework has incorporated the critical success factors and the success criteria which have been highlighted in the case study findings that have influenced the successful implementation of AI-based CAs implementation in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. Therefore, special attention needs to be given to these factors and the summary of the CAs implementation CSFs and the success criteria given in the following section.

6.5.1 Summary of the revised Critical Success Factors

According to the empirical outcomes, this study has identified 13 CSFs under three main categories. These three categories are organisational factors, technological factors, and governance-related factors.

i) Organisational Factors

Based on the empirical findings, the organisation-related CSFs category consists of six factors that are significant to CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. These six factors are 'top management support, vendor selection, implementation strategy, funds and resource allocation, project management, and change management'. A modification has to be made in regards to the 'innovation adoption' CSF identified under this category in the 2.16 conceptual framework. Although the literature suggested innovation adoption can be a separate and significant CSF under the organisational factor category, there wasn't enough evidence to support that argument. The study findings indicate that innovation adoption can also be a sub-theme that could consider under the top management support CSF.

ii) Technological Factors

The study findings present five CSFs under the technological category for the phenomenon under investigation. In addition to the initially identified three CSFs in the conceptual framework in figure 2.15, based upon the empirical findings, a modification has to be made to the technological category by adding two additional CSFs (human handover and CA analytics) organisations must pay close attention during the implementation. Therefore, the proposed five CSFs are 'natural language processing, machine learning, data sharing and integration, human handover and CA analytics'. According to the present study's findings, it was revealed the importance of considering having a 'human service agent in the loop' to avoid user frustrations during a self-service task when a CA fails to respond to a specific query. Hence, during the planning stage, it is suggested to discuss this factor with great importance with the vendor and the technical team to find the best ways to ensure a smooth handover and a faster response after the handover. The CA's analytics was another important technological factor highlighted by many technical participants, and according to them, the success of a CA implementation depends on how the system successfully solves customer self-service tasks after the launch. Although CA analytics comes into play after the launch, the study findings revealed the

importance of organisations preparing themselves well by discussing the use of CA analytics with the vendor and technical team in regards to how live user interaction data provided by CA analytics can be used for continuous improvements.

iii) Governance Related Factors

The present study findings show that all three CSFs identified in the conceptual framework (figure 2.15) under governance-related factors are significant and positively impact an AI-based CA implementation success. These factors are 'data privacy, system security, and transparency'. This study shows that most senior managers in case study organisations were having issues regarding governance-related factors due to lack of knowledge about GDPR and transparency, as those keywords were new concepts for them compared to their previous IS implementations. The study findings highlight that the focus of CAs implementation projects in the UK retail e-commerce context must go beyond simple cost and efficiency gains, and the CA's security and ethics must be considered a top priority. Factors such as 'not giving complete control to the CA to generate fully automated decisions/responses, data protection, ensuring the system's security around the clock, reveal customers that they are communicating with a machine, explainability of the CA's system behaviour' must be critical areas to consider when a UK e-commerce retailer decides to implement a CA in order to ensure the customer and general public's safety.

6.6 Revised Implementation Success Criteria

By adapting the DeLone & McLean (2003)'s IS success quality dimensions, the conceptual framework's CAs implementation success criteria were constructed and empirically investigated in chapter five. According to the empirical outcomes, this study identified some additional CAs implementation success criteria under all three – information quality, system quality, and service quality dimensions and modifications were made to the conceptual framework accordingly.

i) Information Quality

Based on the study findings, there are two factors that are significant to improve the information quality of an AI-based self-service CA during the implementation. These two factors are sentiment analysis and knowledge base. In addition to the initially identified 'sentiment analysis' in the conceptual framework in figure 2.15, a modification has to be made and add 'the knowledge base' as a significant factor to improve the information quality as per the data

analysis indicated in chapter five. Although this study initially discussed the knowledge base as a separate CSF under the 'data related' CSF category in the 2.15 conceptual framework, the study participants' responses received show that knowledge base must be discussed as a success criterion to improve the CA's information quality of the responses.

ii) Service Quality

Study findings indicate that the CA's personality is a significant factor that can improve the service quality when introducing a CA to the UK retail e-commerce frontline as a self-service tool. Although communicative behaviour was identified as the main success criterion to improve a customer service CA's service quality, there wasn't enough evidence to back that argument in this study's empirical findings. Therefore, a modification has to be made by replacing the 'CA's personality' as the main success criterion that organisations must focus on during the implementation to improve the CA's service quality.

ii) System Quality

It was identified that 'usability' as the most significant factor that organisations must focus on during the implementation to improve the CA's service quality. According to the study findings, most organisations have discussed usability testing's importance during the implementation to launch a high-quality self-service CA to their customers. However, it was also identified that an AI-based CA is a tool that has to be improved after the launch based on live interactions, and the usability testing must be a continuous process even after the launch. In the conceptual framework (figure 2.15), 'response quality' was discussed as the most influential success criterion that organisations must focus on to improve the system quality of a CA during a CA implementation. Despite this literature finding, the empirical evidence gathered from the conversational AI experts revealed that response quality is a factor that must be considered under the usability of a CA. Therefore, a modification has to be made by replacing the 'CA's usability' as the main success criterion that organisations must focus on during the implementation to improve the CA's system quality.

Figure 6.1: Revised conceptual framework

Source: Developed by Author

6.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter consisted of two parts, and these two parts were the discussion of the findings and presenting the revised model. The first part of this chapter provided a discussion of the qualitative data analysis presented in chapter five and then a comparative analysis was undertaken to identify the link between the empirical findings and the literature review. The second part of the chapter discussed the revised conceptual framework and its revised factors validated through empirical evidence. The model elements were divided into two main categories that would directly involve ensuring CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context and these two categories were CAs implementation CSFs and success criteria. Under the CSF category, thirteen success factors were identified, and four factors were identified under the Delon and Mclean`s Is success categories.

Chapter 7 : Conclusion and Recommendations

The research context's justification and the research gap have been presented in chapter one in the previous chapters. After critically reviewing the literature, a conceptual framework was developed for AI-based conversational agents' implementation success for the UK e-commerce retailers in chapter two. The research methodology which was adopted to carry out the study by providing the justification for the chosen methodological approaches was presented in chapter three. Chapter four presented the backgrounds of the seven case study organisations selected for this study. Chapter five presented the analysis and empirical findings from the evidence gathered from seven UK e-commerce retailers' case studies. Chapter six presented the findings of the analysis of data collected in order to identify the link between the evidence gathered in the literature review and the findings obtained in this study. Subsequently, based on the study's findings, the revised conceptual framework was presented in chapter six.

7.1 Overview of Research Objectives

It was highlighted in the first chapter that while AI-based CAs could potentially bring significant benefits for the UK retail e-commerce setting as a self-service tool, despite high expectations, the implementation success of these CAs frequently fails. While there's extensive research on CAs implementation in the context of information systems, computer science, and human-computer interaction related fields, there's limited availability of literature about AI-based CAs implementation from a business and organisational perspective. In recent decades, e-commerce transaction in the UK retail sector has gained momentum due to changing consumers' purchasing habits in online shopping and omnichannel presence. Improve efficiency, reduce costs without compromising service quality while satisfying every customer via service channels have been a significant challenge for UK e-commerce retail organisations. As a solution, CAs are identified as a digital customer service companion to deliver a fast, tailored experience to address customer service challenges in the UK e-commerce context. Therefore, the aim of this research thesis was to understand how AI-based CAs can be implemented successfully in the UK retail e-commerce context as a frontline self-service tool. The summary and the conclusions of the research objectives are as follows:

First Objective: To conduct a comprehensive and critical literature review on AI technology and AI-based conversational agents (text-based) in the UK and particularly in the UK retail e-commerce sector.

When it comes to investigating AI-based CAs implementation, it was imperative to understand what AI technology is, what an AI-based CA is, where CAs currently stand, and the future role of domain-specific CAs as a self-service tool. These constructs were explored as the first research objective to familiarise the reader with the main concepts relevant to the phenomenon of AI-based CAs implementation in the UK retail e-commerce sector. Although there were many subsets of AI as well as a heterogeneous set of tools and techniques, this section only covered the background concepts about the AI subsets and technology relevant to power CAs, which was essential to the current study under investigation.

Second Objective: To investigate customer service use case benefits of implementing AI-based conversational agents in the UK retail e-commerce sector.

CAs as a relatively new concept to the enterprise sector; before UK e-commerce retailers blindly invest money for the implementation, it is necessary to reflect upon the implementation benefits. Therefore, it was necessary to get in-depth knowledge about the benefits these CAs have to offer to the UK e-commerce retail organisations. By achieving this objective, this investigation led to a better understanding of available CAs` customer service capabilities and benefits that UK e-commerce retailers could consider when thinking of implementing an AI-based CA for the first time. The findings show that all the case study organisations have achieved several key benefits by implementing a CA as a customer service tool for their online shoppers. A summary of these benefits are: 1) 24/7 service availability, 2) better service agents` productivity, 3) faster information exchange, 4) sales growth and additional revenue stream by personalised recommendations and offers, 5) converse with international customers with their preferred language, 6) customer service cost reduction, 7) fewer customer complaints, 8) getting deeper customer insights, and 10) capture a broader target customer base.

Third Objective: To explore critical success factors (CSFs) and the success criteria that are significant in AI-based conversational agents` implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce sector.

A systematic approach was taken for the identification of available CSFs and success criteria from the existing literature. Based on the CSFs and success criteria identified in the literature review, a conceptual framework was developed in chapter two as a theoretical underpinning

for this research. The developed conceptual framework in figure 2.15 presented 16 CSFs under four categories which were organisational-related, data-related, technical-related, and governance-related factors. In addition, after reviewing the literature, DeLone, and McLean (2003)'s IS success model with more than 5000 citations in the field of information system/enterprise systems implementation success research provided a solid theoretical background to identify the success criteria for the purpose of the current study's CAs implementation. These three success criteria were 'information quality, system quality, and service quality'. It was concluded from the literature findings that there was a lack of scholarly work which focused on mapping the CSFs and success criteria on AI-based CAs implementation, particularly in the UK retail e-commerce context (Lo and Lee, 2017; Gnewuch, et al., 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019). This aspect of the study was considered to be the major contribution of the current study towards the existing literature in the field of AI-based CAs implementation success, especially for UK retail e-commerce sector.

After analysing the data gathered from semi-structured interviews, the revised conceptual framework was presented in chapter 6 (figure 6.1). This revised model presented 13 CSFs under three (organisational-related, technical-related, and governance-related) categories that are significant for AI-based conversational agents' implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce sector. The outcome of the study finding shown that six organisational CSFs that are significant for CAs implementation success. These CSFs are 'top management support, vendor selection, implementation strategy, funds and resource allocation, project management, and change management'. Technical CSFs of this study's findings are 'natural language processing, machine learning, data sharing and integration, human handover and CA analytics'. Governance-related CSFs of this study's findings are 'data privacy, system security, and transparency'. In addition, the critical factors identified under the CAs implementation success criteria are – sentiment analysis and knowledge base creation (under the 'information quality' success criteria); usability of the CA (under the 'system quality' success criteria); the personality of the CA (under the 'service quality success' criteria).

Fourth Objective: To investigate the major challenges the UK retail e-commerce organisations face during the process of AI-based conversational agents implementation.

Although the definition of success is subjective and varies based upon business to business when implementing an AI-based CA, there are some general barriers and challenges organisations may face during the implementation process that would hinder the

implementation success. Thus, the fourth objective aimed to investigate the main challenges the UK retail e-commerce organisations face when implementing a conversational agent as a frontline technology tool. The study findings show that organisations may face challenges under three main categories. These are organisational, technological, and governance-related challenges. According to the study findings, many managerial level participants had discussed vendor management-related challenges under organisational challenges. This vendor management related challenges were – top management`s lack of knowledge to choose the most suitable vendor and the SaaS CA platform; having to fully rely on their chosen vendor when making critical decisions regarding their CA; accommodating an effective relationship with the vendor; lack of transparency in some cases; conflict of ownership and not having a standard pricing model. Employee misconceptions and fear of employees losing jobs were highlighted under the organisational challenges. Data-related challenges such as data preparation, dialogue training, low-performance rate, integration complications, users` poor language use as challenges organisations were facing during the implementation process. Governance-related challenges were discussed under users` security concerns, organisations lack of knowledge about GDPR.

Objective Five: To provide a set of feasible recommendations on the CSFs of AI-based conversational agents implementation.

7.2 Recommendations

(1) Gather adequate knowledge about CAs without blindly follow the hype

Implementing an AI-based CA as a self-service tool to the UK e-commerce customer service context isn`t as easy as installing software. It requires an organisation-wide vision, reasons to justify why a complex technology like AI requires for the organisation, careful planning, expert knowledge, and various information sources that aren`t easily accessible. Thus, top managers of the UK retail e-commerce companies who wish to embark on a CA journey must have a clear idea of the AI capabilities of a CA, its benefits/challenges and limitations, how implementing a CA would contribute toward the organisation`s overall strategic goals, and the awareness of the changes a CA could bring to the organisation culture and its internal and external stakeholders.

(2) Choose the most suitable CA vendor/ implementation partner

One of the serious issues that hinder CAs implementation success is that organisations choosing SaaS 'off-the-shelf' CAs without any AI capabilities for deployment, with little or no customisation due to its low cost and easy to deploy options in the market. When UK retailers consider implementing a CA as a self-service FST, it is highly recommended to avoid the off-the-shelf easy to deploy option and focus on implementing a SaaS, customisable CAs (AI-based) or build in-house. To successfully implement an AI-based customisable CA or build from scratch in-house, UK retailers must focus on working with conversational AI implementation experts in the market who has a proven client portfolio of previous implementation success stories in the same industry and similar use cases.

(3) Start with a clear implementation strategy

Defining a clear strategy during the planning stage with the project team have a higher possibility to achieve CAs implementation success. During the strategy discussions, do not focus on transforming the entire customer service process to automate. As the initial step, choose a narrow scope by prioritising the highly popular, simple, and repetitive tasks for the self-service CA to perform. However, the focal point has to be on to deliver an impressive user experience by training the CA to perform the selected tasks exceptionally well. AI-based CAs improve their efficiency and capabilities with live user experience. Thus, the focus has to be on gradually expanding the CA capabilities and scope after the launch, not during the implementation. In addition, when setting up an implementation strategy, it is critical to identify the most suitable platform to launch the CA (i.e. company website, Facebook, company App) where the company can meet its target audience. It is also important to plan well ahead of areas such as data preparation, usability testing, allocating enough time and resources for the implementation, and the CA's continuous improvements both during and after the launch when setting up the implementation strategy.

(4) Integrate NLP, ML, and sentiment analysis to the CA

When implementing a self-service CA to partially automate the customer service tasks previously done by human employees in a retail e-commerce setting, these CAs must have the capability to provide a high-quality user experience. NLP has been identified as the heart of an AI-based CA as integrating NLP helps a CA to interpret, comprehend, and then decide the most appropriate action to be taken next for a user request. ML allows the CA to learn intuitively from data to produce intelligent responses for user requests without being explicitly

programmed after the launch. Integrating sentiment analysis in a CA helps the system extract positive or negative polarity expressed in a written text by a user during a conversation and measure the user-CA interaction's satisfaction level. During self-service counter interactions, customers are more often reluctant to share their sentiments with firms. Therefore, companies must have a way to instantly recognise dissatisfied customers through sentiment analysis to react fast enough to respond to unhappy customers in order to avoid a bad self-service CA experience. Failure to integrate these three AI subsets and capabilities in CAs have been identified as the main reason many CAs fail a few months after the launch, and organisations abandon their CAs when the system couldn't deliver high quality and a seamless customer self-service experience.

(5) CAs knowledge base creation

The knowledge base has defined as the 'brain' of a CA. Although the noticeable element of a CA is AI technology, the 'content' that generates the responses and information during a conversation also plays a significant role in enhancing the CA's quality and delivering a seamless user experience. Therefore, when implementing an AI-based CA, UK retail e-commerce organisations must consider providing various data sources for the CA to generate context-specific, intelligent responses to the user queries. Depending on self-service tasks, the knowledge base of a CA must be created with company-specific dynamic data sets in addition to integrating the system to the company's CRM, ERP, and public customer service databases to enhance the CAs information response quality. When creating company-specific content for a customer service CA, organisations can gather data from company data sources (structured, semi-structured and unstructured) such as – live chats history, telephone conversations, email conversations, and social media comments. However, data sets gathered from these data sources must be cleaned and prepared before integrating into the knowledge base to enable the CA to produce accurate and quality responses.

(6) Project management and project handover

Consider hiring a dedicated project manager with a domain expert project team to deliver the implementation success as conversational AI technology is still a new and evolving technology in the enterprise context. Focus on choosing the project team members such as CA developers, copywriters, and conversational flow designers based upon the scope and the complexity of the CA's self-service tasks the company wants to automate. Focus on adding well-experienced customer service team leaders and service agents to work with the project team members and

don't wholly rely on CA experts or technology team members to ensure project success. The managers and key customer service employees of e-commerce retailers have extensive knowledge about their business model and the target customer expectations inside and out. Therefore, using internal customer service experts to work closely with the project team will bring valuable insights regarding the company and the customers that would contribute to customise the CA unique to the organisation's specific needs. Also, start planning a successful project handover to the IT team by documenting relevant processes and preparing IT team members from the beginning of the implementation phase to manage the CA's daily monitoring and tasks maintenance after the launch.

(7) Define the personality of the CA

A CA is not only a technical tool in customer service, as what the customer is seeing or experiencing is the personality of a CA. When a customer is messaging to a CA, they are messaging with the company, and the way they receive the CA is the way they see the company. Focusing on the branding aspect effectively helps the target users to recognise, remember the CA as a high-quality self-service tool, and come back to use its services. Thus, when implementing a CA, focus on defining the CA's character by incorporating the branding guidelines and the tone of the company while addressing the target customers' persona. It's also vital that organisations pay close attention to understanding the target audience's demographics when defining the CAs personality.

(8) Usability testing

Usability testing is a crucial factor in ensuring a CA implementation success. It helps to discover viewpoints, requirements, and users' level of satisfaction with the self-service CA experience before the launch from the target users. All the test feedback then must be incorporated to make the necessary system quality improvements before the launch.

(9) Keep a human service agent in the loop

There are always many situations when CAs simply cannot complete all the user queries receive from customers. While CAs can efficiently and effectively address some tasks, it is essential to focus on having the human handover option in a CA to avoid frustrating situations during a conversation. A seamless handover of a user query to a service agent helps organisations to build trust towards the CA and a positive user experience.

(10) Manage the change

Take an extra effort to get employees to work collaboratively with the CA and focus on coming up with strategies on how to encourage the target customer to use the CA as their first option to communicate with the company when they have customer service queries. Consider some of the customer service job redesign and create new job roles if required by recruiting full-time and part-time CA experts to improve the CA performance after the launch. Have a clear and concise communication strategy to reduce employee misconceptions about AI technology and overcome employee resistance to adapt to changes that come after the launch. The focus has to be on augmenting the customer service agents' capabilities while collaboratively working with a CA to enhance productivity, not replacing them with a customer service CA.

(11) The governance of the CA

When implementing a CA powered by AI, organisations focus on CA's data protection, transparency, and system security must be a top priority as the project focus must go beyond cost and efficiency gains. Organisations must be responsible for determining how an AI-based CA can be adopted to capture its significant benefits while mitigating the risks to avoid potential harms it could bring to their customers and society as a whole.

(12) Continuous improvements of the CA even after the launch

CAs projects do not just complete after the launch in contrast to many other IS projects. Implementation of an AI-based CA is a continuous process since, after completion of the implementation phase, the launch phase (post-implementation phase) gets started. Therefore, organisations must provide equal attention during both these phases to ensure a CA project implementation success. A CA's success primarily depends on how well the system performs after the launch, and the most challenging part of an AI-based CA project begins after the launch as solving customer service queries effectively and efficiently is the ultimate goal of self-service CA implementation. Closely monitor the CA's analytics dashboards, expand the knowledge base when recognising new user intents, and allocate continuous resources/funds/attention after the launch to enhance ML. NLP and sentiment analysis capabilities are essential to ensure CAs implementation success.

7.3 Research Contributions

This research provides both research contributions from a theoretical perspective and a practical business perspective.

7.3.1 Contributions to theory

The general outcomes of this study have contributed and extended the existing body of knowledge in the field of AI-based CAs implementation in a number of ways, and these specific contributions to theory are as follows:

First: Although the existing literature provides various discussions about the AI-based CAs adoption in management research, it provides limited information on its implementation success. In addition, the research in the AI-based CAs implementation spectrum has primarily centred on the technical, computer science, and human-computer interaction related fields primarily related to the AI-powered voice-based CAs (such as Siri, Alexa, Google Assistant). However, there`s limited availability of literature about implementing AI-powered text-based CAs as a frontline self-service tool successfully from a business and organisational perspective. Therefore, this study is one of the very few studies investigating AI-powered, text-based CAs implementation success and is the first study of its kind in the UK retail e-commerce context.

Second: While there are a few studies available regarding AI systems implementation CSFs in general, those identified CSFs are highly inconsistent. Common characteristics of all these studies are, a) these studies are not only restricted to AI-based CAs implementation, b) the CSFs affecting AI-powered, text-based CAs implementation success in the context of UK retail e-commerce customer service setting has not yet been examined, c) the existing studies have used different sets of CSF variables using different backgrounds, and thus the findings seem subjective and isolated. Therefore, as a significant contribution to the theory, this study extends the current CSFs literature into a novel concept of AI-powered, text-based CAs implementation CSFs particularly focusing on the UK retail e-commerce customer service context. This study enriches existing knowledge by identifying 13 CSFs under three main categories (organisational, technical, and governance categories). This is one of the first academic studies to highlight such a comprehensive set of CSFs explicitly focusing on enhancing the organisation`s level of understanding towards AI-based CAs implementation success, not only in the UK but also in retail e-commerce customer service contexts in other developed countries.

Third: When determining the AI-powered, text-based CAs implementation success, only identifying the relevant CSFs is not adequate. The quality dimensions of a CA also play a significant role to ensure implementation success. Although there was an extensive number of studies have been discussed how DeLone and McLean (2003)'s IS success model's three quality dimensions can be applicable for other IS implementations (such as ERP, CRM, cloud systems), there were limited studies in the literature that have discussed how these quality dimensions can be applied for CAs implementation success, specifically in the retail e-commerce customer service context. This is one of the first academic studies to highlight a comprehensive set of CAs implementation success criteria under D & M models' three quality dimensions that can be applied to the UK e-commerce market and other customer self-service uses cases in different industries in the UK.

Fourth: The field of AI-based CAs implementation as an academic discipline in the organisational context is new and still evolving. While AI-based customer service CAs benefits and its implementation-related challenges have been widely discussed related to retail e-commerce context in white papers, online forums, trade magazines, and yet to date, little or no comprehensive research can be found with respect to the phenomenon under investigation. Therefore, by investigating the customer service-related benefits e-commerce retailers can achieve by implementing CAs and general challenges e-commerce retailers highly likely might face during the implementation, this study provides another significant perspective to increase the overall body of knowledge on AI-powered, text-based CAs implementation success.

Fifth: Methodologically, this research adopted an interpretivist philosophy, employing qualitative and multiple case study strategy approaches, which were not often used in the existing AI implementation related studies. As the AI-based CAs implementation from an organisational perspective is still new and evolving, the researcher aimed to gain an in-depth understanding of this less-explored phenomenon under investigation. Thus, multiple cases represented replication of evidence that allowed for the development of rich theoretical understanding, new insights, and in-depth description (Johannesson and Perjons, 2014; Yin, 2017) for the research objectives. While the quantitative method could provide concrete, measurable understanding for this research, the qualitative approach allowed the researcher to gain an in-depth and more profound understanding to achieve the research objectives. Therefore, by adopting this methodology, the present study has strengthened the research outcome.

Six: AI-based CAs customer service use cases are not only restricted to the UK retail sector. The study findings of 13 CSFs under three categories, the success criteria, and the implementation challenges, can also be replicated as a general set of guidelines for organisations in relation to other AI-based CAs implementation customer self-service use cases such as `Insurance and healthcare` due to the limited literature availability.

7.3.2 Contribution to Practice

In addition to the above reflected theoretical contribution, this research also contributes to the practices of the UK retail e-commerce customer service context in several ways. These specific contributions to practice are as follows:

First: As mentioned in chapter one, despite technical advances, at this early stage of AI-powered, text-based CAs implementations frequently fail within a few months after the launch. One of the reasons for such failures is that many e-commerce retailers are currently choosing “off the shelf” CAs (without any AI in the system) due to the lack of knowledge about conversational AI technology. As a result, companies are forced to abandon their CAs a few months after the launch when they get complaints from frustrated customers. Therefore to address this issue, this study provides practitioners with guidelines and recommendations for a successful CAs implementation process in: 1) identifying the most suitable customer self-service use case objective; 2) determining the most suitable conversational AI implementation partner; 3) determining the most appropriate implementation strategy; 4) providing the fundamental knowledge about AI features and capabilities that should be integrated when introducing a self-service CA to enhance their customers' shopping experience; 5) determining the change management strategies, 6) the role and responsibilities UK retail e-commerce organisations have to maintain to ensure the governance, 8) how to improve the CAs performance after the launch.

Second: This study provides in-depth knowledge for the top managers of the UK retail companies who wish to implement CAs about available AI-powered, text-based CAs customer service capabilities and their benefits, and also how to avoid the general challenges they may face during the implementation process that may hinder the implementation success.

Third: The UK has been identified as the biggest retail e-commerce market in Europe. Customer service challenges in the UK e-commerce context are evolving every day due to rapid market expansion after the COVID-19 pandemic. The empirical results of the research

finding related to the CAs implementation benefits, CSFs, success criteria, and the challenges to avoid could directly contribute to shed light on a successful CA implementation. Hence, this, in turn, would increase the UK's overall conversational AI competence to address evolving customer service challenges that the UK e-commerce organisations face.

7.4 Future Directions and Limitations of the Research

This study had addressed some important questions with respect to the phenomenon of AI-based conversational agents' implementation success and made several significant contributions as discussed in the above section. Although the empirical findings of this study are promising and valuable, a few limitations have been recognised which might be useful for other researchers to consider in future studies. This study offers scope for future research and raises some questions as this study is probably the first of its kind within the area of the AI-powered CAs (text-based) implementation CSFs and success criteria presented in one model. The model that emerged is still in a formative stage and future work could be done to further refine the relationships of the identified CSFs and success criteria to increase its explanatory power. These three CSF categories and 13 CSFs identified in this research have to be taken into account when implementing an AI-based CA as each of these factors impacts differently, but equally, on the implementation success. If they are not all integrated into one level, the implementation will not be successful and will not be able to fulfil the perceived benefits (at least up to some extent). However, as this is one of the early academic studies that attempted to identify a comprehensive set of CSFs in the identified context to fill the literature gap, investigating the range of functionality/success evaluation of these identified CSFs could be something that needs to be addressed in future research.

In addition, this study was only focusing on the implementation phase, not the entire implementation cycle (which includes the pre-implementation and post-implementation phases) due to the limited literature availability, lack of time, and resources. As this study findings indicate, to ensure CAs implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context, the post-implementation stage plays a significant role. This limitation can be covered in future research, and further research addressing the CAs implementation success by focusing on the entire implementation cycle could be beneficial to fill this literature gap. Another limitation of this study was not incorporating these organisations 'target CA users views' (who are using the CA) during the data collection as this research was conducted from

an organisational and management perspective. However, this limitation can be covered in a future study by focusing on CA's implementation success from a user perspective.

Furthermore, the case studies of this research were based on the UK retail e-commerce sector and the study participants were from UK organisations. Although these results can be generalisable for similar customer self-service use cases in other industries within the UK, these results may not be representative of other countries as the sample size, location, and characteristics of the respondents are not representative of the organisations in other countries that have implemented CAs successfully. As stated in the literature chapter, AI-based CAs implementation is a relatively new research topic, rendering the available CSFs, success criteria, and theory inadequate. This leads to the adoption of an exploratory approach that required a widespread literature review and collect an extensive amount of data to achieve the research objectives and empirically validate the research model.

Due to the holistic approach taken for this research, it is not possible to claim that the study has captured all the CSFs, success criteria or exposed all the CAs implementation benefits and challenges in the UK retail e-commerce context. This is due to various constraints including, but not limited to, lack of resources, data collection challenges experienced during the COVID-19 lockdowns, limited access to organisational information. Moreover, although all the efforts were made to ensure the quality of data captured from interview participants, concerns remain that some information may have been obscured or withheld, meaning that data should not be regarded as unbiased or complete. Therefore, for the reasons outlined above, the generalisability of the conclusions may be limited. A potential improvement to the study in future research would involve a larger sample size that would permit greater scope for the generalisation of the results.

7.5 Personal Reflection

My DBA journey at UWS was the most inspiring, rewarding, and challenging thing I have ever done all at once. I am grateful to have met the most amazing fellow researchers and professors at UWS and academic conferences, for the opportunity I got to engage with leading AI experts at some of the world's largest AI conferences and also to share the experience with some brilliant senior managers during the data collection process.

At the beginning of this study, I used to believe that AI-based CAs implementation was a simple undertaking, and yet this research has shifted my perception diametrically since Artificial Intelligence technology is an extremely complex subject. As a researcher coming

from a business management background, in the beginning, I had to allocate extra six months to comprehend different components of AI subsets and then to gain an in-depth understanding of the technical aspects of AI-powered text-based CAs due to its complexity and infancy nature when it comes to this technology`s organisational wide adoption and implementation. This in-depth learning experience of AI has thus given me an opportunity to stand back from the traditional business and managerial approaches, and to think of innovative ways on how AI could be utilised to unlock the plethora of benefits this technology has to offer.

Throughout the thesis writing, I also learned a great deal about my academic writing from my supervisor`s comments and discussions. Writing almost five drafts of the literature chapter was the most challenging task and took the longest time of this entire thesis given the lack of literature availability under the research topic during the first two years.

Although my experience with respondents yielded more learning on the research topic, it was not an easy task to persuade people to express their views and share their experiences during the interviews. I also found it harder than expected to get access to organisations for data collection as there were considerably a few organisations in the UK retail e-commerce sector that have managed to implement AI-based CAs successfully during the data collecting period. More data collection disruptions occurred when the entire country was on lockdown during the first COVID-19 wave. Lastly, I believe my DBA results of this study have provided a contribution to knowledge as a starting point for future researchers to explore further of this less explored phenomenon.

7.6 References

- Abdul-Kader, SA and Woods, JC. (2015) 'Survey on Chatbot Design Techniques in Speech Conversation Systems.' *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 6 (7). ISSN 2156-5570.
- Abran, A., Khelifi, A., Suryan, W., and Seffah, A. (2003) Consolidating the ISO usability models. In *Proceedings of 11th international software quality management conference*. 2 (2), pp. 23-25.
- Adamopoulou, E., Moussiades, L. (2020) 'An Overview of Chatbot Technology In: Maglogiannis I., Iliadis L., Pimenidis E. (eds) *Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations. AIAI 2020. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology*, vol 584.
- Adam, M., Wessel, M. and Benlian, A. (2020). AI-based chatbots in customer service and their effects on user compliance. *Electronic Markets*.
- Adler, P. S., & Kwon, S., W. (2002) 'Social capital: Prospects for a new concept', *Academy of Management Review*, 27(1), pp.17–40.
- Adner, R., & Helfat, C., E. (2003) 'Corporate effects and dynamic managerial capabilities', *Strategic Management Journal*, 24(10), pp. 1011–1025.
- Akerkar, R. (2019) *Artificial Intelligence for Business*, Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.
- Akma, N., Hafiz, M., Zainal, A., Fairuz, M. and Adnan, Z. (2018) 'Review of Chatbots Design Techniques', *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 181(8), pp.7-10.
- AlHaddad, S., and Kotnour, T. (2015) 'Integrating the organizational change literature: a model for successful change', *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 28(2), pp.234-262.
- Al-hashmi, S.F., Salloum, S. A., and Mhamdi, C. (2019) 'Implementing Artificial Intelligence in the United Arab Emirates Healthcare Sector: An Extended Technology Acceptance Model', *International Journal of Information Technology and Language Studies (IJITLS)*, 3(3), pp.27-42.
- Ammirato, S., Francesco S., Alberto, F., Cinzia, R. (2019) 'A methodology to support the adoption of IoT innovation and its application to the Italian bank branch security context', *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 22 (1), pp.146-174.
- Ambergt M., Fischl F., Wiener M., (2005), *Background of Critical Success Factor Research*, Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nurnberg, Nurnberg.
- Amabile, T. (1983) *The Social Psychology of Creativity*. New York: Springer.
- Anand, S., Sinha, A., Tiwari, U., and Ray, S. (2017) 'Artificial Intelligence', *Literature Review The Centre for Internet and Society*.

- Anaya, L. (2016) 'Realizing Benefits From Enterprise Systems', Doctoral Dissertation, University of Agder.
- Anaya, L., Dulaimi, M., Abdallah, S., & Al-Mashari, M. (2015) 'An investigation into the role of enterprise information systems in enabling business innovation', *Business Process Management Journal*, 21(4), 771-790.
- Amabile, T. (1983) The social psychology of creativity: A componential conceptualization. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 45(2), pp.357-376.
- Applin, S. A., and Fischer, M. D. (2015) 'New technologies and mixed-use convergence: How humans and algorithms are adapting to each other In Technology and Society (ISTAS)', *2015 IEEE International Symposium on*, pp. 1-6. IEEE.
- Arora, S., Batra, K., and Singh, S. (2013) Dialogue System: A Brief Review. Punjab Technical University.
- Atkinson, R. D. (2013) Stop Saying Robots Are Destroying Jobs—They Aren't.
- Atwal, G., & Williams, A. (2009) 'Luxury brand marketing – The experience is everything', *Journal of Brand Management*, 16(5-6), pp.338-346.
- Ayanouz, S., Abdelhakim, B., and Benhmed, M. (2020) 'A Smart Chatbot Architecture based NLP and Machine learning for health care assistance', *Association for Computing Machinery*,
- Araujo, T. (2018). Living up to the chatbot hype: The influence of anthropomorphic design cues and communicative agency framing on conversational agent and company perceptions. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 85, pp.183-189.
- Bachate, R.. and Sharma, A. (2020) 'Acquaintance with Natural Language Processing for Building Smart Society', *E3S Web of Conferences*, 170, pp.02006.
- Bachman, L. F. (1998) Interfaces between second language acquisition and language testing research, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Baez, M., Daniel, F., Casati, F., and Benatallah, B. (2020) 'Chatbot integration in few patterns', *IEEE Internet Computing*, pp.1-1.
- Barrett, M., Davidson, E., Prabhu, J., and Vargo, S. L. (2015) 'Service Innovation in the Digital Age: Key Contributions and Future Directions', *MIS Quarterly*, (39:1), pp. 135-154.
- Baskerville, R.L., and Wood-Harper, A.T. (1996) 'A critical perspective on action research as a method for information systems research', *Journal Information Technology*, 11 (3), pp.235-246.
- Barat J. (1992) Scenario Playing for Critical Success Factor Analysis. In: *Journal of Information Technology*, 7, 12-19.
- Bayan, A., Shawar and Eric., Steven, A. (2005) 'Using corpora in machine learning chatbot systems', *Int. J. Corpus Linguist*, 10, 4 (2005), pp. 489–516.

- Beer, M., Eisenstat, A., and Spector, B. (1990) 'Why change programs don't produce change', *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 68 No. 6, pp. 158-166.
- Ben Mimoun, M. S., Poncin, I. and Garnier, M. (2016) 'Animated Conversational Agents and e-Consumer Productivity: The Roles of Agents and Individual Characteristics', *Information & Management (in press)*.
- Blaikie, N. (2007) *Approaches to social enquiry*, 2nd ed. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Blaikie, H. (2000) *Designing social research: the logic of anticipation*. Cambridge Malden, Blackwell, MA: Polity Press.
- Boinepelli, H. (2015) 'Applications of Big Data', *Journal of Big Data*, pp. 161-179.
- Brandtzaeg, P. B., and Folstad A. (2018) 'Chatbots: changing user needs and motivations', *The Digital Library*, Volume 25, pp. 38-43.
- Brandtzaeg, P., B., Heim, J., and Karahasanovic, A. (2011) 'Understanding the new digital divide—A typology of Internet users in Europe', *International Journal of Human Computer Studies*, 69, 3 (2011), pp. 123–138.
- Bridges, W., and NetLibrary, I. (2003) *Managing Transitions: Making the Most of Change*, 2nd ed. updated and expanded ed. Cambridge, MA: Da Capo.
- Bridgwater, A., Easen, N., Frary, M., Goodman, J., King, L. and Rossi, B. (2017) 'Artificial Intelligence for Business', *The Times*
- Bryman, A. (2012) 'Sampling in qualitative research. Social research methods', 4, pp. 415-429.
- Bryman, A. (2004) *Social Research Methods*, 2nded. New York: Oxford University Press Inc.
- Buchanan, B., G., (2005) 'A (Very) Brief History of Artificial Intelligence', *AI Magazine*, 26(4), pp.53.
- Bughin, J., Hazan, E., Ramaswamy, S., Chui, M., Allas, T., Dahlstrom, P., Henke, N., and Trench, M. (2017) 'Artificial Intelligence, The next digital frontier? McKinsey Global Institute'.
- Bullock, R.J. and Batten, D. (1985) 'It's just a phase we're going through: a review and synthesis of OD phase analysis', *Group and Organization Studies*, 10, December, pp. 383- 412
- Burnes, B. (2004) *Managing Change :A Strategic Approach to Organizational Dynamics*, 4th ed. Harlow: Prentice Hall.
- Buren, E.V., Chew B., Eggers, W. D. (2020) 'AI readiness for government, Are you ready for AI?', *A report from the Deloitte Centre for Government Insights*. Available: <https://www2.deloitte.com/za/en/pages/public-sector/articles/AI-Readiness-for-Government.html>. (Accessed: 15/4/2020).

- Cancel, D. and Gerhardt, D. (2019) *Conversational Marketing. Challenges, Opportunities, Technologies, Reference Architecture*, Springer Nature Switzerland, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons Inc, pp. 249-249.
- Cagliano, R., Caniato, F., and Spina, G. (2006). "The linkage between supply chain integration and manufacturing improvement programmes." *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 26 No.3, pp. 282-299.
- Cardona, D., Werth, O., Schönborn, S. and Breitner, M. (2019) 'A Mixed Methods Analysis of the Adoption and Diffusion of Chatbot Technology in the German Insurance Sector', *Twenty-fifth Americas Conference on Information Systems, Cancun*.
- Carroll, J., M., and Rosson, M., B. (1995) "Managing Evaluation Goals for Training." *Communications of the ACM*, 38 No.7, pp. 40-48.
- Chalhoub-Deville, M., and Deville, C. (2008) 'Utilizing psychometric methods in assessment. In E. Shohamy, and N. H. Hornberger (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of language and education*, 2 (7), pp. 211-224.
- Chatterjee, S., Ghosh, S. and Chaudhuri, R. (2020) 'Knowledge management in improving business process: an interpretative framework for successful implementation of AI-CRM-KM system in organizations', *Business Process Management Journal*, ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print).
- Chakrabarti, C. and Luger, G. (2015) Artificial conversations for customer service chatter bots: Architecture, algorithms, and evaluation metrics. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(20), pp.6878-6897.
- Chen, J., Y., Procci, K., Boyce, M., Wright, A., Garcia, A, Barnes, M. (2016) 'Situation Awareness-Based Agent Transparency', *Tech. Rep. ARL-TR-6905, U.S.*, Army Research Laboratory.
- Chen, H. 'Success Factors Impacting Artificial Intelligence Adoption - Perspective From the Telecom Industry in China', (2019). Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation, Old Dominion University.
- Chong, A.Y.L., Ooi, K.B., Lin, B.S., and Raman, M. (2009) 'Factors affecting the adoption level of e-commerce: An empirical study', *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 50(2), pp. 13-22.
- Chung, M., Ko, E., Joung, H. and Kim, S. (2018) 'Chatbot e-service and customer satisfaction regarding luxury brands', *Journal of Business Research*.
- Clark, L., Pantidi, N., Cooney, O., Doyle, P., Edwards, D., Gilmartin, B., Murad, C., Munteanu, C., Wade, V., and Cowan, B. (2019) 'What Makes a Good Conversation?', *Challenges in Designing Truly Conversational Agents. In Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference*, Glasgow, Scotland, UK.
- Clohessy, T. and Acton, T. (2019) 'Investigating the influence of organizational factors on blockchain adoption', *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 119 (7), pp.1457-1491.

- Cohen, D., and Lane, I. (2016) 'An oral exam for measuring a dialog system's capabilities', *In Proceedings of the Thirtieth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, pp. 835- 841. AAAI Press.
- Conboy, K., Kitzgerald, G., and Mathiassen, L. (2012) 'Qualitative Methods Research in Information Systems: Motivations, Themes, and Contributions'. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 21 (2), pp.133-118.
- Conner, D. (1998) *Leading at the Edge of Chaos: How to Create the Nimble Organization*, New York, NY: John Wiley.
- Creswell, J., (2009) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crotty, M. (1989). *The foundations of social research*. London: Sage
- Cummings, T.,G., and Huse, E.,F. (1989) *Organization Development and Change*, 4th ed. St Paul: West Publishing Co.
- Cui, L., Huang, S., Zhou, M. (2017) SuperAgent: A Customer Service Chatbot for E-commerce Websites: *Proceedings of the 55th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics-System Demonstrations*, pp.97–102.
- Das, S., Dey, A., Pal, A., and Roy, N. (2015) 'Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Machine Learning: Review and Prospect', *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 115(9), pp.31-41.
- Damanpour, F., and Schneider, M. (2006) 'Phases of the adoption of innovation in organizations: Effects of environment, organization and top managers', *British journal of Management*, Vol. 17 No. 3, pp. 215-236.
- Daugherty, P., and Wilson, H. (2018) *Human + machine*. Boston, Mass. Harvard Business Review Press.
- Davenport, T. H., & Ronanki, R. (2018) Artificial Intelligence for the Real World. *Harvard Business Review*, pp.108-116.
- Davis, F. D. (1986) 'A Technology Acceptance Model for Empirically Testing New End-User Information Systems: Theory and Results', Doctoral dissertation, USA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., Warshaw, P. R. (1989) 'User acceptance of computer technology: a comparison of two theoretical models', *Management Science*, 35(8), pp. 982-1003.
- DeLone, W., H., McLean, E.,R. (1992) 'Information systems success: the quest for the dependent variable', *Inf. Syst. Res.* 3(1), pp. 60–95 (1992).
- DeLone, W., H., McLean, E.,R. (2003) The DeLone and McLean Model of Information Systems Success: A Ten-Year Update. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 19(4), pp.9-30.

- Demirkan, H., and Delen, D. (2013), 'Leveraging the capabilities of service-oriented decision support systems: putting analytics and big data in cloud', *Decision Support Systems*, Vol. 55 No. 1, pp.412-421.
- Deng, L., and Liu, Y. (2018) *Deep Learning in Natural Language Processing*. Singapore: Springer Nature.
- Denzin, N. K., and Lincoln, Y. S. (1994) *Handbook of qualitative research*, London: Sage Publications.
- De Keyser, A., Verleye, K., Lemon, K.N., Keiningham, T.L. and Klaus, P. (2019) 'Moving the customer experience field forward: introducing the touchpoints, context, qualities (TCQ) nomenclature', *Journal of Service Research*.
- De Visser, E., J., Cohen, M., Freedy, A., Parasuraman, R., A. (2014) 'Design Methodology for True Cue Calibration in Cognitive Agents', *Presented at the Human-Computer Interaction International (HCII) 2014 Conference*, Crete, Greece, 25 June 2014.
- Dickson, B. (2019) 'Explainable AI; viewing the world through the eyes of neural networks'.
- Depietro, R., Wiarda, E. & Fleischer, M. (1990). The context for change: Organization, technology and environment. *The Processes of Technological Innovation*, 199(0): 151-175.
- Delen, D. (2013) Data, information and analytics as services. *Decision Support Systems*, 55(1), pp.359-363.
- Drucker, P. (1985) *Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Practice and Principles*. Public Productivity Review, 10(1), p.105.
- Duan, Y., Edwards, J. and Dwivedi, Y. (2019) Artificial intelligence for decision making in the era of Big Data – evolution, challenges and research agenda. *International Journal of Information Management*, 48, pp.63-71.
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Hughes, L., Ismagilova, E., Aarts, G., Coombs, C., Crick, T., Williams, M. (2019) 'Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice and policy', *International Journal of Information Management*.
- Eeuwen, M. (2017) 'Mobile conversational commerce: messenger chatbots as the next interface between businesses and consumers', Master's thesis, University of Twente.
- Elish M. C. & Boyd D. (2018) 'Situating methods in the magic of Big Data and AI', *Communication Monographs*, 85:1, pp. 57-80.
- Everett, J., Pizarro, D., and Crockett, M. (2017) 'Why are we reluctant to trust robots?', Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/science/head-quarters/2017/apr/24/why-are-we-reluctant-to-trustrobots>. (accessed 16/11/2020).
- Fadhil, A. (2018) 'Can a Chatbot Determine My Diet?', *Addressing Challenges of Chatbot Application for Meal Recommendation*. University of Trento Trento, Italy.

- Fadhil, A., and Gabrielli, S. (2017) 'Addressing Challenges in Promoting Healthy Lifestyles: The AI-Chatbot Approach', *Association for Computing Machinery*, Barcelona, Spain.
- Fang, H., Cheng, H., Sap, M., Clark, E., Holtzman, A., Choi, Y., Smith, N. and Ostendorf, M. (2018) 'Sounding Board: A User-Centric and Content-Driven Social Chatbot', *NAACL HLT 2018*, p. 96.
- Fang H. (2019) 'Building A User-Centric and Content-Driven Socialbot', PhD Thesis, University of Washington, Washington.
- Feine, J., Morana, S., and Gnewuch, U. (2019) 'Measuring Service Encounter Satisfaction with Customer Service Chatbots using Sentiment Analysis', *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Institute of Information Systems and Marketing (IISM), Karlsruhe, Germany*, 14th International Conference on Wirtschaftsinformatik.
- Fink, J. (2012) 'Anthropomorphism and Human Likeness in the Design of Robots and Human-Robot Interaction', pp. 199-208.
- Fisher, B. (2020) Pandemic Pushes UK Retail Ecommerce Past 30% of Total Retail Sales in 2020, Available at: <https://www.emarketer.com/content/pandemic-pushes-uk-retail-ecommerce-past-30-of-total-retail-sales-2020>. (Accessed: 03/01/2021).
- Fichman, R., Dos Santos, B. and Zheng, Z. (2014) Digital Innovation as a Fundamental and Powerful Concept in the Information Systems Curriculum. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(2), pp.329-343.
- Flick, U. (2014) *An introduction to qualitative research*. 5th ed. London: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Floridi L (2003) *Blackwell Guide to the Philosophy of Computing and Information*, Oxford: Blackwell, 155-166.
- Følstad, A., Brandtzæg, P., B. (2017) 'Chatbots and the new world of HCI', *Interactions*, 24(4), pp. 38–42.
- Forbes (2017) 'How Chatbots improve customer experience in every industry: An infograph', Available from: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/blakemorgan/2017/06/08/how-chatbots-improve-customer-experience-in-every-industry-an-infograph/#2162528867df> (Accessed on: 24/6/2020).
- Forbes (2018) Britain Spins A Big, Bold Investment In A.I. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/parmyolson/2018/04/26/britain-spins-a-big-bold-investment-in-a-i/>: (Accessed: 20/03/2020).
- Følstad, A., Brandtzæg, P.B. (2017) 'Chatbots and the new world of HCI', *Interactions*, 24(4), pp. 38–42.
- Frascaroli, M. (2019) 'Omnichannel Chatbot', *Why Should You Implement It in Your Business*, Available at: <https://www.business2community.com/customer-experience/omnichannel-chatbot-why-should-you-implement-it-in-your-business-02225559>, (Accessed: 05/12/2021).
- IBM. (2018) 'Beyond the hype: A guide to understanding and successfully implementing artificial intelligence within your business',

Available at: <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/8ZDXNKQ4>, (Accessed: 20/19/2019).

French, W., L., and Bell, C. (1984) *Organization Development: Behavioural Science Interventions for Organization Improvement*. 3rd ed. Englewood Cliffs: NJ Prentice-Hall.

Oswald A. J., Mascarenhas, S.J. (2018) ‘Artificial Intelligence and the Emergent Turbulent Markets: New Challenges to Corporate Ethics Today’, *In Corporate Ethics for Turbulent Markets*, Emerald Insight, pp. 215-242.

Galpin, T.,J. (1996) *The Human Side of Change: A Practical Guide to Organization Redesign*, 1st ed. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass Publishers.

Gao, J., Galley, M. and Li, L. (2019) ‘Neural Approaches to Conversational AI. Foundations and Trends’, *in Information Retrieval*, 13(2-3), pp.127-298.

Gates, (2020) *Artificial Intelligence (AI): The Future of Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Neural Networks and Computer Super intelligence*.

Gartner, (2018) ‘Applying Artificial Intelligence to Drive Business Transformation: A Gartner Trend Insight Report’, pp. 2-7.

Goodman, B., and Flaxman, S. (2016) ‘EU regulations on algorithmic decision-making and a “right to explanation”, In ICML workshop on human interpretability in machine learning (WHI 2016), New York, NY. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1606.08813> v1.

Giebelhausen, M., Robinson, S., Sirianni, N. and Brady, M. (2014) Touch versus Tech: When Technology Functions as a Barrier or a Benefit to Service Encounters. *Journal of Marketing*, 78(4), pp.113-124.

Gnewuch, U., Morana, S., and Maedche, A. (2017) ‘Towards Designing Cooperative and Social Conversational Agents for Customer Service, Short Paper, to appear in: Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS).

Gunasekare, T. P. (2015) ‘Mixed Research Method as the Third Research Paradigm: A Literature Review, *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*.

Gupta, N. (2017) ‘A Literature Survey on Artificial Intelligence’, *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*, 5(19).

Griol, D., Carbo, J., & Molina, J. M. (2013) ‘An automatic dialog simulation technique to develop and evaluate interactive conversational agents’, *Applied Artificial intelligence*, 27(9), pp.759-780.

Gwaka, A., Gidion, O., and Mayianda, R. (2016) ‘Organisational Change: A Critical Review of the Literature’, *International Journal of Professional Management*, 11(2).

Hacking, I. (1982) ‘Biopower and the avalanche of printed numbers’, *Humanities in Society*, 5, pp.279 – 295.

Hall, D., W. and Pesenti, J. (2018) ‘Growing the Artificial Intelligence industry in the UK: Available:<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attach>

ment_data/file/652097/Growing_the_artificial_intelligence_industry_in_the_UK.pdf:
(Accessed: 21/3/ 2020).

Hameed, M.A., Counsell, S., and Swift, S. (2012) 'A conceptual model for the process of IT innovation adoption in organizations', *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, Vol. 29 No.3, pp. 358-390.

Hameed, M.A., Counsell, S., and Swift, S. (2012) 'A meta-analysis of relationships between organizational characteristics and IT innovation adoption in organizations', *Information & management*, Vol. 49 No. 5, pp. 218-232.

Harrison, L.,M. (2011) "Transformational leadership, integrity, and power", *New Directions for Student Services*, No. 135, pp. 45-52.

Hayes, B., and Shah, J. A. (2017) 'Improving robot controller transparency through autonomous policy explanation', in *Proceedings of the 12th ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction*.

Helfat, C., E., & Martin, J., A. (2015) 'Dynamic managerial capabilities: Review and assessment of managerial impact on strategic change', *Journal of Management*, 41(5), pp.1281–1312.

Hien, H.,T., Cuong, P.N., Nam, L.N.H., Nhung, H.L.T.K., Thang, L.D. (2018) 'Intelligent assistants in higher-education environments: the FIT-EBot, a chatbot for administrative and learning support. In: Proceedings of the Ninth International Symposium on Information and Communication Technology, pp. 69–76.

Hill, J., Ford, W. R., and Farreras, I. G. (2015) 'Real Conversations with Artificial Intelligence: A Comparison between Human-Human Online Conversations and Human-Chatbot Conversations', *Computers in Human Behaviour*, (49), pp. 245–250.

Hoang, D., Barnes, C., & Munroe, O. (2019) 'Management of traditional retail markets in the UK: comparative case studies. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*', 47(5), pp. 530–551.

Holtgraves, T.M., Ross, S.J., Weywadt, C.R., and Han, T.L. (2007) 'Perceiving artificial social agents', *Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 23 No. 5, pp. 2163-2174.

Hoon, G. K., Yong, J, L. and Yang G. K. (2020) 'Interfacing Chatbot with Data Retrieval and Analytics Queries for Decision Making', Springer Nature Singapore, pp.385-394.

Hotek, D.,R., and White, M.,R. (1999) 'An overview of performance technology', *Journal of Technology Studies*, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 43-50.

House, W. (2016) 'Artificial Intelligence, Automation, and the Economy. Executive office of the President', Available at: <https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/whitehouse.gov/files/documents/ArtificialIntelligence-Automation-Economy>, PDF.

Huang, M. and Rust, R. (2020) 'Artificial Intelligence in Service', *Journal of Service Research*, 21(2), pp.155-172.

Huang, M., Zhu, X., and Gao, J. (2020) 'Challenges in Building Intelligent Open-domain Dialog Systems', *ACM Transactions on Information Systems*, 38(3), pp.1-32.

Huang, G., Kurnia, S. and Linden, T. (2018). A study of Critical Success Factors for Enterprise Systems Implementation by SMEs, Twenty-Second Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems, Japan.

IDRC (2019) AI readiness Available at: <https://www.oxfordinsights.com/ai-readiness2019>: (Accessed: 20/03/2020).

Igo, S. (2007) 'The averaged American: Surveys, citizens, and the making of a mass public', Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA.

Ikumoro, A., and Jawad, M. (2019) 'Intention to Use Intelligent Conversational Agents in e-Commerce among Malaysian SMEs: An Integrated Conceptual Framework Based on Tri-theories including Unified Theory of Acceptance, Use of Technology (UTAUT), and T-O-E', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(11).

Ikumoro, A. and Jawad, M. (2019) 'Assessing Intelligence Conversation Agent Trends-Chatbots-AI Technology Application for Personalized Marketing', *TEST Engineering and Management*, 81, pp.4779 - 4785.

Jablonska M., Polkowski Z. (2017) 'Studies & Proceedings of Polish Association for Knowledge Management', Issue 86, pp.13-23.

Jacobs, D., and Snijders, H. (2008) 'Innovation routine: how managers can support repeated innovation', *Management Studies*

Jain, M. (2018) 'Evaluating and informing the design of chatbots', In Proceedings of the 2018 Designing Interactive Systems Conference. pp. 895–906.

Jarrahi, M.H. (2018) 'Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Work: Human-AI Symbiosis in Organizational Decision Making', *Business Horizons*, 61(4).

Johnson, P., and Clark, M. (2006) 'mapping the terrain: an overview of business and management research methodologies', *Business and Management Research Methodologies*, London: Sage.

Johannesson, P., Perjons E. (2014) Research Strategies and Methods. In: An Introduction to Design Science, Springer.

Jöhnk, J., Oesterle, S. and Ollig, P. (2020) The Complexity of Digital Transformation - Conceptualizing Multiple Concurrent Initiatives. *Conference: 15th International Conference on WirtschaftsinformatikAt: Potsdam*.

Kaganer, E., Pawlowski, S.D., and Wiley-Patton, S. (2010) 'Building legitimacy for IT innovations: the case of computerized physician order entry systems', *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 11 No. 1, pp. 1.

Katz, Y. (2017) Manufacturing an artificial intelligence revolution.

- Kuppelwieser, V. and Klaus, P. (2021) Measuring customer experience quality: The EXQ scale revisited. *Journal of Business Research*, 126, pp.624-633.
- Kendall, S. (2019) 'Selling via e-commerce in the U.K.', *A custom report compiled by Euro monitor International for the High Commission of Canada in the United Kingdom*, Available:https://www.tradecommissioner.gc.ca/guides/uk_e-commerce/commerce_electronique_ru.aspx?lang=eng (Accessed: 03/01/2021).
- Këpuska, V. and Bohouto, G. (2018) 'Next-Generation of Virtual Personal Assistants Microsoft Cortana, Apple Siri, Amazon Alexa and Google Home', *IEEE*, pp.99-103.
- Khurana, D., Koli, A., Khatter, K., Singh, S. (2017) Natural Language Processing: State of The Art, Current Trends and Challenges, *Computer Science> Computation and Language*, Available at:<https://arxiv.org/abs/1708.05148> (Accessed: 05/05/19).
- Klopfenstein L. C., Delpriori S., Ricci, A. (2019) 'Adapting a Conversational Text Generator for Online Chatbot Messaging', *Springer Nature*, Switzerland AG.
- Kolbjørnsrud, V., Amico, R., Thomas, R.J. (2017) 'Partnering with AI: how organizations can win over skeptical managers', *Strategy & Leadership*, 45(1), pp.37 – 43: Available at: <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/full/10.1108/SL-12-2016-0085>.
- Kousa E. (2019) 'Exploring Success Factors in Chatbot Implementation Projects', ARCAD, Master`s Thesis.
- Kumar, S. I. (2017) 'State of the art-intense review on artificial intelligence systems application in process planning and manufacturing', *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 65, pp. 294-329.
- Kurnia, S., Linden, T., and Huang, G. (2019) 'A hermeneutic analysis of critical success factors for Enterprise Systems implementation by SMEs', *Enterprise Information Systems*, 13(9), pp.1195-1216.
- Kröger, F. J., and Johansson, F. (2019) 'Conversational commerce: A quantitative study on preferences towards AI-Fueled c-commerce platforms among digital natives in Sweden and Germany', Master`s Thesis, Jonkoping University.
- Knijnenburg, B. and Willemsen, M. (2016) Inferring Capabilities of Intelligent Agents from Their External Traits. *ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems*, 6(4), pp.1-25.
- Lalonde, C. (2011) "Managing crises through organisational development: a conceptual framework", *Disasters*, 35 (2), pp. 443-464.
- Laney, D. (2001) '3D data management: Controlling data volume, velocity, and variety [Blog Post]', Gartner. Retrieved from <https://blogs.gartner.com/doug-laney/files/2012/01/ad9493D-Data-Management-Controlling-Data-Volume-Velocity-and-Variety.pdf>.
- Larivière, B., Bowen, D., Andreassen, T. W., Kunz, W., Sirianni, N. J., Voss, C., Wunderlich, N. V., and De Keyser, A. (2017) 'Service Encounter 2.0': An Investigation into the Roles of Technology, Employees and Customers', *Journal of Business Research*, (79), pp. 238–246.

- Lawnboy M. (2018) Chatbot Development Challenges – Part 1, Available from: <https://hackernoon.com/chatbot-development-challenges-part-1-bf472062be60>. (Accessed 10/5/2020).
- Lauterbach, J., Kahrau, F., Maedche, A., Mueller, B. (2013) ‘Reconceptualising enterprise systems’, In *Proceedings of IFIP 8.2 PreICIS workshop on organizations and society in information systems*, Milan.
- Leidecker, J. and Bruno, A. (1984). Identifying and using critical success factors. *Long Range Planning*, 17(1), pp.23-32.
- Lee, A.S. (1999) ‘Researching MIS, Rethinking Management Information Systems’, pp. 7-27. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lee, J., D., See, K., A. (2004) ‘Trust in Technology: Designing for Appropriate Reliance’, *Human Factors*, (2004, 46, 50–80).
- Lester, J., Branting, K. and Mott, B. (2004) ‘Conversational Agents. Practical Handbook of Internet Computing’, *CRC Press LL*.
- Lewin, K. (1951). *Field Theory in Social Science*. Harper and Row: New York.
- Liao, Q.,V., et al. (2018) ‘All work and no play?’, In: *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI 2018*. pp. 3:1–3:13. ACM, NY, USA.
- Liang, H., and Xue, Y. (2004) ‘Coping with ERP-Related Contextual Issues in SMEs: A Vendor's Perspective’, *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, (13:4), pp. 399-415.
- Li, L., Su, F., Zhang, W. and Mao, J. (2017) ‘Digital transformation by SME entrepreneurs: A capability perspective’, *Information Systems Journal*, 28(6), pp.1129-1157.
- Lin, C.Y., and Lin, J.S.C. (2017) ‘The influence of service employees’ nonverbal communication on customer-employee rapport in the service encounter’, *Journal of Service Management*, Vol. 28 No. 1, pp. 107-132.
- Lo, H. N., and Lee C.B. (2017) ‘Chatbots and Conversational Agents: A Bibliometric Analysis’, *Proceedings of the 2017 IEEE IEEM*.
- Lohr, S. (2015) *Less Noise but more money in data*, New York Times.
- Loonam, J., Kumar, V., Mitra, A., and AbdRazak, A. (2018) ‘Critical success factors for the implementation of enterprise systems’, A literature review, *Strategic Change*, 27(3), pp.185-194.
- Lohmühler, B. (2003) *Drivers of product innovation: an investigation of German manufacturing companies*. PhD, Cranfield University.
- Luger, E., and Sellen, A. (2016) “‘Like having a really bad PA’: The Gulf between User Expectation and Experience of Conversational Agents”, in *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, San Jose, CA, USA: ACM, pp. 5286–5297.

- Lynch, S. and Barnes, L., 2020. Omnichannel fashion retailing: examining the customer decision-making journey. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 24(3), pp.471-493.
- Manyika, J., Chui, M., Miremadi, M., Bughin, J., George, K., Willmott, P. and Dewhurst, M. (2017) 'A Future That Works: Automation, Employment, and Productivity', McKinsey Global Institute, Available at:<https://www.mckinsey.com/global-themes/digitaldisruption/harnessing-automation-for-a-future-at-works>.
- Margolis, P.,A., DeWalt, D.,A., Simon, J.,E., Horowitz, S., Scoville, R., Kahn, N., and Miles, P. (2010) "Designing a large-scale multilevel improvement initiative: the improving performance in practice program", *Journal of Continuing Education in the Health Professions*, Vol. 30 No. 3, pp. 187-196.
- Martin, J. A. (2011) 'Dynamic managerial capabilities and the multibusiness team: The role of episodic teams in executive leadership groups', *Organization Science*, 22(1), pp.118–140.
- Marshall, C. and Rossman, G.B. (1999) 'The "what" of the study: Building the conceptual framework', *Designing qualitative research*, 3, pp.21-54.
- McCull-Kennedy, J.R., Gustafsson, A., Jaakkola, E., Klaus, P., Radnor, Z.J., Perks, H. and Friman, M. (2015), 'Fresh perspectives on customer experience', *Journal of Services Marketing*, Vol. 29 Nos 6/7, pp. 430-435.
- McGoldrick, P., Keeling, K., and Beatty, S. (2008) 'A typology of roles for avatars in online retailing', *Journal of Marketing Management*, 24(3-4), pp. 433–461. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1362/026725708X306176>
- McTear, M., Callejas, Z., & Griol, D. (2016) 'The conversational interface: talking to smart devices', Cham: Springer.
- McKinsey and Company (2018) The state of fashion 2018. Retrieved from https://cdn.businessoffashion.com/reports/The_State_of_Fashion_2018_v2.
- Mercado, J., Rupp, M., Chen, J., Barnes, M., Barber, D. and Procci, K. (2016) 'Intelligent Agent Transparency in Human–Agent Teaming for Multi-UxV Management. Human Factors', *The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 58(3), pp.401-415.
- Meyer, A. D., Brooks, G.R. and Goes, J.B. (1990), "Environmental jolts and industry revolutions: organizational responses to discontinuous change", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 11 No. 4, pp. 93-110.
- Mergel, I., and Bretschneider, S., I. (2013) 'A three- stage adoption process for social media use in government', *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 73 No. 3, pp. 390-400.
- Mikko, R., Saarijärvi, H., Sarlin, P., and Lähteenmäki, I. (2018) 'Using artificial intelligence to create value in insurance', *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 36 Issue: 6, pp.1145-1168.

- Miller, T. (2019) 'Explanation in artificial intelligence: Insights from the social sciences', *Artificial Intelligence*, 267, pp.1-38.
- Miller, S. (2018) 'AI: Augmentation, more so than automation', *Asian Management Insights*, 5(1), pp. 1-20.
- Milward, H., B., and Provan, K.G. (1998) 'Measuring network structure. Public administration', 76 (2), pp.14-23.
- Mingers, J. (2001) Combining IS research methods: towards a pluralist methodology, *Information systems research*, 12 (3), pp.240-259.
- Miner, A., Chow, A., Adler, S., Zaitsev, I., Tero, P., Darcy, A., and Paepcke, A. (2016) 'Conversational Agents and Mental Health: Theory-Informed Assessment of Language and Affect', in *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Human Agent Interaction, Singapore*, pp. 123–130.
- Miner, A. S., Milstein, A., Schueller, S., Hegde, R., Mangurian, C., and Linos, E. (2016) 'Smartphone-based conversational agents and responses to questions about mental health, interpersonal violence, and physical health', *JAMA internal medicine*, 176(5), pp. 619-625.
- Mislevics A. J., Grundspenkis J., Rollande, R. (2018) 'A Systematic Approach to Implementing Chatbots in Organizations – RTU Leo Showcase', Available at: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2218/paper36.pdf>, (Accessed: 12/09/19)
- Mir, F. and Pinnington, A. (2014) Exploring the value of project management: Linking Project Management Performance and Project Success. *International Journal of Project Management*, 32(2), pp.202-217.
- Moen, R.,D., and Norman, C., L. (2010) *Circling Back, Quality Progress*.
- Mölsä, M. (2017) 'Success factors when implementing AI-powered marketing solutions, Degree thesis', *Business Information Technology*, Haaga-Helia, Helsinki.
- Moore, C. (2011) "The path to business process transformation", *KM World*, Vol. 20 No. 5, pp. 6-7.
- Morgan, B. (2017) '10 things robots can't do better than humans', Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/blakemorgan/2017/08/16/10-things-robots-cant-do-better-than-humans/#547f6ffcc83d>.
- Myers, M. D. (2013) *Qualitative Research in business and management*, USA: Sage.
- Myers, M. D. (2009) *Qualitative Research in Business and Management*, Los Angeles-London-New Deli-Singapore-Washington DC: Sage.
- Najafabadi M.M. et al. (2015) 'Deep Learning Techniques in Big Data Analytics', *Journal of Big Data*, 2(1), pp.1–21.

- Nwokike, C. (2018) 'Conversational Marketing 101: How Chatbots help Improve Customer Engagement', URL: <https://blog.netcoresmartech.com/conversational-marketing-101-howchatbots-help-improve-customer-engagement> (Accessed: 17/4/2020).
- Nuruzzaman, M. and Hussain, O. (2018) A Survey on Chatbot Implementation in Customer Service Industry through Deep Neural Networks. *IEEE 15th International Conference on e-Business Engineering (ICEBE)*, pp.54 - 61.
- Oates, B.J. (2005) *Researching information systems and computing*, London: Sage.
- Oberoi A. (2019) 'Off-the-Shelf or Custom Chatbot Development', *What does your business need?*, Available from: <https://insights.daffodilsw.com/blog/off-the-shelf-or-custom-chatbot-development-what-does-your-business-need> (Accessed 11/05/2020).
- OECD (2020) '*The Impact of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Insurance Sector*', Available at: www.oecd.org/finance/Impact-Big-Data-AI-in-the-Insurance-Sector.htm.
- Oldham, J. (2009) "Achieving large system change in health care", *JAMA: Journal of the American Medical Association*, Vol. 301 No. 9, pp. 965-966.
- Oliveira, T., and Martins, M. (2011) 'Literature review of information technology adoption models at firm level', *The Electronic Journal Information Systems Evaluation*, 14(1), pp.110-121.
- Oliver, S. (2014) Formal learning theory. In Edward N. Zalta, editor, *The Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy*. Spring edition. Available at: <http://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2014/entries/learning-formal/>. (Accessed: 18/5/2017).
- Onnasch, L., Wickens, C., Li, H. and Manzey, D. (2014). Human Performance Consequences of Stages and Levels of Automation. *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 56(3), pp.476-488.
- Oswald, FR., A., J., Mascarenhas, S.,J. (2018). 'Artificial Intelligence and the Emergent Turbulent Markets: New Challenges to Corporate Ethics Today', *In Corporate Ethics for Turbulent Markets*.
- Palmatier, R.W., Dant, R.P., Grewal, D., and Evans, K.R. (2006) 'Factors influencing the effectiveness of relationship marketing: a meta-analysis', *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 70 No. 4, pp. 136-153.
- Perez, S. (2016) 'Microsoft silences its new A.I. bot Tay, after Twitter users teach it racism', Available at: url: <https://techcrunch.com/2016/03/24/microsoft-silences-its-new-a-i-bot-tay-after-twitter-users-teach-it-racism/>; (Accessed: 21 May 2017).
- Piccolo, L., S., G., Roberts, S., Iosif, A., Alani, H. (2018) 'Designing chatbots for crises', *A case study contrasting potential and reality*, In *Proceedings of the British HCI Conference*. (Early Access), ACM, <http://oro.open.ac.uk/55325>; (Accessed:12/2/2019).
- Pickup, O. (2019) 'Are off-the-shelf AI tools a good idea?', Available from: <https://www.raconteur.net/technology/ai-tools-pre-built>, Accessed (11/05/2020).

- Pinto, J. and Slevin, D. (1987) Critical factors in successful project implementation. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, EM-34(1), pp.22-27.
- Pillai, R. and Sivathanu, B. (2020) 'Adoption of AI-based chatbots for hospitality and tourism', *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 32(10), pp.3199-3226.
- Plamen A. (2012) *Autonomous Learning Systems: From Data Streams to Knowledge in Real-time*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Porcheron, M., Fischer, J., E., Reeves, S., Sharples, S. (2018) 'Voice Interfaces in Everyday Life', In *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*.
- Pride, W.M., Ferrell, O.C., Lukas, B.A., Schembri, S., Niininen, O. and Casidy, R. (2018) *Marketing Principles*, 3rd Asia-Pacific ed., Cengage, pp. 449–50.
- Pryss, R., Kraft, R., Baumeister, H., Winkler, J., Probst, T., Reichert, M., Langguth, M., S., Schlee, W. (2018) 'Using Chatbots to Support Medical and Psychological Treatment Procedures:', *Challenges, Opportunities, Technologies, Reference Architecture*, Springer Nature Switzerland, pp. 249-249.
- PWC (2017) "How will artificial intelligence affect the UK economy?" Available: <https://www.pwc.co.uk/services/economics/insights/the-impact-of-artificial-intelligence-on-the-uk-economy.html>. (Accessed: 23/07/2020).
- Pandita, R., Bucuvalas S., Bergier, H., Chakarov, A., and Richards, E., (2018) 'Towards JARVIS for Software Engineering', *Lessons Learned in Implementing a Natural Language Chat Interface*, Workshop NLP Softw. Eng. AAI Conf. Artif. Intell.
- Radziwill, N., M., Benton, M., C. (2017) 'Evaluating quality of chatbots and intelligent conversational agents', Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1704.04579>, Accessed: (15/5/ 2019).
- Radujković, M. and Sjekavica, M. (2017) *Project Management Success Factors*. Creative Construction Conference 2017, CCC 2017, 19-22 June 2017, Primosten, Croatia, pp.608 - 613.
- Rahman, M. (2016) 'The Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches and Methods in Language "Testing and Assessment" Research: A Literature Review', *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(1), pp.102.
- Ram, A., Nagar A., King E., Bland, K., Wartick A., Pan, Y., Song H., Jayadevan, S., Hwang, G., and Pettigrew, A. (2018) *Conversational AI: The Science Behind the Alexa Prize*. CoRR abs/1801.03604.
- Ramezani R. (2014) 'An Artificial Intelligence Framework for Investigative Reasoning' PhD thesis.
- Ranavare, S., and Kamath, R. (2020) 'Artificial Intelligence based Chatbot for Placement Activity at College Using DialogFlow', *Our Heritage Journal*, 68(30), pp.4806-4814.
- Ransbotham, S., Gerbert P., Reeves, M., Kiron D., Spira, M. (2018) 'Artificial Intelligence In Business Gets Real; Pioneering Companies Aim for AI at Scale', *MITSloan Management Review*.

- Reeves, S. (2017) 'Some Conversational challenges of talking with machines', In Talking with Conversational Agents in Collaborative Action Workshop.
- Reshmi, S., K., B. (2018) 'Empowering chatbots with business intelligence by big data integration', *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 627– 631.
- Rese, A., Ganster, L. and Baier, D. (2020) 'Chatbots in retailers' customer communication: How to measure their acceptance?', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 56, pp.102176.
- Rialti, R., Marzi, G., Ciappei, C. and Busso, D. (2019) 'Big data and dynamic capabilities: a bibliometric analysis and systematic literature review', *Management Decision*, 57(8), pp.2052-2068.
- Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Nicholls, C.M., and Ormston, R. (2013) 'Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science researchers.', Sage.
- Robson, C. (2002) *Real World Research*, Oxford: Blackwell.
- Rogers, E., M. (1995) *Diffusion of Innovations*. New York: Free press.
- Rogers, E., M. (2003) *Diffusion of Innovations*, 5th Edition. New York: The Free Press.
- Rose, D. (2018) 'Artificial intelligence for business: What you need to know about Machine Learning and Neural Network', Beaverton: Chicago Lakeshore Press.
- Rockart, J. (1979) Chief Executives Define Their Own Information Needs. In: *Harvard Business Review*, March/April 1979, 81-92.
- Russel, S. and Norvig, P., 2003. *Artificial Intelligence, A Modern Approach*. 2nd ed. University of Michigan Press.
- Saad, M. (2000) *Development through Technology Transfer*, Bristol, UK: Intellect Books.
- Saad, M. (2004) 'Issues and challenges arising from the application of innovation strategies based on the triple helix culture', *International Journal of Technology Management & Sustainable Development*, 3(1), pp.17-34.
- Sabherwal, R., W. (2006) An empirical taxonomy of the decision-making processes concerning strategic applications of information systems. *J. Management Inform. Systems* 11(4)177–214
- Sarikaya, R. (2017) 'The Technology Behind Personal Digital Assistants: An Overview of the System Architecture and Key Components', *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, (34:1), pp. 67–81.
- Sathya, R., and Abraham, A. (2013) 'Comparison of Supervised and Unsupervised Learning Algorithms for Pattern Classification', *International Journal of Advanced Research in Artificial Intelligence*, 2(2).

Satista (2021) “Value of online retail sales in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2012 to 2020” Available:<https://www.statista.com/statistics/315506/online-retail-sales-in-the-united-kingdom>. (Accessed: 10/01/2021).

Salloum, S. and Al Emran, M. (2018) Factors affecting the adoption of e-payment systems by university students: extending the TAM with trust. *International Journal of Electronic Business*, 14(4), p.371.

Saraph, J., Benson, P. and Schroeder, R. (1989) An Instrument for Measuring the Critical Factors of Quality Management. *Decision Sciences*, 20(4), pp.810-829.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A. (2019) *Research Methods For Business Students*. 8th ed. UK: Pearson Education. pp. 122-161.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A. (2009) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 5th ed. UK: Pearson Education. pp.137-166.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2011) *Research methods for business students*, 6th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education.

Saunders, M., Thornhill, A., and Lewis, P. (2009) *Research Methods for Business Students*, England: Pearson education Limited.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A. (2007) *Research methods for business students*, 4thed. Harlow, England: Prentice Hall.

Sangar, A.B., and Lahad, N.B.A. (2013) Critical Factors That Affect the Success of Business Intelligence Systems (BIS) Implementation in an Organization. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, February, 2(2), 176-180.

Saxena, D., and J., McDonagh, (2017) ‘Yet Another ‘list of Critical Success ‘factors’ for Enterprise Systems: Review of Empirical Evidence and Suggested Research Directions’, Paper presented at the UK Academy of Information Systems Conference 2017, UK.

Sundaram, D.S., and Webster, C. (2000) ‘The role of nonverbal communication in service encounters’, *Services Marketing Journal of*, Vol. 14 No. 5, pp. 378-391.

Scherer, A., Wunderlich, N. V, and von Wangenheim, F. (2015) ‘The Value of Self-Service: Long-Term Effects of Technology-Based Self-Service Usage on Customer Retention’, *MIS Quarterly*, (39:1), pp. 177–200.

Schlögl, S., Postulka, C., Bernsteiner, R., and Ploder, C. (2019) ‘Artificial intelligence tool penetration in business, Adoption, challenges and fears Knowledge Management in Organizations, KMO 2019’, *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, pp. 259-270. Springer, Cham.

Schumpeter, J.A. (1942) *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*. Vol. 36, Harper & Row, New York, 132-145.

- Schuetzler, R., Grimes, M., Giboney, J. and Buckman, J. (2014) Facilitating Natural Conversational Agent Interactions: Lessons from a Deception Experiment. *Conference: International Conference on Information Systems*.
- Seaver, N. (2015) 'The nice thing about context is that everyone has it', *Media, Culture, and Society*, 37(7), pp.1101–1109
- Seddon, P. and Kiew, M. (1994) A Partial Test and Development of Delone and Mclean's Model of IS Success. *Australasian Journal of Information Systems*, 4(1).
- Seddon PB (1997) A respecification and extension of the DeLone and McLean model of IS success. *Information Systems Research* 8 (3), 240–253.
- Shah, H., Warwick, K., Vallverdú, J., and Wu, D. (2016) 'Can Machines Talk? Comparison of Eliza with Modern Dialogue Systems', *Computers in Human Behaviour*, (58), pp. 278–295.
- Shams, Z., Vos, de M. Padget, J., O. (2016) 'Normative practical reasoning via argumentation and dialogue', in: *Proceedings of the 25th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI – 16)*, AAAI Press.
- Shaw, J., Rudzicz, F., Jamieson, T. and Goldfarb, A. (2020) 'Artificial Intelligence and the Implementation Challenge', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 21(7).
- Shaw, J., Rudzicz, F., Jamieson, T., & Goldfarb, A. (2019) 'Artificial Intelligence and the Implementation Challenge' *JOURNAL OF MEDICAL INTERNET RESEARCH*.
- Shawar, B. A., and Atwell, E. (2007) 'Chatbots: Are they really useful?', *LDV-Forum* (22:1), pp. 29–49.
- Shevat, A. (2017) *Designing bots*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.
- Sidaoui, K., Jaakkola, M., and Burton, J. (2020) 'AI feel you: customer experience assessment via chatbot interviews', *Journal of Service Management*, 31(4), pp.745-766.
- Silverman, D. (2015) *Interpreting qualitative data*, London: Sage.
- Simon, J. (2019) 'Artificial intelligence: scope, players, markets and geography', *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance*, 21(3), pp.208-237.
- Singh, S., and Srivastava, S. (2019) 'Engaging consumers in multichannel online retail environment', *Journal of Modelling in Management*, 14(1), pp.49-76.
- Singh, S., Darbari, H., Bhattacharjee, K., Verma, S. (2016) 'Open source NLG systems: a survey with a vision to design a true NLG system', **9**, pp.4409–4421.
- Sjøberg, M. (2019) 'Artificial Intelligence in Norwegian organizations', *An exploratory study of challenges in AI adoption*, Master`s Thesis, University of Agder.
- Smith, C. (2018) 'An employee's best friend? How AI can boost employee engagement and performance', *Strategic HR Review*, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/SHR-11-2018-0092>.

- Sony, M., Antony, J. and Douglas, J. (2020) 'Essential ingredients for the implementation of Quality 4.0', *The TQM Journal*, ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print).
- Specht, N., Fichtel, S. and Meyer, A. (2007) 'Perception and attribution of employees' effort and abilities: the impact on customer encounter satisfaction', *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, Vol. 18 No. 5, pp. 534-554.
- Srivastava, B., Rossi, F., Usmani, S. and Bernagozzi, M. (2020) Personalized Chatbot Trustworthiness Ratings. *IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society*, 1(4), pp.184-192.
- Staven, T. (2017) 'What Makes a Good Bot (or Not)? Unit4 Newsletter', Available at: <http://www.unit4.com/blog/2017/03/what-makes-a-good-bot-or-not>. (Accessed: 22/3/2019).
- Steven, F. (2017) 'Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning For Business', 2nd ed. UK: Relativistic.
- Strauss, A. L., and Corbin, J. M. (1990) Basics of qualitative research (Vol. 15), Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Sun, T. Q., & Medaglia, R. (2019) 'Mapping the challenges of Artificial Intelligence in the public sector: Evidence from public healthcare', *Government Information Quarterly*, 36, pp. 368-383.
- Suta, P., Lan, X., Wu, B., Mongkolnam, P. and Chan, J. (2020) An Overview of Machine Learning in Chatbots. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics Research*, pp.502-510.
- Swanson, E. B. (2004) 'How is it an innovation assimilated. IFIP Working Conference on IT Innovation for Adaptability and Competitiveness', Springer, Boston, MA, pp. 267-287.
- Tambe, P., Cappelli, P., and Yakubovich, V. (2019) 'Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources Management', *Challenges and a Path Forward. California Management Review*, 61, pp. 15-42.
- Tammewar A. et al. (2017) "Production Ready Chatbots: Generate if not Retrieve".
- Thieltges, A., Schmidt, F., and Hegelich, S. (2016) 'The Devil's Triangle: Ethical Considerations on Developing Bot Detection Methods', *In 2016 AAAI Spring Symposium Series*.
- Thomas M. (1997) *Machine Learning*. McGraw-Hill.
- Tornatzky, L. and Fleischer, M. (1990) 'The Process of Technology Innovation', Lexington Books, Lexington, MA.
- Turing, A. (1950) 'Computing machinery and intelligence', *Mind*, vol. LIX, no. 236, pp. 433.
- Tzeng, J.Y. (2004) 'Toward a more civilized design: studying the effects of computers that apologize', *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, Vol. 61 No. 3, pp. 319-345.
- Ugale. A.H. (2019) 'Impact of Conversational Agents on Customer Service Employees: Master of Business Thesis, Auckland University of Technology (AUT).

- Urbach, N., Smolnik, S. and Riempp, G. (2009) Development and Validation of a Model for Assessing the Success of Employee Portals, Proceedings of the 17th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2009), June 8-10, Verona, Italy.
- Vagia, M., Transeth, A., and Fjerdings, S. (2016) ‘A literature review on the levels of automation during the years. What are the different taxonomies that have been proposed?’, *Applied Ergonomics*, 53, pp.190-202.
- Van Pinxteren, M., Pluymaekers, M. and Lemmink, J. (2020) ‘Human-like communication in conversational agents: a literature review and research agenda’, *Journal of Service Management*, 31(2), pp.203-225.
- Van Doorn, J., Mende, M., Noble, S., Hulland, J., Ostrom, A., Grewal, D. and Petersen, J. (2016). Domo Arigato Mr. Roboto. *Journal of Service Research*, 20(1), pp.43-58.
- Verhagen, T., van Nes, J., Feldberg, F., and van Dolen, W. (2014) ‘Virtual Customer Service Agents: Using Social Presence and Personalization to Shape Online Service Encounters’, *Journal of Computer Mediated Communication*, (19:3), pp. 529–545.
- Verhoef, P., Kannan, P., and Inman, J. (2015) ‘From Multi-Channel Retailing to Omni-Channel Retailing’, *Journal of Retailing*, 91(2), pp.174-181.
- Vincze, J. (2017) ‘Virtual reference librarians (Chatbots)’, *Library Hi Tech News*, 34(4), pp. 5-8.
- VomBrocke, J., Maaß, W., Buxmann, P., Maedche, A., Leimeister, J., and Pecht, G. (2018) ‘Future Work and Enterprise Systems’, *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 60(4), pp.357-366.
- Von Der Pütten, A. M., Krämer, N. C., Gratch, J., and Kang, S. H. (2010) ‘It doesn’t matter what you are!’ Explaining Social Effects of Agents and Avatars’, *Computers in Human Behaviour*, (26), pp. 1641–1650.
- Vorhies W. (2016) ‘Artificial general intelligence—the Holy Grail of AI’, DataScienceCentral.com: (Accessed: 23/02/2019).
- Waghmare, C. (2019) ‘Introducing Azure Bot Service: Building Bots For Business’, Springer Science+Business Media, New York.
- Wagner, E., L., S., Newell, and G., Piccoli, (2010) Understanding project survival in an ES.
- Wang, Y.M., Wang, Y.S., and Yang, Y.F. (2010) ‘Understanding the determinants of RFID adoption in the manufacturing industry’, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 77 No. 5, pp. 803-815.
- Weber, F., and Schütte, R. (2019) ‘State-of-the-art and adoption of artificial intelligence in retailing’, *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance*, 21(3), pp.264-279.
- Wei, C., Yu, Z., Fong, S. (2018) ‘How to build a chatbot: Chatbot framework and its capabilities’, In: Proc of the 2018 10th Intl Conf on Machine Learning and Computing, pp. 369–373. ICMLC 2018, ACM.

- Weizenbaum, J. (1966) 'ELIZA - A Computer Program for the Study of Natural Language Communication between Man and Machine', *Communications of the ACM*, (9:1), pp. 36–45.
- Wirtz, B. W., Weyerer, J. C., & Geyer, C. (2019) 'Artificial Intelligence and the Public Sector—Applications and Challenges', *International Journal of Public Administration*, PP. 596-615.
- Wong, K. (2005) Critical success factors for implementing knowledge management in small and medium enterprises. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 105(3), pp.261-279.
- Wu, J. H., and Wang, Y. M. (2006) Measuring ERP success: the ultimate users' view. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*. 26(8), pp.882-903.
- Xu, A., et al. (2017) 'A new chatbot for customer service on social media', pp. 3506–3510. ACM, NY, USA.
- Yan Z. (2018) 'DocChat: An information retrieval approach for chatbot engines using unstructured documents', in Proc. of the 54th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers), 2016, pp. 516–525.
- Yin, R. (2012) *Application case study research*, 6th ed. London: SAGE Publications.
- Yin, R. (2013) *Application case study research*. London: SAGE Publications.
- Yin, R.K. (2017) *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*, Sage publications.
- Zadrozny, W., Budzikowska, M., Chai, J., Kambhatla, N., Levesque, S., and Nicolov, N. (2000) 'Natural Language Dialogue for Personalized Interaction', *Communications of the ACM*, (43:8), pp. 116–120.
- Zamora, J. (2017) 'I'm sorry, dave, I'm afraid I can't do that:', *Chatbot perception and expectations*, In: Proc of the 5th Intl Conf on Human Agent Interaction, pp. 253–260. HAI '17, ACM.
- Zatarain, J. (2017) The role of automated technology in the creation of copyright works: the challenges of artificial intelligence. *International Review of Law, Computers & Technology*, 31(1), pp.91-104.
- Zhou, L., Gao, J., Li, D., and Shum, H.,Y. (2018) 'The Design and Implementation of XiaoIce', *an Empathetic Social Chatbot*. CoRR abs/1812.08989.
- Zhou, L., Gao, J., Li, D.. and Shum, H. (2020) 'The Design and Implementation of XiaoIce, an Empathetic Social Chatbot', *Computational Linguistics*, 46(1), pp.53-93.
- Zhang, J., Følstad, A. and Bjørkli, C. (2020). Organizational Factors Affecting Successful Implementation of Chatbots for Customer Service. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, pp.1-35.
- Zook, C. (2007) 'Finding your next CORE business', *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 85 No. 4, pp. 66-75.
- Zwikael, O. (2008) 'Top management involvement in project management', *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 1(4), pp.498-511

Appendices

Participant Information Sheet

You are invited to participate in a study, which is a part of the doctoral research project conducted by Nishamani Anupama Madduma Patabendige. Before you decide on your participation, you must understand why the research is being done and why your participation is important. Please take time to read the following information carefully and ask questions if anything you read is not clear or requires more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to understand how AI-based conversational agents (chatbots) can be implemented successfully in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context as a frontline self-service tool.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because your company is recognised as one of the UK retail e-commerce organisations already using conversational AI technology for your customer service purposes. Your participation in this study will significantly contribute to achieving the research purpose.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All the responses collected during the interview will be kept in a password-protected place and will be used only to analyse your responses received for interview questions. During the entire process, anonymity and confidentiality will be kept. Company names will not be mentioned, and individuals who will be interviewed will not be mentioned using their names will only use their job title. All the data retrieved during the entire interview process will be kept in a secure/password-protected place that only the researcher has permission to access.

What will happen to the result of this research?

The results will be communicated via the doctoral thesis (publically accessible).

Who has approved the study?

This study has been approved by the University of the West of Scotland Research Ethics Committee.

Consent Form

Title of the Study:

Conversational AI implementation success in the UK retail e-commerce customer service context

Name of the Researcher:

This project is undertaken by Nishamani Anupama Madduma Patabendige, a DBA student (Doctorate in Business Administration) at the University of the West of Scotland.

Please Tick the Box

	Yes	No
• I, the undersigned confirm that I have read and understood the information Sheet and have had the opportunity to ask questions related to my participation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I understand that my participation in this study is voluntary and I have the right to withdraw from the study anytime	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I agree to take part in the study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I agree that the interview will be audio recorded	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I agree that I will be quoted anonymously in the study and in any other publications may occur in the future	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Confidentiality

All information provided will be treated confidentially. Published work will always anonymise and never identify the source. Any audio-recording will be kept securely and will be destroyed no more than 12 months after the DBA viva.

Thank you in advance for your interest and assistance with this research.

Participant`s Name: _____

Participant`s Signature: _____ Date: _____

Interview Transcripts (From four interviews)

Company A - Interview 1

Interviewer/Student: Nishamani Patabendige (NP)

Interviewee: Lead Technological Strategist (LTS01)

NP: Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. Before we begin with the main questions I would like to get some of yours` and the company background information.

NP: Could you please tell me your current position at this company and how long have you been working?

LTS01: *Hello there! I am working as a Lead Technological Strategist here and have been working in the company since 2018.*

NP: What kind of a role you played during this implementation?

LTS01: *Well, I did half of the project coordination tasks during the deployment.*

NP: Can you give me a little bit of background about your company and the motivation behind implementing an AI-based CA?

LTS01: *Yeah, sure. We are an online fashion retailer focusing on the UK and the global female millennial market to cater for their fashion needs ranging from clothing, shoes, beauty products and the list goes on every year. Providing excellent customer service is an utmost priority for us as an e-commerce company. I mean mainly the customer support and success side. So we really wanted to capture and actively engage with our customers coming through Facebook and the website. Most of these customers are looking for easy product searches and offers without having a final purchasing decision in their minds.*

Besides that, we wanted to prioritise using `chat` in front as an effective communication method because it was identified as one of the most popular communication methods. That`s why we wanted to bring AI to serve our customers through a chat format. Artificial intelligence is going to play an important role in our digital strategy. Our aim is to revitalise our value chains creating a better-personalised service for our customers and of course create more value for our company. So it was pretty much the plan.

NP: What was your goal for adopting this technology and a CA?

I would say the goal of adopting a chatbot was to give our customers easy access to the information they need with a more personalised touch. We were convinced that this AI-enabled self-service chatbot could bring us closer to our digital native customer and provide more value through every touchpoint.

NP: Great, thanks. Can you tell me when this AI-based chatbot was implemented?

LTS01: *Last year April.*

NP: Right. So correct me if I`m wrong, as mentioned before this meeting, you have integrated your conversational agent into facebook and the company website?

LTS01: *Yes, that`s correct.*

NP: As this is a customer service conversational agent, can you please tell me what kind of customer service use case objectives did you have in your mind when you were implementing the CA?

LTS01: *Well, our primary objective was to provide a personalised customer service experience for our customers specifically coming from Facebook and Website channels. These are new and existing customers who could potentially purchase at any time, so we particularly focused on assisting them with product related queries and personalised recommendations.*

NP: Ok, thanks. Now could you tell me what kind of benefits did you achieve by implementing this CA?

LTS01: *Right, actually there are a few benefits. One of the key benefits is now we have the ability to provide personalised offers to our customers. Another benefit I would say is the faster information exchange rate we now have with our customers.*

Mmm.. another benefit is that we now have a higher customer conversion rate specially from the ones who are coming from Facebook. I think most of all now we are getting valuable deep insights about these target customers. This can be considered as the main benefit because it is helping us to make crucial marketing and business decisions very interestingly. our millennial customer base has been showing more receptiveness to converse with our Facebook Messenger and most of these insights are coming from their Facebook customer base.

NP: That's very interesting. Did this CA replace any existing chat system similar to this? I mean such as a chat window?

LTS01: *we still have our live chat option, but we wanted to reduce its operations and bring the automated chat forward.*

NP: What was your vendor selection approach?

LTS01: *Mmm..Well.. resource and funds assessments were discussed during the initiation stage. Our options were either to choose a cloud-based platform or build it in-house. We decided to build an on-premises one because we already had many resources and infrastructure needed with our previously implemented systems. We have already invested a lot for our cloud database and other infrastructure, and although the initial cost was high to build it with a specialised team, this was the suited and most secure option for us. when it comes to our customer base size, our company's sensitive data protection and also to maintain full control over the vendor.*

NP: Ok so when you choose the vendor what areas did you consider?

We sort of shortlisted two conversational AI specialist companies. And particularly looked at their domain experience, capabilities and the packages they have to offer. Then outsourced a project team from a London based leading start-up company to build the CA considering factors based upon their previous in-house build conversational AI project implementation experience in our domain and project team's specialised capabilities. And yeah.. we were looking for a vendor with a proven record of successful AI systems and particularly CAs implementation who could bring real value from AI technology to their business.

NP: Speaking of the strategy, was there a clearly defined strategy for this implementation? I'm curious to know what was happening at the planning stage for this implementation?

LTS01: *Yes we did. Actually, the strategy was presented by our technical team to define step by step goals at each stage. Also in our strategy, we particularly focused on the most suitable platform to launch the chatbot.*

Our audience is most reachable on Facebook and the website, so it was our main choice. So the first phase was launching the chatbot to our Facebook page and incorporate it for our online sales and customer service engagements. The second phase was launching it to the website target audience, and the third phase Instagram.

NP: Thanks for that. So how did you handle the changes that were coming with this new automated chat edition in your organisation? Particularly during the implementation process?

LTS01: *Well.. job redesign and creating new job roles in our company was a part of our change management strategy to utilise our internal resources adequately. For instance, we hired three full-time conversational AI experts to maintain and improve the CA performance upon project completion. This CA is not only going to change the way we interact with our customers but also it is going to create more roles and opportunities within the company. So we had to think about ways to redesign some of our customer service and marketing agent`s job responsibilities to make them effectively collaborate with the CA in both departments.*

NP: In terms of user training and employee training, what kind of approaches did you take during the implementation?

LTS01: *We had separate training sessions for our customer service employees. User training was not an option because it was not feasible to reach out to our customers for training purposes. Besides using the chatbot is not complex at all. That`s why we were very concerned about the seamless chat experience we could provide them through this chatbot. If the process is simple and easy to handle customers can easily pick up what to do.*

NP: Yes, that`s very true. So can you tell me how did you ensure the service quality of your CA or the chatbot?

LTS01: *That`s a good question! We mainly focused on the personality of our conversational agent. The personality of the CA should really in sync with the corporate identity of the company. When a customer is messaging to our chatbot, they are messaging with our company, and the way they receive the conversational agent is the way they see the company. It`s like a website. If you have a website for your company that is known as the window of a company into the world Right? A CA is exactly the same, and that`s why we wanted to think carefully when designing the correct character of the CA.*

We also had a clear focus on designing conversations more friendly and approachable while adding empathy to imply a more human-like interaction with users. Users can imply a lot about the personality of a chatbot simply through the words and sentences a conversational agent presents during a conversation. Primary users of this chatbot are millennial women who want to empower them through their fashion choices. So our conversation designer considered the most appealing language that can resonate with the user to train the Chatbot.

NP: That`s an interesting aspect.

NP: So How did you ensure the system quality of your chatbot during the implementation? Did you consider the system quality aspect at all?

LST01: *Yes we did. We tested our bot using the target audience to discover their preferences and then used all the feedback we gathered to do the necessary improvements. We asked these*

testers to handle conversations with the chat system and provide feedback describing their experience.

Another important point is that our audience is most reachable from Facebook and website. Defining the audience and then seek people who meet those criteria from both the platforms for user testing was a crucial part. Information gathered were used to obtain insights on key areas such as how receptive the target users to the bot, how the conversational flow works, how long a customer prefer to carry out the conversation, how emotionally they get connected, percentage of error rate and success rate of a conversation completion without involving a human etc.

NP: That`s very insightful. So you mean focusing on the usability aspect can definitely influence to improve the system quality and the overall implementation success?

LST01: Yes, absolutely!

NP: What about the information quality? How did you focus on that area during the implementation?

LST01: *Hmm.. We focused on the content that we wanted to train the system. The content we use in our bot plays a huge role to improve information quality. We hired a content creator to work with the project team. So she was fully focused on creating the conversations addressing intents and entities.*

NP: Moving on to challenges, what kind of challenges were you facing during the implementation?

LST01: *Actually, for us the most important question was how we are going to ensure our CA is providing accurate answers, maintain its functionality and utilise the data we get from daily user interactions to improve AI capabilities after it goes live. In order to do this, we had to hire full time and part-time conversational AI experts to the company as well as provide extensive training to our existing IT staff members. I think at the beginning lack of skills and in-house, knowledge was a challenge too.*

Getting that level of access to our live data, and follow the conversation history every day after the launch was a huge task. It was indeed a challenge because we had to spend a lot of money for new staff and a lot of hours to train IT staff. I mean I can actually remember just after the launch we were going through many response errors as identified during the testing phase. I think that is probably one of the biggest challenges we had to face. But now that has been sort of resolved and it`s not an issue anymore.

So basically it`s really important to prepare a well-trained, competent, full-time and part-time staff before the launch in the IT department to monitor, analyse and improve the conversational daily performance specially during the first six months after the launch.

NP: For me, this is new information, this is great. So from a conversational perspective, what`s the biggest challenge you are facing?

LST01: *I think our automated answers are getting better and better every week. But I would say our CA is still unable to understand the context of some of the conversations, and we are working on its “small talk” component to handle random questions at least up to some extent. It still fails to provide appropriate responses to random questions on some occasions.*

NP: So how do you overcome this challenge, do you have any plans?

LST01: *Yes, we do actually. To overcome this issue we are continuously expanding the training data for intents to understand different ways a user would interact. We have also allocated more money for research and testing.*

NP: Can you recall any governance-related challenges you were facing during the implementation?

LST01: *Mmm.. I think now more of our customers are receptive to use the messaging and chat format to communicate with us. But soon after the launch, getting the target customers` acceptance and engagement was very low across both the platforms. They were hesitant to provide their personal details during a conversation and our data showed it`s mainly due to privacy concerns. This was a huge challenge after the launch. we had to update and introduce a transparent, easy to access data and privacy policy. To be honest we didn`t consider this issue much during the implementation. It took us some time to build up the trust and get customers to engage with the chat interface..*

NP: So do you think this is something crucial to address during the implementation process to avoid this challenge to ensure success?

LST01: *I mean yes, definitely. If the customer doesn`t need or think they don`t need a chat option, we can`t really say the implementation is successful. This issue needs to be addressed during the planning stage and companies must be fully aware of this challenge before it really happens after the launch.*

NP: Brilliant. Thank you very much. That`s all the questions I have for you.

Company A - Interview 2

Interviewee: Project Manager (PM01)

NP: Many thanks for giving me this opportunity to interview you today. Can we begin by describing the job role of this project as the project manager?

PM01: *Thanks for having me. As the project manager, I was responsible to overlook the entire project progress and completion. Some of my main job tasks were to particularly focus on things like setting up the strategy, maintain the communication between the team members and the client, deliver the required resources with management support, facilitate meetings, organise training sessions for employees, testing, keep project logs and you know things like that.*

NP: How would you describe the level of top management support you received?

PM01: *Well, they were very supportive from the beginning throughout the whole process.*

NP: What about after the launch?

PM01: *Yes even after the launch.*

NP: So based upon this implementation experience do you think having top management support is a critical factor for a CA implementation project success? or not?

PM01: *Yes, indeed. It`s the top management role to explain to us their vision of deploying a conversational agent. And then we can develop the roadmap to achieve that goal. Not only that, an in-house built project like this usually requires more money and critical decisions to be made which directly require top management support and involvement. I must say the*

support we received to galvanise resources for the project from the client is another main component that contributed to this project success.

NP: As you just touched the funds and resource allocation aspect, did you manage to complete the project within the allocated budget?

PM01: *That`s a good question. No, we couldn`t complete the project within the budget.*

NP: Can you elaborate on the reasons for that please?

PM01: *Yes sure. Well. Look. This was a huge project even for us. It took eight months to complete this in-house built CA project from the planning phase to the launch date. It`s because we had to take two months extra than the initially planned six months` time frame to complete the implementation phase and then to launch due to some issues we experienced during the testing phase. When we focus on the omnichannel access route, the problem is not the conversational AI technology per se, it`s that the discovery of the services best to automate, how we provide them with this AI-based conversation experience in an exciting way to increase the broader adoption rate to encourage our target customer to use this self-service option instead of choosing the traditional engaging methods. So the testing phase gave us a lot to think about and do some crucial changes to the plan.*

NP: Thanks for that great insight. As you just mentioned on the planning aspect, I also would like to know if you had a clearly defined strategy for this implementation?

PM01: *Yes, we had a strategy. It was a combined effort of both parties. Our client clearly expressed their business goals and their conversational AI vision to us. And then we developed the roadmap to achieve that goal.*

NP: What was the strategy, or can you describe the things you discussed to set up the strategy?

PM01: *Sure sure.. So one of the key discussions were the platform selection to launch the CA. Our audience is most reachable on Facebook and the website. So as the first phase our client wanted to launch the conversational agent to the Facebook page and incorporate it for online sales and customer service engagements. The second phase was launching it to the website target audience within three months, and the third phase was to expand it to Instagram.*

NP: Based on your view and this implementation experience, do you think having a clearly defined implementation strategy can be a critical factor to ensure the project`s implementation success?

PM01: *As a project manager with years of experience in AI projects implementations, I would say it`s definitely a `yes`. Also, I would like to add another point. I think I mentioned this point earlier as well. During our strategy discussions when we were setting up the implementation strategy, during the brainstorming sessions, the way our client expressed their business goals clearly and coherently was really helpful for us to define the implementation strategy.*

NP: Right, thanks. So what kind of members consisted in your project team?

PM01: *Well.. in our project team we had two developers, a data scientist, a copywriter, a conversational flow designer and four members from the client`s side including a senior manager. You know the project team combination is extremely important for an in-house built project like ours.*

NP: Can you give me an example of how effective project management took place during the implementation?

PM01: *Hmm.. example.. I would say, you know our project team was fully committed only to this project without distractions from any other projects, so the availability and the flexibility of the project team members contributed to building an effective partnership between the client and the project team.*

NP: Based on your expertise and experience, do you think focusing on project management is a critical factor to ensure the implementation of these type of AI-based conversational agents?

PM01: *Yes. As a conversational AI project manager, I can assure you that having a project manager and a competent project team is critical for a huge project like this specially when it's building from scratch. I think when we discuss the topic of project management, areas like planning, having skilled team members, providing resources when needed, and communication are really important areas to consider when building an in-house CA powered by AI.*

NP: Great. Thanks. Now I would like to ask a few questions in regards to the technical side of the AI-based conversational agents' implementation.

PM01: *No worries. Go on..*

NP: So what were the important technical level factors did you consider during the implementation and why was it important?

PM01: *For us to build a domain-specific in-house CA with NLP/NLU components, we needed to go beyond standard features available in common APIs such as Dialog flow or IBM Watson. When it comes to conversational AI systems, having NLP in the system is a must but we can say it as a start. Generally, the underlying principle is that an AI-based conversational agent needs to be able to go through at least three main tasks during a conversation. The first task is `its ability to understand the user request and offer an informative answer`. The second task is `to maintain the context all the time during the conversation` and the third task is to maintain the conversation `seamlessly as much as possible just as chatting with a human`. So when it comes to this last task, machine learning plays a huge role. The thing is we still can't present the CA's chats indistinguishable from a human. Well, we all have to agree on the fact that we are not there yet. However, the interesting fact is many customers are still happy to engage with a conversational agent as long as they are helpful, useful or interesting.*

NP: What were the governance-related factors did you consider during the implementation and do you think governance is a critical component to consider during the implementation?

PM01: *Yes absolutely. Halfway through the deployment, our client wanted to work with specialised legal and security teams to craft the conversational privacy policy and security infrastructure that protect users' data. Apart from that as the implementation partner, we also ensured the legal and security requirements were met before the launch. Automation comes with a huge responsibility for organisations and it's absolutely critical to focus on the governance requirements in order to avoid unintended consequences and to mitigate risks involves with AI.*

NP: Thanks for that. I'm also interested to understand how you focused on the quality aspect of the CA system during the implementation.

NP: So can you please tell me how did you ensure the information Quality of your CA during the implementation?

PM01: *You know, the content that generates the outputs for customer requests from a CA plays a key role in a CA to enhance the information quality. So the content we use to create the system's database is a really important area to focus. You know.. I think database creation is*

a huge part of the puzzle and essential to provide a painless user experience. If the conversation is designed poorly, users could potentially be ended up with an extremely bad experience.

NP: Right, so what about the service quality? Did you focus on that aspect during the implementation? If yes, can you tell me what areas did you consider to improve the service quality?

PM01: *Conversational AI in the service sector is all about being conversational and transactional. So how a customer sees a bot through this new self-service communication method plays a huge role to determine whether they would engage with it or reject it. A conversational agent is not only a technical thing in customer service. But what the user is seeing or experiencing is the personality of a chatbot. Many companies don't consider this. But if you want it to partially replace a human employee, you better think of ways to make it like one as much as possible. The way a chatbot is doing a dialogue, its tone of the text message, the language, and the way it's effectively interacting with the user shape the personality of a chatbot and it helps to give a good first impression. So this is a very important aspect for usability and to ensure the success of using a chatbot to fulfil its business needs. Due to these reasons both our client and the implementation team wanted to focus on the personality of the chatbot to improve the service quality. You know I think the project team and organisational leaders' competence to think about the CAs personality they want to expose to their target user and meta aspects of the CA interface defining the company's branding guidelines could create a positive CA user interaction and service quality*

NP: That's a brilliant answer.

NP: How did you address the system quality requirements of your chatbot during the implementation?

PM01: *Uh..mm.. right so the usability of this bot was an important area our client. I also wanted to focus on this during the planning stage as it is one of the crucial ways to maintain the system quality. Our audience is most reachable from Facebook and the website. Defining the audience and then seek people who meet those criteria from both the platforms for user testing was a crucial part of this implementation success.*

NP: Alright, that's all the questions I have for you. I had a great time during this interview. Thanks a lot for your participation.

PM01: *It's a pleasure. Good luck!*

Company B - Interview 3

Interviewee: Senior Manager (SM02)

NP: Thank you for giving me this opportunity and I was really looking forward to this interview. During our previous conversations, you told me that you are a senior manager here. So can you please tell me how long have you been working in this company and the role you played during this AI-powered conversational agent or chatbot implementation project?

SM02: *Thank you, i'm happy to support your research. Actually, that was 2013 I joined the company and since then I have worked in various departments before I got promoted to a senior manager and in this project, I was working with our consultant and the chatbot partner.*

NP: That's great. Could you please explain the nature of your organisation?

SM02: *Yeah so we are a leading supplier of corporate uniforms to a wide range of industries, such as Transport, Aviation, Tourism & Leisure and Hospitality.*

NP: So when was it implemented?

SM02: *Last year, in 2019*

NP: Can you tell me what type of use case or use cases you implemented CA or chatbot perform in your organisation? Can you please explain in detail?

SM02: *Well actually we are currently using a customer service Chabot to improve and partially automate our customer service process. So our chatbot is an automated conversational interface that helps to engage with customers and to answer their uniform queries on its own with less employee involvement.*

NP: Right, so as the main use case of your chatbot you mentioned `partially automate customer service process`, could you describe the reasons for choosing such a use case?

SM01: *Sure. Last year we won two new tenders to work with leading corporate customers in the UK and things started to get really busy in our offices. Although we recruited two account managers and a few more full time and part-time administrators, still we had to deal with a lot of admin work. Our account managers and office administrators used to respond to customer queries for example placing a new order, providing updates about their outstanding uniforms over the phone or emails. Our biggest challenge was to respond to uniform orders and inquiries related to them without a delay while dealing with other important issues. Normally it's a time-consuming task to answer hundreds of our customer queries daily. While we were looking for our options to find a solution to this challenge, we got to know about this conversational AI technology through a consultant who worked previously with our IT department. After we did our research and got to know more about conversational AI and its benefits, we were pretty convinced to invest in it.*

NP: To elaborate further can you describe an example from daily customer service operations or any specific event where this chatbot use case is performed?

SM02: *Right. So what happens is our corporate customer's employees can engage with our Chabot by visiting their given internal e-commerce website. Once they entered the e-commerce website the Chabot pops up to help them with their uniform related queries. For example, When an employee visits their given e-commerce website the Chabot pops up. Then the employee has to provide information the bot asks. To begin with, their customer code so we have coded it as `ABELLI01` and `ABELLI02, and their four-digit employee number begins with `S0`. Then the chatbot provides options for the employee to choose, such as `to place an order/ to make changes to an order/ to make changes to an employee name or delivery address/ get the current status of an order/ get the tracking details of an order` etc. Then the employee can select the option they want and provide keywords the bot asks. If the bot comes across any queries beyond its capabilities to provide an answer, then that query handovers to an administrator via an email to get in touch with that particular employee ASAP.*

NP: Thanks, that's great. So did the chatbot replace any existing systems similar to this? i.e. a live human chat window. If yes, why was it replaced?

SM02: *No. We didn't have any other automated systems to engage with our customers like this before. Our account managers and office administrators used to respond to customer queries (such as placing a new order, providing updates about their outstanding uniforms) over the phone or via emails. We didn't have any other advanced systems to engage with our customers.*

NP: Who was involved in implementing? I mean for example was it built in-house or did you use a pre-built platform?

SM02: *Well, we build our chatbot from a customisable pre-built platform and a consultant also was involved to guide us during the process.*

NP: How long it took to implement your chatbot?

SM02: *Mmm...it took us about four months for the whole implementation process from the planning stage until the bot went live*

NP: Was the implementation project a success? Did you manage to complete on time within the budget?

SM02: *Yes, we started this as a pilot project and I must say the pilot was a great success. We managed to complete the implementation successfully. But it took us more time than we planned and also had to spend over the budget slightly.*

NP: Can you please elaborate on the reasons for that delay and additional cost?

SM02: *Yes, I think it`s mainly because of the issues we experienced while preparing the knowledge base. Data cleaning was an unexpected challenge we had to go through. You know we had to ensure all the data records such as our selected customers' names are in the system with correct spellings, their job numbers, addresses are all accurate. It was not an easy thing to get all these updated details from our customer and cross-check it with the system because we have around 4000 employees under that customer.*

NP: What are some key benefits that you have achieved from this implementation?

SM02: *Hmm..actually there are a few. Now we have the ability to answer customer queries instantly. Without the chatbot, it usually takes 1 – 2 working days to respond to their email inquiries. You know now because our chatbot is 24 x 7 active, employees of our customers can order their uniforms and check their order status during their leisure times even after office hours. We have managed to cut down the operational cost and save time. Also now our employees have manageable workloads and they are quite happy and performing well because of the support they are getting from the chatbot.*

NP: Ok. Nice. Thanks. Now I have a few questions to ask from you regarding the critical factors that affected this implementation success.

NP: Did you have the top management support and if yes, in what way?

SM02: *Yes. Our company director was the one who wanted to implement this chatbot. In fact, he provided full support throughout all the phases. Our company director is always open to adopt new technologies depends on its usefulness, and he`s usually very keen to bring innovative ideas to his company`s business operations. His enthusiasm was a crucial factor for other managers in the company to believe in AI technology.*

I think also I must say our company director or as a manager myself didn`t have much knowledge about this technology or how it works. I mean you know, we wanted to do things right with our pilot chatbot project using AI features. But to begin with, we didn`t know what features to look! Not even our IT team didn`t have a clear idea about how effectively machine learning can be used in our chatbot. To be honest we just followed the hype! So we had to completely rely on our AI consultant and vendor to decide the key features of the use case. Seeking experts` advice and guidance is obviously the most sensible thing to do, but it would have been better if we knew what we were getting into in advance.

NP: That`s something very interesting to know. So do you think having top management support is critical to ensure these types of text-based conversational AI implementations success?

SM02: *Yes, I think so.*

NP: May I ask why you think that way?

SM02: *Well I think this is where everything starts. In this project, it was our company director who was more interested in using AI for customer service more than any of us. So that`s how this journey began. I think without the top management`s support, nothing is feasible.*

NP: Was there a clearly defined business case or a use case to achieve through this implementation initiative, how was it done?

SM02: *Yes yes, that`s the first thing we did. There are thousands of employees under one customer, and we have 7 major customers like that with two new customers partnered with us last year. Normally we receive about hundreds of queries every single day even on weekends, and due to this reason, every employee was overwhelmed with work. So our main goal was to save time and money by using an automated 24/7 chat platform and use our employees to do other administrative tasks.*

NP: Did you have a clearly defined strategy for this implementation?

SM02: *Yes we did. We went through a few different phases in terms of building a strategy for this chatbot implementation.*

NP: What was your implementation strategy and how was it done? Can you please elaborate?

SM02: *Okay. So, first of all, we needed to understand the available chatbots in the market, how this conversational AI technology works and the impact it can create on our organisation. After researching on the internet, we decided to consult an AI expert who can provide more information about chatbots and help us with strategy development. Based on his advice, we choosed a suitable vendor platform for our requirements. Then our first strategic approach was to build a team within the company for this project. Then we used an AI strategy template to capture all the requirements to implement this successfully and had discussions with our project team about ways to work on these areas.*

So in our implementation strategy, we discussed our data related areas such as ethical and legal factors. For example, GDPR because it was completely new to us. Things related to Technology & infrastructure. For example, if this is going to be a cloud deployment or on-premise and data layers, Skills & capacity – we had to evaluate how our employees and our customers` employees would accept this chatbot, training requirements needed for our employees and to the end-users. We also had to discuss all possible scenarios that could happen. Such as how easily the end-user, in our case `Train staff` would adapt and understand how to operate it. So again we had to evaluate the user and employee impact going to create by introducing this technology, communication methods and how to overcome the challenges related to the change that comes with this new way of communication.

NP: That`s great thanks. How did you select a vendor?

SM02: *We wanted to work with a consultant. Although we had to spend some extra money, getting advice from a consultant, his expert guidance made a huge difference to this project. Since we didn`t have a clear idea about AI technology or chatbots at first, our consultant`s*

guidance was really useful during this process. So our AI consultant helped us to find the most suitable vendor to match our purposes and that was a huge relief.

NP: When deciding the vendor selection aspect did you do a vendor assessment?

SM02: *Yes we did. But initially, we just followed the hype with a little knowledge about conversational AI technology. That`s the main reason we wanted to work with a conversational AI expert for consultation. We wanted to feel comfortable saying to our implementation partner that we are new to this technology and have no idea how it works. We checked their customer base and their testimonials. And also they provided us with a personalised demo with a competitive package. We were quite happy with that.*

NP: In your view based on this implementation experience, do you think vendor selection is a critical factor for AI-based chatbots implementation success?

SM02: *Yes. I think choosing the right consultant and the vendor played a key role in helping us to implement our chatbot successfully.*

NP: How was the project management undertaken in the project, was there a specific project manager?

SM02: *Yeah...so we had clear project implementation schedules and planning managed by a dedicated project manager provided by our service provider. Well, we sort of had to pay him an additional amount for getting his services. You know although this wasn`t a large scale project having a project manager with experience and the right qualifications helped us to ensure that our investment and the success of the project was in good hands.*

NP: How was the project progress communicated to all participants and how often?

SM02: *Mmm..The project manager was responsible for things like project progress monitoring, organising and managing checkpoint meetings etc. Communication had to be consistent especially when dealing with an outsourced vendor, consultant and our company. So we mainly communicated through face to face and online meetings, and emails.*

NP: A technology such as artificial Intelligence adoption and implementation is likely to cause changes in existing business processes, structure, and the way people work, how did the organisation manage this change?

SM02: *I`m glad you asked that question. Well since the initial stages, we ensured to have active and robust internal communications efforts in place. When we first bring the news to our employees, some were not very happy about the idea. Some were saying, very well! soon at one point, it`s going to take our jobs. So to avoid a panic among employees about their job security we had to convey to them the reasons for this chatbot adoption and the benefits that come with it. Preparing the company to embrace this new technology before the implementation stage begin was important. We were also keen to listen to our employees` opinions and insights before the implementation process began. During the implementation phase, we had to train our account managers and administrators on ways to deal with the bot. During that process, their feedback was a key factor to make necessary changes.*

NP: Great. How did you involve employees during this project implementation? What about their training, how was this done and at what stage? Is there any ongoing learning environment?

SM02: *You know as I mentioned earlier, this AI chatbot project was initially controversial because people were concerned about their jobs and felt they might not have the technical skills to fit into the chatbot operations. When they realised that this chatbot is easy to operate model*

and only there to release the pressure from the workload and then they became more interested. We got a few selected employees and our customers` selected group of employees involved with the training and testing process. And then we continuously trained our admins before and after the bot went live to monitor and handle the queries the bot can't handle. We also sort of provided guidance and instructions to all department heads who agreed to use our bot by giving their consent.

NP: How adequate was your resources IT infrastructure to integrate a CA or a chatbot with your existing systems, and was there any infrastructure refresh?

SM02: *Well had most of the data required in-house as we have been using the ERP and business objects. However, we didn't require many hardware resources since we didn't build it as we choosed to go with our vendor`s advanced subscription-based ML model to do the customisation according to our requirements.*

NP: How did you collect and arrange data?

SM02: *When we first started this project, there wasn't a lot of textual conversational data available. The majority of all customer interactions were phone calls and emails based customer queries. So we had to get help from our most experienced office administrators to gather the necessary conversational data.*

NP: Can you tell me what kind of conversational data you were particularly interested in?

SM02: *Yeah, so we mainly focused on questions and answers related to the most frequently asked questions and answers, to provide our implementation partner. And all the other data related to the tasks we specified to automate. Our model developers needed unambiguous, logical and hierarchical conversational data. It took us some time to gather, arrange and provide all the data and information they requested.*

NP: What approaches have you taken to ensure the data Privacy of the CA?

SM02: *Okay. Well so to make our chatbot GDPR compliant, we had to get the authorisation and consent from the relevant authorities of our corporate customers/ their head offices. Since all the chatbot users are their employees and all the inquiries were related to their jobs, we didn't have to get consent from each employee. In our privacy policy, we have clearly stated information such as what information is being collected? who is collecting it? Why is it being collected? For how long it will be used?, Who will it be shared with?, How can they withdraw from the agreement to give their data? You know things like that.*

NP: Did you take any approaches to ensure explainability and Transparency of your CAs Outputs?

SM02: *Hmm..Yes, actually we sort of did.*

NP: What was that, can you elaborate?

SM02: *We provided our customers before the bot went live with transparent, distinguishable and easily accessible details to understand what data is collected and how it will be used by the bot and the organisation. We also have a clear and a simple way to access, review and download copies of user data that was collected free of charge, with the permission to erase their conversational history if they want us to do so".*

NP: Do you think the above-discussed factors are critically important to consider during the CAs implementation?

SM02: *Yes. I think all the areas we discussed are really important in my view.*

NP: Do you have any other factors to highlight that organisations should be aware of during the implementation phase?

SM02: *Not really.*

NP: What kind of challenges were you experiencing during this implementation?

SM02: *Well, data preparation was such a challenging task. At first, we didn't know the expected quality of the data and how the data training in the model works. Therefore we had to go through introductory sessions involving all our team members to get an idea about the whole process from the pre-implementation to the post-implementation phase. During this bot building process, it involves data capture, data storage, data preparation and model training with data and tests the model's accuracy with data. Data preparation is a challenging and highly intellectual task. At first, even our best employees had to attend three meetings with our consultant and the vendor to understand the data needed for the bot and to identify the keywords related to that. So you know we had to get both our vendor and consultant's support to understand the expected standard of the quality of the data because of the lack of knowledge we had with regards to that.*

NP: Thanks for that. So can you recall any kind of organisational and managerial challenges such as strategic, change management related, user acceptance related or skills and competence and if you had any of those challenges how did you handle them?

SM02: *Yeah you know choosing the most suitable chatbot was challenging at first as well. So our consultant really helped us to select the best service provider. And At the first majority of the employees were not very keen to engage with this initiation due to job security fears. Educating them about the benefits of this initiation was crucial to get them on board with this. We had to carefully manage the change. You know some of our employees were worried about losing their jobs mainly because they are too old to learn and won't be competent enough to work with a complex technology like AI. As a solution, we had shared emails among employees with background details about the purpose of adopting conversational AI technology, how the CA works, and the benefits employees get by collaborating their work with the CA. Another challenge was that after the bot went live, we had to train someone within the company to handle and monitor the bot's day to day operations since getting professional support every week was expensive to afford. Knowledge transition was challenging.*

NP: Any governance-related challenges can you recall you had to experience during the implementation?

SM02: *Ya so initially we didn't have a clear understanding of GDPR and data protection requirements. You know I had to spend a few days reading and gathering information about the data protection requirements and to understand the responsibilities we have as a company when using this conversational AI technology. But other than that we had to fully rely on our consultant and the service provider to fulfil these requirements.*

NP: Thanks so much for your time. That's all the questions I have.

Company B - Interview 4

Interviewee: AI Consultant (AIC02)

NP: Good morning. Thanks so much for this opportunity.

AIC02: Thank you. Glad to be here!.

NP: I have a few questions to ask from your conversational AI expert perspective. To begin with can you please tell me what kind of technical factors were important for this AI-based conversational agent implementation success?

AIC02: *Absolutely. For me to sum it up you know it was really important to have a self-learning conversational AI capability in our CA with advanced Artificial Intelligence features with API connectors that can integrate with the company's CRM and ERP system.*

AIC02: *You know infusing NLP and Machine Learning into our conversational agent with a combination of API calls was a must to provide an enhanced conversational and personalised user experience.*

NP: Right, so can you tell me a bit about your project team and how did you undertake the project management during the implementation?

AIC02: *Yeah, there was a senior manager and two administrators who were fully dedicated to data preparation and to support the team with all the other information needs representing the company.*

NP: Can you tell me more about the team composition please?

AIC02: *Actually, from the vendor's team, there was a project manager, two developers, and a copywriter. Our project planning was sort of undertaken to focus on each stage of the implementation during the first two weeks, and we had clear project implementation schedules. We also had a strategy in hand to avoid bumps along the way with a road map for each step of the project getting involved with relevant stakeholders at each stage as it happened.*

NP: In your view do you think project management is a critical factor to consider when implementing an AI-based conversational agent?

AIC02: *Yes totally.*

AIC02: *But you know I think the size of a conversational agent's project management can be varied depending on things like context, the scope of action, customisation, and the use case objectives of the project take place.*

NP: How did you set up your implementation strategy?

AIC02: *Mmm..We discussed many areas when setting up the implementation strategy. But most importantly we wanted to implement the first version as a pilot project focusing on one particular customer limiting the CA's capabilities only to few selected tasks and train the bot to do those tasks exceptionally well. Obviously, it's a very difficult task to program the CA to answer every possible question under the sun initially at once [laughs]. So our goal was to understand user expectations clearly and define what our CA can help with and what it can't, then focus on doing those expected tasks really well. So the first step was to consider our user's expectations, their demographics and pain points they normally face when they reach out to us with their queries. Customer-centricity is a crucial factor to consider as this is a customer service chatbot.*

NP: How did you focus on the system quality of this conversational agent during the implementation? I mean was there a particular area or areas did you focus?

AIC02: *Yeah well we conducted user testing involving a selected group of users to test our chatbot and then the feedback received were taken to modify the model before the launch. And*

right after user testing, user training and customer service employees training to handle certain queries when the conversational agent handovers to them were undertaken. Our service provider had also provided training to two IT executives to monitor chats, error messages, the wait time between messages and the overall analytic dashboard. So our conversational agent was tested with a pre-determined usability testing protocol to test and evaluate the ease of task completion, to identify usability errors and to evaluate participant opinions on the Chatbot.

AIC02: You see the usability issues identified by subsequent participants were considered unique if previous participants had not been identified with the same issues. And then the next step was setting up KPIs. For example to monitor and measure things like CA's activity volume you know to evaluate the number of daily weekly interactions, conversation bounce rate meaning the number of conversations sessions the CA fails to accomplish during their intended customer self-service tasks, and opinions then were taken into improving the system performance and its quality before and after the final launch.

NP: How did you focus on the Information quality of this conversational agent during the implementation? I mean was there a specific area did you focus on?

AIC02: Hmm..information quality. A good question.

AIC02: Hmm..when choosing SaaS customisable CAs from our service provider, we had to ensure that the conversational platform consists of knowledge bases that could understand our user languages specific to our company and business's nature. This is actually a key area to focus. There are so many knowledge bases available in the market at the moment. But you know we have to carefully choose the most suitable ones that match our customers and the business.

NP: Right. So what about the service quality? Anything, in particular, did you focus on?

AIC02: Again a good question [Laughs]

AIC02: Well, It's important to make sure we monitor the bot's performance regularly to ensure the service quality. If the bot failed to provide an answer, we have to make sure that one of our employees looks into that matter as soon as possible and gets in touch with that employee to help them with their inquiry. That's why we monitor how many inquiries manage to handle by our bot on its own and how many inquiries were directed to our employees by the bot. When its response rate was too low for specific questions, we had to train the model with new intents and entities.

NP: How did you ensure the system quality of the conversational agent or chatbot?

AIC02: Well the focal point was to provide fast responses in a friendly more human-like manner. Because these two areas are really important for a conversational AI project success. The goal of a customer self-service CA is to provide efficient customer service to our customers without holding them too long for an email reply or a telephone call.

AIC02: And you know this is a completely new experience to our customers, making them feel like they are chatting with a human is important. To achieve that, a bot's fast, efficient friendly user approach is important. But if I'm absolutely honest with you still, even after the launch, the system can't provide 100% accurate responses. It is an expected challenge in an AI-based Chatbot during the early days after the launch. This is why it is imperative to closely monitor the bot's performances and provide more training data sets while the bot learns from its own experience.

NP: Based on this implementation experience, what kind of data-related challenges did you face and how did you handle those challenges?

NP: You know particularly I'm interested to know in terms of data availability, data preparation, and data sharing and integration.?

AIC02: *Hmm well.. Yeah, getting all these lists of employee names, employee numbers, addresses and delivery locations from customers and then cross-checking each and every single employee's record with our internal database was a massive task. So we had to go through all our customers I mean in this instance potential users' name lists, station addresses, job grades and check their correct uniform sets to ensure accuracy. This is also called the process of cleaning the unclean data. For example, We found out that in our ERP system we had some of the employee names, surnames, addresses spelling errors, wrong locations, wrong uniform allocations for their job grades. We had to spend additional eight weeks to clean our employee data. During the data preparation, we found out that about 20% of employee data are not accurate. We found out spelling errors of their names, wrong delivery location records, and also employee number errors. It was a challenge you know. For example, we found out when first created the employee record in the system, some of our client's data entry operators had keyed in O (capital O) instead of 0 (Zero) for the 'S0' employee code before their four-digit employee number. And as a result, employee details didn't match against the ERP system's database. And then to provide the delivery updates with the users uniform orders, we had to liaise with our warehouse team to ensure that they provide the accurate nine-digit tracking number and the correct courier name you know like TNT, UPS or FedEx etc. Data related biggest challenge was data preparation. Even though this was a small project compared with large scale chatbot implementations, we had to spend nearly two months collecting and cleansing data.*

NP: That's a fantastic answer. Thanks for that. Similar to that example can you recall any kind of organisational and managerial challenges?

AIC02: *Yeah well you know.. One of the misconceptions among some of the top managers was seeing AI-powered models as magical devices that can do anything. This is not true, and we had to convince its capabilities and restrictions to top management and some staff members. So at early stages, it's important to understand its capabilities and limitations beforehand to make the investment decision to avoid disappointments. You know I have worked on many conversational AI projects. Another huge issue I have experienced in all these projects is the lack of technical experts in-house.*

NP: Thank you. That's all the questions I have to ask from you today!